

DOCTORAL THESIS

Integrating ecological and evolutionary processes at species-level for the analysis of the assembly and structure of arthropod communities on islands

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Cover and back cover silhouettes: *Lepromoris*, drawing by Daniel Suárez

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Universidad de La Laguna (ULL)

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TESIS DOCTORAL

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THESIS ABSTRACT

Thesis abstract

Oceanic islands represent a singular systems due to their unique history and biodiversity, making them especially valuable for testing ecological and evolutionary hypotheses. However, these ecosystems are currently threatened by several factors, including climate change and introduced species. A comprehensive understanding of the ecological and evolutionary processes that modulate the arthropod communities on these islands is essential for effective conservation and to provide guidelines for assessing the risk of extinction of island species. The present thesis, with a primary focus on Coleoptera, demonstrates that introduced species are more likely to establish successfully in laurel forest communities when phylogenetically related species are already established. This finding provides support for the preadaptation hypothesis over the competition-relatedness hypothesis. Additionally, it is revealed that many species previously considered native non-endemic species are, in fact, introduced species, a pattern that is referred to as the Humboldtian shortfall. This thesis also demonstrates that, when focusing exclusively on endemic and native non-endemic species, particularly those present on multiple islands, using an Evolutionary Significant Units (ESU) approach is an objective way to quantify species extinction risk. Island populations within multi-island species can be genetically independent from each other, revealing them to be conceptually closer to single island endemic species, with an associated increase in their island-level extinction risk. Also, beetles with low dispersal ability are more likely to be composed of multiple ESUs, and thus have a higher extinction risk. A detailed study case involved the analysis of the populations of an monotypic endemic genus, *Lepromoris*, which is distributed throughout the Canary Islands and is characterised by its apterous nature (low dispersion capacity). Through an integrative taxonomic approach that combined mitochondrial and nuclear genetic markers with morphological measurements, it was inferred that the genus *Lepromoris* consists of two species rather than one, as previously thought. The thesis as a whole demonstrates the usefulness of genetic techniques as an objective approach for conservation purposes, being essential to understand the impact of introduced species on native communities, to better delimit those species at highest risk of extinction, or even to infer new species.

GENERAL INTRODUCTION

Oceanic islands: the scientist's playground

Since Darwin's voyage aboard the *Beagle*, inspiring the development of The Theory of Evolution (Darwin, 1859), islands have been the focus of numerous studies due to their unique geology, ecosystems and biodiversity. The present interest in island systems has been further motivated by the works of Edward O. Wilson and Robert H. MacArthur in the mid-20th century, particularly The Theory of Island Biogeography (1967), a pillar of many current studies and theories (e.g. Hubbell, 2001; Kimura, 1983; Simberloff, 1974; Simon, 2008; Tschardt *et al.*, 2012). For example, a bibliographic analysis of the term "island biology" in Google Scholar (<https://scholar.google.es/>) and Web of Science (<https://www.webofscience.com/>) revealed more than 38,000 and 25,000 records, respectively, for the past five years (data consulted on 8 March 2024). This finding underscores the significance of island systems in contemporary scientific research.

According to Fernández-Palacios and Morici (2004), the classification of islands can be divided into three primary categories: (i) Oceanic islands – formed by volcanic activity on the seabed and never connected to continental masses, exhibiting unique and distinct biodiversity, such as the Canary Islands or the Hawaiian Islands; (ii) Ancient continental islands – old fragments of continental crust currently surrounded by water as a result of various tectonic processes, with a biodiversity significantly different from that of nearby continental areas, as is the case of the Balearic Islands, Madagascar and New Zealand; and (iii) Recent continental islands - islands currently separated from continents but that were united to them in various glacial periods when the sea level was lower, resulting in a similar biodiversity to that of nearby continents, as is the case of the British Isles and New Guinea. Other island categories include coral islands (formed by the emergence of coral, for example, the Great Barrier Reef), sedimentary islands (accumulation of sediment at the mouth of a river, such as the Ebro Delta in Spain), fluvial islands (any portion of land located in the middle of the course of a river, such as the Bananal Island in Brazil) or artificial islands created by humans (for example, the archipelago Palm Jumeirah in Dubai). However, from an evolutionary and biodiversity perspective, the latter categories of islands are of particular interest. This is due to the very recent origin of these islands, as opposed to oceanic or continental islands.

Both continental and oceanic islands are represented in most biodiversity delimited hotspots (Mittermeier *et al.*, 2004), regions of the planet with high levels of

species diversity, with a significant proportion of these species endemic to the region, and many of them threatened or endangered (Myers *et al.*, 2000). However, oceanic islands have the highest proportion of endemic species and are therefore of greater interest than continental islands (Kier *et al.*, 2009). This elevated level of endemism can be primarily attributed to the *de novo* and typically isolated origins of oceanic islands, implying that their constituent biodiversity must be established *de novo*. In contrast, continental islands commonly share fauna and flora with continental areas prior to their separation (Gillespie & Roderick, 2002). With increased isolation from continental masses and generally small sizes in comparison with continental islands, the odds of speciation events that originates endemic species in oceanic archipelagos are very high (Emerson, 2002). Thus, impressive species radiation have happened on oceanic islands across very different taxa: the genus of weevils *Laparocerus* in Macaronesia with 264 described species (Machado, 2022), the plant subfamily Lobelioideae with at least 126 endemic species in the Hawaiian Islands (Wolkis *et al.*, 2022), the Hawaiian *Drosophila* species represented by circa 800 species on the archipelago (Craddock & Kambysellis, 1997; Emerson, 2002), the more than 110 species of *Anolis* lizards recorded on the Greater Antilles in the Caribbean Sea (Jackman *et al.*, 1999), or the independent radiations experienced by the genera of sinistral land snails *Achatinella*, *Amastra* and *Lyropupa* in the Hawaiian Islands (Hoso, 2012). These radiation events are often classified in two types, adaptive or non-adaptive. Adaptive radiations are speciation events in which multiple species originate from a single ancestral species as a consequence of the occupation and exploitation of diverse and new ecological niches (Emerson, 2002; Losos & Ricklefs, 2009; Schluter, 2000). Conversely, non-adaptive radiations are characterised by mechanisms such as allopatry, leading to speciation events resulting from the geographical separation of populations within a species. This is due to the presence of barriers that hinder gene flow among populations, thereby promoting divergence that can culminate in reproductive incompatibility and speciation (Bush, 1975; Mayr, 1963). It is notable that both of these processes can give rise to a substantial number of species within a particular lineage on oceanic archipelagos. Paradoxically, oceanic islands also host many examples of endemic monotypic genera, that is, endemic genera composed exclusively of a single described species (e.g. Arechavaleta *et al.*, 2009; Borges *et al.*, 2008; Eldredge & Miller, 1997). Some of these monotypic genera exclusive to oceanic islands occur amongst Coleoptera, such as *Amaroschema*, *Canarinus* and *Pelleas* in the Canary Islands (Arechavaleta *et al.*, 2009);

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Doryonichus (Araneae; Gillespie *et al.*, 1998) and *Kanaloa* (Fabaceae; Lorence & Wood, 1994) in Hawaii; *Deucalion* on Selvagens Islands (Coleoptera; Borges *et al.*, 2008), or land snails like *Idiomela* and *Lampadia* in Porto Santo (Borges *et al.*, 2008).

As a consequence of their isolation and smaller size compared to continental masses, the flora and fauna of oceanic islands are typically better studied and catalogued than their adjacent continental masses. This facilitates the use of oceanic islands as natural laboratories to test general eco-evolutionary hypotheses (Gillespie, 2007; Gillespie & Roderick, 2002). The classification of island species is typically divided into three categories, determined by their origin and establishment within islands: endemic species, native non-endemic species and introduced species. Island endemic species can be further categorised as either neoendemic or paleoendemic. Neoendemic species are those whose speciation and evolutionary history have occurred within a specific location from an ancestor that arrived naturally to that region/island; whereas paleoendemic species are relict species that have suffered extinctions in the rest of their distribution (Gillespie & Roderick, 2002). In both cases, endemic species are geographically restricted to a delimited area such as an island or an archipelago after they have been established in such area over evolutionary time-scales. For example, the Cerambycidae *Deroplia schurmanni* is exclusive to El Hierro (Arechavaleta *et al.*, 2009); the Pamphagidae *Acrostira euphorbiae* is restricted to La Palma island (Arechavaleta *et al.*, 2009); or the Lycosidae *Hogna ingens*, present only in the Desertas Islands (Borges *et al.*, 2008). In contrast, native non-endemic species are species whose distribution is not limited to a single region, island or archipelago but is present in several nearby archipelagos or continents. Their native status implies a more recent origin than that attributed to endemic species. For example, the mantis *Blepharopsis mendica* has been observed in the Canary Islands, as well as in various countries across North Africa, including Morocco and Egypt, with further occurrences extending to India (Mirzaee *et al.*, 2024). Finally, introduced species refers to those that have arrived and established themselves as a result of human action. This action can be direct, as for example, the release of the honey bee, *Apis mellifera*, into Galápagos Islands for commercial purposes (Peck *et al.*, 1998), or indirect, as happened with the North American termite *Reticulitermes flavipes*, reported in several European countries, including islands such as Tenerife, as a consequence of the importation of infected ornamental or fruit trees (Hernández-Teixidor *et al.*, 2019).

Introduced species: an important threat to island biodiversity

Introduced species represent a significant threat to global biodiversity, as well as to human economy and public health (e.g. Cuthbert *et al.*, 2022; Diagne *et al.*, 2021; Early *et al.*, 2016). This threat is particularly acute and challenging on oceanic islands, due to their unique ecosystems and biodiversity, with a high degree of endemism, isolation and reduced geographic area, in comparison with continental masses (Bellard *et al.*, 2017; Leclerc *et al.*, 2018; Lenzner *et al.*, 2020; Reaser *et al.*, 2007). Introduced species have been responsible for the extinction of countless endemic and native non-endemic species (Bellard *et al.*, 2016; Leclerc *et al.*, 2018), spread of diseases (Ogden *et al.*, 2019), severe damage to ecosystems and alterations in their functions and services (Vilà & Hulme, 2017), and impacts on food security by negatively affecting agriculture (Paini *et al.*, 2016). Globally, the economic costs of combating introduced species have been estimated at over 1.2 trillion U.S. dollars in the past 50 years (Diagne *et al.*, 2021). In the context of invertebrates, which are considered one of the most problematic groups, along with mammals and plants, an estimated annual cost of over 8.7 billion U.S. dollars has been allocated to preventive or reactive responses during the same period (Diagne *et al.*, 2021). Likewise, the funds allocated to alleviate the effects of introduced species are distributed very unevenly across regions, with North America and Oceania receiving significantly more than the combined total for all other continents (Cuthbert *et al.*, 2022; Diagne *et al.*, 2021).

In contrast with introduced plant taxa, for which detailed introduction histories are often reasonably well documented (e.g. flora of the Azores; Schaefer *et al.*, 2011), relatively little attention has been paid to the introduction of invertebrates, particularly arthropods. This is likely due to several complicating factors. Arthropods, due to their small size, often elusive nature, or nocturnal or subterranean habits (Simberloff, 2013), are usually difficult to detect upon arrival (especially in the early stages of invasion). Consequently, there is often a significant delay between their arrival and first detection, complicating eradication efforts (Roques *et al.*, 2009). For example, the introduction of crazy ant *Anoplolepis gracilipes* on Christmas Island was detected only when the ant had already spread throughout the rainforest habitat. Its high population density had already affected the habitat and associated species of plants, invertebrates, and even birds (O'Dowd *et al.*, 2003).

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A considerable number of hypotheses have been postulated to explain the successful establishment of introduced species in novel regions. **Figure 1** comprises 35 distinct hypotheses that aim to clarify the mechanisms behind successful establishment, invoking diverse explanations such as human interference, environmental factors, and inherent characteristics of the introduced species (Jeschke & Heger, 2018).

Figure 1. Network with 35 hypotheses proposed to explain the successful establishment of introduced species. The larger the circle, the greater the number of hypotheses with which it shares similarity. Each color represents the most important factor that explains the hypothesis, with red being a high role of mutualism relationships, purple a greater importance of human action, and green a greater relevance of the natural enemies of the introduced species, that is, predators and parasites. Hypothesis names are abbreviated as follows: ADP = adaptation, BA = biotic acceptance, BID = biotic indirect effects, BR = biotic resistance, DN = Darwin's naturalization, DS = disturbance, DEM = dynamic equilibrium, EN = empty niche, EI = enemy inversion, EE = enemy of my enemy, ERD = enemy reduction, ER = enemy release, EVH = environmental heterogeneity, EICA = evolution of increased competitive ability, GC = global competition, HF = habitat filtering, HC = human commensalism, IW = ideal weed, IRA = increased resource availability, IS = increased susceptibility, IM = invasional meltdown, ISH = island susceptibility hypothesis, LS = limiting similarity, MM = missed mutualisms, NAS = new associations, NW = novel weapons, OW = opportunity windows, PH = plasticity hypothesis, PP = propagule pressure, RI = reckless invader, RER = resource-enemy release, SP = sampling, SDH = shifting defence hypothesis, SG = specialist-generalist, TEN = tens rule. Figure extracted from Jeschke & Heger, 2018.

As demonstrated in **Figure 1**, these hypotheses are interconnected through grades of similarity, complementing each other in different ways. Typically, plants have been the primary focus to test hypotheses, due to the greater availability of historical data (Fristoe *et al.*, 2021; Li *et al.*, 2015; Schaefer *et al.*, 2011) and the relative ease of detecting introduced species in this group. Among these hypotheses, those that have received the most attention are the adaptation (or preadaptation) hypothesis and the competition-relatedness (also known as Darwin's naturalization) hypothesis. These competing hypotheses form the so-called Darwin's naturalization conundrum (Li *et al.*, 2015; Schaefer *et al.*, 2011). The adaptation hypothesis, postulated formally by Duncan and Williams (2002) although considered by Darwin (1859) as an alternative to his hypothesis, and supported by Li *et al.* (2015), proposes that alien species closely related to native species are more likely to establish, compared to less related species. This phenomenon is attributed to the presence of shared traits, such as analogous physiological tolerances to temperature or water stress, or comparable niche requirements. Conversely, the second hypothesis, postulated by Darwin himself (1859) and supported by Schaefer *et al.* (2011), proposes instead that alien species are more likely to establish when they are sufficiently different from resident, native species, thus allowing them to occupy empty niches. The diversity of the remaining hypotheses in **Figure 1** are captured by the following three examples: the enemy-release hypothesis (Keane & Crawley, 2002) which posits that the absence of natural predators or parasitoids facilitates the establishment of alien species; the disturbance hypothesis (Elton, 1958; Hobbs & Huenneke, 1992), which predicts higher probability of establishment within disturbed ecosystems (e.g., fire, soil erosion, human action); and the novel weapon hypothesis (Callaway & Ridenour, 2004), which postulates that alien species with different traits in relation to closely related native species (e.g. leaves with very toxic compounds that prevent predation or roots with greater extension and absorption of nutrients) may confer a competitive advantage that would favour their establishment and the displacement of native species. The evaluation of any of these hypotheses requires robust species inventories regarding the status of native species and the detection of introduced species.

Genetic tools have become a valuable complement for the analysis and testing of the aforementioned hypotheses (Li *et al.*, 2015; Marx *et al.*, 2016; Schaefer *et al.*, 2011; Xu *et al.*, 2022). Specifically, DNA barcoding has proven to be a useful tool to understand native versus introduced species status. For example, the woodlouse species

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Halophiloscia couchii was considered to be native to the Canary Islands. However, a subsequent analysis of barcode sequences from both continental and insular populations revealed it to be a recent introduction (Bidegaray-Batista *et al.*, 2015).

Know to preserve: understanding extinction risk for an evidence-based approach to conservation

Since 1500, more than 60% of documented extinctions of terrestrial endemic species have occurred on oceanic islands (Whittaker *et al.*, 2017). This phenomenon, in conjunction with the documented impacts of introduced species on oceanic islands (Bellard *et al.*, 2017), underscores the necessity for improved strategies to effectively protect oceanic island biodiversity. The risk of extinction faced by endemic species on oceanic islands is influenced by both intrinsic characteristics of the species themselves, and extrinsic factors of the environment in which they inhabit. The mitigation of extrinsic factors, which include ongoing human impacts (e.g. habitat destruction, water pollution), climate change, desertification and natural disasters such as hurricanes or earthquakes, is a challenging endeavour (Caujapé-Castells *et al.*, 2010; Harter *et al.*, 2015; Heinen *et al.*, 2018; Huang *et al.*, 2020; Kier *et al.*, 2009; Palm *et al.*, 2022; Whittaker & Fernández-Palacios, 2007). In addition, these factors may synergistically pose a heightened extinction risk on oceanic islands. Also, oceanic islands themselves accentuate extinction risk due to their geographical isolation and often small area (Emerson, 2002; Heinen *et al.*, 2018; Terzopoulou *et al.*, 2015; Trevino *et al.*, 2007). The isolation between islands limits gene flow among co-specific populations, an effect that is particularly accentuated in poorly dispersing species such as those without the ability to fly or without the ability to balloon, in the case of spiders (Suárez *et al.*, 2022; Waters *et al.*, 2020). This factor increases the extinction risk of poorly dispersing species compared to well-dispersing species because the latter can mitigate local extinctions under a ‘rescue effect’ for the migration of individuals to those populations at risk (Brown & Kodric-Brown, 1977). Additionally, other traits that have been demonstrated to increase the risk of extinction include larger body size (Nolte *et al.*, 2019; Terzopoulou *et al.*, 2015), low population density (Purvis *et al.*, 2000), specialist feeding, especially during immature phases (Seibold *et al.*, 2015), or the association with rare habitats with localised geographical distributions, or with other threatened species (Nolte *et al.*, 2019).

It is hypothesised that single-island endemic species (SIE) may be subject to a higher risk of extinction than those which inhabit multiple islands.. This is attributed to their smaller geographic range and, in many cases, their smaller population size, which is less resistant to demographic fluctuations or natural disasters (Nolte *et al.*, 2019; Purvis *et al.*, 2000; Terzopoulou *et al.*, 2015). However, under certain conditions it may be that species distributed across multiple islands are subject to similar extinction risk. Connectivity of populations of multiple-island endemic species (MIE) can occur within a spectrum between two extremes. The first is characterised by panmixia, with high levels of gene flow between islands as in the case of very generalist and well dispersing species (e.g. Backs & Ashley, 2016; García-Verdugo *et al.*, 2010). The second is where species exhibit strong population structure within islands, with an absence of gene flow among them. Within the latter scenario, the extinction of island populations would be an irreversible event, thus contributing to enhanced extinction risk at the species level (e.g. Emerson *et al.*, 2000a; Mairal *et al.*, 2015).

In the context of increasing risk of species extinction, genetic studies are of considerable utility in providing information on the status of MIE species and the genetic connectivity between their populations, thereby facilitating the improvement of conservation policies. The application of competing but conceptually related conservation units such as Evolutionary Significant Units (ESUs: Ryder, 1986; Waples, 1995), Designatable Units (DUs: Mee *et al.*, 2015), Management Units (MUs: Funk *et al.*, 2012; Palsbøll *et al.*, 2007), or Distinct Population Segments (DPSs: Waples, 1991) has been demonstrated to be effective in the characterisation of variation within MIE, thus achieving conservation objectives. This is particularly evident in the case of ESUs, where genetic variability has been effectively resolved into conservation-relevant units within species such as the tiger quoll *Dasyurus maculatus* (Firestone *et al.*, 1999), Australian mammals (Weeks *et al.*, 2016) or American fishes (Coates *et al.*, 2018).

With growing evidence for the widespread presence of cryptic species within arthropods (Bickford *et al.*, 2007; Li & Wiens, 2023), the study of MIE species has the potential to infer cryptic species on islands. By definition, cryptic species are those in which two or more different species are misclassified (and hidden) under a single species due to a lack of morphological diagnosability (Bickford *et al.*, 2007). A compelling illustration of this phenomenon is provided by the Neotropical skipper butterfly *Astraptes fulgerator*, with the inference of ten cryptic species from barcode

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sequences (Hebert et al., 2004). In the context of oceanic islands and MIE species, the barcode sequencing of the soil-adapted beetle *Geomitopsis franzi* has resulted in the delimitation of at least eight cryptic species within the Canary Islands (Pérez-Delgado *et al.*, 2022). A similar approach was adopted by Saitoh *et al.* (2015), who barcoded island bird populations within the Japanese archipelago, revealing at least 11 cryptic lineages within 11 different species of birds. Finally, in a comparable study, barcoding was used to infer a cryptic lineage within the butterfly species *Eurema hecabe* in the Samoan Islands (Bruschini *et al.*, 2023).

Study framework: focusing on Canary Islands

The Canary Islands are a volcanic oceanic archipelago with a surface area of 7,450 km², and located approximately 100 km from the African continent. The archipelago is composed of eight major islands (from east to west, La Graciosa, Lanzarote, Fuerteventura, Gran Canaria, Tenerife, La Gomera, La Palma and El Hierro) along with five islets (Montaña Clara, Alegranza, Roque del Este, Roque del Oeste and Lobos). The estimated geological origin of the islands ranges from 1 to 20.6 million years (Mya) (Troll & Carracedo, 2016), with the age of the islands decreasing from east to west (**Figure 2**). The currently more favoured model for the east-west age structure is the movement of the African tectonic plate over a stationary mantle plume (Zaczek *et al.*, 2015).

Figure 2. Map of the Canary Islands with annotations of the geological age according to Troll & Carracedo (2016).

The Canary Islands, in conjunction with the Atlantic archipelagos of the Azores, Madeira, the Selvagens and Cape Verde, constitute the Macaronesian region. These archipelagos are included in the Mediterranean biodiversity hotspot, with particularly high levels of endemism (Myers *et al.*, 2000). Among the five archipelagos, the Canary Islands are the most biologically diverse, with approximately 16,300 known species, of which 27% are endemic (<https://www.biodiversidadcanarias.es/biota/> accessed on March 3, 2024). This high endemism is thought to be due to a combination of factors that promote habitat diversity (Troll & Carracedo, 2016; Whittaker & Fernández-Palacios, 2007), such as: (i) the subtropical location of the archipelago and its climatic influence; (ii) the age range of the islands, which varies from 1 to 20.6 my; (iii) altitudes of up to 3,715 meters above sea level; (iv) the influence of the north-east trade winds ('alisios'), and; (v) the isolation of the archipelago with respect to the nearest continental masses, such as Africa (approximately 100km) and Europe (approximately 1,000 km). Collectively, these factors render the Canary Islands a favourable location for the study of biodiversity, biogeography and evolutionary processes (e.g. Andújar *et al.*, 2022; Emerson & Oromí, 2005; García-Olivares *et al.*, 2019; Juan *et al.*, 2000; Patiño *et al.*, 2015; Pérez-Delgado *et al.*, 2022; Salces-Castellano *et al.*, 2021; Sanmartín *et al.*, 2008; Suárez *et al.*, 2022).

The Canary Islands can be categorised into six well-differentiated habitats. These habitats, in increasing altitude from sea level, are: (i) *Euphorbia* shrublands; (ii) thermo-sclerophyllous woodlands; (iii) laurel forests; (iv) Canarian pine forests; (v) summit shrublands; and, (vi) alpine habitat (del Arco Aguilar *et al.*, 2010; del Arco Aguilar & Delgado Rodríguez, 2018). In the context of this doctoral thesis, the focal habitats are the laurel forest and the *Euphorbia* shrublands (**Figure 3**).

Figure 3. Photographs of the two habitats studied in this doctoral thesis, laurel forest and *Euphorbia* shrublands. (a) Anaga laurel forest, Tenerife; (b) Anaga laurel forest, Tenerife; (c) Los Tilos laurel forest, La Palma; (d) San Andrés *Euphorbia* shrublands, Tenerife; (e) *Euphorbia canariensis*, one of the dominant species on *Euphorbia* shrublands; and, (f) Güimar *Euphorbia* shrublands, Tenerife.

Laurel forest is the focal habitat of the first two chapters of this doctoral thesis. Laurel forests (**Figure 3 a-c**) are tree formations located at altitudes between 350 and 1,500m on windward slopes with high influence of trade wind clouds (del Arco Aguilar *et al.*, 2010; del Arco Aguilar & Delgado Rodríguez, 2018). These forests are predominantly located in Tenerife, La Gomera, La Palma and El Hierro, with smaller remnant patches surviving human disturbance on the islands of Gran Canaria and Fuerteventura. The laurel forest is absent from the islands of Lanzarote and La Graciosa. The annual temperature within this habitat ranges between 13 and 18°C, with an annual rainfall regime between 500 and 1,200 mm, depicting a sub-humid climate (del Arco Aguilar & Delgado Rodríguez, 2018). Laurel forests are mainly composed of endemic plant species such as *Laurus novocanariensis*, *Arbutus canariensis*, *Sideroxylon canariense* and *Canarina canariensis*; as well as native non-endemic species including *Ilex canariensis*, *Apollonias barbujana*, *Persea indica*, *Visnea mocanera*, *Prunus lusitanica*, and *Morella faya* (Aguilera Klink *et al.*, 1994; del Arco Aguilar & Delgado Rodríguez, 2018).

Euphorbia shrublands (**Figure 3 d-f**) are the focal habitat of the third chapter of the thesis. This habitat, present in all the Canary Islands, is characterised by an arid or semi-arid climate with average annual temperatures above 19°C, annual rainfall between 50-300 mm and high exposure to solar radiation (del Arco Aguilar *et al.*, 2010; del Arco Aguilar & Delgado Rodríguez, 2018). *Euphorbia* shrublands are located from sea level to approximately 300m, on windward slopes, or 600m, on leeward slopes. This habitat has a dominant component of endemic plant species including *Euphorbia canariensis*, *Euphorbia handiensis*, *Euphorbia lamarckii*, *Kleinia neriifolia* and *Rumex lunaria*, together with native non-endemic species such as *Euphorbia balsamifera*, *Euphorbia regis-jubae*, *Periploca laevigata* and *Schizogyne sericea* (Aguilera Klink *et al.*, 1994; del Arco Aguilar & Delgado Rodríguez, 2018).

Arthropods (**Figure 4**) constitute more than half of the approximately 16,300 species recorded in the Canary Islands, with approximately 8,246 species of which 3,271 are endemic and 4,058 native non-endemic species. The remaining 917 species (11.1% of the recorded arthropods) are considered introduced. The present doctoral thesis is focused on the study of the Coleoptera and Araneae. Of the 2,264 species of Coleoptera species recorded on the Canary Islands, 1,345 are endemic, of which 494 can be classified as MIE and 851 as SIE. A further 716 species are native non-endemic, of which 538 are present in multiple islands (multi-island native non-endemic: MINE) and 178 are only recorded in a single island (single-island native non-endemic: SINE). The remaining 203 species are considered to be introduced. Within the Araneae order, 510 species inhabit the islands of which 314 are endemic. Among the endemic species, 105 are classified as MIE, while 209 are categorised as SIE. In the case of native non-endemic species, from the 166 species recorded, 117 are classified as MINE and 49 as SINE. The remaining 30 species are considered to be introduced (<https://www.biodiversidadcanarias.es/biota/> consulted on 7 March 2024).

General introduction

Figure 4. Examples of the biodiversity of arthropods present in the Canary Islands. (a) *Acherontia atropos* (native non-endemic); (b) *Camponotus feae* (endemic); (c) *Macarophaeus varius* (endemic); (d) *Philanthus triangulum* (native non-endemic); (e) *Ancistrocerus haematodes* (native non-endemic); (f) *Olios canariensis* (endemic); (g) *Dicladispa occator* (endemic); (h) *Menemerus semilimbatus* (native non-endemic); (i) *Lycaena phlaeas* (native non-endemic); (j) *Lepromoris gibba* (endemic); (k) *Aphaenogaster hesperia* (endemic); (l) *Eristalis tenax* (native non-endemic); (m) *Danaus chrysippus* (native non-endemic); (n) *Thyreus histrionicus* (native non-endemic); (o) *Blepharopsis mendica* (native non-endemic); (p) *Pimelia ascendens* (endemic).

Objectives

This doctoral thesis implements a structured sampling approach to both Coleoptera and Araneae within the Canary Islands, with the objective of addressing ecological and evolutionary processes. The central aim of this thesis is twofold: firstly, to improve our knowledge of the mechanisms that drive community assembly; and secondly, to increase our understanding about the extinction risks faced by individual species. To achieve this, the following specific objectives are developed throughout the three chapters of the thesis:

1. To understand how alien species can become established in native communities using well-characterised communities of Canary Island laurel forest beetles, beetles, within the framework of Darwin's conundrum hypotheses, through a genetic approach (**Chapter I**).
2. To assess how the extinction risk of native endemic and non-endemic beetle and spider species varies as a function of the evolutionary independence among island populations by implementing an Evolutionary Significant Unit (ESU) based protocol using mitochondrial genetic data from Canary Island laurel forests species (**Chapter II**).
3. To understand the interaction of different processes in the evolutionary history of the monotypic flightless genus *Lepromoris*, characteristic of the *Euphorbia* shrublands of the Canary Islands, using an integrative taxonomic approach (**Chapter III**).

CHAPTER I

Toward understanding insect species introduction and establishment: a community-level barcoding approach using island beetles

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Abstract

Since Darwin put forward two opposing hypotheses to explain the successful establishment of species in areas outside their native ranges, the preadaptation and competition-relatedness hypotheses, known as Darwin's naturalisation conundrum, numerous studies have sought to understand the relative importance of each. Here we take advantage of well-characterised beetle communities across laurel forests of the Canary Islands for a first evaluation of the relative support for Darwin's two hypotheses within arthropods. We generated a mitogenome backbone tree comprising nearly half of the beetle genera recorded within the Canary Islands for the phylogenetic placement of native and introduced species sampled in laurel forests, using cytochrome c oxidase I (COI) sequences. For comparative purposes, we also assembled and phylogenetically placed a data set of COI sequences for introduced beetle species that were not sampled within laurel forests. Our results suggest a stronger effect of species preadaptation over resource competition, while also revealing an underappreciated shortfall in arthropod biodiversity data-knowledge of species as being native or introduced. We name this the Humboldtian shortfall, and suggest that similar studies using arthropods should incorporate DNA barcode sequencing to mitigate this problem.

Introduction

Since Darwin first observed the establishment of exotic or alien species in areas outside their native distribution ranges, leading him to postulate what is now known as Darwin's naturalisation conundrum (Darwin, 1859), understanding the drivers of alien species establishment, and in some cases their biological invasion, has become a major area of investigation (Fristoe *et al.*, 2021; Mack *et al.*, 2000; Richardson *et al.*, 2000; Vilà *et al.*, 2011). Darwin's naturalisation conundrum proposes two alternative hypotheses that may favour the establishment of non-native species (**Figure 1**).

Figure 1. Darwin's naturalisation conundrum. Upper panel: hypothetical phylogeny of beetle species indicating relatedness among native (black) and non-native (grey) species. Bottom left panel: the preadaptation hypothesis predicts that introduced species that are evolutionarily related to native species are expected to have higher establishment success than less related species, facilitated by trait similarity. Bottom right panel: the competition-relatedness hypothesis predicts that introduced species that are unrelated to native species will have higher establishment success, through limited resource competition with native species.

The first is the preadaptation hypothesis (**Figure 1**), where alien species that are evolutionarily related to native species are expected to have higher establishment success than less related species (Li *et al.*, 2015). The proposed mechanistic explanation is that alien species that are closely related to native species are likely to share similar traits with those native species, such as diet, physiological tolerances and ecological niche requirements, facilitating their establishment (Burns & Strauss, 2012; Li *et al.*, 2015; Schaefer *et al.*, 2011). The second is the competition-relatedness hypothesis (**Figure 1**),

where alien species that are unrelated to native species are suggested to have higher establishment success through limited resource competition with native species (Darwin, 1859). The proposed mechanistic explanation is that alien species that are more distantly related to native species are less likely to share similar niche requirements. Such niche differentiation should act to both limit competition for resources, and facilitate the occupation of new or unfilled niches (Fristoe *et al.*, 2021; Schaefer *et al.*, 2011). In the current climate of global biodiversity loss, with concomitant negative knock-on effects to ecosystem services (Kumschick *et al.*, 2015; Mack *et al.*, 2000), and increasing economic costs from alien species (Diagne *et al.*, 2021), understanding the ecological and evolutionary dynamics of biological invasion is an important area of investigation (Davidson *et al.*, 2011; Fristoe *et al.*, 2021; Li *et al.*, 2015; Park *et al.*, 2020; Procheş *et al.*, 2008), for which establishment dynamics are a fundamental foundation.

In addition to the original hypotheses that form the so-called Darwin's naturalisation conundrum, at least 33 additional hypotheses have been proposed as potential mechanistic explanations for alien species establishment (Jeschke & Heger, 2018), of which four make predictions based upon similarity among species. All four are consistent with Darwin's competition-relatedness hypothesis, in that they predict that introduced species that are less related (similar) to native species will have higher establishment success. The first of these is the enemy-release hypothesis (Keane & Crawley, 2002), which posits that the absence of natural predators or parasitoids may enhance the successful establishment of alien species in new territories. Thus alien species that are distantly related to native species will have an establishment advantage over more related species by not being subjected to the pressure of native predators or parasitoids (Liu & Stiling, 2006; Torchin *et al.*, 2001). The second is the life-history hypothesis (Cassey, 2002; Jeschke & Strayer, 2006; Van Kleunen *et al.*, 2010), which argues that evolutionarily distant alien species may have numerous different functional traits in comparison with native species, and that these may allow them to successfully establish and coexist with native species. The third is the limiting similarity hypothesis, which proposes that the probability of successful establishment of a given introduced species increases as a function of how different it is from native species (MacArthur & Levins, 1967). While this hypothesis does not explicitly reference evolutionary relatedness, it can be considered an extension of Darwin's competition-relatedness hypothesis under a general model where species diverge in multidimensional trait space through time.

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Finally, the novel weapons hypothesis predicts that introduced species with novel traits, relative to traits within the native community, will have a higher likelihood of establishment through competitive advantage (Callaway & Ridenour, 2004). This hypothesis is consistent with Darwin's competition-relatedness hypothesis, under the assumption that the more unrelated species are, the more likely they are to present different weapons.

Our understanding of how relatedness between introduced and native species may influence establishment success has been informed by phylogenetic analysis of community assembly. This has been studied particularly more in plants than in other organisms such as invertebrates (e.g., insects or arachnids), given the comparatively greater availability of historical data for plants (Daehler, 2014; Diez *et al.*, 2008; Fristoe *et al.*, 2021; Li *et al.*, 2015; Schaefer *et al.*, 2011). Well-studied floristic systems have also provided comprehensive time series, such as the flora of the Azorean islands, where introduced species records extend back to 1494 (Schaefer *et al.*, 2011). In contrast, invertebrates in general, and arthropods in particular, have received relatively little attention, and this is likely due to several complicating factors. Introduced species are likely to be difficult to detect, even in the early stages of invasion, as exemplified by the crazy ant *Anoplolepis gracilipes* on Christmas Island, detected only when it had already spread through rainforest habitat, causing serious problems to biodiversity (O'Dowd *et al.*, 2003). The typically small size and often cryptic nature of invertebrate species may also lead to detection difficulties (Simberloff, 2013).

The lack of community phylogenetic investigations focusing on introduced invertebrate species is an obstacle to understanding what, if any, general principles may underpin the successful establishment of introduced invertebrate species. This is particularly relevant given the substantial threats to biodiversity, associated ecosystems services, and food security, posed by invertebrate species. At a global scale, it has been estimated that approximately 8.7 billion U.S. dollars are spent yearly to counteract the negative effects of introduced invertebrate species or to prevent their establishment (Diagne *et al.*, 2021). While elimination is desirable, mitigation efforts are often more realistic, as exemplified by *Lymantria dispar* and *Reticulitermes flavipes*. The first is a European moth, capable of devastating forest damage within its introduced North American range (Sharov & Liebhold, 1998). The second is a subterranean termite native to the east of the United States, capable of extensive damage to native forests, buildings

and cultural heritages within its introduced European range (Khan & Ahmad, 2018). Global food security now has to mitigate against species such as the Colorado potato beetle, *Leptinotarsa decemlineata*, introduced to Europe (Grapputo *et al.*, 2005), the Japanese beetle, *Popillia japonica*, introduced to both North America and Europe (Mori *et al.*, 2021), and the globally established whitefly, *Bemisia tabaci* (Oliveira, *et al.*, 2001).

Despite the challenges posed by arthropod systems, progress can be made if regional faunas have been well-characterised, and local communities have been subject to detailed inventory. Here we take advantage of well-characterised communities of beetle species within the laurel cloud forests of the Canary Islands (Salces-Castellano *et al.*, 2021) to evaluate the influence of phylogenetic relatedness on introduced species establishment. Using species inventory data from 31 plots sampled across the four western Canary Islands, together with data from a regional biodiversity databank, and publicly available DNA sequences, we categorise species as native (NAT) or introduced as a result of human activity (INT), and further categorise NAT species as endemic (END) or not endemic (NATnotend). Distinguishing between NATnotend and INT species origins is often challenging (Patiño & Vanderpoorten, 2015), and we address this by recategorizing presumed NATnotend species as INT if they present high sequence matching ($\geq 99\%$ similarity) to individuals sampled outside the Canary Islands. We use this data to determine the presence of introduced beetle species within laurel cloud forest habitat of the Canary Islands, and to test between the relative roles of the preadaptation and competition hypotheses.

Endemic species, by virtue of their evolved nature within the archipelago (but see Emerson & Kolm, 2005) can typically be assumed to have been present within the archipelago prior to the arrival of NATnotend species. In turn, species derived from human introductions represent a subsequent and more recent phase of community assembly. This temporal structure provides an opportunity to contrast phylogenetic structure among different establishment cohorts to infer community assembly processes through time. As community assembly progresses and species richness and complexity increase, the dimensionality of unoccupied niche space should diminish, providing less opportunity for species to establish as a consequence of increased competition for limited resources. We therefore hypothesise that more recently established species within the laurel cloud forests (INT species) will typically present stronger signatures for the preadaptation hypothesis, compared to species of less recent origin (NATnotend species).

To address the aforementioned hypotheses, we first construct a mitogenome backbone tree for sampled genera, and use phylogenetic placement of COI sequences for individual species within genera to then estimate phylogenetic relatedness among species.

Materials and Methods

Study taxa and sampling framework

The beetle fauna of the Canary Islands comprises 2,264 described species, corresponding to 736 genera from 70 families (<https://www.biodiversidadcanarias.es/biota>; accessed: 21 June 2022). Across the four most western islands of Tenerife, La Gomera, La Palma and El Hierro the fauna comprises 1,755 species within 643 genera, of which 1,572 species (from 545 genera) are categorised as native, among which 978 species are endemic (END) to the Canary Islands. The remaining 183 species are categorised as introduced (INT), and belong to 137 genera, of which 98 are only represented within the four islands.

Field sampling, mtDNA sequencing, and PBS delimitation

In addition to the 25 laurel forest plots described in Salces-Castellano *et al.* (2021), six plots were sampled in 2019 and 2020 (**Figure 2**, **Table S1**), following the protocol described in Emerson *et al.* (2017).

Figure 2. Laurel forest sampling plots across the four western Canary Islands. See **Table S1** for specific details for each sampling plot.

Individuals from the newly sampled plots were sorted to parataxonomic units (PU), from which four individuals within each plot, if possible, were sequenced for an 824 bp region of the mtDNA COI gene (hereafter referred to as COI-3P, reflecting its location toward the 3' end of the gene). For some particularly difficult taxonomic groups (e.g. the genera *Atheta* (Staphylinidae) and *Laparocerus* (Curculionidae), and the tribe Cryptorhynchini), more than 4 individuals were sequenced. Sequences were then combined with those from Salces-Castellano *et al.* (2021). To identify presumed biological species (PBS; Emerson *et al.*, 2017), a custom R script available from GitHub (Salces-Castellano *et al.*, 2021; <https://github.com/asalcescastellano/Divergence-threshold.git>) was used to produce an unweighted pair group method with arithmetic mean (UPGMA) tree from pairwise K2P distances, using an alignment of all sequences from all PUs. This script first implements a conservative maximum intraspecific divergence threshold of 8% to create individual lineage alignments. Under this divergence threshold, it is assumed that all individuals of a given biological species will be represented within a single lineage, but that a given lineage may comprise more than one biological species. The script then generates a Table summarising: (i) the PU composition within each lineage; (ii) for each PU within a lineage, the proportion of individuals from that PU included within the lineage, and (iii) when a lineage comprises individuals from more than one PU, the presence or absence of monophyly among individuals from the same PU. Lineages exclusively comprising all individuals within a given PU were inferred to represent a single PBS. Individuals from PUs that segregated across more than one lineage were revised to evaluate potential PU assignment error or possible laboratory contamination, with the removal of any sequences ascribed to the latter. When two or more PUs segregated within the same lineage, individuals were revised morphologically, and in the absence of any differences the lineage was inferred to represent a single PBS. For lineages comprising two or more morphologically distinct PUs, and where PUs were phylogenetically structured within the lineage, PUs were inferred to represent different PBS. Morphologically distinct PUs that showed no clear segregation with regard to mtDNA variation were inferred to represent recent speciation with incomplete lineage sorting and/or gene flow, and were removed for subsequent analyses.

For each PBS, from one to four individuals representative of mtDNA sequence variation within that PBS were sequenced for the 658 bp barcode region of the COI gene (hereafter referred to as COI-5P, reflecting its location toward the 5' end of the gene, see

Appendix S1, for more details about PCR amplification conditions). COI-5P and COI-3P are non-overlapping fragments of the COI gene. For both COI regions, PCR products were sequenced using the Sanger DNA sequencing service of Macrogen (www.macrogen.com).

Taxonomic assignment of PBS

Specimens from PBS were examined and taxonomically assigned by HL and EJJ using dichotomous keys and additional information (Appendix S2). Taxonomic assignments were further assessed and refined by comparison of barcode sequences against a near complete reference library for the 626 species of Curculionoidea (weevils) of the Canary Islands (Machado, 2022; Stüben, 2021), and public databases. Barcode sequences were used for (i) BLAST search (`blastn -outfmt 5 -evalue 0.001 -max_target_seqs 100`) against the NCBI *nucleotide* database and, (ii) species identification using the BOLD identification system within the BOLD System database.

Assessing existing native and introduced species categorisations

Inferred native but not endemic (NATnotend), endemic (END) or introduced (INT) status of species are provided within the Canary Islands Biodiversity databank (<https://www.biodiversidadcanarias.es/biota>). However, it is recognised that distinguishing between native and introduced status is often difficult in natural communities (Anderson *et al.*, 2019). Thus, to further refine inferences between NATnotend and INT species status, we used high barcode sequence matching ($\geq 99\%$) to individuals sampled outside the macaronesian region as evidence that inferred NATnotend species are more likely of introduced origin (Andújar *et al.*, 2022; Cicconardi *et al.*, 2017).

For those species that could only be identified to the genus level, assignment to either NATnotend, END or INT, was based upon species records for the genus within the Canary Islands, together with patterns of genetic variation among sequenced individuals. If all described species within a genus are END, then the species is assumed to be one of these endemisms, with a similar inference framework if all species within a genus are NATnotend, or INT. For genera with both END and NATnotend species, we took two

approaches for downstream analyses. As a first approach, we assigned a status when the probability of a sampled species having that status was $\geq 80\%$, and excluded those species for which this could not be achieved. As a second approach, we excluded all species where status could not be definitively assigned. For all other cases, we assessed patterns of genetic variation and its spatial structuring, assuming species with moderate to high, and/or geographically structured genetic variation, to be NATnotend or END, and species with no, or limited but geographically unstructured genetic variation, to be INT, with equivocal species being excluded.

MtDNA COI reference sequences for unsampled introduced species

To obtain reference sequences for introduced species not sampled by us, taxonomic searches were performed in BOLD Systems and GenBank for all introduced species recorded within the four western Canary Islands. For those species for which a reference sequence was not available, and for which the species was the only representative of the genus among the islands, sequences from a congeneric species, when available, were used as a proxy for the introduced species. When possible, both COI regions were extracted from complete mitogenomes. In the absence of a complete mitogenome, we downloaded both regions and concatenated them in Geneious Prime 2019.1.1 (Biomatters, Auckland, New Zealand). We prioritised obtaining both regions from the same individual, opting for different individuals of the same species when this was not possible. In the absence of both regions, a single region was used

Mitogenome sequencing, assembly and alignment

With the objective of generating a robust mitogenome phylogenetic backbone tree for all sampled genera, a GenBank search was carried out to identify all available mitogenomes corresponding to genera cited for the Canary Islands. These mitogenomes were complemented by *de novo* generation of mitogenomes for all genera sampled within the cloud forest plots that were not represented in GenBank.

For *de novo* generation of mitogenomes, one individual from each genus was used for DNA extraction, using complete specimens with the head/pronotum and abdomen separated. Extractions were carried out using the Mag-Bind® Blood & Tissue DNA HDQ

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96 kit (Omega Bio-tek, GA, USA) with a KingFisher Flex (ThermoFisher). DNA concentrations (ng/ μ L) were then quantified using a Tecan Infinite 200Pro M Nano+, for the purpose of sample concentration normalisation and pooling. A total of eight equimolar pools (**Table S2**), comprising a total of 131 genera, were prepared. Pools were subjected to DNA fragmentation through sonication with a Covaris M220 ultrasonicator, prior to preparing eight DNA libraries (one per pool) using the TruSeq Nano DNA Library Prep kit. Due to low yield, a single library was concentrated using the Zymo Research DNA Clean & Concentratortm-5 kit (Zymo Research, Irvine, CA, USA). Sequencing of the eight libraries was performed on the Illumina MiSeq platform (Illumina Inc., San Diego, CA) (2x 300 bp).

Sequence products were processed and assembled using four different methods: IDBA (Peng *et al.*, 2012), Ray (Boisvert *et al.*, 2010), SPAdes (Bankevich *et al.*, 2012) and Celera (Myers *et al.*, 2000). Parameters used for each method are provided in **Table S3**. The resulting contigs from each method were then evaluated in Geneious Prime to eliminate those with less than 2,000 bp, for the purpose of improved processing time. Using the function *De Novo Assemble* in Geneious Prime, contigs were then assembled into supercontigs. Using the mitogenome of *Tenebrio obscurus* (GenBank accession number MG739327) as a reference, mitogenomic supercontigs were identified. Only regions consistently retrieved with at least two assemblers were retained, and a 50% majority rule consensus sequence was generated. Reference COI-3P and COI-5P sequences (described above) were then used to taxonomically assign each mitogenome. Mitogenomes were annotated using the MITOS webserver (Bernt *et al.*, 2013) and then corrected if necessary in Geneious Prime, avoiding gene overlaps and correcting gene start codon positions to correspond to a Methionine. Protein coding genes (PCGs) were then extracted from individual mitogenomes and aligned individually with MAFFT in Geneious Prime before concatenating all 13 PCGs within a single FASTA. An additional FASTA was also generated with the 13 PCGs translated to proteins.

Mitogenome backbone tree

RAxML and Phylobayes were used to reconstruct phylogenetic relationships among genera using both the nucleotide and amino acid alignments for the 13 PCGs. Partitioning by gene and by codon was used for the nucleotide alignment for the RAxML analysis,

with the following parameters: 25 distinct rate categories (-c), the GTRCATI model, 12345 as the number seed, Lewis ascertainment bias correction, and 75 iterations. For the amino acid alignment, the following parameters were implemented within RAxML: 25 distinct rate categories (-c), the PROTCATGTR model, 12345 as the number seed, and 25 iterations. Due to computational limitations, RAxML analyses were run using 75 iterations in the case of the nucleotide alignment and 25 iterations for the amino acid alignment. For the Phylobayes analyses, for both the nucleotide and amino acid alignments, two independent chains (same options for nucleotide and amino acid chains, containing default options with constant sites removed (-dc) and -cat -gtr as an infinite mixture model) were run for 30 days, assessing chain convergence every three days, together with the number of iterations within each chain, using the software Tracer. Resulting trees were compared to recently published higher-level phylogenies for Coleoptera (e.g., Mckenna *et al.*, 2015; Timmermans *et al.*, 2016; Zhang *et al.*, 2018) to evaluate consistency with regard to previously described relationships.

Phylogenetic tree placement

Phylogenetic placement of COI sequences on the mitogenome backbone tree was performed using the tool “RAxML-HPC v.8 on XSEDE (8.2.12) - Phylogenetic tree inference using maximum likelihood/rapid bootstrapping run on XSEDE” on the CIPRES Science Gateway V. 3.3. The input file was generated with a global alignment of all PBS, together with sequences for introduced species obtained from BOLD and GenBank, using MAFFT in Geneious Prime. Phylogenetic tree placement was run with the default options, with the above mentioned mitogenome backbone tree defined as the Binary Backbone (-r), a GTRCAT model, and 1000 alternative runs. Results were visually assessed in FigTree to evaluate the taxonomic consistency of phylogenetic placement within the mitogenome tree.

Relatedness analyses

In a first step, the R packages “ape” (Paradis *et al.*, 2004) and “picante” (Kembel *et al.*, 2010) were used to prune (function *prune.sample*) the phylogenetic placement tree to yield the following pruned trees: (i) a tree including END, NATnotend and INT species

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sampled within laurel forests; (ii) a tree with END and NATnotend species sampled within laurel forests, together with INT species that were not sampled within laurel forests, and; (iii) a tree with END and NATnotend species sampled within laurel forests. To test for the existence of phylogenetic clustering or overdispersion, the following partitions were created within the three datasets, respectively: (i) NAT species vs INT species sampled in laurel forests; (ii) NAT species vs INT species not sampled in laurel forests, and; (iii) END species vs NATnotend species. The first and second datasets are used to test between the relative roles of the preadaptation and competition-relatedness hypothesis. The first and third data sets are used to address our hypothesis that more recently established species within the laurel cloud forests will typically present stronger signatures for the preadaptation hypothesis, compared to species of less recent origin. Within each partition of each dataset, cophenetic distances were calculated with the *cophenetic.distance* function, to then calculate the mean nearest taxon distance (mntd) with the *ses.mntd* (standard effect size of mntd) function using “taxa.label” as the null model with a total of 1000 iterations. This null model randomises labels across taxa within the distance matrix. Analyses yield a mntd.obs.z value (*ses.mntd* vs. null communities) with an associated p-value with the following interpretation: mntd.obs.z values greater than 0 with p-value > 0.95 indicate significant phylogenetic overdispersion, while a negative value of mntd.obs.z and a p-value < 0.05 indicates significant phylogenetic clustering (**Figure 3**). The above analyses were also performed at the scale of individual islands. For island-level analyses, species records from the biota databank were used to complete distributions of introduced species at the island scale.

Analyses were also carried out comparing among the set of introduced species sampled within laurel forest, to further test between the preadaptation and competition hypotheses. Species were ranked by the number of plots within which they were sampled and ranks were progressively grouped, in both an ascending and descending order, conducting mntd analyses at each level. Under the assumption that higher plot occupancy for introduced species reflects higher establishment success, we expect relatedness trends observed across the full phylogeny to be more pronounced for more established introduced species. Consistency with relatedness trends observed across the full phylogeny was also evaluated using the R package “stats”, to conduct a GLM comparing mean relatedness to the nearest NAT species between the set of introduced species sampled in a single plot, and those introduced species sampled in more than one plot.

Figure 3. Community-level relatedness among introduced and native species under different phylogenetic expectations for establishment success. (A) Hypothetical phylogeny of beetle species indicating relatedness among native (black) and non-native (grey) species. (Bi) Six species introductions into a native community of three species, for which phylogenetic relationships are represented in (A). (Bii) Non-native species that are phylogenetically more related to native species have higher establishment success, resulting in a dominant signature of phylogenetic clustering at the community level. (Biii) Non-native species that are phylogenetically less related to native species have higher establishment success, resulting in a dominant signature of phylogenetic overdispersion at the community level. (Biv) Establishment success of non-native species is not phylogenetically related, resulting in the absence of phylogenetic structure at the community level.

Results

Sampling and mtDNA COI sequencing

A total of 4,225 individuals were sampled across the six new plots and classified to PU, from which 1,817 were selected for COI-3P sequencing, with a sequencing success of 88%, yielding a total of 1,591 COI-3P sequences. These sequences were combined with those from 25 previously sampled plots (Salces-Castellano *et al.*, 2021) yielding a total of 4,708 sequences, which segregated into 360 PBS (**Table S4**).

One hundred and sixty-two COI-5P sequences, representing 160 PBS, were obtained from Arjona *et al.* (2023), and these were complemented with the sequencing of further 426 individuals from across the remaining 200 PBS, yielding 402 new COI-5P sequences (94% sequencing success) for a total of 564 COI-5P sequences. Across the 360 PBS, 351 (97.5% of the total) were represented by both COI-5P and COI-3P sequences, while the remaining 9 PBS were only represented by COI-3P (**Table S4**).

Taxonomic assignment, species status, and new species records

A total of 268 PBS could be confidently taxonomically assigned to species level, with 92 assigned only to genus level. Four previously unrecorded species are herein reported for the Canary Islands. The species *Corticaria fagi*, *Corticarina cavicollis*, *Ischnopterapion modestum* and *Psylliodes instabilis* were all assigned with $\geq 99\%$ sequence similarity to individuals sampled outside the Canary Islands. Two previously unrecorded genera for the archipelago, *Cephennium* and *Pterostichus*, were both sampled for a single species, but without species-level taxonomic assignment. Due to their lack of previous records, these six species are likely to represent relatively recent introductions. Among the remaining 354 species, 224 were classified as END within the regional databank, with a further 56 classified as NATnotend and 19 as INT. Among the 56 species classified as NATnotend in the regional databank, we identified 19 as being INT, based on high sequence similarity to populations outside the Canary Islands. A further 55 species with only genus-level taxonomic assignment could not be unequivocally assigned biogeographic status using the regional databank, however 3 were assigned as INT based on their sequence similarity to populations outside the Canary Islands. Finally, 24 species without clear biogeographic status could be classified as END and 2 more as NATnotend

with a level of confidence using the 80% criterion (see methods). Thus, the 360 species were classified as 248 END species, 39 NATnotend, and 47 INT species, with only 26 remaining unassigned between END or NATnotend (**Table S4**).

MtDNA COI reference sequences for unsampled introduced species

A total of 183 species of Coleoptera are classified as introduced across the four western Canary Islands (<https://www.biodiversidadcanarias.es/biota>; accessed: 21 June 2022), and after excluding the 19 species that were sampled within the laurel forests (i.e., not including the six new species records and the recategorisation of 22 NATnotend species as INT), 164 species are inferred to be established in other habitats. Among these, sequences for the COI-3P, COI-5P, or both regions were available on either GenBank or BOLD for 131 (**Table S5**). Among the remaining 33 species, available sequences from congeneric species were used as proxies for 14 introduced species that are the single representatives of their genera in the Canary Islands (**Table S5**). A total of 93 species were represented by both COI regions, while 42 species only had COI-5P (barcode region) and 10 species only COI-3P. Thus, COI sequence data was obtained for 145 of the 164 introduced species not sampled within the laurel forest, yielding a total of 505 species together with the 360 PBS sampled by us, of which 444 species were represented by both COI regions.

Mitogenome sequencing

A total of 212 genera (29%) among the 736 recorded for the Canary Islands had an available mitogenome in GenBank (**Table S6**), including 59 of the 169 genera sampled in laurel forests. Individuals from the remaining 110 genera were selected for *de novo* mitogenome sequencing. This yielded a total of 82 mitogenomes, with the majority (75%) including all 13 PCG (**Table S7**). An additional thirty-one tribal- or subfamily-level mitogenomes were publicly available for genera that uniquely represent their corresponding tribe or subfamily within the archipelago (**Table S6**). This yielded a total of 341 mitogenomes, representing 141 of 169 (83%) genera sampled within laurel forests, and 56 of 118 (48%) genera corresponding to introduced species that were not sampled within laurel forest.

Mitogenome backbone tree generation and phylogenetic tree placement

Of the two mitogenome backbone trees that were generated with RAxML (amino acid and 13 PCG), only the 13 PCG tree resolved relationships at the superfamily level and, to a lesser extent, family-level, consistent with other previous beetle phylogenetic works (Crampton-Platt *et al.*, 2015; Timmermans *et al.*, 2016). For the Phylobayes analyses, only the two 13 PCG chains converged. No convergence was obtained for the amino acid chains after one month of analysis, therefore these analyses were not taken any further. Thus, the two trees derived from the 13 PCG matrix were considered as candidates for subsequent analyses. Among the two trees, the 13 PCG mitogenome backbone tree generated with Phylobayes was the more consistent with previously published mitogenome phylogenies for Coleoptera (Crampton-Platt *et al.*, 2015; Timmermans *et al.*, 2016; Zhang *et al.*, 2018), providing similar superfamily and family-level resolution. Thus, the Bayesian 13 PCG backbone tree was used for the placement of the 505 species using their associated COI sequence data. The resulting tree was visually assessed in Figtree to ensure that genera were monophyletic, and that genera fell within their corresponding families.

Relatedness analyses

Assessing the relatedness of INT species sampled within laurel forests against NAT laurel forest species at the archipelago scale revealed phylogenetic clustering, but with only marginal significance (mntd.obs.z value = -1.5278 , p-value = 0.06; **Table S8**). In contrast, comparing the relatedness of INT species that were not sampled in laurel forests, against NAT laurel forest species revealed significant overdispersion (mntd.obs.z value = $+2.7626$, p-value = 0.997; **Table S9**). Assessing relatedness of NATnotend species against END species yielded a marginally significant trend toward overdispersion (mntd.obs.z = $+1.5641$, p-value = 0.939; **Table S10**). However, no significant result was obtained when the species with uncertain biogeographic status (indicated in the **Table S4**) were excluded from the NATnotend against END analysis (**Table S11**).

At the scale of individual islands, assessing the relatedness of INT species sampled within laurel forests against NAT laurel forest species yielded significant clustering in each case: (TF: mntd.obs.z = -2.2860 , p-value = 0.013; LG: mntd.obs.z = -1.7408 , p-value = 0.041; LP: mntd.obs.z = -2.3849 , p-value = 0.011;

EH: $mntd.obs.z = -1.9269$, $p\text{-value} = 0.028$). Comparing the relatedness of INT species that were not sampled in laurel forests, against NAT laurel forest species yielded no significance (**Table S9**). Assessing the relatedness of NATnotend species against END species also yielded no significant relationships, whether using species under the 80% criterion or omitting all species with uncertain biogeographical origin (**Tables S10 and S11**, respectively).

Analyses of introduced species ranked by plot occurrence with ranks progressively grouped in both ascending and descending order, yielded trends toward phylogenetic clustering for all cumulative rank categories, with the exception of species sampled in only a single plot, which presented non-significant overdispersion. However, only three cumulative rank categories were marginally significant, with the remainder being non-significant (**Table S12**). Comparing relatedness to the nearest NAT species for INT species sampled in only a single plot ($N = 26$), and those sampled in two or more plots ($N = 21$) revealed that INT species with higher plot occurrence are significantly more closely related to NAT species (**Figure 4**) as indicated by the GLM ($p\text{-value} = 0.005$, **Table S13**).

Figure 4. Boxplots comparing nearest taxon distances to a native species for introduced species in laurel forest that were present in either one plot ($N=26$) or in two or more plots ($N=21$).

Discussion

Our results show that introduced species within the laurel forest of the Canary Islands are more closely related to native species than expected by chance, consistent with a dominant influence of species preadaptation over limited resource competition. The establishment of phylogenetically distant species, such as *Biphyllus lunatus* (Biphyllidae) and *Anommatus duodecimstriatus* (Bothrideridae), both sampled across multiple plots and each being the only species of their respective families in the Canary Islands, appears to have occurred less frequently. At the scales of both the archipelago, and of individual islands, introduced species of beetle sampled in laurel forest are typically more closely related to native laurel forest species than expected by chance. The relationship appears weaker at the archipelago scale, where it is only marginally significant. In contrast, introduced beetle species within the focal islands, but not sampled in laurel forests, are significantly less related at the archipelago scale to native species sampled within laurel forests. However, at the scale of individual islands, this relationship was not significant. These results are broadly concordant with the findings of Li *et al.* (2015) and Marx *et al.* (2016), both of whom used plant community data to test Darwin's naturalisation conundrum, and those of Xu *et al.* (2022) who analysed communities of freshwater lake fish. All three studies converge on the observation that successfully established introduced species tend to be more phylogenetically related to native species, providing support for the preadaptation hypothesis. While support for the preadaptation hypothesis varies across the different geographic partitions of our data, additional support for a dominant role of preadaptation comes from our analyses specifically contrasting relatedness patterns of introduced species sampled in the laurel forest and the native species that they are most closely related to. Comparing mean phylogenetic distances to the nearest native species for introduced species sampled in only one plot (a proxy of less established species) against introduced species sampled in two or more plots (a proxy for more established species) revealed significantly smaller phylogenetic distances for species present in two or more plots (**Figure 4**).

Competitive displacement of related native species, or trait mediated coexistence?

For plants at least, it is generally recognised that exotic species are often competitively superior to native species (Jakobs *et al.*, 2004; Levine *et al.*, 2003; Vilà *et al.*, 2011), favouring the displacement of native species by exotics. While it remains unclear to what extent the same may apply to insects, there are reasons to expect a similar relationship within insular environments, where some studies have detected a progressive increase in the arrival and establishment of introduced species (Borges *et al.*, 2020; Pyšek *et al.*, 2020), as well as a tendency toward the decline of endemic species populations in insular systems such as the Azorean islands (Borges *et al.*, 2020). The typically reduced species richness on islands has been linked to reduced intensity of interspecific interactions, compared to continental settings (Patton *et al.*, 2021). In turn, this has led to suggestions that island species are likely to be less adapted to competitive and predatory interactions (Elton, 1958; Kalmar & Currie, 2006; Wilson, 1961; Wilson & MacArthur, 1967), thus favouring their displacement when related species colonise from continental settings. Additionally, colonising species of beetle are likely to be better dispersers than related endemic species, due the evolution of secondary flightlessness in the latter (Waters *et al.*, 2020). This is exemplified by genera such as *Calathus* (Carabidae), where phylogenetic analyses have revealed that at least three flighted lineages have colonised the archipelago, each subsequently becoming flightless (Emerson *et al.*, 2000b). Recent work indicates that a shift from higher to lower dispersal ability is likely to increase the longer term extinction probability of a lineage (Suárez *et al.*, 2022), thus favouring the displacement of native species when related introduced species have higher dispersal ability. Displacement of native species by closely related introduced species may be accentuated by hybridization and introgression (Rhymer & Simberloff, 1996). In addition to close phylogenetic relatedness, both Li *et al.* (2015) and Marx *et al.* (2016) found that established introduced species of plant also tend to be functionally or ecologically distinct from native species. Their results thus argue for a primary importance of preadaptation, within which traits for competition avoidance are also favoured, thus favouring the coexistence of native species with introduced relatives. In the absence of relevant functional and ecological data for species of beetle within this study, it is not possible to understand the extent to which distinctiveness may also be associated with close phylogenetic relatedness. However, distinctiveness between related native and introduced species should favour their coexistence, while similarity should lead to competition, and

this may be reflected in co-occurrence and abundance data. Sampling data for *Ocyrops aethiops*, an introduced species, and its native congeneric *O. umbricola*, are suggestive of competitive displacement (**Figure S1**). *Ocyrops aethiops* is a recent introduction to the Canary Islands, first recorded in 2012 (Wojas, 2021), where it was sampled from a single location within the laurel forest of Anaga. Across the 10 plots sampled in Anaga, Tenerife, in 2012 (with three plots resampled between 2017 and 2018), *O. aethiops* was sampled exclusively in the three most western plots of the Anaga peninsula, being absent or at a much lower frequency than the native congeneric species, *O. umbricola*, across the seven more eastern plots. Li *et al.* (2015) have demonstrated the utility of temporal sampling for plants to show native species displacement by closely related introduced species. In the absence of robust functional or ecological data for insects, temporal sampling focused on related native and introduced species may be a useful approach to understand the relative importance of coexistence and displacement dynamics.

Preadaptation, competition-relatedness, and temporal patterns in community assembly

In addition to evaluating relative support for the preadaptation and competition-relatedness hypotheses, we also tested the hypothesis that more recently established species (i.e. introduced species) will typically present stronger signatures for the preadaptation hypothesis, compared to species of less recent origin (i.e. native not endemic species). Patterns of phylogenetic relatedness are consistent with a history of community assembly, prior to human-mediated species introductions, within which species establishment is essentially random with regard to the preadaptation and competition-relatedness hypotheses. However, as pointed out for plants by Li *et al.* (2015), a dominant influence of preadaptation could be masked if newly arrived species are competitively superior to closely related native species, and thus capable of displacing them, leading to their eventual extinction. The observation of Li *et al.* (2015) highlights the context dependency for interpreting patterns of phylogenetic relatedness with regard to competition. In a scenario of pre-equilibrium community assembly, where immigration exceeds extinction, assembly patterns are likely to be stochastic and less deterministic (Emerson & Gillespie, 2008). Such a dynamic should favour random patterns of relatedness for newly established species, with regard to already established species, consistent with our results. However, as extinction (and speciation) becomes more important, and assembly dynamics tend toward equilibrium, turnover of species should

eventually lead to a more deterministic set of species within a community (Simberloff & Wilson, 1970), for which competition effects are likely to have been more important. Within this dynamic, the concerns of Li *et al.* (2015) become relevant, complicating the inference of establishment dynamics of phylogenetically divergent native lineages. This reinforces the need for studies understanding the nature of competitive differences or trait divergence between contemporary pairs of related native and introduced species. Such studies may provide a helpful framework for understanding probable ecological processes behind patterns of phylogenetic relatedness in earlier phases of community assembly.

Barcode assisted assignment of introduced species status

Distinguishing between introduced and native not endemic species status within natural communities is often difficult, particularly among invertebrates. This has prompted efforts to use relatedness information from DNA sequence data to infer probable status, both for traditional specimen-based sampling of invertebrate communities (Andersen *et al.*, 2019; Smith & Fisher, 2009) and metabarcode sequencing (Kennedy *et al.*, 2022). Here we were able to address this limitation, and make species-level taxonomic assignments for 268 of the 360 species sampled, providing a direct association to their recorded native or introduced species status. The remaining 92 species were all assigned to their respective genera, with 55 of these (15.2% of all sampled species) being of equivocal biogeographic origin, due to the existence of unsampled native not endemic and introduced species within their constituent genera. Of these 55 species, three could be assigned as INT species comparing with external barcode databank, two as native not endemic and 24 as endemic using the 80% criterion explained in the methods section (**Table S4**).

While our level of taxonomic assignment addresses the limitations faced by Andersen *et al.* (2019) and Kennedy *et al.* (2022), we considered an additional source of error. For any given native not endemic species, it remains possible that historical inferences of native or introduced status may be incorrect. This is a particularly relevant concern on islands, where such cases have been previously documented (Alonso-Zarazaga *et al.*, 2017; Bidegaray-Batista *et al.*, 2015; Lökkös *et al.*, 2014; Zonstein & Marusik, 2019). Nineteen species inferred to be native not endemic within the Canary Islands Biodiversity Databank presented sequence similarities of $\geq 99\%$ to individuals

sampled from distant continental regions. Such high sequence similarity has been shown to be consistent with human-mediated introduction for other fractions of arthropod diversity in the Canary Islands (Cicconardi *et al.*, 2017). These 19 species thus highlight the power of barcode reference sequences for distinguishing between native and introduced species status. It would seem likely that there are other presumed native not endemic species sampled by us that are in fact of introduced origin, but for which barcode reference sequences are lacking. Unless such species are non-random, with regard to their phylogenetic relatedness to native species, these are unlikely to impact the inferences drawn from our analyses. However, this does highlight a potentially more general problem for the analysis of arthropod biodiversity.

Native or introduced species status- an overlooked biodiversity knowledge shortfall

The approximately 95% increase in the number of introduced species within Canary laurel forest through barcode sequence matching highlights an underappreciated shortfall in arthropod biodiversity data-knowledge of species native or introduced status. In addition to previously recognised shortfalls and challenges (Cardoso *et al.*, 2011; Emerson *et al.*, 2022; Hortal *et al.*, 2015), a lack of reliable data on whether species are native or introduced will also constrain efforts to effectively monitor, understand, manage, and ultimately conserve biodiversity. It is unlikely that our results are an idiosyncrasy, or unique to our focal taxonomic group and habitat. It is rather more likely to be a universal concern, which may vary across different geographic regions and fractions of arthropod diversity. In harmony with the naming of previous shortfalls (Brown & Lomolino, 1998; Cardoso *et al.*, 2011; Diniz-Filho *et al.*, 2013; Hortal *et al.*, 2015; Lomolino, 2004), we refer to this as the Humboldtian shortfall - the limited knowledge on the status of species as being either native or introduced.

Our results highlight the value of the BOLD (Ratnasingham & Hebert, 2007) and GenBank (Sayers *et al.*, 2020) DNA sequence repositories for addressing the Humboldtian shortfall, adding to already well-established benefits of DNA barcoding for taxonomic assignment (Hebert, Cywinska, *et al.*, 2003; Landry *et al.*, 2013; Lopez-Vaamonde *et al.*, 2019; Smith & Fisher, 2009), as a tool for species discovery (Hebert *et al.*, 2004; Packer & Ruz, 2017; Pérez-Delgado *et al.*, 2022; Smith & Fisher, 2009), and as a taxonomic aid (Hebert & Gregory, 2005; Landry *et al.*, 2013). The importance of

complete local barcode reference libraries has been well-argued (Dincă *et al.*, 2011; Kneibelsberger *et al.*, 2014; Kuzmina *et al.*, 2012). Such libraries facilitate taxonomic assignment of specimens through local reference library barcode matching. However, understanding the status of a given species as either native or introduced within a given sampling area is necessarily dependent upon broader global initiatives and sampling. This is exemplified by the “German Barcode of Life (GBOL)” project (www.bolgermany.com), and its campaign to provide a comprehensive DNA barcode database for Central European beetles, yielding barcode reference sequences for more than 3500 beetle species (Hendrich *et al.*, 2015). This Central European reference library provided high sequence matching to six Canary Islands species, previously considered native: *Cartodere nodifer* - 100%; *Sericoderus lateralis* - 100%; *Corticaria fagi* - 99.9%; *Tachyporus pussilus* - 99.8%; *Atomaria scutellaris* - 99.5%; *Atheta coriaria* - 99.5%. Initiatives to taxonomically and geographically scale up local and regional barcode reference library production (Hobern, 2021) are thus likely to have a positive collateral impact upon the Humboldtian shortfall.

Conclusions

To our knowledge, this is the first community-level phylogenetic analysis to address the dynamics of arthropod species introduction and establishment. Our results are consistent with previous work on plants (Li *et al.*, 2015; Marx *et al.*, 2016), and fish (Xu *et al.*, 2022), indicating a dominant role for species preadaptation over competition avoidance. The importance of phylogenetic relatedness as a predictor of establishment by introduced species of beetle to laurel forest habitat is reinforced by lower relatedness for introduced species that were not sampled within forests, and higher occupancy within forests for introduced species more closely related to native species. We find indirect evidence for competitive displacement by introduced species, however further work is needed to understand the relative importance of competitive displacement and trait mediated coexistence.

The combined mitogenome phylogeny and barcode approach presented here provides a generalisable framework for investigating arthropod species introduction and establishment dynamics. With the costs and logistics of whole mitochondrial genome and barcode sequencing becoming more affordable and streamlined (Srivathsan *et al.*, 2021) the approach can be applied to better understand the dynamics of establishment of introduced arthropod species. However, our results also highlight a potential concern for arthropod biodiversity research. High barcode sequence matching to individuals from distant continental areas revealed 19 species that had been presumed to be native, to be introduced, doubling the number of introduced species to 38. The extent to which this problem manifests itself across different taxonomic domains and geographic areas will be determined by the completeness of relevant barcode reference libraries. In this context, globally coordinated efforts to generate taxonomically assigned barcode and metabarcoding sequence data for arthropods (Arribas *et al.*, 2020; Emerson *et al.*, 2022) are needed.

Supplementary material

- **Appendix S1.** Detailed amplification conditions for COI-5P region (barcode region) and primers used for sequencing.
- **Appendix S2.** Taxonomic literature used for the morphological identification of the coleopteran species.
- **Figure S1.** Abundances of the native species *Ocypus umbricola* and the introduced congener, *O. aethiops*, across 10 sampling sites within the Anaga peninsula.
- **Table S1.** Sampling plots with coordinates.
- **Table S2.** Mitogenome sequencing pools.
- **Table S3.** Mitogenome assemblers used, and their associated parameter settings.
- **Table S4.** Information about the 360 beetle species sampled within laurel forests of the Canary Islands.
- **Table S5.** Information about the introduced beetle species recorded for the four western Canary Islands, not sampled in the laurel forests, and with available sequences in GenBank and/or BOLD Systems.
- **Table S6.** List of the mitogenomes obtained from GenBank.
- **Table S7.** Details for the 98 *de novo* generated mitogenomes.
- **Table S8.** Mntd analysis results comparing introduced species sampled in the laurel forest against native not endemic and endemic species.
- **Table S9.** Mntd analysis results comparing introduced species not sampled in the laurel forest against native not endemic and endemic species.
- **Table S10.** Mntd analysis results comparing native not endemic species against endemic species (without any restrictions in the native not endemic or endemic species used for the analysis).
- **Table S11.** Mntd analysis results comparing native not endemic species against endemic species (excluding all the species in blue indicated in the **Table S4**).
- **Table S12.** . Mntd analysis results comparing introduced species sampled in the laurel forest against native not endemic and endemic species but classifying by the number of plots occupied by the introduced species.
- **Table S13.** GLM results of the comparison of the minimum distance to the near native species (MinDis) between two possible categories, introduced species sampled only in one plot (N=26) and introduced species sampled in two or more plots (N=21).

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Appendix S1. Detailed amplification conditions for COI-5P region and primers used for sequencing.

For COI-5P (658bp), 2 μ l of either pure or diluted (1/10) DNA extract was amplified with 23 μ l of PCR mix (for a total volume of 25 μ l), comprised of 14.4 μ l of water, 2.5 μ l of 10x NH₄ buffer (Bioline), 1.5 μ l of 50 mM MgCl₂ (Bioline), 2 μ l of 2.5 mM dNTPs (Bioline), 0.5 μ l of BSA (20 mg/ml), 1 μ l of each primer (10 μ M), and 0.1 μ l of Taq polymerase (BIOTAQ). Primers used were FoldF and FoldR primers (Yu *et al.*, 2012). PCR amplification conditions were as follows: an initial 95°C for 10 minutes followed by 40 cycles, each comprising denaturation at 95°C for 45s, primer annealing at 46-52°C for 45s and primer extension at 72°C for 90s, and then a final extension at 72°C for 10 min.

Appendix S2. Taxonomic literature used for the morphological identification of the coleopteran species.

Species were identified using different taxonomic literature as Angelini and De Marzo (1983) for *Agathidium* Panzer, 1797; Biondi (1995) for tribe Alticini; Israelson (1974) for family Anobiidae; Israelson (1971) for *Astenus* Dejean, 1833; Johnson (1970) for *Atomaria* Stephens, 1829; Franz (1982) for *Aulonothroscus* Horn, 1890; Machado (1992) for family Carabidae; Bowstead (1999) for family Corylophidae; Erber and Scholler (2006) for *Cryptocephalus* Geoffroy, 1762; Otero (2013) for subfamily Cryptophaginae; Stüben (2018) for subfamily Cryptorhynchinae; Besuchet (1968) for *Euplectus* Leach, 1817; Smetana (1962) for *Gabrius* Stephens, 1829; Israelson (1977) for tribe Leiodini; Palm (1975) for *Malthinus* Latreille, 1806; Zerche (1998) for *Metopsia* Wollaston, 1854; Kapp (2019) for *Oligota* Mannerheim, 1830; Israelson (1972) for *Stenichnus* Thomson, 1859; and consulting the webpages Käfer Europas (<http://coletonet.de/coleo/>) in general for coleoptera, and Curculio-Institute (<https://www.curci.de/institute/index.php>) for Curculionidae. This process of identification was further supported with reference to the entomological collection of the Department of Animal Biology, University of La Laguna, Canary Islands, Spain (coll. DZUL) and that of the Island Ecology and Evolution Group (GEEI) of the Instituto de Productos Naturales y Agrobiología (IPNA-CSIC), Tenerife, Canary Islands, Spain (coll. GEEI). For some specimens, it was necessary to consult with external expert Paolo Audisio from Italy for Nitidulidae, and local entomologists Pedro Oromí, Antonio Machado and Rafael García for several additional groups.

Figure S1. Abundances of the native species *Ocyptus umbricola* (black) and the introduced congener, *O. aethiops* (grey) across 10 sampling sites within the Anaga peninsula. Details for each sampling site are provided in Table S1. All sites were sampled in 2012, as detailed in the methods, with four sites subject to additional sampling over a 2 year period from 2017-2018 (second pie chart to the right).

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Table S1. Sampling plots with coordinates.

Plot code	Plot name	Island	Latitude	Longitude
AGU	Monte Aguirre	Tenerife	28.5334	-16.2698
ANE	Aguas Negras	Tenerife	28.5400	-16.2251
CHI	Chinobre	Tenerife	28.5590	-16.1736
CTE	Cabezo Tejo	Tenerife	28.5620	-16.1714
IJU	Hoya de Ijuana	Tenerife	28.5602	-16.1692
MOQ	El Moquinal	Tenerife	28.5368	-16.3088
NIE	Barranco Nieto	Tenerife	28.5341	-16.3163
PIJ	Pijaral	Tenerife	28.5520	-16.1892
TAG	Vueltas de Taganana	Tenerife	28.5443	-16.2260
ZAP	Zapata	Tenerife	28.5355	-16.2962
COC	Barranco Cochinos	Tenerife	28.3228	-16.8234
PAS	Barranco Los Pasos	Tenerife	28.3349	-16.8316
AGA	Agua García	Tenerife	28.4579	-16.4041
PBL	Palo Blanco	Tenerife	28.3573	-16.5874
CUB	Cubo de La Galga	La Palma	28.7664	-17.7703
CUM	Hilera de la Cumbre	La Palma	28.6304	-17.8267
LOM	Camino del Lomito	La Palma	28.8038	-17.8203
NIQ	Niquiomo	La Palma	28.6003	-17.8103
TAB	El Tablado	La Palma	28.8184	-17.8833
MAG	Barranco de Magdalena	La Palma	28.8109	-17.9079
ACE	Los Acebiños	La Gomera	28.1410	-17.2225
APA	Apartacaminos	La Gomera	28.1540	-17.3008
CED	El Cedro	La Gomera	28.1240	-17.2240
EHA	Encima de Las Hayas	La Gomera	28.1355	-17.2773
FUE	Fuensanta	La Gomera	28.1453	-17.2522
MEV	Meseta de Vallehermoso	La Gomera	28.1539	-17.2934
REV	Reventón Oscuro	La Gomera	28.1221	-17.2138
FAY	El Fayal	El Hierro	27.7322	-17.9949
HDC	Hoya del Creal	El Hierro	27.8060	-17.9490
MEN	Mencáfete	El Hierro	27.7363	-18.0735
PDR	Pedraje	El Hierro	27.7338	-18.0231

Table S2. Mitogenome sequencing pools.

Pool	Concentration (ng/ μ L)	Volume (μ L)	DNA adapter sequence	Number of individuals
1	5.24	27	CGATGT(A)	15
2	3.58	27	TGACCA(A)	19
3	5.54	29	ACAGTG(A)	36
4	6.89	29	GCCAAT(A)	13
5	8.63	29	CAGATC(A)	12
6	9.49	29	CTTGTA(A)	12
7	9.07	29	AGTCAA(C)	12
8	12.5	29	AGTTCC(G)	12

Table S3. Mitogenome assemblers used, and their associated parameter settings.

Mitogenome assembler	Conditions used (parameters set default if no specify in the table)
IDBA	Modules used gcc/6.1.0; idba/1.1.3 Number of threads 8; maxk 300 to mink 60
SPAdes	Modules used python/3.4.5; python/2.7.10; spades/3.14.0 t as 16 k as 21 ,33, 55, 77, 99, 127
Ray	Modules used: mpich/3.1.4; gcc/6.1.0; ray/2.3.1 k as 61 Minimum seed length set in 100 Minimum contig length set in 1000
Celera	Modules used gcc/6.1.0; celera-assembler/8.3 RunCa command with the bogart method for unitigger computations, and Unitig Repeat/Unique Toggling was conducted from unitigs longer than 500 bp

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Table S4. Beetle species sampled within laurel forests of the Canary Islands (360 species), ordered by family. Biogeographical status (native, endemic or introduced) recorded within the Canary Islands biodiversity databank (BIOTA) is listed, together with revised status based on high DNA sequence relatedness ($\geq 99\%$) to continental samples and the western Canary islands where they were recorded (Biota plus our sampling). Details of relatedness underlying status changes are provided under observations, together with new species/genus citations for the Canary Islands. For introduced species, the number of plots where they were sampled was included in the observation section (see Table S1 for more information about plot location or abbreviation). END = endemic; NAT_notend = native but not endemic; INT = introduced; --- = no previous or no available data; TF = Tenerife; LG = La Gomera; LP = La Palma; EH = El Hierro; COI-5P = COI barcode region; COI-3P = COI Jerry region. Species for which status changed from NAT_notend to INT are highlighted in yellow. Species newly recorded for the Canary Islands are highlighted in green. Species identified only to genus level are indicated in bold. Species highlighted in red could not be assigned to END or NAT_notend, and were removed from both END vs NAT_notend analyses. Species highlighted in blue could be assigned to END or NAT_notend above an 80% threshold, and were removed from only one of the two END vs NAT_notend analyses.

GenBank accession number COI-5P	GenBank accession number COI-3P	Family	Species	BIOTA status	Final revised status	Distribution	Observation
OQ739289	OQ730966	Anthicidae	<i>Aulacoderus canariensis</i>	END	END	TF, LG, LP, EH	
OQ739206	OQ730882	Attelabidae	<i>Auletobius anceps</i>	END	END	TF, LG, LP, EH	
OQ739405	OQ731088	Biphyllidae	<i>Biphyllus lunatus</i>	INT	INT	LG, LP	Sampled in three plots (LOM, MAG and NIQ).
OQ739375	OQ731056	Bothrideridae	<i>Anommatus duodecimstriatus</i>	INT	INT	TF, LG, LP, EH	Sampled in four plots (ANE, COC, CTE and TAG).
OQ739447	OQ731130	Brentidae	<i>Aspidapion radiolus</i>	NAT_notend	NAT_notend	TF, LG, LP, EH	
OQ739398	OQ731080	Brentidae	<i>Eutrichapion vorax</i>	NAT_notend	INT	TF, LG, LP	95.5% sequence similarity to specimens from the United Kingdom, Germany and Norway; and 99.4% to Italy. Sampled in two plots (CED and MEV).
OQ739474	OQ731158	Brentidae	<i>Holotrichapion ononis</i>	NAT_notend	NAT_notend	TF, LG, LP, EH	
OQ739425	OQ731108	Brentidae	<i>Holotrichapion rotundipenne</i>	NAT_notend	NAT_notend	TF, LG, LP, EH	
OQ739413	OQ731096	Brentidae	<i>Ischnopterapion modestum</i>	---	INT	TF	New species record for the Canary Islands. 99.7% sequence similarity to sequences from Portugal; 99.5% to the United Kingdom; and 99.4% to Germany. Sampled in one plot (AGA).
OQ739422	OQ731105	Brentidae	<i>Kalcapion semivittatum</i>	NAT_notend	NAT_notend	TF, LG, LP, EH	
---	OQ731039	Brentidae	<i>Lepidapion curvipilosum</i>	END	END	TF, LG, LP, EH	Only COI-3P fragment used for analyses
OQ739431	OQ731114	Brentidae	<i>Taeniapion delicatulum</i>	NAT_notend	NAT_notend	TF, LG, LP, EH	
OQ739502	OQ731186	Brentidae	<i>Taeniapion urticarium</i>	NAT_notend	NAT_notend	TF, EH	
OQ739403	OQ731085	Carabidae	<i>Amara aenea</i>	INT	INT	TF, LG, LP, EH	Sampled in two plots (FAY and MAG).
OQ739220	OQ730896	Carabidae	<i>Amaroschema gaudini</i>	END	END	TF	

GenBank accession number COI-5P	GenBank accession number COI-3P	Family	Species	BIOTA status	Final revised status	Distribution	Observation
OQ739503	OQ731188	Carabidae	<i>Bembidion</i> sp.	NAT_notend or END or INT	NAT_notend or END	LP	9 species recorded for the Canary Islands: 5 NAT_notend, 3 END, 1 INT. BOLD sequenced for INT species does not provide a match.
OQ739208	OQ730884	Carabidae	<i>Bradycellus ventricosus</i>	END	END	TF	
OQ739327	OQ731004	Carabidae	<i>Brosicus crassimargo</i>	END	END	LG	
OQ739242	OQ730918	Carabidae	<i>Calathidius acuminatus</i>	END	END	TF	
OQ739241	OQ730917	Carabidae	<i>Calathidius sphodroides</i>	END	END	TF	
OQ739195	OQ730871	Carabidae	<i>Calathus abaxoides</i>	END	END	TF	
OQ739229	OQ730905	Carabidae	<i>Calathus angustulus</i>	END	END	TF	
OQ739193	OQ730869	Carabidae	<i>Calathus gomerensis</i>	END	END	LG	
OQ739196	OQ730872	Carabidae	<i>Calathus laurenticola</i>	END	END	LG	
OQ739194	OQ730870	Carabidae	<i>Calathus spretus</i>	END	END	EH	
OQ739262	OQ730939	Carabidae	<i>Carabus faustus</i>	END	END	TF	
OQ739218	OQ730894	Carabidae	<i>Cymindis simillima</i>	END	END	LP	
OQ739217	OQ730893	Carabidae	<i>Cymindis velata</i>	END	END	LP	
OQ739216	OQ730892	Carabidae	<i>Cymindis zargoides</i>	END	END	TF	
OQ739258	OQ730935	Carabidae	<i>Dicrodontus aptinoides</i>	END	END	LG	
OQ739259	OQ730936	Carabidae	<i>Dicrodontus brunneus</i>	END	END	TF	
OQ739488	OQ731172	Carabidae	<i>Dromius angustus</i>	NAT_notend	NAT_notend	TF, LG, LP, EH	
---	OQ730930	Carabidae	<i>Eutrichopus canariensis</i>	END	END	TF	Only COI-3P fragment used for analyses
OQ739254	OQ730931	Carabidae	<i>Eutrichopus gonzalezi</i>	END	END	TF	
OQ739285	OQ730962	Carabidae	<i>Gomerina</i> sp.	END	END	LG	
OQ739406	OQ731089	Carabidae	<i>Laemostenus complanatus</i>	INT	INT	TF, LP, EH	Sampled in three plots (CUM, NIQ and PBL).
OQ739250	OQ730926	Carabidae	<i>Leistus nubivagus</i>	END	END	TF	
OQ739240	OQ730916	Carabidae	<i>Licinopsis angustula</i>	END	END	LP	
OQ739239	OQ730915	Carabidae	<i>Licinopsis oblitterata</i>	END	END	LG, EH	
OQ739269	OQ730946	Carabidae	<i>Olisthopus glabratus</i>	END	END	TF, LG, EH	
OQ739270	OQ730947	Carabidae	<i>Olisthopus palmensis</i>	END	END	LP	
OQ739187	OQ730863	Carabidae	<i>Paradromius amoenus</i>	END	END	TF	
OQ739186	OQ730862	Carabidae	<i>Paradromius iucundus</i>	END	END	LG, LP	
OQ739372	OQ731052	Carabidae	<i>Paradromius linearis</i>	INT	INT	LG, LP, EH	Sampled in three plots (CUM, MEV and PDR).
OQ739288	OQ730965	Carabidae	<i>Paraeutrichopus harpaloides</i>	END	END	EH	
OQ739286	OQ730963	Carabidae	<i>Paraeutrichopus pecoudi</i>	END	END	LG	
---	OQ731031	Carabidae	<i>Philorhizus atlanticus</i>	END	END	TF, LG, LP, EH	Only COI-3P fragment used for analyses
OQ739212	OQ730888	Carabidae	<i>Philorhizus bravoorum</i>	END	END	LG	

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GenBank accession number COI-5P	GenBank accession number COI-3P	Family	Species	BIOTA status	Final revised status	Distribution	Observation
OQ739213	OQ730889	Carabidae	<i>Philorhizus elliptipennis</i>	END	END	TF	
OQ739347	OQ731024	Carabidae	<i>Philorhizus ferranius</i>	END	END	EH	
OQ739461	OQ731145	Carabidae	<i>Philorhizus</i> sp.	NAT_notend or END	NAT_notend or END	TF	13 <i>Philorhizus</i> species are recorded for the Canary Islands: 11 END, 2 NAT_notend. 4 END species were sampled. Thus, could be one 7 END or 2 NAT_notend species.
OQ739287	OQ730964	Carabidae	<i>Platyderus alticola</i>	END	END	TF, LG, EH	
OQ739400	OQ731082	Carabidae	<i>Pterostichus</i> sp.	---	INT	LG	New genus record for the Canary Islands. 93.4% sequence similarity to specimens of <i>Pterostichus strenuus</i> from Germany. Sampled in one plot (FUE).
OQ739161	OQ730837	Carabidae	<i>Trechus cabrerai</i>	END	END	TF	
OQ739162	OQ730838	Carabidae	<i>Trechus felix</i>	END	END	TF, EH	
OQ739164	OQ730840	Carabidae	<i>Trechus flavocinctus</i> complex	END	END	TF, LG, EH	
OQ739163	OQ730839	Carabidae	<i>Trechus flavocircumdatus</i>	END	END	LP	
OQ739165	OQ730841	Carabidae	<i>Trechus</i> sp.	END	END	TF	
OQ739362	OQ731042	Carabidae	<i>Trechus sylviae</i>	END	END	LP	
OQ739160	OQ730836	Carabidae	<i>Trechus uyttenboogaarti</i>	END	END	TF	
OQ739333	OQ731010	Carabidae	<i>Zargus crotchianus</i>	END	END	LG	
OQ739429	OQ731112	Cerambycidae	<i>Blabrinotus spinicollis</i>	NAT_notend	NAT_notend	TF, LG, LP	
OQ739369	OQ731049	Cerambycidae	<i>Stenidea</i> sp.	END	END	TF	
OQ739273	OQ730950	Cerambycidae	<i>Stictoleptura palmi</i>	END	END	TF	
---	OQ731131	Chrysomelidae	<i>Bruchidius</i> sp.	NAT_notend or END or INT	NAT_notend or END	TF	12 species recorded for Canary Islands (6 INT, 4 END and 2 NAT_notend). Genetic variation consistent with END or NAT_notend. Only COI-3P fragment used for analyses
OQ739222	OQ730898	Chrysomelidae	<i>Chrysolina costalis</i>	END	END	TF	
OQ739350	OQ731027	Chrysomelidae	<i>Chrysolina gemina</i>	END	END	TF, LG, LP, EH	
OQ739475	OQ731159	Chrysomelidae	<i>Chrysolina wollastoni</i>	END	END	LG	
OQ739433	OQ731116	Chrysomelidae	<i>Cryptocephalus</i> sp. 1	END	END	TF, LG, LP, EH	
OQ739489	OQ731173	Chrysomelidae	<i>Cryptocephalus</i> sp. 2	END	END	LP	
OQ739494	OQ731178	Chrysomelidae	<i>Cryptocephalus</i> sp. 3	END	END	LP	
OQ739399	OQ731081	Chrysomelidae	<i>Longitarsus cerinthes</i>	NAT_notend	INT	TF, LG, LP	100% sequence similarity to specimens from Spain (Iberian Peninsula). Sampled in one plot (MEV).

GenBank accession number COI-5P	GenBank accession number COI-3P	Family	Species	BIOTA status	Final revised status	Distribution	Observation
OQ739260	OQ730937	Chrysomelidae	<i>Longitarsus inconspicuus</i>	END	END	TF	
OQ739377	OQ731058	Chrysomelidae	<i>Longitarsus nigrofasciatus</i>	NAT_notend	INT	TF, LG, LP, EH	99.71% sequence similarity to specimens from Bulgaria. Sampled in two plots (PIJ and TAG).
OQ739427	OQ731110	Chrysomelidae	<i>Longitarsus</i> sp. 1	NAT_notend or END	NAT_notend or END	TF, LG, EH	17 species recorded for the Canary Islands: 9 NAT_notend, 6 END and 2 INT (previously considered NAT_notend). BOLD sequences for 7 NAT_notend species did not provide a match. Thus, could be one of 6 END or 2 NAT_notend.
OQ739434	OQ731117	Chrysomelidae	<i>Longitarsus</i> sp. 2	NAT_notend or END	NAT_notend or END	TF	17 species recorded for the Canary Islands: 9 NAT_notend, 6 END and 2 INT (previously considered NAT_notend). BOLD sequences for 7 NAT_notend species did not provide a match. Thus, could be one of 6 END or 2 NAT_notend.
OQ739476	OQ731160	Chrysomelidae	<i>Longitarsus</i> sp. 3	NAT_notend or END	NAT_notend or END	LG, EH	17 species recorded for the Canary Islands: 9 NAT_notend, 6 END and 2 INT (previously considered NAT_notend). BOLD sequences for 7 NAT_notend species did not provide a match. Thus, could be one of 6 END or 2 NAT_notend.
OQ739484	OQ731168	Chrysomelidae	<i>Longitarsus</i> sp. 4	NAT_notend or END	NAT_notend or END	LP, EH	17 species recorded for the Canary Islands: 9 NAT_notend, 6 END and 2 INT (previously considered NAT_notend). BOLD sequences for 7 NAT_notend species did not provide a match. Thus, could be one of 6 END or 2 NAT_notend.
OQ739387	OQ731068	Chrysomelidae	<i>Oulema melanopus</i>	INT	INT	TF, LG, LP, EH	Sampled in one plot (NIE).
OQ739384	OQ731065	Chrysomelidae	<i>Psylliodes instabilis</i>	---	INT	TF	New species record for the Canary Islands. 98.6% sequence similarity to a specimen from Spain (Iberian Peninsula). Sampled in one plot (COC).

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GenBank accession number COI-5P	GenBank accession number COI-3P	Family	Species	BIOTA status	Final revised status	Distribution	Observation
OQ739452	OQ731136	Chrysomelidae	<i>Psylliodes</i> sp. 1	NAT_notend or END	NAT_notend or END	TF, LG, LP, EH	7 species recorded for the Canary Islands: 4 NAT_notend, 3 END (plus 1 new INT record). BOLD sequence for 1 NAT_notend species did not provide a match. Thus, could be one of 3 END or 3 NAT_notend.
OQ739487	OQ731171	Chrysomelidae	<i>Psylliodes</i> sp. 2	NAT_notend or END	NAT_notend or END	LP	7 species recorded for the Canary Islands: 4 NAT_notend, 3 END (plus 1 new INT record). BOLD sequence for 1 NAT_notend species did not provide a match. Thus, could be one of 3 END or 3 NAT_notend.
OQ739385	OQ731066	Chrysomelidae	<i>Sphaeroderma rubidum</i>	INT	INT	TF	Sampled in one plot (CHI).
OQ739207	OQ730883	Ciidae / Cisidae	<i>Atlantocis canariensis</i>	END	END	TF, LG	
OQ739445	OQ731128	Ciidae / Cisidae	<i>Cis</i> sp.	NAT_notend or END	NAT_notend or END	TF	2 species recorded for the Canary Islands: 1 END, 1 NAT_notend.
OQ739430	OQ731113	Ciidae / Cisidae	<i>Octotemnus opacus</i>	NAT_notend	NAT_notend	TF, LG, LP	
OQ739265	OQ730942	Ciidae / Cisidae	<i>Orthocis sagittiferus</i>	END	END	TF, LG, LP	
OQ739329	OQ731006	Clambidae	<i>Clambus complicans</i>	END	END	TF, LG, LP	
OQ739284	OQ730961	Coccinellidae	<i>Coccinella miranda</i>	END	END	TF, LG, LP, EH	
OQ739381	OQ731062	Coccinellidae	<i>Coccinella septempunctata</i>	NAT_notend	INT	TF, LG, LP, EH	100% sequence similarity to specimens from Malta; 99.5% to Germany, Pakistan and Canada. Sampled in six plots (APA, CED, FAY, NIE, PAS and REV).
OQ739389	OQ731070	Coccinellidae	<i>Hippodamia variegata</i>	INT	INT	TF, LG, LP, EH	Sampled in one plot (PIJ).
OQ739495	OQ731179	Coccinellidae	<i>Nephus</i> sp.	NAT_notend or END	NAT_notend	LP	9 species are recorded for the Canary Islands: 8 NAT_notend, 1 END. Thus, most likely to be NAT_notend (89%).
OQ739401	OQ731083	Coccinellidae	<i>Novius cardinalis</i>	INT	INT	TF, LG, LP, EH	Sampled in one plot (FAY)
OQ739477	OQ731161	Coccinellidae	<i>Parexochomus</i> sp.	NAT_notend or END	END	LG	3 species recorded for the Canary Islands; 2 END and 1 NAT_notend. BOLD sequences for the NAT_notend species did not provide a match.
OQ739256	OQ730933	Coccinellidae	<i>Scymnus canariensis</i>	END	END	TF, LG, LP, EH	

GenBank accession number COI-5P	GenBank accession number COI-3P	Family	Species	BIOTA status	Final revised status	Distribution	Observation
OQ739383	OQ731064	Coccinellidae	<i>Scymnus nubilus</i>	NAT_notend	INT	TF, LG, LP, EH	100-99.8% sequence similarity to specimens from South Africa. Sampled in two plots (NIE and TAG).
OQ739435	OQ731118	Coccinellidae	<i>Scymnus</i> sp.	NAT_notend or END	NAT_notend or END	TF, LG	9 species recorded for the Canary Islands: 3 END, 5 NAT_notend and 1 INT (previously considered NAT_notend). 1 END and 1 INT sampled, plus BOLD sequences for 3 NAT_notend species did not provide a match. Thus, could be one of 2 END or 2 NAT_notend.
OQ739376	OQ731057	Corylophidae	<i>Sericoderus lateralis</i> 1	NAT_notend	INT	TF, LG, LP, EH	100% sequence similarity to specimens from Germany, China and Canada. Sampled in four plots (CUB, LOM, MOQ and NIE).
OQ739410	OQ731093	Corylophidae	<i>Sericoderus lateralis</i> 2	NAT_notend	INT	TF, LG, LP, EH	99.7% sequence similarity to specimens from the United States; 99.5% to South Africa and Australia. Sampled in one plot (CUB).
OQ739232	OQ730908	Cryptophagidae	<i>Atomaria marginicollis</i>	END	END	TF	
OQ739379	OQ731060	Cryptophagidae	<i>Atomaria scutellaris</i>	NAT_notend	INT	TF, LG, LP, EH	99.5% sequence similarity to specimens from Germany. Sampled in two plots (COC and PAS)
OQ739471	OQ731155	Cryptophagidae	<i>Atomaria</i> sp. 1	NAT_notend or END	NAT_notend or END	LG	11 species recorded for the Canary Islands: 5 END, 5 NAT_notend and 1 INT (previously considered NAT_notend). 2 END and 1 INT sampled, plus BOLD sequences for 3 NAT_notend and 1 END did not provide a match. Thus could be one of 2 NAT_notend or 2 END.

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GenBank accession number COI-5P	GenBank accession number COI-3P	Family	Species	BIOTA status	Final revised status	Distribution	Observation
---	OQ731187	Cryptophagidae	<i>Atomaria</i> sp. 2	NAT_notend or END	NAT_notend or END	LP	11 species recorded for the Canary Islands: 5 END, 5 NAT_notend and 1 INT (previously considered NAT_notend). 2 END and 1 INT sampled, plus BOLD sequences for 3NAT_notend and 1 END did not provide a match. Thus could be one of 2 NAT_notend or 2 END. Only COI-3P fragment used for analyses
OQ739370	OQ731050	Cryptophagidae	<i>Atomaria venusta</i>	END	END	LG	
OQ739248	OQ730924	Cryptophagidae	<i>Cryptophagus fusiformis</i>	END	END	TF, LP, EH	
---	OQ731055	Cryptophagidae	<i>Cryptophagus laticollis</i>	NAT_notend	INT	EH	99.6% sequence similarity to a specimen from the United Kingdom. Sampled in one plot (PDR). Only COI-3P fragment used for analyses
OQ739439	OQ731122	Cryptophagidae	<i>Cryptophagus</i> sp. 1	NAT_notend or END	END	TF, LG, LP	11 species recorded for the Canary Islands: 6 END, 5 NAT_notend. BOLD sequences for all 5 NAT_notend species did not provide matches.
OQ739464	OQ731148	Cryptophagidae	<i>Cryptophagus</i> sp. 2	NAT_notend or END	END	TF	11 species recorded for the Canary Islands: 6 END, 5 NAT_notend. BOLD sequences for all 5 NAT_notend species did not provide matches.
OQ739491	OQ731175	Cryptophagidae	<i>Cryptophagus</i> sp. 3	NAT_notend or END	END	LP	11 species recorded for the Canary Islands: 6 END, 5 NAT_notend. BOLD sequences for all 5 NAT_notend species did not provide matches.
OQ739493	OQ731177	Cryptophagidae	<i>Cryptophagus</i> sp. 4	NAT_notend or END	END	LP	11 species recorded for the Canary Islands: 6 END, 5 NAT_notend. BOLD sequences for all 5 NAT_notend species did not provide matches.
OQ739189	OQ730865	Cryptophagidae	<i>Micrambe hesperia</i> 1	END	END	TF, LG, LP, EH	
OQ739317	OQ730994	Cryptophagidae	<i>Micrambe hesperia</i> 2	END	END	TF, LG, LP, EH	
OQ739501	OQ731185	Cryptophagidae	<i>Micrambe ulicis</i>	NAT_notend	NAT_notend	TF, LG, LP	
OQ739415	OQ731098	Curculionidae	<i>Acalles globulipennis</i> 1	NAT_notend	NAT_notend	TF	

GenBank accession number COI-5P	GenBank accession number COI-3P	Family	Species	BIOTA status	Final revised status	Distribution	Observation
OQ739462	OQ731146	Curculionidae	<i>Acalles globulipennis</i> ₂	NAT_notend	NAT_notend	TF	
OQ739332	OQ731009	Curculionidae	<i>Acalles granulimaculosus</i>	END	END	LG	
OQ739344	OQ731021	Curculionidae	<i>Acalles pilula</i>	END	END	TF, LP, EH	
OQ739251	OQ730927	Curculionidae	<i>Alloplinthus musicus</i>	END	END	TF	
OQ739203	OQ730879	Curculionidae	<i>Calacalles affinis</i>	END	END	TF	
OQ739261	OQ730938	Curculionidae	<i>Calacalles exiguus</i>	END	END	TF, LP	
OQ739282	OQ730959	Curculionidae	<i>Calacalles minutus</i>	END	END	TF, LG	
OQ739249	OQ730925	Curculionidae	<i>Calacalles pumilio</i>	END	END	TF, LG	
OQ739349	OQ731026	Curculionidae	<i>Coelositona palmensis</i>	END	END	LP	
OQ739391	OQ731072	Curculionidae	<i>Coelositona puberulus</i>	INT	INT	TF, LP	Sampled in one plot (COC)
OQ739271	OQ730948	Curculionidae	<i>Dendroacalles ruteri</i>	END	END	TF, LG, LP, EH	
OQ739272	OQ730949	Curculionidae	<i>Dendroacalles sigma</i>	END	END	LP	
OQ739185	OQ730861	Curculionidae	<i>Echinodera angulipennis</i>	END	END	TF	
OQ739307	OQ730984	Curculionidae	<i>Echinodera cf. hystrix</i>	END	END	LP	
OQ739309	OQ730986	Curculionidae	<i>Echinodera hystrix</i>	END	END	LP, EH	
OQ739192	OQ730868	Curculionidae	<i>Echinodera orbiculata</i>	END	END	TF, LP	
OQ739310	OQ730987	Curculionidae	<i>Echinodera palmaensis</i>	END	END	LP	
OQ739308	OQ730985	Curculionidae	<i>Echinodera pseudohystrix</i>	END	END	LG	
OQ739366	OQ731046	Curculionidae	<i>Ficusacalles senilis</i>	END	END	TF, LG, EH	
OQ739382	OQ731063	Curculionidae	<i>Gonipterus platensis</i>	INT	INT	TF, LG	Sampled in one plot (TAG).
OQ739368	OQ731048	Curculionidae	<i>Hylastes lowei</i>	END	END	TF, LG, LP	
---	OQ731077	Curculionidae	<i>Hypera postica</i>	NAT_notend	INT	TF, LG, LP, EH	99.9% sequence similarity to specimens from Iran. Sampled in one plot (CED). Only COI-3P fragment used for analyses
OQ739246	OQ730922	Curculionidae	<i>Laparocerus aeneotinctus femoralis</i>	END	END	LP	
OQ739180	OQ730856	Curculionidae	<i>Laparocerus aethiops garajonay</i>	END	END	LG	
OQ739166	OQ730842	Curculionidae	<i>Laparocerus anagae</i>	END	END	TF	
OQ739197	OQ730873	Curculionidae	<i>Laparocerus auarita</i>	END	END	LP	
OQ739200	OQ730876	Curculionidae	<i>Laparocerus bimbache</i>	END	END	EH	
OQ739168	OQ730844	Curculionidae	<i>Laparocerus campestris</i>	END	END	LP	
OQ739294	OQ730971	Curculionidae	<i>Laparocerus cephalotes</i>	END	END	EH	
OQ739198	OQ730874	Curculionidae	<i>Laparocerus cf. auarita</i>	END	END	TF, LP	
OQ739360	OQ731040	Curculionidae	<i>Laparocerus combrecitensis</i>	END	END	LP	
OQ739361	OQ731041	Curculionidae	<i>Laparocerus crassifrons</i>	END	END	TF	

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OQ739247	OQ730923	Curculionidae	<i>Laparocerus crassus</i>	END	END	TF	
OQ739291	OQ730968	Curculionidae	<i>Laparocerus debilis</i>	END	END	TF	
OQ739306	OQ730983	Curculionidae	<i>Laparocerus decipiens</i>	END	END	LP	
OQ739157	OQ730833	Curculionidae	<i>Laparocerus edaphicus</i>	END	END	TF	
OQ739221	OQ730897	Curculionidae	<i>Laparocerus ellipticus</i>	END	END	TF, LG, LP, EH	
OQ739292	OQ730969	Curculionidae	<i>Laparocerus elongatus</i>	END	END	LP	
OQ739155	OQ730831	Curculionidae	<i>Laparocerus escaleraorum</i>	END	END	TF	
OQ739178	OQ730854	Curculionidae	<i>Laparocerus excavatus</i>	END	END	TF, LG	
OQ739199	OQ730875	Curculionidae	<i>Laparocerus freyi</i>	END	END	TF	
OQ739158	OQ730834	Curculionidae	<i>Laparocerus grossepunctatus</i>	END	END	TF	
OQ739156	OQ730832	Curculionidae	<i>Laparocerus grossepunctatus combrecitensis</i>	END	END	LP	
OQ739188	OQ730864	Curculionidae	<i>Laparocerus impressicollis</i>	END	END	TF	
OQ739234	OQ730910	Curculionidae	<i>Laparocerus inaequalis globulipennis</i>	END	END	LP	
OQ739235	OQ730911	Curculionidae	<i>Laparocerus inaequalis inaequalis</i>	END	END	TF	
OQ739341	OQ731018	Curculionidae	<i>Laparocerus inflatus</i>	END	END	LG	
OQ739305	OQ730982	Curculionidae	<i>Laparocerus juelensis juelensis</i>	END	END	LG	
OQ739293	OQ730970	Curculionidae	<i>Laparocerus junonius</i>	END	END	LG	
OQ739179	OQ730855	Curculionidae	<i>Laparocerus laevis</i>	END	END	LP	
OQ739211	OQ730887	Curculionidae	<i>Laparocerus lepidopterus</i>	END	END	TF, LG, LP, EH	
OQ739363	OQ731043	Curculionidae	<i>Laparocerus mendicus</i>	END	END	EH	
OQ739201	OQ730877	Curculionidae	<i>Laparocerus microphthalmus</i>	END	END	EH	
OQ739167	OQ730843	Curculionidae	<i>Laparocerus subcalvus</i>	END	END	EH	
OQ739354	OQ731033	Curculionidae	<i>Laparocerus supranubius</i>	END	END	LP	
OQ739202	OQ730878	Curculionidae	<i>Laparocerus tessellatus</i>	END	END	TF	
OQ739154	OQ730830	Curculionidae	<i>Laparocerus undatus</i>	END	END	TF	
OQ739367	OQ731047	Curculionidae	<i>Laparocerus zarazagai criniger</i>	END	END	LP	
OQ739172	OQ730848	Curculionidae	<i>Lauriacalles acutus</i>	END	END	TF, LP	
OQ739328	OQ731005	Curculionidae	<i>Leiosoma apionides</i>	END	END	TF, LG, LP	
OQ739441	OQ731124	Curculionidae	<i>Liparthrum bituberculatum</i>	NAT_notend	NAT_notend	TF, LG, LP, EH	
OQ739412	OQ731095	Curculionidae	<i>Liparthrum mandibulare</i>	NAT_notend	INT	TF, LG, EH	100% sequence similarity to specimens from France. Sampled in one plot (HDC).
OQ739444	OQ731127	Curculionidae	<i>Micrelius ferrugatus</i>	NAT_notend	NAT_notend	TF	

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OQ739342	OQ731019	Curculionidae	<i>Onyxacalles neglectus</i>	END	END	LG, EH	
OQ739351	OQ731028	Curculionidae	<i>Onyxacalles ringeli</i>	END	END	LP	
OQ739177	OQ730853	Curculionidae	<i>Onyxacalles verrucosus</i>	END	END	TF, LG, EH	
OQ739352	OQ731029	Curculionidae	<i>Pselactus affinis</i>	END	END	TF, LG, LP, EH	
OQ739253	OQ730929	Curculionidae	<i>Pselactus simplicipes</i>	END	END	TF	
OQ739257	OQ730934	Curculionidae	<i>Pselactus</i> sp. 1	END	END	TF, LG	
OQ739358	OQ731037	Curculionidae	<i>Pselactus</i> sp. 2	END	END	LP	
OQ739274	OQ730951	Curculionidae	<i>Pseudodichromacalles xerampelinus</i>	END	END	TF	
OQ739169	OQ730845	Curculionidae	<i>Rhopalomesites complanatus</i>	END	END	LP	
OQ739170	OQ730846	Curculionidae	<i>Rhopalomesites persimilis</i>	END	END	TF, LG	
OQ739298	OQ730975	Curculionidae	<i>Rhopalomesites proximus</i>	END	END	TF, LG, LP	
OQ739173	OQ730849	Curculionidae	<i>Silvacalles cedroensis</i>	END	END	LG	
OQ739176	OQ730852	Curculionidae	<i>Silvacalles instabilis</i>	END	END	TF	
OQ739175	OQ730851	Curculionidae	<i>Silvacalles lepidus</i>	END	END	LG, LP	
OQ739174	OQ730850	Curculionidae	<i>Silvacalles mundus</i>	END	END	TF, LP	
OQ739457	OQ731141	Curculionidae	<i>Sirocalodes nigroterminatus</i>	NAT_notend	NAT_notend	TF, LG, LP, EH	
OQ739460	OQ731144	Curculionidae	<i>Sitona lineatus</i>	NAT_notend	NAT_notend	TF, LG, LP	
OQ739396	OQ731078	Curculionidae	<i>Sitona macularius</i>	INT	INT	TF, LG, LP, EH	Sampled in one plot (CED).
OQ739482	OQ731166	Curculionidae	<i>Smicronyx albosquamosus</i>	NAT_notend	NAT_notend	TF, LG, LP, EH	
OQ739326	OQ731003	Curculionidae	<i>Torneuma aphroditae</i>	END	END	LG	
OQ739353	OQ731032	Curculionidae	<i>Torneuma lindrothi</i>	END	END	LP	
OQ739454	OQ731138	Curculionidae	<i>Tychius colonnellii</i>	NAT_notend	NAT_notend	TF	
OQ739388	OQ731069	Curculionidae	<i>Xyleborinus saxesenii</i>	INT	INT	TF, LG, LP	Sampled in one plot (ANE).
OQ739440	OQ731123	Dryopidae	<i>Dryops gracilis</i>	NAT_notend	NAT_notend	TF, LG, LP, EH	
OQ739244	OQ730920	Elateridae	<i>Coptostethus brunneipennis</i>	END	END	TF	
OQ739243	OQ730919	Elateridae	<i>Coptostethus</i> cf. <i>obscurus</i>	END	END	EH	
OQ739204	OQ730880	Elateridae	<i>Coptostethus</i> sp. 1	END	END	TF	
OQ739300	OQ730977	Elateridae	<i>Coptostethus</i> sp. 2	END	END	TF	
OQ739324	OQ731001	Elateridae	<i>Coptostethus</i> sp. 3	END	END	LG	
OQ739365	OQ731045	Elateridae	<i>Coptostethus</i> sp. 4	END	END	EH	
OQ739302	OQ730979	Endomychidae	<i>Dapsa</i> sp.	END	END	TF, LP, EH	
OQ739311	OQ730988	Endomychidae	<i>Lycoperdina gomeræ</i>	END	END	LG	
OQ739280	OQ730957	Endomychidae	<i>Lycoperdina humeralis</i>	END	END	TF	
OQ739312	OQ730989	Endomychidae	<i>Lycoperdina sanchezi</i>	END	END	LP	

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OQ739414	OQ731097	Endomychidae	<i>Mycetaea subterranea</i>	INT	INT	TF, LG	Sampled in one plot (PBL).
OQ739357	OQ731036	Erotylidae	<i>Xenoscelis lauricola</i>	END	END	LP	
OQ739318	OQ730995	Erotylidae	<i>Xestus</i> sp.	END	END	LG	
OQ739184	OQ730860	Erotylidae	<i>Xestus throscooides</i>	END	END	TF	
OQ739231	OQ730907	Eucinetidae	<i>Nycteus wollastoni</i>	END	END	TF, LG, LP, EH	
OQ739322	OQ730999	Histeridae	<i>Aeletes gemmula</i>	END	END	LG	
OQ739281	OQ730958	Histeridae	<i>Eubrachium</i> sp.	END	END	TF, LG	
OQ739449	OQ731133	Histeridae	<i>Kissister minimus</i>	NAT_notend	NAT_notend	TF	
OQ739478	OQ731162	Histeridae	<i>Paromalus luderti</i>	NAT_notend	NAT_notend	TF, LG, LP	
OQ739277	OQ730954	Histeridae	<i>Teretrius cylindricus</i>	END	END	TF, LG, LP, EH	
OQ739338	OQ731015	Kateretidae	<i>Brachypterus aeneomicans</i>	END	END	TF, LG, LP	
OQ739359	OQ731038	Kateretidae	<i>Brachypterus longimanus</i>	END	END	TF, LG, LP	
OQ739499	OQ731183	Kateretidae	<i>Brachypterus</i> sp.	NAT_notend or END	NAT_notend or END	LP	5 species recorded for the Canary Islands: 4 END, 1 NAT_notend. 2 END sampled, thus could be one of 2 END or 1 NAT_notend.
OQ739393	OQ731074	Laemophloeidae	<i>Cryptolestes</i> sp.	NAT_notend or INT	INT	TF, LP	3 species recorded in Canary Islands (2 INT, 1 NAT_notend). As 1 INT and 1 NAT_notend were also sampled, this is assumed to be the second INT. Sampled in one plot (PAS).
OQ739408	OQ731091	Laemophloeidae	<i>Cryptolestes pusillus</i>	INT	INT	TF	Sampled in two plots (CUB and TAB).
OQ739437	OQ731120	Laemophloeidae	<i>Cryptolestes spartii</i>	NAT_notend	NAT_notend	TF, LG, LP, EH	
OQ739438	OQ731121	Laemophloeidae	<i>Placonotus granulatus</i>	NAT_notend	NAT_notend	TF, LG, LP, EH	
OQ739378	OQ731059	Latridiidae	<i>Cartodere nodifer</i>	NAT_notend	INT	TF, LG, LP	100% sequence similarity to specimens from Germany, Belgium, Finland, Sweden, United Kingdom, Bulgaria, New Zealand and Canada. Sampled in five plots (ANE, COC, LOM, MOQ and TAB).
OQ739407	OQ731090	Latridiidae	<i>Corticaria fagi</i>	---	INT	LP	New species record for the Canary Islands. 99.9% sequence similarity to specimens from Germany. Sampled in one plot (CUM).

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OQ739420	OQ731103	Latridiidae	<i>Corticaria</i> sp. 1	NAT_notend or END	END	TF, LG, LP, EH	11 species recorded for the Canary Islands, including a new INT record: 1 INT, 5 NAT_notend, 5 END. BOLD sequences for 4 NAT_notend species did not provide a match. Thus, among the remaining possibilities (5 END, 1 NAT_notend), most likely to be END (83%).
OQ739453	OQ731137	Latridiidae	<i>Corticaria</i> sp. 2	NAT_notend or END	END	TF, LG	11 species recorded for the Canary Islands, including a new INT record: 1 INT, 5 NAT_notend, 5 END. BOLD sequences for 4 NAT_notend species did not provide a match. Thus, among the remaining possibilities (5 END, 1 NAT_notend), most likely to be END (83%).
OQ739392	OQ731073	Latridiidae	<i>Corticarina cavicollis</i>	---	INT	TF	New species record for the Canary Islands. 99.5% sequence similarity to specimens from Canada. Sampled in one plot (TAG).
OQ739486	OQ731170	Latridiidae	<i>Corticarina delicatula</i>	END	END	LP	
OQ739340	OQ731017	Latridiidae	<i>Latridius canariensis</i>	END	END	TF, LG, LP, EH	
OQ739432	OQ731115	Latridiidae	<i>Metopthalmus</i> sp. 1	NAT_notend or END	NAT_notend or END	TF, LG, LP	5 species recorded for the Canary Islands: 3 END, 2 NAT_notend.
OQ739468	OQ731152	Latridiidae	<i>Metopthalmus</i> sp. 2	NAT_notend or END	NAT_notend or END	EH	5 species recorded for the Canary Islands: 3 END, 2 NAT_notend.
OQ739492	OQ731176	Latridiidae	<i>Metopthalmus</i> sp. 3	NAT_notend or END	NAT_notend or END	LP, EH	5 species recorded for the Canary Islands: 3 END, 2 NAT_notend.
OQ739183	OQ730859	Leiodidae	<i>Agathidium</i> sp. 1	NAT_notend or END	END	TF, LG, LP, EH	9 species recorded for the Canary Islands: 8 END, 1 NAT_notend. Likely to be END (89%).
OQ739325	OQ731002	Leiodidae	<i>Agathidium</i> sp. 2	NAT_notend or END	END	LG	9 species recorded for the Canary Islands: 8 END, 1 NAT_notend. 1 END sampled. Thus likely to be END (88%).
OQ739283	OQ730960	Leiodidae	<i>Catops antoniomachadoi</i>	END	END	TF	
OQ739264	OQ730941	Leiodidae	<i>Leiodes canariensis</i>	END	END	TF, LG, LP, EH	
OQ739190	OQ730866	Leiodidae	<i>Leiodes oceanica</i>	END	END	TF, LG	
OQ739339	OQ731016	Leiodidae	<i>Nargus</i> sp.	END	END	LG	

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OQ739458	OQ731142	Meloidae	<i>Meloe</i> sp.	NAT_notend or END	NAT_notend	TF, LG, EH	7 species recorded for the Canary Islands: 6 NAT_notend and 1 END. BOLD sequences for the END species did not provide a match.
OQ739237	OQ730913	Melyridae	<i>Aplocnemus sculpturatus</i>	END	END	TF, LG, LP	
OQ739238	OQ730914	Melyridae	<i>Aplocnemus vestitus</i>	END	END	EH	
OQ739386	OQ731067	Mycetophagidae	<i>Litargus balteatus</i>	INT	INT	TF, LP	Sampled in one plot (MOQ).
OQ739278	OQ730955	Nitidulidae	<i>Acanthogethes hercules</i>	END	END	TF	
OQ739266	OQ730943	Nitidulidae	<i>Afrogethes canariensis</i>	END	END	TF, LG, LP, EH	
OQ739450	OQ731134	Nitidulidae	<i>Cybocephalus</i> sp.	NAT_notend or END	NAT_notend or END	TF, LP	4 species recorded in the Canary Islands: 3 NAT_notend and 1 END.
OQ739394	OQ731075	Nitidulidae	<i>Eपुरaea imperialis</i>	INT	INT	TF, LG	Sampled in one plot (ACE).
OQ739374	OQ731054	Nitidulidae	<i>Eपुरaea ocularis</i>	NAT_notend	INT	TF, LG, LP	99.4% sequence similarity to specimens from French Polynesia, West Papua and Malaysia. Sampled in five plots (CHI, CTE, IJU, NIE and PIJ).
OQ739279	OQ730956	Nitidulidae	<i>Paleogethes wollastoni</i>	END	END	TF, LG, LP, EH	
OQ739191	OQ730867	Nitidulidae	<i>Xenostromgylus canariensis</i>	END	END	TF, LG, LP, EH	
OQ739295	OQ730972	Nitidulidae	<i>Xenostromgylus titanus</i>	END	END	TF, LG	
OQ739443	OQ731126	Phalacridae	<i>Olibrus</i> sp.	NAT_notend or END	NAT_notend or END	TF, LG, LP, EH	4 species recorded in the Canary Islands: 3 NAT_notend and 1 END. BOLD sequence for 1 NAT_notend did not provide a match. Thus, could be one of 2 NAT_notend or 1 END.
OQ739417	OQ731100	Ptiliidae	<i>Acrotichis</i> sp.	NAT_notend or END	NAT_notend or END	TF, LG, LP, EH	8 species recorded in the Canary Islands: 6 NAT_notend, 2 END. BOLD sequences for 4 NAT_notend and 1 END species did not provide a match. Thus, could be one of 2 NAT_notend or 1 END.
OQ739451	OQ731135	Ptiliidae	<i>Ptenidium laevigatum</i>	NAT_notend	NAT_notend	TF, LG, LP, EH	
OQ739485	OQ731169	Ptiliidae	<i>Ptinella aptera</i>	NAT_notend	NAT_notend	LP, EH	

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OQ739483	OQ731167	Ptinidae	<i>Lasioderma</i> sp.	NAT_notend or END or INT	END	LP, EH	8 species are recorded for Canary Islands: 3 INT, 1 NAT_notend and 4 END. BOLD sequenced for 2 INT species did not provide a match, and genetic variation within and between islands is inconsistent with an INT species. Thus, among the remaining possibilities (4 END and 1 NAT_notend), most likely to be END (80%).
OQ739219	OQ730895	Ptinidae	<i>Stagetus hirtulus</i>	END	END	TF, LG, LP, EH	
OQ739498	OQ731182	Salpingidae	<i>Sphaeriestes impressus</i>	NAT_notend	NAT_notend	TF, LG, LP	
OQ739421	OQ731104	Scraptiidae	<i>Anaspis proteus</i>	NAT_notend	NAT_notend	TF, LG, LP, EH	
OQ739182	OQ730858	Silphidae	<i>Heterotemna figurata</i>	END	END	TF	
OQ739181	OQ730857	Silphidae	<i>Heterotemna tenuicornis</i>	END	END	TF	
OQ739268	OQ730945	Staphylinidae	<i>Afropselaphus fernandezi</i>	END	END	TF	
OQ739459	OQ731143	Staphylinidae	<i>Aleochara funebris</i>	NAT_notend	NAT_notend	TF, LG, LP, EH	
OQ739337	OQ731014	Staphylinidae	<i>Alevonota</i> sp. 1	END	END	LG	
OQ739496	OQ731180	Staphylinidae	<i>Alevonota</i> sp. 2	END	END	LP	
OQ739497	OQ731181	Staphylinidae	<i>Aloconota</i> sp.	NAT_notend	NAT_notend	LP	
OQ739419	OQ731102	Staphylinidae	<i>Astenus</i> sp.	NAT_notend or END	NAT_notend or END	TF, LG, LP, EH	10 species recorded for the Canary Islands: 5 NAT_notend, 5 END.
OQ739371	OQ731051	Staphylinidae	<i>Atheta aeneicollis</i>	NAT_notend	INT	TF, LG, LP, EH	99.9% sequence similarity to specimens from Belgium and Germany. Sampled in five plots (AGU, COC, PAS, PBL and PIJ).
OQ739390	OQ731071	Staphylinidae	<i>Atheta coriaria</i>	NAT_notend	INT	TF, LG, LP, EH	99.5% sequence similarity to specimens from Germany. Sampled in one plot (PIJ).
OQ739411	OQ731094	Staphylinidae	<i>Atheta fungi</i>	NAT_notend	INT	TF, LG, LP, EH	100% sequence similarity to specimens from France and New Zealand. Sampled in one plot (PDR).
OQ739171	OQ730847	Staphylinidae	<i>Atheta rufofusca</i>	END	END	TF, EH	

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OQ739416	OQ731099	Staphylinidae	<i>Atheta</i> sp. 1	NAT_notend or END or INT	NAT_notend or END	TF, LG, EH	24 species recorded for the Canary Islands: 13 NAT_notend, 7 END and 3 INT (previously considered NATnotend). 1 END and 3 INT sampled, plus BOLD sequenced for 10 NAT_notend did not provide a match. Thus, could be one of 3 NAT_notend or 6 END.
OQ739424	OQ731107	Staphylinidae	<i>Atheta</i> sp. 2	NAT_notend or END or INT	NAT_notend or END	TF, LG, LP, EH	24 species recorded for the Canary Islands: 13 NAT_notend, 7 END 3 INT (previously considered NATnotend). 1 END and 3 INT sampled, plus BOLD sequenced for 10 NAT_notend did not provide a match. Thus, could be one of 3 NAT_notend or 6 END.
OQ739404	OQ731086	Staphylinidae	<i>Atheta</i> sp. 3	NAT_notend or END or INT	INT	TF, LP, EH	Limited genetic variation consistent with INT species. Sampled in ten plots (AGA, CUB, CUM, HDC, LOM, MAG, NIQ, PBL, PDR and TAB).
---	OQ731087	Staphylinidae	<i>Atheta</i> sp. 4	NAT_notend or END or INT	INT	LP	Limited genetic variation consistent with INT species. Sampled in two plots (CUM and NIQ). Only COI-3P fragment used for analyses
OQ739228	OQ730904	Staphylinidae	<i>Canariobolitobius filicornis</i>	END	END	TF, LG, LP, EH	
OQ739395	OQ731076	Staphylinidae	<i>Cephennium</i> sp.	---	INT	TF	New genus record for the Canary Islands. 92.0% similarity to sequences of <i>Cephennium thoracicum</i> from Germany. Sampled in one plot (NIE).
OQ739275	OQ730952	Staphylinidae	<i>Entomoculia lauricola</i>	END	END	TF	
OQ739297	OQ730974	Staphylinidae	<i>Entomoculia</i> sp.	END	END	TF	
OQ739290	OQ730967	Staphylinidae	<i>Euplectus</i> sp.	NAT_notend or END	END	TF	10 <i>Euplectus</i> species are for the Canary Islands, 9 END and 1 NAT_notend. Likely to be END (90%).
OQ739245	OQ730921	Staphylinidae	<i>Euplectus wollastoni</i>	END	END	TF, LG, LP	
OQ739331	OQ731008	Staphylinidae	<i>Eutheia tenerifae</i>	END	END	TF, LG, LP, EH	

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OQ739448	OQ731132	Staphylinidae	<i>Gabrius</i> sp.	NAT_notend or END	NAT_notend or END	TF, LG, EH	4 species recorded for the Canary Islands: 2 END, 2 NAT_notend. BOLD sequences for 1 NAT_notend did not provide a match. Thus, could be one of 2 END or 1 NAT_notend.
OQ739233	OQ730909	Staphylinidae	<i>Geomitopsis franzi</i> complex 1	END	END	TF	
OQ739236	OQ730912	Staphylinidae	<i>Geomitopsis franzi</i> complex 2	END	END	TF	
OQ739299	OQ730976	Staphylinidae	<i>Geomitopsis franzi</i> complex 3	END	END	TF	
OQ739397	OQ731079	Staphylinidae	<i>Habrocerus capillaricornis</i>	NAT_notend	INT	TF, LG, LP	100 % sequence similarity to specimens from Greece, Germany, Belgium, and the United States. Sampled in four plots (EHA, LOM, PBL and TAB).
OQ739330	OQ731007	Staphylinidae	<i>Heterothops canariensis</i>	END	END	TF, LG, LP, EH	
OQ739442	OQ731125	Staphylinidae	<i>Holobus chrysopygus</i>	NAT_notend	NAT_notend	TF, LG, LP	
OQ739335	OQ731012	Staphylinidae	<i>Ischnosoma monilicorne</i>	END	END	TF, LG, LP	
OQ739426	OQ731109	Staphylinidae	<i>Lordithon thoracicus</i>	NAT_notend	NAT_notend	TF, LG, LP, EH	
OQ739276	OQ730953	Staphylinidae	<i>Medon subcoriaceus</i>	END	END	TF, LG, LP, EH	
OQ739504	OQ731189	Staphylinidae	<i>Megalinus hesperius</i>	NAT_notend	NAT_notend	TF, LG, LP, EH	
OQ739418	OQ731101	Staphylinidae	<i>Megarthus wollastoni</i> 1	NAT_notend	NAT_notend	TF, LG, LP, EH	
OQ739470	OQ731154	Staphylinidae	<i>Megarthus wollastoni</i> 2	NAT_notend	NAT_notend	TF, LG, LP, EH	
OQ739252	OQ730928	Staphylinidae	<i>Metopsia cimicoides</i>	END	END	TF	
OQ739356	OQ731035	Staphylinidae	<i>Metopsia palmensis</i>	END	END	LP	
OQ739479	OQ731163	Staphylinidae	<i>Mycetoporus</i> sp.	NAT_notend or END	NAT_notend or END	LG	7 species recorded for the Canary Islands: 4 END, 3 NAT_notend.
OQ739373	OQ731053	Staphylinidae	<i>Ocypus aethiops</i>	INT	INT	TF	Sampled in nine plots (AGA, AGU, ANE, COC, MOQ, NIE, PBL, TAG and ZAP).
OQ739402	OQ731084	Staphylinidae	<i>Ocypus olens</i>	INT	INT	TF, LG, LP, EH	Sampled in three plots (FAY, MEN and PDR).

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GenBank accession number COI-5P	GenBank accession number COI-3P	Family	Species	BIOTA status	Final revised status	Distribution	Observation
OQ739465	OQ731149	Staphylinidae	<i>Ocypus</i> sp. 1	NAT_notend or END or INT	END	LG	11 species recorded for the Canary Islands: 7 END, 2 NAT_notend, 2 INT. 1 INT, 1 NAT_notend and 1 END already sampled. Thus, among the remaining possibilities (6 END, 1 NAT_notend), most likely to be END (86%).
OQ739466	OQ731150	Staphylinidae	<i>Ocypus</i> sp. 2	NAT_notend or END or INT	END	LG	11 species recorded for the Canary Islands: 7 END, 2 NAT_notend, 2 INT. 1 INT, 1 NAT_notend and 2 END already sampled. Thus, among the remaining possibilities (5 END, 1 NAT_notend), most likely to be END (83%).
OQ739490	OQ731174	Staphylinidae	<i>Ocypus</i> sp. 3	NAT_notend or END or INT	END	LP	11 species recorded for the Canary Islands: 7 END, 2 NAT_notend, 2 INT. 1 INT, 1 NAT_notend and 3 END already sampled. Thus, among the remaining possibilities (4 END, 1 NAT_notend), most likely to be END (80%).
OQ739481	OQ731165	Staphylinidae	<i>Ocypus subaenescens</i>	NAT_notend	NAT_notend	TF, LG, LP, EH	
OQ739263	OQ730940	Staphylinidae	<i>Ocypus umbricola</i>	END	END	TF	
OQ739455	OQ731139	Staphylinidae	<i>Oligota</i> sp.	NAT_notend or END	NAT_notend or END	TF, LG, LP	9 species recorded for the Canary Islands: 5 END, 4 NAT_notend (4 native not endemic and 5 endemic). BOLD sequences for 2 NAT_notend species did not provide a match. This, this could be one of 5 END or two NAT_notend species.
---	OQ731030	Staphylinidae	<i>Othius philonthoides</i>	END	END	TF, LG, LP, EH	Only COI-3P fragment used for analyses
OQ739267	OQ730944	Staphylinidae	<i>Othius</i> sp. 1	END	END	TF	
OQ739304	OQ730981	Staphylinidae	<i>Othius</i> sp. 2	END	END	LG	
OQ739336	OQ731013	Staphylinidae	<i>Othius</i> sp. 3	END	END	LG	
OQ739345	OQ731022	Staphylinidae	<i>Othius</i> sp. 4	END	END	EH	

GenBank accession number COI-5P	GenBank accession number COI-3P	Family	Species	BIOTA status	Final revised status	Distribution	Observation
OQ739428	OQ731111	Staphylinidae	<i>Oxypoda</i> sp. 1	NAT_notend or END	END	TF, LG	26 species recorded in the Canary Islands: 21 END, 5 NAT_notend. BOLD sequences for 2 NAT_notend species did not provide a match. Thus, among the remaining possibilities (21 END, 3 NAT_notend), most likely to be END (88%).
OQ739467	OQ731151	Staphylinidae	<i>Oxypoda</i> sp. 2	NAT_notend or END	END	LG	26 species recorded in the Canary Islands: 21 END, 5 NAT_notend. 1 END sampled and BOLD sequences for 2 NAT_notend species did not provide a match. Thus, among the remaining possibilities (19 END, 3 NAT_notend), most likely to be END (86%).
OQ739469	OQ731153	Staphylinidae	<i>Oxypoda</i> sp. 3	NAT_notend or END	END	LG	26 species recorded in the Canary Islands: 21 END, 5 NAT_notend. 2 END sampled and BOLD sequences for 2 NAT_notend species did not provide a match. Thus, among the remaining possibilities (18 END, 3 NAT_notend), most likely to be END (86%).
OQ739436	OQ731119	Staphylinidae	<i>Philorinum floricola</i>	NAT_notend	NAT_notend	TF, LG, LP, EH	
OQ739209	OQ730885	Staphylinidae	<i>Protogoerius brullei</i>	END	END	TF	
OQ739456	OQ731140	Staphylinidae	<i>Quedius</i> sp. 1	NAT_notend or END	END	TF, LG, EH	10 species recorded in the Canary Islands: 6 END, 4 NAT_notend. BOLD sequences for 3 NAT_notend species did not provide a match. Thus, among the remaining possibilities (6 END, 1 NAT_notend), most likely to be END (86%).
OQ739472	OQ731156	Staphylinidae	<i>Quedius</i> sp. 2	NAT_notend or END	END	LG	10 species recorded in the Canary Islands: 6 END, 4 NAT_notend. 1 END sampled and BOLD sequences for 3 NAT_notend species did not provide a match. Thus, among the remaining possibilities (5 END, 1 NAT_notend), most likely to be END (83%).

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GenBank accession number COI-5P	GenBank accession number COI-3P	Family	Species	BIOTA status	Final revised status	Distribution	Observation
OQ739423	OQ731106	Staphylinidae	<i>Sepedophilus</i> sp. 1	NAT_notend or END	END	TF, LP	3 species recorded in the Canary Islands: 2 NAT_notend, 1 END. BOLD sequences for 2 NAT_notend species did not provide a match.
OQ739446	OQ731129	Staphylinidae	<i>Sepedophilus</i> sp. 2	NAT_notend or END	END	TF	3 species recorded in the Canary Islands: 2 NAT_notend, 1 END. BOLD sequences for 2 NAT_notend species did not provide a match.
OQ739463	OQ731147	Staphylinidae	<i>Sepedophilus</i> sp. 3	NAT_notend or END	END	TF, LG	3 species recorded in the Canary Islands: 2 NAT_notend, 1 END. BOLD sequences for 2 NAT_notend species did not provide a match.
OQ739473	OQ731157	Staphylinidae	<i>Sepedophilus</i> sp. 4	NAT_notend or END	END	LG	3 species recorded in the Canary Islands: 2 NAT_notend, 1 END. BOLD sequences for 2 NAT_notend species did not provide a match.
OQ739500	OQ731184	Staphylinidae	<i>Sepedophilus</i> sp. 5	NAT_notend or END	END	TF	3 species recorded in the Canary Islands: 2 NAT_notend, 1 END. BOLD sequences for 2 NAT_notend species did not provide a match.
OQ739223	OQ730899	Staphylinidae	<i>Stenichnus</i> sp. 1	END	END	TF, LG	
OQ739296	OQ730973	Staphylinidae	<i>Stenichnus</i> sp. 2	END	END	TF, LP	
OQ739321	OQ730998	Staphylinidae	<i>Stenichnus</i> sp. 3	END	END	LG	
OQ739323	OQ731000	Staphylinidae	<i>Stenichnus</i> sp. 4	END	END	LG	
OQ739230	OQ730906	Staphylinidae	<i>Stenus fortunatus</i>	END	END	TF	
OQ739255	OQ730932	Staphylinidae	<i>Sunius brevipennis</i>	END	END	TF, LG, LP, EH	
OQ739380	OQ731061	Staphylinidae	<i>Tachyporus chrysomelinus</i>	NAT_notend	INT	TF, LP	99.6% sequence similarity to specimens from Portugal (Azores). Sampled in four plots (ANE, COC, LOM and TAB).
OQ739409	OQ731092	Staphylinidae	<i>Tachyporus pusillus</i>	NAT_notend	INT	TF, LG, LP, EH	99.8% sequence similarity to specimens from Germany, Belarus and Finland. Sampled in one plot (CUB).
OQ739480	OQ731164	Staphylinidae	<i>Trichophya</i> sp.	NAT_notend	NAT_notend	LG	
OQ739343	OQ731020	Tenebrionidae	<i>Crypticus</i> sp.	END	END	EH	
OQ739205	OQ730881	Tenebrionidae	<i>Nesotes conformis</i>	END	END	TF, LP, EH	
OQ739346	OQ731023	Tenebrionidae	<i>Nesotes congestus</i>	END	END	LP, EH	
OQ739348	OQ731025	Tenebrionidae	<i>Pimelia laevigata</i>	END	END	LG, LP, EH	
OQ739319	OQ730996	Throscidae	<i>Aulonothroscus elongatulus</i>	END	END	LG	

GenBank accession number COI-5P	GenBank accession number COI-3P	Family	Species	BIOTA status	Final revised status	Distribution	Observation
OQ739226	OQ730902	Throscidae	<i>Aulonothroscus latiusculus</i>	END	END	EH	
OQ739227	OQ730903	Throscidae	<i>Aulonothroscus</i> sp. 1	END	END	TF	
OQ739320	OQ730997	Throscidae	<i>Aulonothroscus</i> sp. 2	END	END	LP	
OQ739225	OQ730901	Throscidae	<i>Aulonothroscus tenerifae</i>	END	END	TF	
OQ739224	OQ730900	Throscidae	<i>Aulonothroscus wollastoni</i>	END	END	LP	
OQ739334	OQ731011	Trogossitidae	<i>Leipaspis lauricola gomerensis</i>	END	END	LG, EH	
OQ739210	OQ730886	Trogossitidae	<i>Leipaspis lauricola lauricola</i>	END	END	TF, LP	
OQ739364	OQ731044	Trogossitidae	<i>Leipaspis</i> sp.	END	END	EH	
OQ739313	OQ730990	Zopheridae	<i>Tarphius camelus</i>	END	END	EH	
OQ739159	OQ730835	Zopheridae	<i>Tarphius canariensis</i> or <i>simplex</i> or <i>elongatus</i>	END	END	TF, LG, LP	
OQ739214	OQ730890	Zopheridae	<i>Tarphius congestus</i>	END	END	TF	
OQ739215	OQ730891	Zopheridae	<i>Tarphius gigas</i>	END	END	TF	
OQ739314	OQ730991	Zopheridae	<i>Tarphius monstrosus</i>	END	END	LG	
OQ739316	OQ730993	Zopheridae	<i>Tarphius palmensis</i>	END	END	LP	
OQ739355	OQ731034	Zopheridae	<i>Tarphius quadratus</i>	END	END	LP	
OQ739303	OQ730980	Zopheridae	<i>Tarphius setosus</i>	END	END	LG, EH	
OQ739301	OQ730978	Zopheridae	<i>Tarphius</i> complex 1	END	END	TF	
OQ739315	OQ730992	Zopheridae	<i>Tarphius</i> complex 2	END	END	LG, LP	

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Table S5. Introduced beetle species recorded for the four western Canary Islands, not sampled in the laurel forests, and with available sequences in GenBank and/or BOLD Systems. Species names in bold indicate that they were used as a proxy for congeneric species for which sequences were not available (see methods). COI-3P corresponds to the 824 bp region of the mtDNA cytochrome oxidase I gene while COI-5P refer to the 658bp barcode region. ‘---’ denotes no data available. TF = Tenerife; LG = La Gomera; LP = La Palma; EH = El Hierro. When the complete COI region was extracted from a mitogenome, the corresponding start and end bases of the COI region were indicated in the ‘Observation column’. ‘Partially complete COI’ denotes sequences with both but not complete COI regions.

Family	Species	Distribution	GenBank Accession number COI-5P	GenBank Accession number COI-3P	BOLD Systems Accession number COI-5P	BOLD Systems Accession number COI-3P	Observation
Anthribidae	<i>Araecerus fasciculatus</i>	TF	KM446808	EF484370	FBCOI809-12	GBCL26975-19	
Anthribidae	<i>Trigonorhinus tomentosus</i>	TF, LG, LP, EH	FJ867819	---	GBCL5151-09	---	<i>T. tomentosus</i> is a proxy for <i>T. areolatus</i> . Only COI-5P fragment used for analyses
Bostrichidae	<i>Lyctus brunneus</i>	TF, LG	KM451715	---	FBCON493-13	---	Only COI-5P fragment used for analyses
Bostrichidae	<i>Minthea rugicollis</i>	LP	---	KM435096	---	GBCL27135-19	Only COI-3P fragment used for analyses.
Bostrichidae	<i>Rhyzopertha dominica</i>	TF, LP	MH817139	MH817139	GBMNA39667-19	GBMNA39667-19	Complete COI gene extracted from mitogenome (from bases 1,370 to 2,900).
Bostrichidae	<i>Sinoxylon muricatum</i>	TF	MN182825	---	PSFOR614-13	---	Only COI-5P fragment used for analyses
Bostrichidae	<i>Trogoxylon</i> sp.	TF	KF801957	KF801957	GBCL27138-19	GBCL27138-19	<i>Trogoxylon</i> sp. is a proxy for <i>T. impressum</i> . Partially complete COI
Buprestidae	<i>Buprestis laeiventris</i>	TF, LG	KM364353	KM364353	GBCL24379-15	GBCL24379-15	<i>B. laeiventris</i> is a proxy for <i>B. decora</i> . Partially complete COI
Buprestidae	<i>Dicerca moesta</i>	TF	KJ965352	---	COLFE627-13	---	Only COI-5P fragment used for analyses
Carabidae	<i>Bembidion varium</i>	TF, LG, LP	KX087242	KX087242	GBCL31832-19	GBCL31832-19	Complete COI gene extracted from mitogenome (from base 7,208 to 8,752).
Carabidae	<i>Bradycellus verbasci</i>	LP	KM442589	HQ165625	FBCOI931-12	GBCL30621-19	
Carabidae	<i>Demetrias atricapillus</i>	TF	HQ953962	DQ155934	FBCOB341-10	GBCL30991-19	
Carabidae	<i>Harpalus distinguendus</i>	TF, LG, LP	KM446086	AJ583347	GBCOL790-12	GBCL7768-12	
Carabidae	<i>Licinus punctatulus</i>	TF	---	JF778786	---	---	Only COI-3P fragment used for analyses
Carabidae	<i>Notiobia terminata</i>	TF, LG, LP, EH	HQ984441	---	USCOC921-10	---	<i>Notiobia terminata</i> is a proxy for <i>Notiobia cupripennis</i> . Only COI-5P fragment used for analyses
Carabidae	<i>Perigona nigriceps</i>	TF, LG	---	HQ164741	---	GBCL31007-19	Only COI-3P fragment used for analyses
Carabidae	<i>Sphodrus leucophthalmus</i>	TF	ON206715	---	GBMNF50762-22	---	Only COI-5P fragment used for analyses
Carabidae	<i>Tschitscherinellus cordatus</i>	TF	MK510518	AJ583280	GBMNB25887-20	GBCL7827-12	
Cerambycidae	<i>Hylotrupes bajulus</i>	TF, LG, LP	GU003930	GU003930	GBMIN39962-13	GBMIN39962-13	Complete COI gene.

Family	Species	Distribution	GenBank Accession number COI-5P	GenBank Accession number COI-3P	BOLD Systems Accession number COI-5P	BOLD Systems Accession number COI-3P	Observation
Cerambycidae	<i>Monochamus galloprovincialis</i>	LP	MZ057913	MZ057913	---	---	Complete COI gene.
Cerambycidae	<i>Nathrius brevipennis</i>	TF	OP270245	---	AUCER001-22	---	Only COI-5P fragment used for analyses
Cerambycidae	<i>Phoracantha recurva</i>	TF	---	---	COAS1395-12	---	Only COI-5P fragment used for analyses
Cerambycidae	<i>Phoracantha semipunctata</i>	TF, LG	HQ559064	---	COAS039-10	---	Only COI-5P fragment used for analyses
Cerambycidae	<i>Stromatium longicorne</i>	TF	MN315185	---	GBMNB25523-20	---	<i>Stromatium longicorne</i> is a proxy for <i>Stromatium unicolor</i> . Only COI-5P fragment used for analyses
Chrysomelidae	<i>Acanthoscelides macrophthalmus</i>	LP	---	AY947517	---	GBCCH2467-19	Only COI-3P fragment used for analyses
Chrysomelidae	<i>Acanthoscelides obtectus</i>	TF, LP, EH	KX825864	KX825864	GBMNA9684-19	GBMNA9684-19	Complete COI gene extracted from mitogenome (from base 1,562 to 3,101).
Chrysomelidae	<i>Bruchidius bimaculatus</i>	LP	AY390672	AY390672	GBCL1538-06	GBCL1538-06	Partially complete COI
Chrysomelidae	<i>Bruchidius incarnatus</i>	EH	AY625388	AY625388	GBCL1729-06	GBCL1729-06	Partially complete COI
Chrysomelidae	<i>Bruchidius lividimanus</i>	TF, LG, LP	AY390677	AY390677	GBCL1543-06	GBCL1543-06	Partially complete COI
Chrysomelidae	<i>Bruchidius murinus</i>	EH	HQ177499	HQ177499	GBCCH2703-19	GBCCH2703-19	Partially complete COI
Chrysomelidae	<i>Bruchidius quinqueguttatus</i>	TF	HQ177503	HQ177503	GBCCH2742-19	GBCCH2742-19	Partially complete COI
Chrysomelidae	<i>Bruchus pisorum</i>	TF, LG, LP, EH	KU982562	EF570094	GBMIN46617-17	GBCL4872-09	
Chrysomelidae	<i>Bruchus rufimanus</i>	TF, LG, LP, EH	AY997313	AY997313	GBCL2248-06	GBCL2248-06	Partially complete COI
Chrysomelidae	<i>Bruchus rufipes</i>	TF, LP	AY390696	AY390696	GBCL1560-06	GBCL1560-06	Partially complete COI
Chrysomelidae	<i>Bruchus signaticornis</i>	TF, LP	AY390697	AY390697	GBCL1561-06	GBCL1561-06	Partially complete COI
Chrysomelidae	<i>Callosobruchus chinensis</i>	TF, LP	KX641890	KX641890	GBCCH2874-19	GBCCH2874-19	Complete COI gene extracted from mitogenome (from base 1 to 1,504).
Chrysomelidae	<i>Callosobruchus maculatus</i>	TF	NC_053358	NC_053358	---	---	Complete COI gene extracted from mitogenome (from base 692 to 2,234).
Chrysomelidae	<i>Caryedon gonagra</i>	TF	KP216605	---	GBCCH2312-15	---	Only COI-5P fragment used for analyses
Chrysomelidae	<i>Cassida vittata</i>	TF	---	HQ165024	GMGMJ372-14	GBCCH3146-19	
Chrysomelidae	<i>Chrysolina americana</i>	TF	KF654762	KP762971	GBCCH3576-19	GBCCH3578-19	
Chrysomelidae	<i>Chrysolina bankii</i>	TF, LP	KF652453	KP762978	GBCCH3597-19	GBCCH3621-19	
Chrysomelidae	<i>Chrysolina peregrina</i>	LP	KF653530	KP763036	GBCCH3757-19	GBCCH3759-19	
Chrysomelidae	<i>Lema bilineata</i>	TF	MT002932	---	GBMNC63156-20	---	Only COI-5P fragment used for analyses
Chrysomelidae	<i>Mimosestes mimosae</i>	LP	AB499958	AB499958	GBCCH072-10	GBCCH072-10	Complete COI gene.

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Family	Species	Distribution	GenBank Accession number COI-5P	GenBank Accession number COI-3P	BOLD Systems Accession number COI-5P	BOLD Systems Accession number COI-3P	Observation
Chrysomelidae	<i>Sphaeroderma testaceum</i>	TF, LP	KX943444	KX943444	GBCCH11714-19	GBCCH11714-19	Complete COI gene extracted from mitogenome (from base 1,396 to 2,938).
Cleridae	<i>Necrobia ruficollis</i>	TF, LP, EH	MK422543	MK422543	---	---	Complete COI gene extracted from mitogenome (from base 1,444 to 2,980).
Cleridae	<i>Necrobia rufipes</i>	TF, LG, LP, EH	KC524712	KC524712	GBCL33018-19	GBCL33018-19	Complete COI gene.
Cleridae	<i>Tarsostenus univittatus</i>	LP	MN182989	KM435099	PSFOR1162-17	GBCL33084-19	
Coccinellidae	<i>Cryptolaemus montrouzieri</i>	TF, LG, LP, EH	KT878321	KT878321	GBCL33817-19	GBCL33817-19	Complete COI gene extracted from mitogenome (from base 1 to 1,449).
Coccinellidae	<i>Delphastus catalinae</i>	TF, LG	---	MF152800	TZBCA018-06	GBCL33989-19	.
Coccinellidae	<i>Harmonia axyridis</i>	TF	KU877028	KU877028	---	---	Complete COI gene extracted from mitogenome (from base 4,081 to 5,619).
Coccinellidae	<i>Myrrha octodecimguttata</i>	LG, EH	KM448818	GU073899	FBCON731-13	GBCL10842-12	
Coccinellidae	<i>Oenopia doublieri</i>	TF	---	GU073900	---	GBCL10843-12	Only COI-3P fragment used for analyses
Coccinellidae	<i>Olla vnigrum</i>	TF	KP829565	KP829565	GBMIN50036-17	GBMIN50036-17	Partially complete COI
Coccinellidae	<i>Rhizophorus litura</i>	TF, LG, LP, EH	KU919344	DQ155937	GCOL10838-16	GBCL33215-19	
Coccinellidae	<i>Vibidia duodecimguttata</i>	TF	MT114193	MT114193	---	---	Complete COI gene extracted from mitogenome (from base 4,587 to 6,123).
Curculionidae	<i>Aulacobaris caerulescens</i>	TF	KM443494	MT739393	GBCOU1980-13	GBMND70622-21	
Curculionidae	<i>Caulophilus oryzae</i>	LG, LP	MK347526	---	GBMNF52468-22	---	Only COI-5P fragment used for analyses
Curculionidae	<i>Ceutorhynchus pallidactylus</i>	TF, LG, LP, EH	KJ962663	EU110990	COLFE1504-13	GBCL10975-12	
Curculionidae	<i>Charagmus gressorius</i>	TF, LG, LP	KU919439	---	GCOL10134-16	---	Only COI-5P fragment used for analyses
Curculionidae	<i>Coccotrypes carpophagus</i>	TF	AF444069	AF444069	GBCL0779-06	GBCL0779-06	Partially complete COI
Curculionidae	<i>Coccotrypes dactyliperda</i>	TF, LP	AF444064	AF444064	GBCL0774-06	GBCL0774-06	Partially complete COI
Curculionidae	<i>Diaprepes abbreviatus</i>	TF	HQ891432	HQ891432	GBCL7233-11	GBCL7233-11	Partially complete COI
Curculionidae	<i>Eccoptyrus spinosus</i>	TF, LG, LP, EH	MN619919	---	GBMNB27806-20	---	Only COI-5P fragment used for analyses
Curculionidae	<i>Hypoborus ficus</i>	TF	MH404130	MH404130	---	---	Complete COI gene extracted from mitogenome (from base 1,638 to 3,135).
Curculionidae	<i>Hypothenemus eruditus</i>	TF, LG, LP, EH	JX416904	JX416904	GBCL15614-13	GBCL15614-13	Partially complete COI
Curculionidae	<i>Listroderes costirostris</i>	TF, LP	---	---	CURSA072-20	---	Only COI-5P fragment used for analyses
Curculionidae	<i>Mecinus pascuorum</i>	TF	KM451505	HQ164911	GBCOD687-13	GBCL46789-19	

Family	Species	Distribution	GenBank Accession number COI-5P	GenBank Accession number COI-3P	BOLD Systems Accession number COI-5P	BOLD Systems Accession number COI-3P	Observation
Curculionidae	<i>Naupactus cervinus</i>	TF, LG, LP, EH	GQ406829	GQ406829	GBCL7169-10	GBCL7169-10	
Curculionidae	<i>Otiiorhynchus cribricollis</i>	LG	MT909045	---	GBMNE16991-21	---	Only COI-5P fragment used for analyses
Curculionidae	<i>Phloeosinus aubei</i>	TF, LP, EH	JX416905	---	GBCL15613-13	---	Only COI-5P fragment used for analyses
Curculionidae	<i>Phloeosinus thujae</i>	TF	KM443374	---	FBCOO420-13	---	Only COI-5P fragment used for analyses
Curculionidae	<i>Phloeotribus cristatus</i>	LP	MN182974	---	PSFOR1216-17	---	Only COI-5P fragment used for analyses
Curculionidae	<i>Phloeotribus scarabaeoides</i>	TF	KM286371	---	PSFOR709-13	---	Only COI-5P fragment used for analyses
Curculionidae	<i>Pissodes castaneus</i>	TF, LP	KT258999	KT258999	---	---	Complete COI gene.
Curculionidae	<i>Premnobius ambitiosus</i>	TF, LG, LP, EH	---	---	KMPDJ1147-19	---	Only COI-5P fragment used for analyses
Curculionidae	<i>Pteleobius kraatzi</i>	LP	---	---	SCOL221-12	---	Only COI-5P fragment used for analyses
Curculionidae	<i>Rhinocyllus conicus</i>	TF	KJ962286	DQ155736	COLFF724-13	GBCL46563-19	
Curculionidae	<i>Rhytideres plicatus</i>	TF, LG, LP, EH	MT909068	---	GBMNE16986-21	---	Only COI-5P fragment used for analyses
Curculionidae	<i>Romualdius scaber</i>	TF	MG054578	---	ASCMT214-11	---	Only COI-5P fragment used for analyses
Curculionidae	<i>Scolytotplatypus africanus</i>	TF, LG, LP, EH	EU191866	---	GBCL3690-08	---	Only COI-5P fragment used for analyses
Curculionidae	<i>Sitona discoideus</i>	TF, LG, LP, EH	EF118295	EF118295	GBCL3778-08	GBCL3778-08	Complete COI gene.
Curculionidae	<i>Sitona obsoletus</i>	TF	MH814932	MH814932	GBMNA39665-19	GBMNA39665-19	Complete COI gene extracted from mitogenome (from base 1,746 to 3,288).
Curculionidae	<i>Xyleborus perforans</i>	TF, LG, LP, EH	HM398370	JX412850	COQT537-09	GBCL48798-19	
Curculionidae	<i>Xyleborus xylographus</i>	TF, LG, LP, EH	HM064150	---	ACB4094	---	Only COI-5P fragment used for analyses
Curculionidae	<i>Xylosandrus compactus</i>	TF, LG, LP, EH	JQ015165	---	GBCL14135-12	---	Only COI-5P fragment used for analyses
Dermestidae	<i>Anthrenus sp.</i>	TF	HQ232808	HQ232808	GBCL15633-13	GBCL15633-13	<i>Anthrenus</i> sp. is a proxy for <i>Anthrenus coloratus</i> . Complete COI gene extracted from mitogenome (from base 1 to 1,540).
Dermestidae	<i>Dermestes maculatus</i>	TF, LG, LP, EH	MG457037	MG457037	GBMNA9671-19	GBMNA9671-19	Complete COI gene extracted from mitogenome (from base 1,746 to 3,288).
Dermestidae	<i>Dermestes peruvianus</i>	TF	HM398866	DQ221956	CSP027-09	GBCL34135-19	
Dermestidae	<i>Dermestes undulatus</i>	TF, LP	KU909778	---	GCOL10981-16	---	Only COI-5P fragment used for analyses
Dryophthoridae	<i>Cactophagus spinolae</i>	TF	AY131112	AY131112	GBCL1040-06	GBCL1040-06	<i>Cactophagus spinolae</i> is a proxy for <i>Cactophagus crenatus</i> . Partially complete COI
Dryophthoridae	<i>Cosmopolites sordidus</i>	TF, LG, LP	MH281567	MH281567	---	---	Complete COI gene extracted from mitogenome (from base 1,909 to 3,372).

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Family	Species	Distribution	GenBank Accession number COI-5P	GenBank Accession number COI-3P	BOLD Systems Accession number COI-5P	BOLD Systems Accession number COI-3P	Observation
Dryophthoridae	<i>Diocalandra frumenti</i>	TF, LG, LP	AY131104	AY131104	GBCL1032-06	GBCL1032-06	Partially complete COI
Dryophthoridae	<i>Rhynchophorus ferrugineus</i>	TF	KT428893	KT428893	GBMNA9701-19	GBMNA9701-19	Complete COI gene extracted from mitogenome (from base 1,338 to 2,882).
Dryophthoridae	<i>Sitophilus granarius</i>	TF, LP, EH	HM398890	JN163959	CSP088-09	GBCL47223-19	
Dryophthoridae	<i>Sitophilus linearis</i>	TF	AY131102	AY131102	GBCL1030-06	GBCL1030-06	Partially complete COI
Dryophthoridae	<i>Sitophilus oryzae</i>	TF, LG, LP, EH	KX641892	KX641892	GBCL51302-19	GBCL51302-19	Complete COI gene extracted from mitogenome (from base 1,213 to 2,754).
Dryophthoridae	<i>Sitophilus zeamais</i>	TF, LG, LP, EH	MT294139	MT294139	---	---	Complete COI gene extracted from mitogenome (from base 1,323 to 2,864).
Dryophthoridae	<i>Sphenophorus venatus</i>	TF, LG, LP	---	MG437085	BBCCA3257-12	GBCL54015-19	
Elateridae	<i>Melanotus dichrous</i>	LP, EH	MN182830	---	PSFOR1306-17	---	Only COI-5P fragment used for analyses
Endomychidae	<i>Symbiotes gibberosus</i>	LP	GQ302381	GQ302381	GBMIN26128-13	GBMIN26128-13	Partially complete COI
Histeridae	<i>Acritus nigricornis</i>	TF	KU918413	HQ165584	GCOL11467-16	GBCL37039-19	<i>Acritus nigricornis</i> is as proxy for <i>Acritus analis</i> .
Hydrophilidae	<i>Pachysternum capense</i>	TF, LP	MW594151	MW594019	GBMNF54683-22	GBMNF54682-22	
Laemophloeidae	<i>Cryptolestes ferrugineus</i>	LG	KT182067	KT182067	GBMNA9707-19	GBMNA9707-19	Complete COI gene extracted from mitogenome (from base 1,423 to 2,964).
Mycetophagidae	<i>Litargus connexus</i>	TF, LG, LP, EH	MH020363	MH020363	GBCL43155-19	GBCL43155-19	<i>Litargus connexus</i> is a proxy for <i>Litargus coloratus</i> .
Mycetophagidae	<i>Typhaea stercorea</i>	TF, LG, LP, EH	---	---	BARSC462-16	---	Only COI-5P fragment used for analyses
Nitidulidae	<i>Amphotis marginata</i>	TF, LP	KM439450	MT140900	GBCOC821-12	GBMNC62589-20	<i>Amphotis marginata</i> is a proxy for <i>Amphotis orientalis</i> .
Nitidulidae	<i>Epuraea luteola</i>	TF, LG, LP, EH	MH674104	---	---	---	Only COI-5P fragment used for analyses
Nitidulidae	<i>Lobiopa insularis</i>	TF, LP	---	MT140920	---	GBMNC62569-20	Only COI-3P fragment used for analyses
Nitidulidae	<i>Nitidula carnaria</i>	TF	---	---	INRMA2536-15	---	Only COI-5P fragment used for analyses
Oedemeridae	<i>Oedemera nobilis</i>	TF	KM451568	DQ221991	GBCOB126-12	GBCL43820-19	
Ptinidae	<i>Anobium punctatum</i>	TF, LG, LP, EH	KU494026	HQ164762	CICRP094-15	GBCL26882-19	
Ptinidae	<i>Lasioderma serricorne</i>	TF, LG, LP	MT254408	MT254408	---	---	Complete COI gene extracted from mitogenome (from base 1,383 to 2,922).
Ptinidae	<i>Mezium affine</i>	TF, LG, LP, EH	KU494136	---	CICRP079-15	---	<i>Mezium affine</i> is a proxy for <i>Mezium americanum</i> . Only COI-5P fragment used for analyses
Ptinidae	<i>Nicobium castaneum</i>	TF, LP	KU494146	KM435097	CICRP046-15	GBCL26885-19	

Family	Species	Distribution	GenBank Accession number COI-5P	GenBank Accession number COI-3P	BOLD Systems Accession number COI-5P	BOLD Systems Accession number COI-3P	Observation
Ptinidae	<i>Ptinus dubius</i>	TF, LP	KM444597	---	FBCOC878-10	---	Only COI-5P fragment used for analyses
Ptinidae	<i>Stegobium paniceum</i>	TF, LG, LP, EH	KX819317	KX819317	GBMNA9669-19	GBMNA9669-19	Complete COI gene extracted from mitogenome (from base 1 to 1,531).
Salpingidae	<i>Aglenus brunneus</i>	TF, LG, LP, EH	---	HQ165206	---	GBCL44365-19	Only COI-3P fragment used for analyses
Scarabaeidae	<i>Protaetia cuprea</i>	TF	DQ295301	DQ295301	GBCL2548-06	GBCL2548-06	Complete COI gene.
Scarabaeidae	<i>Protaetia opaca</i>	TF	MT909062	MG813321	GBMNE17420-21	GBCLS1222-19	
Silphidae	<i>Silpha tyrolensis</i>	TF	KX087347	KX087347	GBCL44945-19	GBCL44945-19	<i>Silpha tyrolensis</i> is a proxy for <i>Silpha puncticolis</i> . Complete COI gene extracted from mitogenome (from base 509 to 2,048).
Silvanidae	<i>Oryzaephilus mercator</i>	TF, LP	MW728029	---	GBMND71813-21	---	Only COI-5P fragment used for analyses
Silvanidae	<i>Oryzaephilus surinamensis</i>	TF, LG, LP, EH	MN535903	MN535903	---	---	Complete COI gene extracted from mitogenome (from base 11,545 to 13,111).
Silvanidae	<i>Silvanus unidentatus</i>	TF	KM442937	DQ155740	FBCOJ264-12	GBCL44997-19	
Staphylinidae	<i>Atheta pasadenae</i>	TF, LP, EH	GQ980921	GQ980921	GBCL15087-13	GBCL15087-13	Complete COI gene.
Tenebrionidae	<i>Alphitobius diaperinus</i>	TF, LG, LP	MT610905	MT610905	---	---	Complete COI gene extracted from mitogenome (from base 1,425 to 2,958).
Tenebrionidae	<i>Alphitobius laevigatus</i>	TF, LP	---	KP410252	---	---	Only COI-3P fragment used for analyses
Tenebrionidae	<i>Blaps gigas</i>	TF, LG, LP, EH	MH265164	---	GBMNA37037-19	---	Only COI-5P fragment used for analyses
Tenebrionidae	<i>Blaps lethifera</i>	TF, LP	KM441591	---	GBCOU1461-13	---	Only COI-5P fragment used for analyses
Tenebrionidae	<i>Centorus elongatus</i>	TF	MK692707	MK692707	---	---	Complete COI gene extracted from mitogenome (from base 2,862 to 4,362).
Tenebrionidae	<i>Corticeus pini</i>	TF, LG, LP, EH	KM285989	---	PSFOR232-13	---	Only COI-5P fragment used for analyses
Tenebrionidae	<i>Cossyphus moniliferus</i>	TF, LP	MT909007	---	GBMNE17735-21	---	Only COI-5P fragment used for analyses
Tenebrionidae	<i>Gnatocerus cornutus</i>	TF, LG, LP, EH	KJ963565	---	COLFF758-13	---	Only COI-5P fragment used for analyses
Tenebrionidae	<i>Latheticus oryzae</i>	TF	JF889674	EU048283	FBCOC536-10	GBCL65919-19	
Tenebrionidae	<i>Lyphia</i> sp.	TF, LG, LP, EH	---	JQ753340	---	GBCL65926-19	<i>Lyphia</i> sp. is a proxy for <i>Lyphia angusta</i> . Only COI-3P fragment used for analyses
Tenebrionidae	<i>Myrmechixenus vaporarium</i>	TF	KM441348	HQ165103	FBCOG451-12	GBCL65357-19	
Tenebrionidae	<i>Palorus subdepressus</i>	LP	KM452267	---	FBCOG487-12	---	Only COI-5P fragment used for analyses

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Family	Species	Distribution	GenBank Accession number COI-5P	GenBank Accession number COI-3P	BOLD Systems Accession number COI-5P	BOLD Systems Accession number COI-3P	Observation
Tenebrionidae	<i>Scaurus uncinus</i>	TF	MK692593	MK692593	---	---	Complete COI gene extracted from mitogenome (from base 1,504 to 3,001).
Tenebrionidae	<i>Sclerum multistriatum</i>	TF, LP	---	FN544725	---	GBCL66219-19	<i>Sclerum multistriatum</i> is a proxy for <i>Sclerum armatum</i> . Only COI-3P fragment used for analyses
Tenebrionidae	<i>Tenebrio molitor</i>	LP	NC_024633	NC_024633	GBMNA9723-19	GBMNA9723-19	Complete COI gene extracted from mitogenome (from base 1,423 to 2,956).
Tenebrionidae	<i>Tenebrio obscurus</i>	TF, LG, LP, EH	NC_037196	NC_037196	GBMNA9724-19	GBMNA9724-19	Complete COI gene extracted from mitogenome (from base 1,606 to 3,145).
Tenebrionidae	<i>Tribolium castaneum</i>	TF, LG, LP, EH	NC_003081	NC_003081	---	---	Complete COI gene extracted from mitogenome (from base 1,395 to 2,942).
Tenebrionidae	<i>Tribolium confusum</i>	TF	NC_026702	NC_026702	GBMNA9726-19	GBMNA9726-19	Complete COI gene extracted from mitogenome (from base 1,410 to 2,943).
Tenebrionidae	<i>Tribolium destructor</i>	TF, EH	FJ743723	FJ743723	GBCL15733-13	GBCL15733-13	Complete COI gene.
Trogossitidae	<i>Tenebroides mauritanicus</i>	TF, LG	OM161967	OM161967	---	---	Complete COI gene extracted from mitogenome (from base 1,405 to 2,935).

Table S6. Two hundred and forty-three mitogenomes accessed from GenBank, ordered by family. Bold highlighting indicates the taxonomic level for which this mitogenome was chosen for the creation of the backbone tree. ‘---’ indicates unavailability or uncertainty regarding subfamily, tribal or genus-level taxonomic assignment.

Accession number	Family	Subfamily	Tribe	Genus	Species
JX412763	Aderidae	---	---	---	Aderidae sp.
JX412857	Anthicidae	Anthicinae	Formicomini	<i>Formicomus</i>	<i>Formicomus</i> sp.
HQ232825	Anthicidae	Anthicinae	Anthicini	Omonadus	<i>Omonadus floralis</i>
KX087350	Anthicidae	Anthicinae	Anthicini	Stricticollis	<i>Stricticollis tobias</i>
JX412830	Anthribidae	Anthribinae	Ecelonerini	<i>Chirotenon</i>	<i>Chirotenon longimanus</i>
JX412859	Anthribidae	Urodontinae	---	<i>Urodontus</i>	<i>Urodontus glabratus</i>
MH817139	Bostrichidae	Dinoderinae	---	Rhyzopertha	<i>Rhyzopertha dominica</i>
JX412742	Bostrichidae	Bostrichinae	Sinoxylolini	Sinoxylon	<i>Sinoxylon</i> sp.
MK692719	Bothriideridae	Anommatainae	---	Anommatus	<i>Anommatus</i> sp.
JN163970	Brachyceridae	Brachycerinae	Brachycerini	Brachycerus	<i>Brachycerus muricatus</i>
MN459662	Brentidae	Apioninae	Exapiini	Lepidapion	<i>Lepidapion squamigerum</i>
JN163946	Brentidae	Nanophyinae	Nanophyini	<i>Nanophyes</i>	<i>Nanophyes marmoratus</i>
FJ613420	Buprestidae	Polycestinae	Acmaeoderini	Acmaeodera	<i>Acmaeodera</i> sp.
KT363854	Buprestidae	Agrilinae	Agrilini	Agrilus	<i>Agrilus planipennis</i>
JX412831	Buprestidae	Buprestinae	Buprestini	Anthaxia	<i>Anthaxia</i> sp.
MK692708	Cantharidae	Malthininae	Malthinini	Malthinus	<i>Malthinus balteatus</i>
MK692647	Cantharidae	Malthininae	Malthinini	Malthodes	<i>Malthodes</i> sp.
JX412835	Carabidae	Platyninae	Platynini	Agonum	<i>Agonum mueller</i>
MN335930	Carabidae	Pterostichinae	Zabrini	Amara	<i>Amara aulica</i>
KX087242	Carabidae	Trechinae	Bembidiini	Bembidion	<i>Bembidion varium</i>
MF497819	Carabidae	Broscinae	Broscini	Broscus	<i>Broscus cephalotes</i>
MK692626	Carabidae	Platyninae	Sphodrini	Calathus	<i>Calathus granatensis</i>
GU176340	Carabidae	Carabinae	Carabini	Calosoma	<i>Calosoma</i> sp.
MN122870	Carabidae	Carabinae	Carabini	Carabus	<i>Carabus granulatus</i>
MN995217	Carabidae	Licininae	Licinini	<i>Diplocheila</i>	<i>Diplocheila zealandica</i>
JX412824	Carabidae	Cicindelinae	Cicindelini	Habrodera	<i>Habrodera capensis</i>
MN310888	Carabidae	Harpalinae	Harpalini	Harpalus	<i>Harpalus sinicus</i>
MK692552	Carabidae	Lebiinae	Lebiini	Microlestes	<i>Microlestes mauritanicus</i>
KT876906	Carabidae	Nebriinae	Nebriini	Nebria	<i>Nebria brevicollis</i>
MK692555	Carabidae	Pterostichinae	Pterostichini	Orthomus	<i>Orthomus</i> sp.
MW629557	Carabidae	Brachininae	Brachinini	Pheropsophus	<i>Pheropsophus occipitalis</i>
KX087338	Carabidae	Trechinae	Pogonini	Pogonus	<i>Pogonus iridipennis</i>
MF497822	Carabidae	Scaritinae	Scaritini	Scarites	<i>Scarites buparius</i>
MK692681	Carabidae	Lebiinae	Lebiini	Syntomus	<i>Syntomus foveatus</i>
KX035142	Carabidae	Trechinae	Bembidiini	Tachyta	<i>Tachyta nana</i>
MK692574	Carabidae	Trechinae	Trechini	Trechus	<i>Trechus obtusus</i>
KY773692	Cerambycidae	Lamiinae	Agapanthiini	Agapanthia	<i>Agapanthia daurica</i>
MW067122	Cerambycidae	Spondylidinae	Asemini	Arhopalus	<i>Arhopalus unicolor</i>
KY796055	Cerambycidae	Cerambycinae	Clytini	Chlorophorus	<i>Chlorophorus simillimus</i>

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Accession number	Family	Subfamily	Tribe	Genus	Species
KY773691	Cerambycidae	Lamiinae	Monochamini	Monochamus	<i>Monochamus sartor</i>
KY765550	Cerambycidae	Cerambycinae	Callidiini	<i>Semanotus</i>	<i>Semanotus bifasciatus</i>
KY773688	Cerambycidae	Cerambycinae	Hesperophanini	Trichoferus	<i>Trichoferus campestris</i>
HQ232821	Cerylonidae	Ceryloninae	---	<i>Cerylon</i>	<i>Cerylon histeroides</i>
KX825864	Chrysomelidae	Bruchinae	Bruchini	Acanthoscelides	<i>Acanthoscelides obtectus</i>
KX943467	Chrysomelidae	Galerucinae	Alticini	Aphthona	<i>Aphthona albertinae</i>
KX087249	Chrysomelidae	Eumolpinae	Bromiini	<i>Bromius</i>	<i>Bromius obscurus</i>
MN594498	Chrysomelidae	Bruchinae	Bruchini	Bruchidius	<i>Bruchidius uberatus</i>
KY039140	Chrysomelidae	Bruchinae	Bruchini	Bruchus	<i>Bruchus</i> sp.
KY856744	Chrysomelidae	Bruchinae	Bruchini	Callosobruchus	<i>Callosobruchus chinensis</i>
KX943500	Chrysomelidae	Galerucinae	Luperina	Calomicrus	<i>Calomicrus suturalis</i>
KX943468	Chrysomelidae	Cassidinae	Cassidini	Cassida	<i>Cassida viridis</i>
MG021087	Chrysomelidae	Galerucinae	Alticini	Chaetocnema	<i>Chaetocnema pelagica</i>
KX943457	Chrysomelidae	Chrysomelinae	Chrysomelini	Chrysolina	<i>Chrysolina rufoaenea</i>
KX943485	Chrysomelidae	Criocerinae	Crioceris	Crioceris	<i>Crioceris asparagi</i>
KX943434	Chrysomelidae	Cryptocephalinae	Cryptocephalini	Cryptocephalus	<i>Cryptocephalus cynarae</i>
KX087282	Chrysomelidae	Galerucinae	Alticini	Dibolia	<i>Dibolia rugulosa</i>
JX412769	Chrysomelidae	Criocerinae	Lemini	Lema	<i>Lema</i> sp.
KX943357	Chrysomelidae	Galerucinae	Alticini	Longitarsus	<i>Longitarsus aeneus</i>
KX943486	Chrysomelidae	Galerucinae	Alticini	Mantura	<i>Mantura chrysanthemii</i>
KX087328	Chrysomelidae	Criocerinae	Lemini	Oulema	<i>Oulema melanopus</i>
KX943499	Chrysomelidae	Chrysomelinae	Chrysomelini	Phaedon	<i>Phaedon tumidulus</i>
MK256930	Chrysomelidae	Galerucinae	Alticini	Phyllotreta	<i>Phyllotreta striolata</i>
KX943355	Chrysomelidae	Galerucinae	Alticini	Psylliodes	<i>Psylliodes affinis</i>
KX943444	Chrysomelidae	Galerucinae	Alticini	Sphaeroderma	<i>Sphaeroderma testaceum</i>
KX943463	Chrysomelidae	Cryptocephalinae	Stylosomini	Stylosomus	<i>Stylosomus ilicicola</i>
MH473532	Curculionidae	Entiminae	Laparocerini	Laparocerus	<i>Laparocerus freyi</i>
KX087259	Ciidae	Ciinae	Ciini	Cis	<i>Cis micans</i>
KX087326	Ciidae	Ciinae	Ciini	Orthocis	<i>Orthocis pygmaeus</i>
MK422543	Cleridae	Korynetinae	---	Necrobia	<i>Necrobia ruficollis</i>
KT808467	Cleridae	Clerinae	---	<i>Trichodes</i>	<i>Trichodes sinae</i>
MN053054	Coccinellidae	Chilocorinae	Chilocorini	Chilocorus	<i>Chilocorus bipustulatus</i>
MN447521	Coccinellidae	Sticholotidinae	Microweiseini	<i>Coccidophilus</i>	<i>Coccidophilus cariba</i>
JQ321839	Coccinellidae	Coccinellinae	Coccinellini	Coccinella	<i>Coccinella septempunctata</i>
KT878321	Coccinellidae	Scymninae	Scymnini	Cryptolaemus	<i>Cryptolaemus montrouzieri</i>
KR108208	Coccinellidae	Coccinellinae	Coccinellini	Harmonia	<i>Harmonia axyridis</i>
MK334129	Coccinellidae	Coccinellinae	Coccinellini	Hippodamia	<i>Hippodamia variegata</i>
NC050855	Coccinellidae	Scymninae	Scymnini	Nephus	<i>Nephus oblongosignatus</i>
MW530420	Coccinellidae	Coccinellinae	Coccinellini	Oenopia	<i>Oenopia sauzeti</i>
MN053055	Coccinellidae	Coccidulinae	Noviini	Rodolia	<i>Rodolia quadrimaculata</i>
MK692625	Cryptophagidae	Cryptophaginae	Cryptophagini	Cryptophagus	<i>Cryptophagus pilosus</i>
KX087317	Cryptophagidae	Cryptophaginae	Cryptophagini	Micrambe	<i>Micrambe villosus</i>

Accession number	Family	Subfamily	Tribe	Genus	Species
MK614513	Cucujidae	---	---	<i>Pediacus</i>	<i>Pediacus</i> sp.
MK654679	Curculionidae	Curculioninae	Anthonomini	<i>Anthonomus</i>	<i>Anthonomus rubi</i>
MH404106	Curculionidae	Bagoinae	Bagoini	<i>Bagous</i>	<i>Bagous</i> sp.
MH404151	Curculionidae	Entiminae	Brachyderini	<i>Brachyderes</i>	<i>Brachyderes rugatus</i>
JN163960	Curculionidae	Cossoninae	Onycholipini	<i>Brachytemnus</i>	<i>Brachytemnus porcatus</i>
MN180050	Curculionidae	Ceutorhynchinae	Ceutorhynchini	<i>Ceutorhynchus</i>	<i>Ceutorhynchus obstrictus</i>
JN163958	Curculionidae	Cioninae	Cionini	<i>Cionus</i>	<i>Cionus olens</i>
MH404114	Curculionidae	Scolytinae	Crypturgini	<i>Crypturgus</i>	<i>Crypturgus pusillus</i>
MG674390	Curculionidae	Dryophthorinae	Rhynchophorini	<i>Cyrtotrachelus</i>	<i>Cyrtotrachelus buqueti</i>
MH473536	Curculionidae	Cyclominae	Dichotrachelini	<i>Dichotrachelus</i>	<i>Dichotrachelus manueli</i>
KX035216	Curculionidae	Scolytinae	Dryocoetini	<i>Dryocoetes</i>	<i>Dryocoetes villosus</i>
MK692645	Curculionidae	Cryptorhynchinae	Cryptorhynchini	<i>Echinodera</i>	<i>Echinodera andalusiensis</i>
KX035212	Curculionidae	Scolytinae	Hylastini	<i>Hylastes</i>	<i>Hylastes attenuatus</i>
MH404130	Curculionidae	Scolytinae	Hypoborini	<i>Hypoborus</i>	<i>Hypoborus ficus</i>
KX035163	Curculionidae	Scolytinae	Cryphalini	<i>Hypothenemus</i>	<i>Hypothenemus</i> sp.
JN163952	Curculionidae	Cleoninae	Lixini	<i>Larinus</i>	<i>Larinus turbinatus</i>
KX087312	Curculionidae	Curculioninae	Mecinini	<i>Mecinus</i>	<i>Mecinus janthinus</i>
JN163955	Curculionidae	Baridinae	Baridini	<i>Melanobaris</i>	<i>Melanobaris laticollis</i>
GU176345	Curculionidae	Entiminae	Naupactini	<i>Naupactus</i>	<i>Naupactus xanthographus</i>
KX035213	Curculionidae	Scolytinae	Ipini	<i>Orthotomicus</i>	<i>Orthotomicus laricis</i>
MH404148	Curculionidae	Entiminae	Otiiorhynchini	<i>Otiiorhynchus</i>	<i>Otiiorhynchus globulus</i>
MW447510	Curculionidae	Scolytinae	Phloeosinini	<i>Phloeosinus</i>	<i>Phloeosinus perlatus</i>
MH404115	Curculionidae	Scolytinae	Phloeotribini	<i>Phloeotribus</i>	<i>Phloeotribus spinulosus</i>
MH404102	Curculionidae	Molytinae	Pissodini	<i>Pissodes</i>	<i>Pissodes</i> sp.
MH431908	Curculionidae	Scolytinae	Xyleborini	<i>Premnobius</i>	<i>Premnobius cavipennis</i>
KX087356	Curculionidae	Entiminae	Trachyphloeini	<i>Romualdius</i>	<i>Romualdius bifoveolatus</i>
MK636870	Curculionidae	Scolytinae	Scolytini	<i>Scolytus</i>	<i>Scolytus schevyrewi</i>
MH404129	Curculionidae	Curculioninae	Tychiini	<i>Sibinia</i>	<i>Sibinia fulva</i>
MH814932	Curculionidae	Entiminae	Sitonini	<i>Sitona</i>	<i>Sitona obsoletus</i>
MF383367	Curculionidae	Entiminae	Tanymecini	<i>Sympiezomias</i>	<i>Sympiezomias velatus</i>
MK692554	Curculionidae	Cryptorhynchinae	Torneumatini	<i>Torneuma</i>	<i>Torneuma</i> sp.
MK692568	Curculionidae	Curculioninae	Tychiini	<i>Tychius</i>	<i>Tychius pusillus</i>
KX035203	Curculionidae	Scolytinae	Xyleborini	<i>Xyleborinus</i>	<i>Xyleborinus saxesenii</i>
KX035179	Curculionidae	Scolytinae	Xyleborini	<i>Xyleborus</i>	<i>Xyleborus</i> sp.
KX035196	Curculionidae	Scolytinae	Xyleborini	<i>Xylosandrus</i>	<i>Xylosandrus crassiusculus</i>
MT560591	Curculionidae	Curculioninae	Derelomini	<i>Elaeidobius</i>	<i>Elaeidobius kamerunicus</i>
KX087239	Dermestidae	Megatominae	Anthrenini	<i>Anthrenus</i>	<i>Anthrenus verbasci</i>
JX412837	Dermestidae	Megatominae	Anthrenini	<i>Attagenus</i>	<i>Attagenus hottentotus</i>
MH678621	Dermestidae	Dermestinae	Dermestini	<i>Dermestes</i>	<i>Dermestes frischii</i>
MK692678	Dermestidae	Thorictinae	Thorictini	<i>Thorictus</i>	<i>Thorictus</i> sp.
MT113335	Dermestidae	Megatominae	Megatomini	<i>Trogoderma</i>	<i>Trogoderma granarium</i>
MH281567	Dryophthoridae	Rhynchophorinae	Sphenophorini	<i>Cosmopolites</i>	<i>Cosmopolites sordidus</i>

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Accession number	Family	Subfamily	Tribe	Genus	Species
KT428893	Dryophthoridae	Rhynchophorinae	Rhynchophorini	<i>Rhynchophorus</i>	<i>Rhynchophorus ferrugineus</i>
KX373615	Dryophthoridae	Rhynchophorinae	Litosomini	<i>Sitophilus</i>	<i>Sitophilus oryzae</i>
GU176342	Dryophthoridae	Rhynchophorinae	Sphenophorini	<i>Sphenophorus</i>	<i>Sphenophorus</i> sp.
KT876888	Dryopidae	---	---	<i>Dryops</i>	<i>Dryops luridus</i>
KX087233	Dytiscidae	Colymbetinae	Agabini	<i>Agabus</i>	<i>Agabus uliginosus</i>
KT876885	Dytiscidae	Colymbetinae	Colymbetini	<i>Colymbetes</i>	<i>Colymbetes fuscus</i>
KX087277	Dytiscidae	Dytiscinae	Cybistrini	<i>Cybister</i>	<i>Cybister lateralimarginalis</i>
MN781132	Dytiscidae	Dytiscinae	Eretini	<i>Eretes</i>	<i>Eretes sticticus</i>
MW465241	Dytiscidae	Hydroporinae	Hydroporini	<i>Graptodytes</i>	<i>Graptodytes eremitus</i>
KT876897	Dytiscidae	Hydroporinae	Hydroporini	<i>Hydroporus</i>	<i>Hydroporus erythrocephalus</i>
KT876901	Dytiscidae	Hydroporinae	Hygrotini	<i>Hygrotus</i>	<i>Hygrotus confluens</i>
MG912994	Dytiscidae	Hydroporinae	Bidessini	<i>Limbodessus</i>	<i>Limbodessus palmulaoides</i>
MW465256	Dytiscidae	Hydroporinae	Hydroporini	<i>Nebrioporus</i>	<i>Nebrioporus canaliculatus</i>
MW465301	Dytiscidae	Hydroporinae	Hydroporini	<i>Stictionectes</i>	<i>Stictionectes escheri</i>
KT876879	Elateridae	Elaterinae	Agriotini	<i>Agriotes</i>	<i>Agriotes obscurus</i>
MN370897	Elateridae	Agrypninae	Agrypnini	<i>Agrypnus</i>	<i>Agrypnus</i> sp.
MK692585	Elateridae	Cardiophorinae	Cardiophorini	<i>Cardiophorus</i>	<i>Cardiophorus signatus</i>
HQ232815	Elateridae	Agrypninae	Drilini	<i>Drilus</i>	<i>Drilus flavescens</i>
KT876904	Elateridae	Melanotinae	Melanotus	<i>Melanotus</i>	<i>Melanotus villosus</i>
EF398270	Elateridae	Agrypninae	Pyrophorini	<i>Pyrophorus</i>	<i>Pyrophorus divergens</i>
MK692652	Endomychidae	Merophysiinae	---	---	Merophysiinae sp.
KX087294	Gyrinidae	Gyrininae	Gyrinini	<i>Gyrinus</i>	<i>Gyrinus substriatus</i>
KT876890	Haliplidae	---	---	<i>Haliplus</i>	<i>Haliplus lineatocollis</i>
KX035139	Helophoridae	---	---	<i>Helophorus</i>	<i>Helophorus</i> sp.
GU176344	Histeridae	Saprininae	---	<i>Euspilotus</i>	<i>Euspilotus scissus</i>
MK692590	Histeridae	Dendrophilinae	Dendrophilini	<i>Kissister</i>	<i>Kissister minimus</i>
KT780657	Histeridae	Histerinae	Histerini	<i>Margarinotus</i>	<i>Margarinotus merdarius</i>
JX412766	Histeridae	Dendrophilinae	Paromalini	<i>Paromalus</i>	<i>Paromalus flavicornis</i>
MT628557	Hydraenidae	Hydraeninae	Hydraenini	<i>Hydraena</i>	<i>Hydraena gracilis</i>
MT822981	Hydraenidae	Ochthebiinae	Ochthebiini	<i>Ochthebius</i>	<i>Ochthebius atriceps</i>
KT876892	Hydrochidae	Hydrochinae	---	<i>Hydrochus</i>	<i>Hydrochus</i> sp.
KT876883	Hydrophilidae	Hydrophilinae	Berosini	<i>Berosus</i>	<i>Berosus affinis</i>
KX087255	Hydrophilidae	Sphaeridiinae	Megasternini	<i>Cercyon</i>	<i>Cercyon borealis</i>
KT876891	Hydrophilidae	Hydrophilinae	Hydrophilini	<i>Helochares</i>	<i>Helochares</i> sp.
KT780677	Hydrophilidae	Sphaeridiinae	Sphaeridiini	<i>Sphaeridium</i>	<i>Sphaeridium bipustulatum</i>
KT070713	Laemophloeidae	---	---	<i>Cryptolestes</i>	<i>Cryptolestes pusillus</i>
MK692677	Latridiidae	Corticariinae	---	<i>Corticaria</i>	<i>Corticaria</i> sp.
JX313681	Latridiidae	Latridiinae	---	<i>Enicmus</i>	<i>Enicmus brevicornis</i>
KX087234	Leiodidae	Leiodinae	Agathidiini	<i>Agathidium</i>	<i>Agathidium nigripenne</i>
KX087305	Leiodidae	Leiodinae	Leiodini	<i>Leiodes</i>	<i>Leiodes picea</i>

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KT780661	Leiodidae	Cholevinae	Cholevini	<i>Nargus</i>	<i>Nargus velox</i>
JX412833	Melyridae	Malachiinae	Malachiini	<i>Clanoptilus</i>	<i>Clanoptilus assimilis</i>
JX412801	Melyridae	Dasytinae	Dasytini	<i>Psilothrix</i>	<i>Psilothrix</i> sp.
KX035132	Monotomidae	Monotominae	Monotomini	<i>Monotoma</i>	<i>Monotoma quadricollis</i>
KX087340	Monotomidae	Rhizophaginae	---	<i>Rhizophagus</i>	<i>Rhizophagus aeneus</i>
FJ859904	Mordellidae	Mordellinae	Mordellini	<i>Mordella</i>	<i>Mordella atrata</i>
MN604384	Nitidulidae	Carpophilinae	---	<i>Carpophilus</i>	<i>Carpophilus dimidiatus</i>
KX087289	Nitidulidae	Carpophilinae	Eupuraeini	<i>Epuraea</i>	<i>Epuraea guttata</i>
NC050852	Nitidulidae	Nitidulinae	Nitidulini	<i>Omosita</i>	<i>Omosita colon</i>
JX412790	Oedemeridae	Oedemerinae	Asclerini	<i>Ischnomera</i>	<i>Ischnomera caerulea</i>
KX087319	Oedemeridae	Nacerdinae	Nacerdini	<i>Nacerdes</i>	<i>Nacerdes carniolica</i>
HQ232826	Oedemeridae	Oedemerinae	Oedemerini	<i>Oedemera</i>	<i>Oedemera virescens</i>
JX313671	Ptinidae	Anobiinae	Xyletinini	<i>Xyletinus</i>	<i>Xyletinus</i> sp.
KT696259	Ptiliidae	---	---	Ptiliidae	Ptiliidae sp.
KU302777	Ptiliidae	Ptiliinae	Nanosellini	<i>Scydosella</i>	<i>Scydosella musawasensis</i>
KX087290	Ptinidae	Ernobiinae	---	<i>Ernobius</i>	<i>Ernobius pini</i>
KX087292	Ptinidae	Anobiinae	---	<i>Gastrallus</i>	<i>Gastrallus laevigatus</i>
MF417629	Ptinidae	Xyletininae	Lasiodermini	<i>Lasioderma</i>	<i>Lasioderma serricorne</i>
HQ232819	Ptinidae	Ptininae	Ptinini	<i>Ptinus</i>	<i>Ptinus rufipes</i>
MK947052	Ptinidae	Anobiinae	---	<i>Stegobium</i>	<i>Stegobium paniceum</i>
KX087240	Scarabaeidae	Aphodiinae	Aphodiini	<i>Aphodius</i>	<i>Aphodius foetens</i>
MW632131	Scarabaeidae	Dynastinae	Oryctini	<i>Oryctes</i>	<i>Oryctes rhinoceros</i>
MK692607	Scarabaeidae	Aphodiinae	Psammodiini	<i>Pleurophorus</i>	<i>Pleurophorus caesus</i>
KC775706	Scarabaeidae	Cetoniinae	Cetoniini	<i>Protaetia</i>	<i>Protaetia brevitarsis</i>
FJ859903	Scarabaeidae	Melolonthinae	Melolonthini	<i>Rhopaea</i>	<i>Rhopaea magnicornis</i>
EU877949	Scirtidae	Scirtinae	---	<i>Contacyphon</i>	<i>Contacyphon</i> sp.
JX412856	Scraptiidae	Anaspidinae	Anaspidini	<i>Anaspis</i>	<i>Anaspis</i> sp.
KX087347	Silphidae	Silphinae	---	<i>Silpha</i>	<i>Silpha tyrolensis</i>
MK692621	Silvanidae	Silvaninae	---	<i>Airaphilus</i>	<i>Airaphilus</i> sp.
KX641891	Silvanidae	Silvaninae	---	<i>Oryzaeophilus</i>	<i>Oryzaeophilus surinamensis</i>
KX035149	Silvanidae	Brontinae	Brontini	<i>Uleiota</i>	<i>Uleiota</i> sp.
JX412803	Sphindidae	Sphindinae	---	<i>Sphindus</i>	<i>Sphindus dubius</i>
MK692556	Staphylinidae	Paederinae	Paederini	<i>Achenium</i>	<i>Achenium seditiosum</i>
KT780620	Staphylinidae	Aleocharinae	Athetini	<i>Acrotona</i>	<i>Acrotona obfuscata</i>
KT780622	Staphylinidae	Aleocharinae	Aleocharini	<i>Aleochara</i>	<i>Aleochara</i> sp.
KT780624	Staphylinidae	Aleocharinae	Geostibini	<i>Aloconota</i>	<i>Aloconota currax</i>
MK692661	Staphylinidae	Oxytelinae	Oxytelini	<i>Anotylus</i>	<i>Anotylus inustus</i>
KT780626	Staphylinidae	Paederinae	Paederini	<i>Astenus</i>	<i>Astenus lyonessius</i>
KT780629	Staphylinidae	Aleocharinae	Athetini	<i>Atheta</i>	<i>Atheta gagatina</i>
KT780632	Staphylinidae	Staphylininae	Staphylinini	<i>Bisnius</i>	<i>Bisnius sordidus</i>
KX087254	Staphylinidae	Oxytelinae	Oxytelini	<i>Carpelimus</i>	<i>Carpelimus fuliginosus</i>
KM586245	Staphylinidae	Pselaphinae	Euplectini	<i>Euplectus</i>	<i>Euplectus karstenii</i>
KT780647	Staphylinidae	Aleocharinae	Homalotini	<i>Euryusa</i>	<i>Euryusa optabilis</i>

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Accession number	Family	Subfamily	Tribe	Genus	Species
KT780649	Staphylinidae	Staphylininae	Staphylinini	Gabronthus	<i>Gabronthus thermanum</i>
MK692616	Staphylinidae	Aleocharinae	Geostibini	Geostiba	<i>Geostiba</i> sp.
KT780650	Staphylinidae	Staphylininae	Xantholinini	Gyrophypnus	<i>Gyrophypnus fracticornis</i>
KT780653	Staphylinidae	Tachyporinae	Mycetoporini	Ischnosoma	<i>Ischnosoma splendidum</i>
KT780654	Staphylinidae	Paederinae	Paederini	Lathrobium	<i>Lathrobium brunripes</i>
KX087309	Staphylinidae	Tachyporinae	Mycetoporini	Lordithon	<i>Lordithon exoletus</i>
KT780658	Staphylinidae	Paederinae	Paederini	Medon	<i>Medon apicalis</i>
MW256421	Staphylinidae	Staphylininae	Xantholinini	Megalinus	<i>Megalinus hunanensis</i>
KT780659	Staphylinidae	Proteininae	Proteinini	Metopsia	<i>Metopsia clypeata</i>
KT780660	Staphylinidae	Aleocharinae	Falagriini	Myrmecocephalus	<i>Myrmecocephalus concinnus</i>
KT780662	Staphylinidae	Staphylininae	Staphylinini	Neobisnius	<i>Neobisnius villosulus</i>
KT780664	Staphylinidae	Staphylininae	Staphylinini	Nudobius	<i>Nudobius lentus</i>
KT876908	Staphylinidae	Staphylininae	Staphylinini	Ocypus	<i>Ocypus olens</i>
JX412759	Staphylinidae	Omaliinae	Omaliini	Omalius	<i>Omalius rivulare</i>
MK692560	Staphylinidae	Staphylininae	Othiini	Othius	<i>Othius subuliformis</i>
KT780667	Staphylinidae	Aleocharinae	Oxypodini	Oxypoda	<i>Oxypoda acuminata</i>
JX412796	Staphylinidae	Oxytelinae	Oxytelini	Oxytelus	<i>Oxytelus</i> sp.
KT780669	Staphylinidae	Staphylininae	Staphylinini	Philonthus	<i>Philonthus fimetarius</i>
KT780670	Staphylinidae	Aleocharinae	Oxypodini	Phloeopora	<i>Phloeopora testacea</i>
KT780671	Staphylinidae	Paederinae	Paederini	Rugilus	<i>Rugilus geniculatus</i>
KT780676	Staphylinidae	Tachyporinae	Tachyporini	Sepedophilus	<i>Sepedophilus bipunctatus</i>
KT876913	Staphylinidae	Steninae	---	Stenus	<i>Stenus boops</i>
KT780696	Staphylinidae	Paederinae	Paederini	Sunius	<i>Sunius melanocephalus</i>
KX087351	Staphylinidae	Tachyporinae	Tachyporini	Tachinus	<i>Tachinus subterraneus</i>
MK692579	Staphylinidae	Tachyporinae	Tachyporini	Tachyporus	<i>Tachyporus nitidulus</i>
KT780697	Staphylinidae	Staphylininae	Staphylinini	Tasgius	<i>Tasgius compressus</i>
MT610905	Tenebrionidae	Tenebrioninae	Alphitobiini	Alphitobius	<i>Alphitobius diaperinus</i>
MN267802	Tenebrionidae	Tenebrioninae	Blaptini	Blaps	<i>Blaps rhynchoptera</i>
MK692707	Tenebrionidae	Lagriinae	Belopini	Centorus	<i>Centorus elongatus</i>
MK692606	Tenebrionidae	Pimeliinae	Cnemeplatiini	Cnemeplatia	<i>Cnemeplatia atropos</i>
KU236386	Tenebrionidae	Tenebrioninae	Opatrini	Gonocephalum	<i>Gonocephalum</i> sp
MK692593	Tenebrionidae	Tenebrioninae	Scaurini	Scaurus	<i>Scaurus uncinus</i>
KF418153	Tenebrionidae	Tenebrioninae	Tenebrionini	Tenebrio	<i>Tenebrio molitor</i>
KM244661	Tenebrionidae	Tenebrioninae	Triboliini	Tribolium	<i>Tribolium castaneum</i>
MK937809	Trogidae	Omorginae	---	Omorgus	<i>Omorgus chinensis</i>
JX412734	Trogidae	Troginae	---	Trox	<i>Trox</i> sp.
JX412752	Trogossitidae	Trogossitinae	Trogossitini	Temnoscheila	<i>Temnoscheila virescens</i>

Table S7. Details for the 98 *de novo* generated mitogenomes, ordered by family. See Table S2 for detailed information regarding pools. PCG = number of protein coding genes. ‘---’ indicates unavailability or uncertainty regarding subfamily, tribal or genus-level taxonomic assignment.

Accession number	Family	Subfamily	Tribe	Genus	Species	PCG	Length (bp)	Pool
OQ716363	Anthicidae	Anthicinae	Microhoriini	---	<i>Microhoriini</i> sp.	13	15,582	1
OQ716315	Anthicidae	Anthicinae	Microhoriini	<i>Aulacoderus</i>	<i>Aulacoderus canariensis</i>	13	15,497	3
OQ716316	Attelabidae	Rhynchitinae	Auletini	<i>Auletobius</i>	<i>Auletobius</i> sp.	13	17,224	5
OQ716322	Biphyllidae	---	---	<i>Biphyllus</i>	<i>Biphyllus lunatus</i>	13	16,650	6
OQ716313	Brentidae	Apioninae	Aspidapiini	<i>Aspidapion</i>	<i>Aspidapion radiolus</i>	13	18,756	5
OQ716346	Brentidae	Apioninae	Oxystomatini	<i>Holotrichapion</i>	<i>Holotrichapion rotundipenne</i>	13	19,027	6
OQ716348	Brentidae	Apioninae	Kalcapiini	<i>Kalcapion</i>	<i>Kalcapion semivittatum</i>	13	19,096	4
OQ716390	Brentidae	Apioninae	Kalcapiini	<i>Taeniapion</i>	<i>Taeniapion delicatulum</i>	13	18,012	3
OQ716332	Byrrhidae	Syncalyptinae	---	<i>Curimopsis</i>	<i>Curimopsis</i> sp.	13	15,046	3
OQ716336	Carabidae	Dryptinae	Zuphiini	<i>Dicrodontus</i>	<i>Dicrodontus aptinoides</i>	13	15,837	8
OQ716321	Carabidae	Harpalinae	Harpalini	<i>Bradycellus</i>	<i>Bradycellus ventricosus</i>	13	16,791	2
OQ716334	Carabidae	Lebiinae	Lebiini	<i>Cymindis</i>	<i>Cymindis zargoides</i>	5	4,006	1
OQ716337	Carabidae	Lebiinae	Lebiini	<i>Dromius</i>	<i>Dromius angustus</i>	13	17,432	7
OQ716374	Carabidae	Lebiinae	Lebiini	<i>Paradromius</i>	<i>Paradromius</i> sp.	13	16,770	6
OQ716376	Carabidae	Lebiinae	Lebiini	<i>Philorhizus</i>	<i>Philorhizus</i> sp.	13	16,522	4
OQ716355	Carabidae	Nebriinae	Nebriini	<i>Leistus</i>	<i>Leistus nubivagus</i>	13	15,123	7
OQ716310	Carabidae	Platyninae	Sphodrini	<i>Amaroschema</i>	<i>Amaroschema gaudini</i>	13	13,380	7
OQ716324	Carabidae	Platyninae	Sphodrini	<i>Calathidius</i>	<i>Calathidius</i> sp.	13	17,786	4
OQ716325	Carabidae	Platyninae	Sphodrini	<i>Calathus</i>	<i>Calathus gomerensis</i>	13	16,764	8
OQ716349	Carabidae	Platyninae	Sphodrini	<i>Laemostenus</i>	<i>Laemostenus complanatus</i>	13	16,997	8
OQ716368	Carabidae	Platyninae	Platynini	<i>Olisthopus</i>	<i>Olisthopus</i> sp.	13	16,775	7
OQ716375	Carabidae	Platyninae	Sphodrini	<i>Paraeutrichopus</i>	<i>Paraeutrichopus</i> sp.	13	15,733	2
OQ716340	Carabidae	Pterostichinae	Pterostichini	<i>Eutrichopus</i>	<i>Eutrichopus gonzalezi</i>	13	16,368	8
OQ716306	Carabidae	Trechinae	Trechini	<i>Aepus</i>	<i>Aepus gracilicornis</i>	13	16,685	2
OQ716397	Carabidae	Trechinae	Bembidiini	<i>Typhlocharis</i>	<i>Typhlocharis</i> sp.	13	14,925	2
OQ716319	Cerambycidae	Cerambycinae	Saphanini	<i>Blabinotus</i>	<i>Blabinotus spinicollis</i>	13	15,610	8
OQ716389	Cerambycidae	Lepturinae	Lepturini	<i>Stictoleptura</i>	<i>Stictoleptura palmi</i>	13	16,870	5
OQ716314	Ciidae	Ciinae	Orophiini	<i>Atlantocis</i>	<i>Atlantocis canariensis</i>	13	15,297	3
OQ716366	Ciidae	Ciinae	Orophiini	<i>Octotemnus</i>	<i>Octotemnus opacus</i>	13	15,724	3
OQ716370	Ciidae	Ciinae	Ciini	<i>Orthocis</i>	<i>Orthocis sagittiferus</i>	13	16,381	4
OQ716329	Clambidae	Clambinae	---	<i>Clambus</i>	<i>Clambus complicans</i>	13	16,356	3
OQ716382	Coccinellidae	Scymninae	Scymnini	<i>Scymnus</i>	<i>Scymnus canariensis</i>	13	17,646	3
OQ716383	Corylophidae	Corylophinae	Sericoderini	<i>Sericoderus</i>	<i>Sericoderus</i> sp.	13	15,127	3
OQ716331	Cryptophagidae	Cryptophaginae	Cryptophagini	<i>Cryptophagus</i>	<i>Cryptophagus affinis</i>	13	15,790	1
OQ716362	Curculionidae	Ceutorhynchinae	Ceutorhynchini	<i>Micrelus</i>	<i>Micrelus ferrugatus</i>	13	19,286	3
OQ716385	Curculionidae	Ceutorhynchinae	Ceutorhynchini	<i>Sirocalodes</i>	<i>Sirocalodes nigroterminatus</i>	13	15,270	5
OQ716311	Curculionidae	Cossoninae	Dryotribini	<i>Amaurorhinus</i>	<i>Amaurorhinus</i> sp.	13	15,205	2

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Accession number	Family	Subfamily	Tribe	Genus	Species	PCG	Length (bp)	Pool
OQ716304	Curculionidae	Cryptorhynchinae	Cryptorhynchini	<i>Acalles</i>	<i>Acalles globulipennis</i>	13	16,843	4
OQ716323	Curculionidae	Cryptorhynchinae	Cryptorhynchini	<i>Calacalles</i>	<i>Calacalles pumilio</i>	13	17,029	3
OQ716335	Curculionidae	Cryptorhynchinae	Cryptorhynchini	<i>Dendroacalles</i>	<i>Dendroacalles sp.</i>	13	14,631	5
OQ716373	Curculionidae	Cryptorhynchinae	Cryptorhynchini	<i>Onyxacalles</i>	<i>Onyxacalles verrucosus</i>	13	16,233	7
OQ716380	Curculionidae	Cryptorhynchinae	Cryptorhynchini	<i>Pseudodichromacalles</i>	<i>Pseudodichromacalles xerampelinus</i>	13	15,294	6
OQ716384	Curculionidae	Cryptorhynchinae	Cryptorhynchini	<i>Silvacalles</i>	<i>Silvacalles cedroensis</i>	13	15,211	7
OQ716394	Curculionidae	Cryptorhynchinae	Torneumatini	<i>Torneuma</i>	<i>Torneuma sp. 1</i>	13	15,630	1
OQ716395	Curculionidae	Cryptorhynchinae	Torneumatini	<i>Torneuma</i>	<i>Torneuma sp. 2</i>	13	14,970	2
OQ716393	Curculionidae	Cryptorhynchinae	Torneumatini	<i>Torneuma</i>	<i>Torneuma aphroditae</i>	13	15,489	4
OQ716343	Curculionidae	Curculioninae	Gonipterini	<i>Gonipterus</i>	<i>Gonipterus platensis</i>	13	14,856	8
OQ716386	Curculionidae	Curculioninae	Smicronychini	<i>Smicronyx</i>	<i>Smicronyx albosquamosus</i>	13	15,211	4
OQ716396	Curculionidae	Curculioninae	Tychiini	<i>Tychius</i>	<i>Tychius colonnellii</i>	13	17,299	3
OQ716350	Curculionidae	Entiminae	Laparocerini	<i>Laparocerus</i>	<i>Laparocerus sp.</i>	13	14,884	1
OQ716318	Curculionidae	Molytinae	Molytini	<i>Baezia</i>	<i>Baezia litoralis</i>	13	15,675	1
OQ716353	Curculionidae	Molytinae	Molytini	<i>Leiosoma</i>	<i>Leiosoma apionides</i>	13	14,813	6
OQ716356	Curculionidae	Scolytinae	Hypoborini	<i>Liparthrum</i>	<i>Liparthrum bituberculatum</i>	13	16,235	3
OQ716347	Curculionidae	Hyperinae	Hyperini	<i>Hypera</i>	<i>Hypera postica</i>	13	15,441	8
OQ716358	Endomychidae	Lycoperdininae	---	<i>Lycoperdina</i>	<i>Lycoperdina humeralis</i>	13	16,414	8
OQ716401	Erotylidae	Erotylinae	Dacnini	<i>Xestus</i>	<i>Xestus sp.</i>	13	17,141	7
OQ716400	Erotylidae	Xenoscelinae	---	<i>Xenoscelis</i>	<i>Xenoscelis lauricola</i>	13	15,883	5
OQ716365	Eucinetidae	---	---	<i>Nycteus</i>	<i>Nycteus wollastoni</i>	13	15,582	7
OQ716305	Histeridae	Abraeinae	Acritini	<i>Aeletes</i>	<i>Aeletes sp.</i>	13	14,697	1
OQ716392	Histeridae	Abraeinae	Teretriini	<i>Teretrius</i>	<i>Teretrius cylindricus</i>	13	16,352	3
OQ716320	Kateridae	---	---	<i>Brachypterus</i>	<i>Brachypterus aeneomicans</i>	13	18,392	4
OQ716379	Laemophloeidae	---	---	<i>Placonotus</i>	<i>Placonotus granulatus</i>	13	15,123	3
OQ716327	Latridiidae	Latridiinae	---	<i>Cartodere</i>	<i>Cartodere nodifer</i>	13	15,679	4
OQ716361	Latridiidae	Latridiinae	---	<i>Metopthalmus</i>	<i>Metopthalmus sp.</i>	13	15,467	1
OQ716328	Leiodidae	Cholevinae	Cholevini	<i>Catops</i>	<i>Catops antoniomachadoi</i>	13	14,931	3
OQ716308	Leiodidae	Leiodinae	Agathidiini	<i>Agathidium</i>	<i>Agathidium sp.</i>	13	19,016	6
OQ716352	Leiodidae	Leiodinae	Leiodini	<i>Leiodes</i>	<i>Leiodes sp.</i>	13	17,144	4
OQ716360	Meloidae	Meloinae	Meloini	<i>Meloe</i>	<i>Meloe sp.</i>	13	15,638	6
OQ716357	Mycetophagidae	Mycetophaginae	Mycetophagini	<i>Litargus</i>	<i>Litargus balteatus</i>	13	16,603	4
OQ716333	Nitidulidae	Cybocephalinae	---	<i>Cybocephalus</i>	<i>Cybocephalus sp.</i>	13	16,866	3
OQ716359	Nitidulidae	Meligethinae	---	---	Meligethinae sp.	13	16,479	6
OQ716398	Nitidulidae	Nitidulinae	Cychramini	<i>Xenostrogylus</i>	<i>Xenostrogylus canariensis</i>	13	17,960	3
OQ716399	Nitidulidae	Nitidulinae	Cychramini	<i>Xenostrogylus</i>	<i>Xenostrogylus titanus</i>	13	15,634	7
OQ716367	Phalacridae	Phalacrinae	---	<i>Olibrus</i>	<i>Olibrus sp.</i>	13	16,009	5
OQ716381	Ptiliidae	---	---	---	Ptiliidae sp.	13	16,553	3
OQ716351	Ptinidae	Xyletininae	Lasiodermini	<i>Lasioderma</i>	<i>Lasioderma sp.</i>	13	15,344	5

Accession number	Family	Subfamily	Tribe	Genus	Species	PCG	Length (bp)	Pool
OQ716387	Salpingidae	Salpinginae	---	<i>Sphaeriestes</i>	<i>Sphaeriestes impressus</i>	13	15,589	3
OQ716309	Staphylinidae	Aleocharinae	Geostibini	<i>Aloconota</i>	<i>Aloconota</i> sp.	13	17,435	7
OQ716345	Staphylinidae	Aleocharinae	Hypocyphitini	<i>Holobus</i>	<i>Holobus chrysopygus</i>	13	15,987	3
OQ716338	Staphylinidae	Leptotyphlinae	Entomoculiini	<i>Entomoculia</i>	<i>Entomoculia lauricola</i>	13	17,414	2
OQ716369	Staphylinidae	Omaliinae	Omaliini	<i>Omalius</i>	<i>Omalius</i> sp.	13	17,691	3
OQ716377	Staphylinidae	Omaliinae	Anthophagini	<i>Philorinum</i>	<i>Philorinum floricola</i>	4	8,899	2
OQ716341	Staphylinidae	Osoriinae	Thoracophorini	<i>Geomitopsis</i>	<i>Geomitopsis franzi</i> complex 1	13	17,000	1
OQ716342	Staphylinidae	Osoriinae	Thoracophorini	<i>Geomitopsis</i>	<i>Geomitopsis franzi</i> complex 2	13	16,985	2
OQ716312	Staphylinidae	Oxytelinae	Oxytelini	<i>Anotylus</i>	<i>Anotylus</i> sp.	13	16,228	3
OQ716307	Staphylinidae	Pselaphinae	Pselaphini	<i>Afropselaphus</i>	<i>Afropselaphus fernandezi</i>	13	19,454	2
OQ716339	Staphylinidae	Pselaphinae	Euplectini	<i>Euplectus</i>	<i>Euplectus wollastoni</i>	13	15,686	3
OQ716388	Staphylinidae	Scydmaeninae	Cyrtoscydmini	<i>Stenichnus</i>	<i>Stenichnus</i> sp.	13	17,211	2
OQ716344	Staphylinidae	Staphylininae	Staphylinini	<i>Heterothops</i>	<i>Heterothops canariensis</i>	13	17,458	5
OQ716371	Staphylinidae	Staphylininae	Othiini	<i>Othius</i>	<i>Othius</i> sp. 1	13	15,710	4
OQ716372	Staphylinidae	Staphylininae	Othiini	<i>Othius</i>	<i>Othius</i> sp. 2	13	19,400	5
OQ716326	Staphylinidae	Tachyporinae	Mycetoporini	<i>Canariobolitobius</i>	<i>Canariobolitobius filicornis</i>	13	18,535	3
OQ716330	Tenebrionidae	Diaperinae	Crypticini	<i>Crypticus</i>	<i>Crypticus</i> sp.	13	16,195	7
OQ716378	Tenebrionidae	Pimeliinae	Pimeliini	<i>Pimelia</i>	<i>Pimelia laevigata</i>	13	15,545	6
OQ716364	Tenebrionidae	Tenebrioninae	Helopini	<i>Nesotes</i>	<i>Nesotes</i> sp.	13	15,790	6
OQ716317	Throscidae	---	---	<i>Aulonothroscus</i>	<i>Aulonothroscus</i> sp.	13	17,249	5
OQ716354	Trogossitidae	Trogossitinae	Trogossitini	<i>Leipaspis</i>	<i>Leipaspis lauricola</i>	13	15,650	7
OQ716391	Zopheridae	Colydiinae	Synchitini	<i>Tarphius</i>	<i>Tarphius congestus</i>	13	16,358	1

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Table S8. Mntd analysis results comparing introduced species sampled in the laurel forest against native not endemic and endemic species. Significance is indicated in bold, with marginal significance indicated in bold with an asterisk.

Analysis focus	N	Mntd obs.	Mntd rand. mean	Mntd rand. sd	Mntd obs. rank	Mntd obs. z value	p-value	Meaning
All islands	47	0.4920	0.5605	0.0449	60	-1.5277	0.06*	Marginally significant phylogenetic clustering
Only TF	41	0.5166	0.6201	0.0453	13	-2.2860	0.013	Significant phylogenetic clustering
Only LG	30	0.5867	0.6698	0.0470	41	-1.7408	0.041	Significant phylogenetic clustering
Only LP	35	0.5268	0.6430	0.0487	11	-2.3849	0.011	Significant phylogenetic clustering
Only EH	23	0.5643	0.6878	0.0641	28	-1.9269	0.028	Significant phylogenetic clustering

Table S9. Mntd analysis results comparing introduced species not sampled in the laurel forest against native not endemic and endemic species. Significance is indicated in bold.

Analysis focus	N	Mntd obs.	Mntd rand. mean	Mntd rand. sd	Mntd obs. rank	Mntd obs. z value	p-value	Meaning
All islands	145	0.5494	0.4879	0.0223	997	2.7626	0.997	Significant phylogenetic overdispersion
Only TF	125	0.5671	0.5578	0.0215	653	0.4342	0.653	Non-significant, phylogenetically unstructured
Only LG	55	0.6500	0.6512	0.0356	484	-0.0325	0.484	Non-significant, phylogenetically unstructured
Only LP	85	0.5631	0.5923	0.0272	139	-1.0727	0.139	Non-significant, phylogenetically unstructured
Only EH	45	0.6221	0.6549	0.0407	222	-0.8055	0.222	Non-significant, phylogenetically unstructured

Table S10. Mntd analysis results comparing native not endemic species against endemic species (without any restrictions in the native not endemic or endemic species used for the analysis). Significance is indicated in bold, with marginal significance indicated in bold with an asterisk.

Analysis focus	N	Mntd obs.	Mntd rand. mean	Mntd rand. sd	Mntd obs. rank	Mntd obs. z value	p-value	Meaning
All islands	39	0.6370	0.5573	0.0513	939	1.5641	0.939*	Marginally significant phylogenetic overdispersion
Only TF	35	0.6299	0.6194	0.0493	601	0.2126	0.601	Non-significant, phylogenetically unstructured
Only LG	30	0.6620	0.6563	0.0530	533	0.1084	0.533	Non-significant, phylogenetically unstructured
Only LP	31	0.6665	0.6510	0.0545	621	0.2851	0.621	Non-significant, phylogenetically unstructured
Only EH	24	0.6210	0.6830	0.0620	164	-0.9981	0.164	Non-significant, phylogenetically unstructured

Table S11. Mntd analysis results comparing native not endemic species against endemic species (excluding all the species in blue indicated in the **Table S4**). Significance is indicated in bold, with marginal significance indicated in bold with an asterisk.

Analysis focus	N	Mntd obs.	Mntd rand. mean	Mntd rand. sd	Mntd obs. rank	Mntd obs. z value	p-value	Meaning
All islands	38	0.6275	0.5600	0.0552	888	1.2216	0.888	Non-significant, phylogenetically unstructured
Only TF	35	0.6349	0.6240	0.0530	599	0.2058	0.599	Non-significant, phylogenetically unstructured
Only LG	30	0.6620	0.6714	0.0541	432	-0.1739	0.432	Non-significant, phylogenetically unstructured
Only LP	30	0.6589	0.6485	0.0561	560	0.1850	0.56	Non-significant, phylogenetically unstructured
Only EH	24	0.6210	0.6811	0.0644	180	-0.9318	0.18	Non-significant, phylogenetically unstructured

Table S12. Mntd analysis results comparing introduced species sampled in the laurel forest against native not endemic and endemic species but classifying by the number of plots occupied by the introduced species (from 1 to 10 plots, without any species present in 7 plots or 8 plots), both ascending and descending. Significance is indicated in bold, with marginal significance indicated in bold with an asterisk. Mntd analysis using only species in 10 plots (N=1) was not feasible due to limitations of Mntd analysis.

Occupied plots	N	Mntd obs.	Mntd rand. mean	Mntd rand. sd	Mntd obs. rank	Mntd obs. z value	p-value	Meaning
All	47	0.4920	0.5605	0.0449	60	-1.5276	0.06*	Marginally significant phylogenetic clustering
1	26	0.6752	0.6444	0.0639	686	0.4825	0.686	Non-significant, phylogenetically unstructured
1-2	33	0.5893	0.6069	0.0568	373	-0.3047	0.373	Non-significant, phylogenetically unstructured
1-3	37	0.5846	0.5925	0.0541	443	-0.1462	0.443	Non-significant, phylogenetically unstructured
1-4	41	0.5459	0.5773	0.0492	262	-0.6364	0.262	Non-significant, phylogenetically unstructured
1-5	44	0.5162	0.5684	0.0478	136	-1.0927	0.136	Non-significant, phylogenetically unstructured
1-6	45	0.5114	0.5689	0.0474	114	-1.2131	0.114	Non-significant, phylogenetically unstructured
1-9	46	0.5024	0.5653	0.0451	83	-1.3971	0.083*	Marginally significant phylogenetic clustering
≥9	2	0.8464	1.1419	0.2716	124	-1.0880	0.124	Non-significant, phylogenetically unstructured
≥6	3	0.8950	1.0192	0.2094	269	-0.5928	0.269	Non-significant, phylogenetically unstructured
≥5	6	0.6283	0.8696	0.1450	57	-1.6640	0.057*	Marginally significant phylogenetic clustering
≥4	10	0.6496	0.7756	0.1071	118	-1.1748	0.118	Non-significant, phylogenetically unstructured
≥3	14	0.5917	0.7307	0.0926	69	-1.5011	0.069*	Marginally significant phylogenetic clustering
≥2	21	0.6056	0.6623	0.0742	228	-0.7647	0.228	Non-significant, phylogenetically unstructured

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Table S13. GLM results of the comparison of the minimum distance to the near native species (MinDis) between two possible categories, introduced species sampled only in one plot (N=26) and introduced species sampled in two or more plots (N=21).

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	0.7100	0.0898	7.906	4.72e-10 ***
Category	-0.1719	0.0587	-2.928	0.00534 **

Signif. codes: 0 '***', 0.001 '**', 0.01 '*', 0.05 '.', 0.1 ' ', 1

CHAPTER II

Molecular delimitation of evolutionary significant units reveals underappreciated extinction risks for island

Jiménez-García, E., Suárez, D., Andújar, C., López, H. & Emerson, B.C. (2024). Molecular delimitation of evolutionary significant units reveals underappreciated extinction risks for island arthropods. *Diversity and Distributions* (under review)

Abstract

Globally, arthropod biodiversity is under threat, with increased risk of species-level extinctions, and this threat is particularly acute on oceanic islands. A fundamental first step toward understanding extinction risk is to understand genetic connectivity among the constituent populations of a species. Here we develop and implement a protocol based on mtDNA sequence data for the delimitation of evolutionary significant units (ESUs) to characterise genetic connectivity among island populations, and evaluate extinction risk among species of beetle and spider distributed across multiple islands within the Canarian Archipelago. Our results reveal that more than half of the species analysed are comprised of two or more ESUs. We also find that low dispersal ability was a significant predictor of ESUs within species of Coleoptera, but with no significant difference for Araneae. In addition, most ESUs are consistent with early stage differentiation, or incipient speciation, with some exceeding a conservative interspecific threshold, thus indicative of cryptic species. We suggest that extending our approach with the integration of other species-level traits may provide for a more refined predictive framework for understanding extinction risks across island arthropod species.

Introduction

Globally, a significant number of insect species are likely to have gone extinct unnoticed (Terzopoulou *et al.*, 2015), and this is supported by analyses testing the possibility that all major taxonomic groups have equally high rates of extinction and threat. In fact, it appears that insects and other invertebrates are likely to have higher rates of threat than many other taxa. This assertion is supported by global extinction and threat data that follow a model where apparent differences for extinction and threat are caused by sampling biases. Comparisons in well-studied regions show that the global disparity among taxa is greatly reduced (McKinney, 1999). Island biotas have provided the majority of recorded global extinctions since 1500 AD, typically through extensive deforestation, transformation of natural habitats and the introduction of non-native species (Whittaker & Fernández-Palacios, 2007). However, much of this documented extinction is of plant and vertebrate taxa, with little reported data for invertebrate taxa (but see the Lepidoptera *Glaucopsyche xerces* (Grewe *et al.*, 2021) and gastropods of the genus *Partula* on the Island of Moorea (Murray *et al.*, 1988)). There is thus a need for improved data and understanding regarding invertebrate extinction risk in island systems, both in response to lag effects from historical influences (Triantis *et al.*, 2010) and ongoing global change.

Small geographical range size has been revealed to be a strong driver of extinction risk within insular systems. In their analysis of endemic Azorean beetle species and extinction risk, Terzopoulou *et al.* (2015) found a primary role for geographic range size. They found that single-island endemic (SIE) species were more prone to extinction than those occurring across multiple islands (multiple island endemic species, MIE). Terzopoulou *et al.* (2015) put forward several potential explanations for this relationship, pointing out that species with larger range sizes also tend to have greater local abundances, with larger populations being more resistant to demographic fluctuations. They also suggest that metapopulation restocking effects can reduce the effect of local population decline. Regarding this second point, in addition to the observations of Terzopoulou *et al.* (2015), a metapopulation dynamic will also positively contribute to effective population size, with immigration and gene flow among island populations acting to counteract the local influence of genetic drift.

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Categorising species as SIE or MIE has proven to be a useful tool for island biogeographic analyses (e.g. Caujapé-Castells *et al.*, 2022; Sakai *et al.*, 1995; Terzopoulou *et al.*, 2015; Whittaker *et al.*, 2007). However, the grouping of species together as MIEs does not take into account how species may vary with regard to genetic connectivity among islands. At one extreme, a MIE species may present panmixia across islands, and this should be favoured for highly dispersive species, particularly if they are habitat generalists, for which immigration and establishment between islands is favoured (Backs & Ashley, 2016; García-Verdugo *et al.*, 2010; Holland & Cowie, 2007). At the other extreme, a MIE species may be structured into island populations among which there is no effective gene flow (Emerson *et al.*, 2000a; Illera *et al.*, 2007; Mairal *et al.*, 2015), and this is more likely for dispersal limited species (Salces-Castellano *et al.*, 2021; Suárez *et al.*, 2022). When evidence suggests that divergences between MIE populations exceed thresholds that are typically representative of different species, island populations may be better considered as a series of cryptic or overlooked SIE species (e.g. Pérez-Delgado *et al.*, 2022; Pflingstl *et al.*, 2021) (**Figure 1**).

Figure 1. Single island endemism (SIE), multiple island endemism (MIE) and gene flow. (a) Graphical representation of a SIE and MIE on an island archipelago. (b) Two contrasting MIE species, with one (in grey) characterised by gene flow between islands, while the other (in white) has no gene flow between islands. (c) Modification of scenario (b) where MIE 2 (MIE without gene flow) is best considered as two cryptic independent SIE.

The implication of considering divergent MIE island populations as either cryptic species, or subspecies, or genetically isolated populations, is that in all cases individual island populations are conceptually closer to SIE species, in terms of extinction risk. Specifically, such populations receive no external recruitment that may buffer against adverse demographic and environmental change by increasing effective population size and restocking. This issue can also be extrapolated to single and multiple island non-

endemic native species (SINE and MINE), where limitations to gene flow among islands, and cryptic differentiation, may also emerge. For both MIEs and MINEs, we implement a categorisation approach based on evolutionary significant units (ESUs). ESU delimitation has its origins in the objective prioritisation of conservation value below the species level through the characterisation unambiguous units for conservation (Fraser & Bernatchez, 2001). Since the term was first proposed by Ryder (1986), there have been many propositions for how to characterise ESUs (see Hoelzel, 2023 for a review), and among these, Moritz (1994, 2002) has proposed the reciprocal monophyly of mtDNA as a key diagnostic. While placing primary importance on mtDNA has raised concerns (Crandall *et al.*, 2000; Fraser & Bernatchez, 2001; Waples, 1995), and one would ideally incorporate complementary nuclear data as suggested by Moritz (1994, 2002), it does provide a pathway to characterise ESUs at scale across entire communities of species. We take advantage of this to characterise ESUs among island populations within 77 MIE and MINE species of spider and beetle, obtained through systematic community sampling within a network of 31 laurel cloud forest plots distributed across the four western Canary Islands. We first test for geographic structuring of genetic variation among island populations within species, and then identify which geographically structured units also correspond to mtDNA monophyly, and thus consistency with ESUs. We do not implement Moritz's (1994, 2002) constraint of reciprocal monophyly, thus the delimitation of a monophyletic ESU comprising all individuals of one or more islands is not contingent upon patterns of monophyly among other islands. This allows for island colonisation through founder events, and multiple colonisations to the same island, which may give rise to non-monophyly of mtDNA variation.

To provide further evolutionary and taxonomic context for ESUs, we also evaluate genetic divergences among ESUs within species against empirically derived estimates of expected intraspecific variation, through to species level differentiation. We also test the hypothesis that dispersal ability is a driver of island differentiation within MIE and MINE species. Previous analyses characterising how genetic variation is structured among and within islands for both spiders and beetles have provided clear evidence for differences in dispersal ability explaining variation within islands, but not among islands (Suárez *et al.*, 2022). However, to incorporate taxonomic uncertainty, the analyses of Suárez *et al.* (2022) were not conducted at the level of individual species, instead applying conservative divergence thresholds to define lineages of maternal dispersal history

(LMDH). These lineages were defined to provide a comparable evolutionary time frame for analyses, and maximise the probability that all individuals of a given biological species were assigned to a single LMDH. Thus, LMDHs may represent different stages of the speciation process, from single panmictic species, through to geographically structured species, incipient species, and species complexes, and ultimately different biological species, which may or may not be taxonomically diagnosable. To understand the role of dispersal ability as a driver of differentiation among island populations within a species, here we focus analyses at the level of taxonomically assigned species. This allows us to test the hypothesis that limited dispersal ability (i.e. wingless vs winged beetle species and non-ballooning vs ballooning spider species) drives differentiation among island populations of MIE and MINE species.

Materials and Methods

Field sampling, mtDNA sequencing and species delimitation

Beetle and spider communities were sampled from 31 laurel forest plots across the four western Canary Islands of Tenerife, La Gomera, La Palma and El Hierro (**Figure 2**), following the protocol described in Emerson *et al.* (2017).

Figure 2. Laurel forest sampling plots across the four western Canary Islands.

Species were sorted morphologically as parataxonomic units (PUs) prior to selecting four individuals per PU per plot (less if less than four were sampled) for sequencing of the cytochrome c oxidase subunit 1 (COI) gene region of the mitochondrial genome. For some particularly difficult taxonomic groups (e.g. the genera *Atheta* (Staphylinidae) and *Laparocerus* (Curculionidae), and the tribe Cryptorhynchini), more than four individuals were sequenced. The COI-5P “barcode” region, a 658 bp COI gene fragment close to the 5' end of the gene, was sequenced for spiders (see Suárez *et al.*, 2022 for details regarding PCR conditions and individuals sequenced) while the COI-3P region, a 824 bp COI gene fragment close to the 3' end of the gene, was the chosen for beetles (see Jiménez-García *et al.*, 2023 for more information about PCR conditions and individuals sequenced).

To identify presumed biological species (PBS; Emerson *et al.*, 2017) a custom R script (Salces-Castellano *et al.*, 2021; <https://github.com/asalcescastellano/Divergence-threshold.git>) was used to produce trees from pairwise Kimura 2-parameter (K2P) distances, using the unweighted pair group method with arithmetic mean (UPGMA), using an alignment of all sequences from all PUs, for beetles and spiders separately. Within the script we implemented a conservative maximum intraspecific divergence threshold of 6.8% for spiders (Suárez *et al.*, 2022) and 8% for beetles (Jiménez-García *et al.*, 2023; Salces-Castellano *et al.*, 2021) to create individual lineage alignments. Under these divergence thresholds, it is assumed that all individuals of a given biological species will be represented within a single lineage, but that a given lineage may comprise more than one biological species. The script also generates a table summarising: (i) the PU composition within each lineage; (ii) for each PU within a lineage, the proportion of individuals from that PU included within the lineage, and (iii) when a lineage comprises individuals from more than one PU, the presence or absence of monophyly among individuals from the same PU. Lineages exclusively comprising all individuals within a given PU were inferred to represent a single PBS. Individuals from PUs that segregated across more than one lineage were revised to evaluate potential PU assignment error or possible laboratory contamination, with the removal of any sequences ascribed to the latter. When two or more PUs segregated within the same lineage, individuals were revised morphologically, and in the absence of any differences the lineage was inferred to represent a single PBS. For lineages comprising two or more morphologically distinct PUs, and where PUs were phylogenetically structured within the lineage, PUs were

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inferred to represent different PBS. Morphologically distinct PUs that showed no clear segregation with regard to mtDNA variation were inferred to represent recent speciation with incomplete lineage sorting and/or gene flow, and were removed for subsequent analyses. Specimens from PBS were examined and taxonomically assigned using dichotomous keys and available taxonomic literature (see Jiménez-García *et al.*, 2023; Suárez *et al.*, 2022 for literature details). Taxonomic assignments were further assessed and refined by comparison of COI sequences against the public databases of GenBank and BOLD Systems.

Species of beetles and spiders were chosen for analysis if they satisfied two criteria: (i) they were sampled on two or more islands, and; (ii) taxonomy was assigned with high confidence to the level of species. When two or more PBS from different lineages were assigned exclusively and unequivocally to the same taxonomic species, they were considered jointly as a single species in downstream analyses.

Analyses of population genetic structure and the delimitation of ESUs.

SPAGeDi version 1.5d (Hardy & Vekemans, 2002) was used to estimate population structure within each species. DNACollapser from FaBox 1.5 (Villesen, 2007) was used to identify unique haplotypes, and population structure was estimated using the N_{ST} index, which incorporates haplotype similarity as measured by the number of mutational differences (Pons & Petit, 1996). With the aim of defining if individual species were formed by one or several ESUs, species were analysed using the following workflow consisting of 3 steps (**Figure 3**).

(a) Delimitation of ESUs

(b) Characterisation of divergence among ESUs

Figure 3. Workflow for delimiting ESUs within species distributed across two or more islands (a), and characterising their extent of divergence from other ESUs (b). Detailed explanations of the delimitation process and the characterisation of divergences are described in the main text.

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STEP 1: N_{ST} was first estimated globally across all islands within each species. *Output.* Species presenting non-significant values for N_{ST} were considered to be a single ESU, hereafter referred to as a type 1 ESU (**Figure 4**). Species with significant values for N_{ST} passed to step 2.

STEP 2: N_{ST} was calculated between each island and a group comprising all remaining islands. For significantly differentiated islands, monophyly was evaluated within neighbour-joining trees in Geneious Prime 2019.1.1 (Biomatters, Auckland, New Zealand). *Output.* Significantly differentiated and monophyletic island populations were classified as type 2 ESUs (**Figure 4**). Undifferentiated or significantly differentiated but non-monophyletic island populations passed to step 3.

STEP 3. N_{ST} was estimated between all pairs of island populations within a species, and monophyly evaluated when differentiation was significant. *Output.* Islands, or island groups, were considered to be type 2 ESUs if they were both differentiated and monophyletic with respect to each other. In the case of non-significance, or significance without monophyly across all comparisons within a species, the species was inferred to be a type 1 ESU. Under the requirement of monophyly within an ESU, differentiated island populations characterised by paraphyletic or polyphyletic variation (**Figure 4**) are excluded from further ESU inferences. Lineages within such islands require additional data (e.g. nuclear, morphological, and ecological) to understand their evolutionary significance.

For type 2 ESUs identified in Steps 2 and 3, their divergence from the most closely-related sequence from another island was calculated (**Figure 3b**). Using the thresholds described below, divergences were categorised as either: (i) *Early stage inter-island differentiation*. Divergence from the most closely-related sequence from another island is below the threshold estimated for incipient speciation, with divergences thus being consistent with expectations for intraspecific variation; (ii) *Incipient speciation or species-level differentiation*. Divergence is above the intraspecific threshold, but below the conservative interspecific threshold; (iii) *Species-level divergence*. Divergence is higher than the conservative interspecific threshold.

Figure 4. Schematic illustration of the two categories of ESU. (a) A hypothetical example of four populations, one per island indicated with capital letters from A to D. (b) The four populations are genetically undifferentiated and form a single ESU for the species (type 1 ESU). (c) genetic variation is structured into three geographically independent monophyletic groups (type 2 ESUs) corresponding to the islands A, B and C+D. (d) Islands B, C and D each comprise monophyletic groups, geographically independent of each other and island A (type 2 ESUs), while island A is paraphyletic and therefore excluded for ESU analyses.

Threshold estimation for population differentiation

In addition to the upper thresholds of genetic divergence for beetles (8%) and spiders (6.8%), above which individuals can confidently be assumed to belong to different species, thresholds were also estimated, above which divergences between ESUs can be considered consistent with early stages of differentiation or incipient speciation. Thresholds were calculated for beetles using data from Hendrich *et al.* (2015), and for spiders using data from Astrin *et al.* (2016). Hendrich *et al.* (2015) sequenced the barcode region for 15,948 individuals from 3,514 species of beetle, sampled from Germany and

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neighbouring countries, while Astrin *et al.* (2016) sequenced 3,339 individuals from 561 species of spider across the same region. We filtered the data for species with eight or more different haplotypes, sampled across at least three countries in the case of beetles, or from at least three geographically disjunct regions of Germany in the case of spiders. This filtering strategy was designed to conservatively exclude species with low intraspecific divergences due to limited geographic or genetic sampling. The upper 99% confidence interval of maximum intraspecific divergence values within species was used to define a threshold, for beetles and spiders respectively, above which the early stages of differentiation or incipient speciation is suggested between ESUs.

To provide a more general context, we also evaluate divergences among ESUs with the 2.2% threshold proposed by Hebert *et al.* (2003), which has been developed by Ratnasingham & Hebert (2013) for the identification of Barcode Index Numbers (BINs) within the Barcode of Life Data System (BOLD; Ratnasingham & Hebert, 2007). This 2.2% divergence threshold is often associated with probable species boundaries (Hausmann *et al.*, 2013; Sharkey *et al.*, 2021), however this is highly debated (Meier *et al.*, 2022; Yeo *et al.*, 2020). Due to the centralised implementation of this 2.2% threshold within BOLD, and the debate surrounding its biological relevance, we feel it relevant to comment on its implications when applied to our data.

Dispersal ability categorisation

Generalised linear models were implemented in R v. 4.2.0 (glm function, *stats* package) to test if limited dispersal ability is significantly associated with the delimitation of multiple ESUs within species. Species of beetle were characterised as good dispersers if they had wings, while species without wings, or with non-functional vestigial wings were classified as poor dispersers. Species of spider were categorised as good dispersers if they are capable of ballooning (following the classification at family level established by Carvalho & Cardoso, 2014), while non-ballooning species were characterised as poor dispersers.

Results

Species selection

A total of 360 beetle PBS (Jiménez-García *et al.*, 2023) and 119 spider PBS (Suárez *et al.*, 2022) were delimited, of which 168 and 49, respectively, were sampled from more than one island. Of these multi-island species, 49 beetle species, from 44 genera, and 28 spider species, from 27 genera, could be taxonomically assigned to species level with high confidence, and were chosen for subsequent analyses (**Table S1**). These species belong to 21 Coleoptera families and 17 Araneae families, representing 30% and 39.5%, respectively, of families recorded in the Canary Islands. Nineteen species of Coleoptera (39%) are poor dispersers, due to the absence or dysfunction of wings while the remaining 30 species (61%) have fully developed wings, and can be considered good dispersers. Nine species of spider (32%) are poor dispersers, through the absence of ballooning, with the remaining 19 ballooning species (68%) are considered good dispersers. Fifteen species of Coleoptera (31%) are recognised as native non-endemic, with the remaining 34 species (69%) being endemic. Seventeen species of Araneae (61%) are recognised as native non-endemic, with the remaining 11 species (39%) being endemic (<https://www.biodiversidadcanarias.es/biota>; accessed: 20 September 2023; **Table S1**).

Delimitation of intraspecific divergence thresholds

Intraspecific genetic divergence thresholds of 1.62% and 1.67% were estimated for species of beetle and spider respectively, above which we consider genetic differentiation between populations to be consistent with early stages of differentiation or incipient speciation. These thresholds, together with the 8% and 6.8% thresholds to conservatively differentiate between species of beetle and spider, respectively, were used to classify type 2 ESUs as being representative of either (i) early inter-island differentiation, (ii) incipient speciation or species-level differentiation, or (iii) species-level differentiation (**Figure 3b**).

Analyses of population genetic structure and ESU delimitation

Among the 49 species of beetle analysed for ESU delimitation, only five (10%) presented no significant genetic structure across all islands (Step 1), and were thus classified as type 1 ESUs (**Tables S2 to S8** summarise the results of ESU delimitation for beetle species). The remaining 44 species were sampled for a total of 124 island populations, among which samples from six island populations (all belonging to different species) were too small for the calculation of N_{ST} . These six populations were thus excluded, with the remaining 118 populations representing 10 species sampled on four islands, 10 species sampled on three islands, and 24 species sampled on two islands. Of these 118 populations, 105 were significantly differentiated by N_{ST} when compared against a population comprising all other islands (Step 2). Of these 105 populations, 67 were found to be monophyletic and thus classified in Step 2 as type 2 ESUs. Among the remaining 38 non-monophyletic populations, and the 13 undifferentiated populations, together representing 18 species, pairwise analyses of N_{ST} among islands (Step 3) yielded a total of 17 ESUs (9 type 1, 8 type 2) with all but three comprising multi-island ESUs. Two populations belonging to 2 species were excluded due to paraphyly/polyphyly. Thus, across the 49 species of beetle analysed, a total of 89 ESUs were identified, with 35 species (72%) presenting evidence for more than one ESU. The 75 type 2 ESUs (68 single island ESU and 7 multi-island) were compared to the intraspecific and interspecific divergence thresholds, with: (i) 27 below the intraspecific threshold, consistent with an early stage of differentiation; (ii) 47 with divergences exceeding intraspecific levels, but below the conservative species-level threshold, and; (iii) one exceeding the conservative species-level divergence.

Among the 28 species of spider, eight presented no significant geographic structuring of genetic variation among islands (Step 1), consistent with each species comprising a type 1 ESU (**Tables S2 to S8** summarise the results of ESU delimitation for spider species). Among the remaining 20 spider species, none of the 74 island populations were discarded due to sample size limitations, yielding 15 species sampled for four island populations, four species sampled for three island populations and one species sampled for two island populations. Among the 74 populations, 61 were significantly differentiated from all remaining populations, with the remaining 13 being undifferentiated (Step 2). Only 20 of the 61 differentiated island populations were monophyletic, consistent with type 2 ESUs. The remaining 41 non-monophyletic

populations, together with the 13 undifferentiated populations, representing 18 species, were subjected to pairwise analyses of N_{ST} and monophyly assessment (Step 3) yielding a total of 17 ESUs (8 type 1, 9 type 2), with all but three comprising multi-island ESUs. Two populations belonging to 2 species were excluded due to paraphyly/polyphyly. Thus, across the 28 species of spiders analysed, a total of 45 ESUs were identified, with 12 species (43%) presenting evidence for more than one ESU. The 29 type 2 ESUs were compared against the intraspecific and interspecific thresholds, resulting in: (i) 11 below the intraspecific threshold, consistent with early stage differentiation; (ii) 17 with divergences exceeding the intraspecific threshold, but below the conservative species level threshold, and; (iii) one above the conservative species-level threshold.

Globally, across the 77 species analysed (49 beetle and 28 spider), a total of 134 ESUs (89 for beetles and 45 for spiders) were identified of which 89 (68 beetle and 21 spider) were restricted to a single island, while 45 (21 beetle and 24 spider) were distributed across two or more islands. The 134 ESUs comprise 30 type 1 ESU (14 beetle and 16 spider) and 104 type 2 ESU (75 beetle and 29 spider).

Dispersal ability analysis

For Coleoptera, 17 of the 19 species (89%) with low dispersal ability were comprised of more than one ESU, while in the case of species with high dispersal ability, 18 of the 30 species (60%) were comprised of more than one ESU. This difference between dispersal categories was found to be significant (binomial GLM, p-value: 0.037; **Table S9**). Within the Araneae, of the nine species considered as poor dispersers, six (67%) were comprised of more than one ESU, while in the case of the remaining 19 species with high dispersal ability, only six (32%) presented two or more ESUs. However, this difference was not found to be significant (binomial GLM, p-value: 0.089; **Table S10**).

Discussion

From a total of 77 species, 30 comprise a single ESU across all sampled populations, with the remaining 47 presenting evidence for more than one ESU. Across the 35 species of Coleoptera comprising more than one ESU (71% of all species), a total of 75 ESUs were recovered, of which 68 were single-island ESUs, with the remaining seven being multi-island ESUs. Within the Araneae, 12 species (43%, of all species) presented more than one ESU, with a total of 29 ESUs delimited, of which 21 were single-island ESUs with the remaining eight being multi-island ESUs. Dispersal ability was found to be a significant predictor of multiple ESUs within species for Coleoptera, but not for Araneae, although there was a trend toward higher incidence of ESUs within less dispersive species. Dispersal ability has recently been revealed to be associated with higher extinction rates within genera of both Coleoptera and Araneae across the Canary Islands by Suárez *et al.* (2022), and our results suggest a potential mechanistic explanation for this. At an archipelago scale, reduced gene flow among island populations will result in ESUs confined to single islands, consequently reducing effective population sizes and promoting genetic drift and local inbreeding, the effects of which will scale with the extent of gene flow limitation (Bertrand *et al.*, 2014; Frankham, 1997; Furlan *et al.*, 2012). This loss of genetic diversity can result in island populations with reduced evolutionary potential, relative to an idealised scenario of panmixia across islands, thus increasing extinction risk at the island scale. In the extreme of zero dispersal among islands, local (i.e. island-level) extinction events will not be reversed through population reestablishment from other islands (Forester *et al.*, 2022; Furlan *et al.*, 2012). Thus, as gene flow among islands tends toward zero with increasing dispersal limitation, both island-level and archipelago-level extinction rates will be elevated.

Conservation and management implications

Our results highlight a diversity continuum that is not captured by conventional biogeographic terms. Single-island vs multi-island and endemic vs non-endemic simplify a more complex reality by polarising species. Across the 12 species of Araneae comprising two or more ESUs, six are endemic species, with the remaining six being non-endemic. Within the Coleoptera, 27 of the 35 species (77%) comprising two or more ESUs are endemic species, with the remaining eight being non-endemic. The high level

of geographic structuring within the six species of spider and eight species of beetle, classified as native non-endemic, reveals their conceptual similarity to endemic species, within which such diversification is expected (Atkins *et al.*, 2020; Turchetto *et al.*, 2016; Wang, 2020). While most divergences among ESUs within native non-endemic species are consistent with intraspecific expectations, divergences within six spider ESUs (three species) largely exceed intraspecific expectations (**Figure 5**), suggesting the possibility of cryptic or overlooked species.

Figure 5. Distribution of genetic divergences (p-distance) between ESUs and their most closely related sequence from another ESU, for native non-endemic (grey) and endemic (black) species of Coleoptera (a) and Araneae (b). Intraspecific thresholds, BIN thresholds and interspecific thresholds are represented with the letters A, B and C, respectively.

Barcode sequencing of presumed native non-endemic species has previously been demonstrated to be a powerful tool for determining origins to be human-mediated introduction, rather than native. In an analysis of cloud forest beetle communities across the Canary Islands (Jiménez-García *et al.*, 2023), barcode sequence matching to BOLD revealed 19 of 56 species categorised as being native have in fact established through human introduction. Additionally, barcoding across the genus *Halophiloscia* by Bidegaray-Batista *et al.* (2015) revealed the presumed native species *H. couchii* to be introduced. Our results, together with those of Bidegaray-Batista *et al.* (2015) and Jiménez-García *et al.* (2023), highlight how representative barcode sequencing across the ranges of presumed native non-endemic arthropod species can contribute to evidence-based understanding of their conservation relevance.

Our results reveal that island populations within multi-island species can be genetically independent of each other, revealing them to be conceptually closer to single island endemic species, with an associated increase in their extinction risk. Extrapolating our results across the entire beetle and spider fauna of the Canary Islands provides broader context for the extent to which extinction risks may be underestimated within MIE and MINE species. Filtering species distribution records for the Canary Islands (<https://www.biodiversidadcanarias.es/biota>; accessed: 20 September 2023) for native species (including endemics) recorded in two or more islands yields a total of 1,032 out of 2,061 species of Coleoptera and 222 out of 480 species of Araneae. Under the assumption that our sampling is broadly representative of the Coleoptera and Araneae fauna, we estimate that as many as 733 species of Coleoptera (71% of the 1,032 native species recorded from two or more islands; 36% of the total native Canarian species) and 96 Araneae (43% of the 222 native species recorded from two or more islands; 20% of the total native Canarian species) may comprise multiple ESUs that segregate across different islands.

It has previously been suggested that quantifying and recognising ESU status within species can be useful for the development of appropriate conservative policies (Waples, 1995). Analogous or related entities have also been put forward for conservation purposes, such as Management Units (MUs: Funk *et al.*, 2012; Palsbøll *et al.*, 2007), the Distinct Population Segment (DPSs) used by the USA Endangered Species Act (Waples, 1991) or Designatable Units (DUs) adopted by the Committee on the Status of Endangered Wildlife in Canada (Mee *et al.*, 2015). We suggest that in insular geographic

settings, DNA barcoding provides a simple, scalable and cost effective (Meier *et al.*, 2016; Srivathsan *et al.*, 2021, 2024; Wang *et al.*, 2018) conservation tool for the characterisation of ESUs and related units.

Subspecies taxonomy and ESUs

No species of spider are taxonomically divided into subspecies. However, across the 49 species of Coleoptera analysed, 11 are taxonomically divided into subspecies (**Table S1 and S8**), with described subspecies coinciding with delimited ESUs for five. Among these five species, the two ESUs delineated within *Dromius angustus* correspond to *D. angustus plagipennis* (El Hierro), and *D. angustus dissimilis* (La Palma), with mtDNA divergence between them (0.65%) being consistent with expectations for intraspecific variation, falling below both the BIN threshold of 2.2%, and our empirically derived threshold of 1.62%. Similarly, the 1.7% divergence between the subspecies *Laparocerus inaequalis inaequalis* (Tenerife), and *L. inaequalis globulipennis* (La Palma) is below the BIN threshold, and only marginally above our empirically derived threshold for intraspecific variation. Divergences between subspecies are marginally below the BIN threshold (2.07% and 2.13% respectively) between *Echinodera hystrix hystrix* (El Hierro), and *E. hystrix benahorita* (La Palma) and between *Paradromius iucundus iucundus* (La Palma), and *P. iucundus gillerforsi* (La Gomera). The highest divergence between subspecies of 2.77% is found between *Licinopsis oblitterata oblitterata* (La Gomera) and *L. oblitterata franzi* (El Hierro).

Contrasting with the five species described above, there are four features of our data that highlight a dissociative relationship between ESUs and morphological subspecies. First, there are species that have been taxonomically partitioned into subspecies, (*Sunius brevipennis* and *Trechus flavocinctus*) but resolve to a single ESU. Second, there are species that have been partitioned into subspecies that are in direct conflict with ESUs (*Laparocerus lepidopterus* and *Stagetus hirtulus*). Third, there are species with some subspecies correspondence to ESUs, but with further ESU segregation within subspecies. As an example, *Micrambe hesperia* has been partitioned into two subspecies, *M. hesperia occidentalis* (El Hierro) and *M. hesperia hesperia* (La Gomera and Tenerife). Here we recover an ESU specific to El Hierro, consistent with *M. hesperia occidentalis*. However, *M. hesperia hesperia* further segregates into one ESU on La

Gomera, and another on Tenerife. Additionally, *Nesotes conformis turgidicollis* (La Palma) is recovered as an ESU, but *N. conformis conformis* (El Hierro and Tenerife) further segregates into one ESU on El Hierro, and the paraphyletic and discarded populations on Tenerife. Fourth, there are species with no subspecific taxonomy that are structured into divergent ESUs. Examples include *Leiodes oceanica* and *Nesotes congestus*, which each segregate into two island specific ESUs, with 7.63% and 3.05% divergence between them, respectively.

How to reconcile between ESUs and subspecies has been the subject of debate (Braby *et al.*, 2012; Coates *et al.*, 2018; Firestone *et al.*, 1999; Kindler & Fritz, 2018; Molinari, 2023; Weeks *et al.*, 2016). From a practical perspective, our results indicate that while existing subspecies designations can be reflective of evolutionary divisions within species, they may also overestimate, underestimate, or directly contradict such groupings. We therefore suggest that, at least for insular arthropods, the utilisation of existing subspecies taxonomy for conservation and management decision making may be of limited value or, in the worst case scenario, directly misleading. Thus, our results also argue that even limited mtDNA surveys across insular invertebrate populations can enhance taxonomic data as a management tool.

ESUs, species divergence thresholds, and species discovery

With growing evidence for the widespread existence of cryptic or otherwise overlooked species within arthropods (e.g. Bickford *et al.*, 2007; Li & Wiens, 2023; Pérez-Delgado *et al.*, 2022), there is increasing interest in fast-tracking species descriptions through the incorporation of barcode sequence data. This interest is captured by the work of Sharkey *et al.* (2021), who described 403 new species of Costa Rican braconid parasitoid wasp, based largely on differences in the barcode region. The “minimalist revision” approach of Sharkey *et al.* (2021) has received criticism (Ahrens *et al.*, 2021; Engel *et al.*, 2021; Fernández-Triana, 2022; Meier *et al.*, 2022; Zamani *et al.*, 2022), largely due to its assumption that Barcode Index Numbers (BINs: Ratnasingham & Hebert, 2013), computed within BOLD (Ratnasingham & Hebert, 2007), with a clustering threshold of 2.2% are reflective of species boundaries.

Discussion surrounding the estimation and application of mtDNA divergence thresholds to delimit presumptive species largely exists in the absence of a species concept. By their definition, divergence thresholds imply correlation between genomic (nuclear and mitochondrial) divergence and species formation, and that the strength of this relationship is consistent across taxonomic diversity to which the thresholds are to be applied. However, neither a typological, nor the Biological Species Concept (BSC: Coyne & Orr, 2004; Mayr, 1942), predict genetic divergence thresholds, and evidence to date for these (Ratnasingham & Hebert, 2013) is based upon limited reference data (Meier *et al.*, 2022). Recent considerations of the speciation continuum in the context of the BSC (Stankowski & Ravinet, 2021) highlight that populations can accumulate reproductive isolation at very different rates, as such isolation can emerge due to one or a few large effect loci (lower genomic divergence), many small effect barrier loci scattered across the genome (higher genomic divergence) or some combination of both (intermediate levels of genomic divergence; Butlin & Stankowski, 2020).

Here we have sought to avoid a single threshold, instead attempting to encompass the so-called “grey zone of speciation” (Roux *et al.*, 2016) through the interrogation of taxonomically relevant regional barcode data from beetle and spider species (Astrin *et al.*, 2016; Hendrich *et al.*, 2015). Our results reveal intraspecific variation in both taxonomic groups that extends well above the well-known 2.2% BIN threshold (**Figure 5**). While no divergences among ESUs within native non-endemic Coleoptera exceed the BIN threshold, ten endemic species yield a total of 21 ESUs, the divergences among which exceed the BIN threshold, as do three native non-endemic spider species (six ESUs) and two endemic spider species (five ESUs). We contextualise this variation by characterising two thresholds encompassing the grey zone of speciation, below this range variation can be more confidently reconciled with single species-level variation, while divergences above the range can confidently be reconciled with different species. Divergences between both thresholds are thus representative of the grey zone, within which isolating barriers causing reproductive isolation (RI) are such that $0 \leq \text{RI} \leq 1$.

Rather than unequivocally assigning monophyletic lineages with divergences that fall within this interval to different species, we highlight their relevance as ESUs. We note that as divergence values tend toward the upper threshold, the probability that each lineage is representative of biological species increases, and that divergences themselves could be used as an index for the probability of species-level differentiation. Populations

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that are divergent from each other within this interval can be seen as candidates for revisionary taxonomic work. Our ESU delimitation highlights two cases where divergences exceed the upper threshold. *Micrambe hesperia* (Cryptophagidae) is an endemic species of beetle, recorded from Tenerife, Gran Canaria, La Gomera and La Palma, whose known distribution has been extended to El Hierro with our sampling. A minimum genetic distance of 8.2% separates an ESU from the island of Tenerife from two more closely related ESUs on the islands of La Gomera and El Hierro, which are themselves characterised by a minimum genetic distance of 6.5% from each other (**Figure S1**). Thus, under a very conservative divergence threshold between species of 8% (Jiménez-García *et al.*, 2023; Salces-Castellano *et al.*, 2021; Suárez *et al.*, 2022), *M. hesperia* is inferred to be at least two cryptic or overlooked species. Notably, scaling the 6.5% divergence between populations on La Gomera and El Hierro from zero to one for the upper threshold indicates both ESUs may also conform to species, with a scaled divergence of 0.8.

The spider *Olios canariensis* (Sparassidae), recorded from Tenerife, La Gomera, La Palma and Lanzarote, whose distribution was recently extended to include El Hierro by Suárez *et al.* (2023), is the only endemic species for the genus *Olios* within the Canary Islands. A minimum genetic distance of 8.2% separates an ESU from the island of Tenerife and two more closely related ESUs on the islands of La Gomera and La Palma, which are themselves characterised by a minimum genetic distance between them of 4.1% (**Figure S1**). Thus, under a very conservative divergence threshold between species of 6.8% (Emerson *et al.*, 2017; Suárez *et al.*, 2022), *O. canariensis* is inferred to be at least two cryptic or overlooked species.

Conclusions

We have revealed unprecedented differentiation into independent evolutionary lineages across insular arthropod species, whose ranges extend beyond single islands. In some cases, genetic divergences exceed even the most conservative species thresholds, indicative of cryptic or overlooked species. The application of mtDNA sequences to characterise ESUs represents a scalable approach that can be applied within insular systems for a better understanding of local (island-level) extinction risks within species. Our results reveal that dispersal ability can serve as a useful indicator for the existence of island-level ESUs within species, but with substantial uncertainty that can be resolved with molecular data. We suggest that our approach could serve as a framework for a more refined understanding of species-level extinction risk, through the integration of relevant species-level trait data that has been associated with extinction risk in arthropods, such as body size, habitat specialisation, range size, and population density (Nolte *et al.*, 2019; Seibold *et al.*, 2015).

Supplementary material

- **Figure S1.** Neighbour joining trees of mtDNA variation within species that exceed conservative species level divergences, indicative of cryptic species.
- **Table S1.** Details of the the 28 Araneae and 49 Coleoptera species selected for analysis.
- **Table S2.** Results of workflow Step 1.
- **Table S3.** Results of workflow Step 2a.
- **Table S4.** Results of workflow Step 2b.
- **Table S5.** Results of workflow Step 3a.
- **Table S6.** Results of workflow Step 3b.
- **Table S7.** Categorisation of type 2 ESUs as indicative of either (A) early stage inter-island differentiation, where divergences are consistent with expectations for intraspecific variation, (B) incipient or species-level differentiation, with divergences above the intraspecific threshold, but below the conservative interspecific threshold, or (C) species-level differentiation, with divergences higher than the conservative interspecific threshold.
- **Table S8.** Summary of the delimited ESUs for each species tested throughout the workflow.
- **Table S9.** Binomial GLM results of the comparison between species of beetle comprised of only one ESU (N=14) and those comprised of two or more (N=35), according to their dispersal capacity (winged or wingless).
- **Table S10.** Binomial GLM results of the comparison between species of spiders comprised of only one ESU (N=16) and those comprised of two or more (N=12), according to their dispersal capacity (ballooner or non-ballooner).

Figure S1. Neighbour joining trees of mtDNA variation within species that exceed conservative species level divergences, indicative of cryptic species. (a) The beetle species *Micrambe hesperia*. (b) The spider species *Olios canariensis*. Minimum genetic divergences measured with p distances between clades are shown.

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Table S1. The 28 Araneae and 49 Coleoptera species selected for analysis. Dashes under Subspecies indicate that subspecies have not been described. Values in parentheses under Sequences are the number of unique haplotypes sampled. Status describes whether a species is native non-endemic (NNE) or endemic (E).

Order	Family	Species	Subspecies	Sampled islands	Sequences	Status	Dispersal
Araneae	Araneidae	<i>Araniella maderiana</i>	-	TF, LG, LP & EH	31 (30)	NNE	Ballooners
Araneae	Cheiracanthiidae	<i>Cheiracanthium canariense</i>	-	TF, LG, LP & EH	134 (69)	NNE	Non-ballooners
Araneae	Pisauridae	<i>Cladycnis insignis</i>	-	TF, LG, LP & EH	114 (74)	E	Non-ballooners
Araneae	Clubionidae	<i>Clubiona minor</i>	-	TF, LG, LP & EH	44 (29)	E	Non-ballooners
Araneae	Araneidae	<i>Cyclosa maderiana</i>	-	TF, LG, LP & EH	56 (14)	NNE	Ballooners
Araneae	Dysderidae	<i>Dysdera silvatica</i>	-	LG & EH	4 (4)	E	Non-ballooners
Araneae	Theridiidae	<i>Echinotheridion gibberosum</i>	-	TF, LG, LP & EH	102 (7)	NNE	Ballooners
Araneae	Theridiidae	<i>Enoplognatha sattleri</i>	-	TF, LG, LP & EH	27 (10)	NNE	Ballooners
Araneae	Mimetidae	<i>Ero tuberculata</i>	-	TF, LG, LP & EH	41 (28)	NNE	Ballooners
Araneae	Uloboridae	<i>Hyptiotes flavidus</i>	-	TF, LG, LP & EH	35 (9)	NNE	Non-ballooners
Araneae	Linyphiidae	<i>Improphantes furcabilis</i>	-	TF, LG & LP	16 (12)	E	Ballooners
Araneae	Linyphiidae	<i>Improphantes multidentatus</i>	-	TF, LG & EH	19 (12)	E	Ballooners
Araneae	Dictynidae	<i>Lathys dentichelis</i>	-	TF, LG, LP & EH	84 (39)	NNE	Non-ballooners
Araneae	Theridiidae	<i>Macaridion barretti</i>	-	TF, LG, LP & EH	55 (31)	NNE	Ballooners
Araneae	Salticidae	<i>Macaroeris nidicolens</i>	-	TF, LG, LP & EH	56 (21)	NNE	Ballooners
Araneae	Gnaphosidae	<i>Macarophaeus varius</i>	-	TF, LG, LP & EH	72 (18)	E	Non-ballooners
Araneae	Araneidae	<i>Mangora acalypha</i>	-	TF, LG, LP & EH	20 (18)	NNE	Ballooners
Araneae	Tetragnathidae	<i>Metellina minima</i>	-	TF, LG & LP	134 (32)	E	Ballooners
Araneae	Linyphiidae	<i>Microlinyphia johnsoni</i>	-	TF, LG, LP & EH	90 (10)	NNE	Ballooners
Araneae	Thomisidae	<i>Misumena spinifera</i>	-	LG, LP & EH	12 (10)	NNE	Ballooners
Araneae	Sparassidae	<i>Olios canariensis</i>	-	TF, LG & LP	61 (15)	E	Non-ballooners
Araneae	Philodromidae	<i>Pulchellodromus wunderlichi</i>	-	TF, LG, LP & EH	121 (10)	E	Ballooners
Araneae	Theridiidae	<i>Steatoda nobilis</i>	-	TF, LG, LP & EH	112 (70)	NNE	Ballooners
Araneae	Linyphiidae	<i>Tenuiphantes canariensis</i>	-	TF, LG & LP	104 (28)	E	Ballooners
Araneae	Theridiidae	<i>Theridion musivivum</i>	-	TF, LG, LP & EH	82 (14)	NNE	Ballooners
Araneae	Thomisidae	<i>Xysticus canariensis</i>	-	LG & EH	19 (18)	E	Ballooners

Order	Family	Species	Subspecies	Sampled islands	Sequences	Status	Dispersal
Araneae	Zoropsidae	<i>Zoropsis rufipes</i>	-	TF, LG, LP & EH	84 (34)	NNE	Non-ballooner
Araneae	Araneidae	<i>Zygiella minima</i>	-	TF, LG, LP & EH	114 (37)	NNE	Ballooner
Coleoptera	Curculionidae	<i>Acalles pilula</i>	-	LP & EH	50 (19)	E	Non-winged
Coleoptera	Nitidulidae	<i>Afrogethes canariensis</i>	-	TF, LG & EH	12 (8)	E	Winged
Coleoptera	Scraptiidae	<i>Anaspis proteus</i>	-	TF, LG, LP & EH	168 (161)	NNE	Winged
Coleoptera	Melyridae	<i>Aplocnemus sculpturatus</i>	-	TF, LP & EH	22 (15)	E	Winged
Coleoptera	Staphylinidae	<i>Atheta laeta</i>	-	TF, LG & EH	71 (12)	NNE	Winged
Coleoptera	Staphylinidae	<i>Atheta fungi</i>	-	TF, LG, LP & EH	101 (20)	NNE	Winged
Coleoptera	Ciidae	<i>Atlantocis canariensis</i>	-	TF & LG	36 (11)	E	Non-winged
Coleoptera	Attelabidae	<i>Auletobius anceps</i>	-	TF, LG, LP & EH	48 (42)	E	Winged
Coleoptera	Cerambycidae	<i>Blabinotus spinicollis</i>	-	TF, LG & LP	19 (13)	NNE	Winged
Coleoptera	Curculionidae	<i>Dendroacalles ruteri</i>	-	TF & LP	10 (6)	E	Non-winged
Coleoptera	Carabidae	<i>Dromius angustus</i>	<i>D. angustus plagipennis</i> (EH) & <i>D. angustus dissimilis</i> (LP)	LP & EH	17 (7)	NNE	Winged
Coleoptera	Curculionidae	<i>Echinodera hystrix</i>	<i>E. hystrix hystrix</i> (EH) & <i>E. hystrix benaharita</i> (LP)	LP & EH	36 (15)	E	Non-winged
Coleoptera	Staphylinidae	<i>Gabrius canariensis</i>	-	TF, LG & EH	15 (15)	E	Winged
Coleoptera	Staphylinidae	<i>Heterothops canariensis</i>	-	LG & EH	14 (9)	E	Winged
Coleoptera	Staphylinidae	<i>Holobus chrysopygus</i>	-	TF, LG & LP	9 (7)	NNE	Winged
Coleoptera	Brentidae	<i>Holotrichapion rotundipenne</i>	-	TF, LG, LP & EH	49 (36)	NNE	Winged
Coleoptera	Brentidae	<i>Kalcapion semivittatum</i>	-	TF, LG, LP & EH	80 (18)	NNE	Winged
Coleoptera	Curculionidae	<i>Laparocerus ellipticus</i>	-	TF & LP	33 (16)	E	Non-winged
Coleoptera	Curculionidae	<i>Laparocerus inaequalis</i>	<i>L. inaequalis inaequalis</i> (TF) & <i>L. inaequalis globulipennis</i> (LP)	TF & LP	16 (11)	E	Non-winged

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Order	Family	Species	Subspecies	Sampled islands	Sequences	Status	Dispersal
Coleoptera	Curculionidae	<i>Laparocerus lepidopterus</i>	<i>L. lepidopterus lepidopterus</i> (TF, LG, LP, EH) & <i>L. lepidopterus lepilis</i> (TF)	TF, LG, LP & EH	92 (40)	E	Non-winged
Coleoptera	Curculionidae	<i>Lauriacalles acutus</i>	-	TF & LP	58 (21)	E	Non-winged
Coleoptera	Leiodidae	<i>Leiodes canariensis</i>	-	TF, LG & LP	22 (20)	E	Winged
Coleoptera	Leiodidae	<i>Leiodes oceanica</i>	-	TF & LG	41 (15)	E	Winged
Coleoptera	Curculionidae	<i>Leiosoma apionides</i>	-	LG & LP	29 (3)	E	Non-winged
Coleoptera	Carabidae	<i>Licinopsis oblitterata</i>	<i>L. oblitterata oblitterata</i> (LG) & <i>L. oblitterata franzi</i> (EH)	LG & EH	15 (8)	E	Non-winged
Coleoptera	Chrysomelidae	<i>Longitarsus kleiniiperda</i>	-	TF, LG & EH	38 (18)	E	Winged
Coleoptera	Staphylinidae	<i>Lordithon thoracicus</i>	-	TF, LG & LP	24 (19)	NNE	Non-winged
Coleoptera	Staphylinidae	<i>Megarthus wollastoni</i>	-	TF, LG, LP & EH	77 (62)	NNE	Winged
Coleoptera	Cryptophagidae	<i>Micrambe hesperia</i>	<i>M. hesperia occidentalis</i> (EH) & <i>M. hesperia hesperia</i> (TF, LG, LP)	TF, LG & EH	120 (89)	E	Winged
Coleoptera	Tenebrionidae	<i>Nesotes conformis</i>	<i>N. conformis conformis</i> (TF, EH) & <i>N. conformis turgidicollis</i> (LP)	TF, LP & EH	39 (25)	E	Non-winged
Coleoptera	Tenebrionidae	<i>Nesotes congestus</i>	-	LP & EH	9 (2)	E	Non-winged
Coleoptera	Eucinetidae	<i>Nycteus wollastoni</i>	-	TF, LG & EH	40 (15)	E	Winged
Coleoptera	Ciidae	<i>Octotemnus opacus</i>	-	TF & LP	34 (14)	NNE	Winged
Coleoptera	Staphylinidae	<i>Ocypus subaenescens</i>	-	LG, LP & EH	19 (8)	NNE	Non-winged
Coleoptera	Phalacridae	<i>Olibrus corticalis</i>	-	TF, LG, LP & EH	36 (31)	E	Winged
Coleoptera	Ciidae	<i>Orthocis sagittiferus</i>	-	TF, LG & LP	18 (13)	E	Winged
Coleoptera	Carabidae	<i>Paradromius iucundus</i>	<i>P. iucundus iucundus</i> (LP) & <i>P. iucundus gillerforsi</i> (LG)	LG & LP	10 (5)	E	Non-winged

Order	Family	Species	Subspecies	Sampled islands	Sequences	Status	Dispersal
Coleoptera	Staphylinidae	<i>Philorinum floricola</i>	-	TF, LG, LP & EH	12 (11)	NNE	Winged
Coleoptera	Laemophloeidae	<i>Placonotus granulatus</i>	-	TF, LG & LP	12 (5)	NNE	Winged
Coleoptera	Curculionidae	<i>Pselactus affinis</i>	-	LP & EH	9 (4)	E	Winged
Coleoptera	Staphylinidae	<i>Quedius megalops</i>	-	TF, LG & EH	17 (17)	E	Winged
Coleoptera	Curculionidae	<i>Rhopalomesites persimilis</i>	-	TF & LG	68 (24)	E	Non-winged
Coleoptera	Coccinellidae	<i>Scymnus canariensis</i>	-	TF & LG	11 (4)	E	Winged
Coleoptera	Ptinidae	<i>Stagetus hirtulus</i>	<i>S. hirtulus hirtulus</i> (EH, LG, TF) & <i>S. hirtulus crenatus</i> (LP, TF)	TF, LG, LP & EH	119 (42)	E	Winged
Coleoptera	Staphylinidae	<i>Sunius brevipennis</i>	<i>S. brevipennis brevipennis</i> (EH, TF), <i>S. brevipennis canariensis</i> (EH, LP, TF) & <i>S. brevipennis gomerensis</i> (LG)	TF, LG & EH	23 (15)	E	Non-winged
Coleoptera	Brentidae	<i>Taeniapion delicatulum</i>	-	TF, LG, LP & EH	116 (22)	NNE	Winged
Coleoptera	Zopheridae	<i>Tarphius setosus</i>	-	LG & EH	42 (25)	E	Non-winged
Coleoptera	Carabidae	<i>Trechus flavocinctus</i>	<i>T. flavocinctus flavocinctus</i> (EH, TF) & <i>T. flavocinctus gomeræ</i> (EH, LG)	TF, LG & EH	87 (37)	E	Non-winged
Coleoptera	Nitidulidae	<i>Xenostromylus canariensis</i>	-	TF, LG, LP & EH	85 (75)	E	Winged

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Table S2. Results of workflow Step 1. Global N_{ST} values for each of the 77 species analysed, sorted by order and ID. Statistically significant values of N_{ST} (p value ≤ 0.5) are highlighted in bold.

Order	Species	Nst
Araneae	<i>Araniella maderiana</i>	0.680
Araneae	<i>Cheiracanthium canariense</i>	0.839
Araneae	<i>Cladycnis insignis</i>	0.517
Araneae	<i>Clubiona minor</i>	0.005
Araneae	<i>Cyclosa maderiana</i>	0.408
Araneae	<i>Dysdera silvatica</i>	0.928
Araneae	<i>Echinotheridion gibberosum</i>	0.079
Araneae	<i>Enoplognatha sattleri</i>	0.823
Araneae	<i>Ero tuberculata</i>	0.356
Araneae	<i>Hyptiotes flavidus</i>	0.115
Araneae	<i>Improphantes furcabilis</i>	0.887
Araneae	<i>Improphantes multidentatus</i>	0.253
Araneae	<i>Lathys dentichelis</i>	0.789
Araneae	<i>Macaridion barretti</i>	0.590
Araneae	<i>Macarokeris nidicolens</i>	0.149
Araneae	<i>Macarophaeus varius</i>	0.801
Araneae	<i>Mangora acalypha</i>	0.399
Araneae	<i>Metellina minima</i>	0.764
Araneae	<i>Microlinyphia johnsoni</i>	0.024
Araneae	<i>Misumena spinifera</i>	0.061
Araneae	<i>Olios canariensis</i>	0.969
Araneae	<i>Pulchellodromus wunderlichi</i>	0.000
Araneae	<i>Steatoda nobilis</i>	0.718
Araneae	<i>Tenuiphantes canariensis</i>	0.329
Araneae	<i>Theridion musivivum</i>	0.218
Araneae	<i>Xysticus canariensis</i>	0.599
Araneae	<i>Zoropsis rufipes</i>	0.697
Araneae	<i>Zygiella minima</i>	0.303
Coleoptera	<i>Acalles pilula</i>	0.832
Coleoptera	<i>Afrogethes canariensis</i>	0.487

Order	Species	Nst
Coleoptera	<i>Anaspis proteus</i>	0.604
Coleoptera	<i>Aplocnemus sculpturatus</i>	0.565
Coleoptera	<i>Atheta laeta</i>	0.677
Coleoptera	<i>Atheta fungi</i>	0.302
Coleoptera	<i>Atlantocis canariensis</i>	0.772
Coleoptera	<i>Auletobius anceps</i>	0.439
Coleoptera	<i>Blabinotus spinicollis</i>	0.706
Coleoptera	<i>Dendroacalles ruteri</i>	0.638
Coleoptera	<i>Dromius angustus</i>	0.733
Coleoptera	<i>Echinodera hystrix</i>	0.622
Coleoptera	<i>Gabrius canariensis</i>	0.062
Coleoptera	<i>Heterothops canariensis</i>	0.843
Coleoptera	<i>Holobus chrysopygus</i>	0.887
Coleoptera	<i>Holotrichapion rotundipenne</i>	0.178
Coleoptera	<i>Kalcapion semivittatum</i>	0.146
Coleoptera	<i>Laparocerus ellipticus</i>	0.628
Coleoptera	<i>Laparocerus inaequalis</i>	0.541
Coleoptera	<i>Laparocerus lepidopterus</i>	0.501
Coleoptera	<i>Lauriacalles acutus</i>	0.837
Coleoptera	<i>Leiodes canariensis</i>	0.867
Coleoptera	<i>Leiodes oceanica</i>	0.959
Coleoptera	<i>Leiosoma apionides</i>	0.982
Coleoptera	<i>Licinopsis obliterated</i>	0.892
Coleoptera	<i>Longitarsus kleiniiperda</i>	0.040
Coleoptera	<i>Lordithon thoracicus</i>	0.736
Coleoptera	<i>Megarthus wollastoni</i>	0.049
Coleoptera	<i>Micrambe hesperia</i>	0.892
Coleoptera	<i>Nesotes conformis</i>	0.805
Coleoptera	<i>Nesotes congestus</i>	1.000
Coleoptera	<i>Nycteus wollastoni</i>	0.150
Coleoptera	<i>Octotemnus opacus</i>	0.893
Coleoptera	<i>Ocypus subaenescens</i>	0.642

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Order	Species	Nst
Coleoptera	<i>Olibrus corticalis</i>	0.528
Coleoptera	<i>Orthocis sagittiferus</i>	0.834
Coleoptera	<i>Paradromius iucundus</i>	0.922
Coleoptera	<i>Philorinum floricola</i>	0.167
Coleoptera	<i>Placonotus granulatus</i>	0.713
Coleoptera	<i>Pselactus affinis</i>	0.929
Coleoptera	<i>Quedius megalops</i>	0.601
Coleoptera	<i>Rhopalomesites persimilis</i>	0.624
Coleoptera	<i>Scymnus canariensis</i>	0.000
Coleoptera	<i>Stagetus hirtulus</i>	0.757
Coleoptera	<i>Sunius brevipennis</i>	0.452
Coleoptera	<i>Taeniapion delicatulum</i>	0.589
Coleoptera	<i>Tarphius setosus</i>	0.800
Coleoptera	<i>Trechus flavocinctus</i>	0.414
Coleoptera	<i>Xenostromylus canariensis</i>	0.333

Table S3. Results of workflow Step 2a. Species from Step 1 with significant N_{ST} are analysed in Step 2a. Significant N_{ST} values are highlighted in bold. Significant island comparisons go to Step 2b, while non-significant comparisons go directly to Step 3a. Unsampled or unoccupied islands are indicated with "---". Sample sizes too small for analysis are indicated with "***".

Order	Species	TF vs ALL	LG vs ALL	LP vs ALL	EH vs ALL
Araneae	<i>Araniella maderiana</i>	0.187	0.419	0.576	0.572
Araneae	<i>Cheiracanthium canariense</i>	0.538	0.661	0.526	0.651
Araneae	<i>Cladycnis insignis</i>	0.302	0.383	0.540	0.099
Araneae	<i>Cyclosa maderiana</i>	0.254	0.022	0.472	0.254
Araneae	<i>Echinotheridion gibberosum</i>	0.098	0.061	0.041	0.051
Araneae	<i>Enoplognatha sattleri</i>	0.691	0.501	0.654	0.670
Araneae	<i>Ero tuberculata</i>	0.026	0.066	0.238	0.480
Araneae	<i>Improphantes furcabilis</i>	0.918	0.250	0.158	---
Araneae	<i>Lathys denticchelis</i>	0.880	0.718	0.509	0.557
Araneae	<i>Macaridion barretti</i>	0.095	0.371	0.685	0.352
Araneae	<i>Macarophaeus varius</i>	0.374	0.861	0.250	0.257
Araneae	<i>Mangora acalypha</i>	0.191	0.140	0.512	0.013
Araneae	<i>Metellina minima</i>	0.564	0.431	0.741	---
Araneae	<i>Olios canariensis</i>	0.851	0.651	0.694	---
Araneae	<i>Steatoda nobilis</i>	0.248	0.141	0.584	0.699
Araneae	<i>Tenuiphantes canariensis</i>	0.418	0.171	0.450	---
Araneae	<i>Theridion musivivum</i>	0.106	0.166	0.086	0.197
Araneae	<i>Xysticus canariensis</i>	---	0.599	---	0.599
Araneae	<i>Zoropsis rufipes</i>	0.554	0.648	0.644	0.329
Araneae	<i>Zygiella minima</i>	0.072	0.161	0.360	0.137
Coleoptera	<i>Acalles pilula</i>	---	---	0.832	0.832
Coleoptera	<i>Afrogethes canariensis</i>	0.288	0.249	---	0.509
Coleoptera	<i>Anaspis proteus</i>	0.538	0.332	0.252	0.500
Coleoptera	<i>Aplocnemus sculpturatus</i>	0.481	---	0.554	***
Coleoptera	<i>Atheta laeta</i>	0.511	0.335	---	0.650
Coleoptera	<i>Atheta fungi</i>	0.049	0.094	0.515	0.090
Coleoptera	<i>Atlantocis canariensis</i>	0.772	0.772	---	---
Coleoptera	<i>Auletobius anceps</i>	0.086	0.567	0.097	0.170
Coleoptera	<i>Blabinotus spinicollis</i>	0.543	***	0.663	---
Coleoptera	<i>Dendroacalles ruteri</i>	0.638	---	0.638	---
Coleoptera	<i>Dromius angustus</i>	---	---	0.733	0.733
Coleoptera	<i>Echinodera hystrix</i>	---	---	0.622	0.622
Coleoptera	<i>Heterothops canariensis</i>	---	0.843	---	0.843
Coleoptera	<i>Holobus chrysopygus</i>	0.725	***	0.743	---
Coleoptera	<i>Holotrichapion rotundipenne</i>	0.129	0.020	0.132	0.186
Coleoptera	<i>Kalcapion semivittatum</i>	0.007	0.042	0.236	0.011
Coleoptera	<i>Laparocerus ellipticus</i>	0.628	---	0.628	---
Coleoptera	<i>Laparocerus inaequalis</i>	0.541	---	0.541	---
Coleoptera	<i>Laparocerus lepidopterus</i>	0.344	0.558	0.166	0.163

Chapter II

Order	Species	TF vs ALL	LG vs ALL	LP vs ALL	EH vs ALL
Coleoptera	<i>Lauriacalles acutus</i>	0.837	---	0.837	---
Coleoptera	<i>Leiodes canariensis</i>	0.786	0.704	0.508	---
Coleoptera	<i>Leiodes oceanica</i>	0.959	0.959	---	---
Coleoptera	<i>Leiosoma apionides</i>	---	0.982	0.982	---
Coleoptera	<i>Licinopsis oblitterata</i>	---	0.892	---	0.892
Coleoptera	<i>Lordithon thoracicus</i>	0.565	0.527	0.727	---
Coleoptera	<i>Micrambe hesperia</i>	0.789	0.652	---	0.808
Coleoptera	<i>Nesotes conformis</i>	0.585	---	0.728	0.640
Coleoptera	<i>Nesotes congestus</i>	---	---	1.000	1.000
Coleoptera	<i>Nycteus wollastoni</i>	0.059	0.157	---	0.164
Coleoptera	<i>Octotemnus opacus</i>	0.893	---	0.893	---
Coleoptera	<i>Ocypus subaenescens</i>	---	***	0.603	0.586
Coleoptera	<i>Olibrus corticalis</i>	0.543	0.542	0.012	0.392
Coleoptera	<i>Orthocis sagittiferus</i>	0.616	0.692	0.583	---
Coleoptera	<i>Paradromius iucundus</i>	---	0.922	0.922	---
Coleoptera	<i>Placonotus granulatus</i>	0.238	0.220	0.717	---
Coleoptera	<i>Pselactus affinis</i>	---	---	0.929	0.929
Coleoptera	<i>Quedius megalops</i>	***	0.174	---	0.504
Coleoptera	<i>Rhopalomesites persimilis</i>	0.624	0.624	---	---
Coleoptera	<i>Stagetus hirtulus</i>	0.635	0.620	0.576	0.136
Coleoptera	<i>Sunius brevipennis</i>	0.395	0.438	---	***
Coleoptera	<i>Taeniapion delicatulum</i>	0.778	0.284	0.216	0.564
Coleoptera	<i>Tarphius setosus</i>	---	0.800	---	0.800
Coleoptera	<i>Trechus flavocinctus</i>	0.001	0.188	---	0.538
Coleoptera	<i>Xenostromylus canariensis</i>	0.053	0.014	0.495	0.049

Table S4. Results of workflow Step 2b. Island populations from Step 2a with significant N_{ST} differentiation them from all other islands are assessed in Step 2b for monophyly. Monophyletic island populations are highlighted in bold. Unsampled or unoccupied islands are indicated with "---". Island populations with non-significant N_{ST} values in Step 2a are indicated with "*".

Order	Species	TF	LG	LP	EH
Araneae	<i>Araniella maderiana</i>	*	NO	NO	NO
Araneae	<i>Cheiracanthium canariense</i>	YES	YES	NO	YES
Araneae	<i>Cladycnis insignis</i>	NO	NO	YES	NO
Araneae	<i>Cyclosa maderiana</i>	NO	*	NO	NO
Araneae	<i>Echinotheridion gibberosum</i>	NO	NO	*	*
Araneae	<i>Enoplognatha sattleri</i>	YES	*	NO	NO
Araneae	<i>Ero tuberculata</i>	*	*	NO	YES
Araneae	<i>Improphantes furcabilis</i>	YES	NO	*	---
Araneae	<i>Lathys dentichelis</i>	YES	NO	NO	NO
Araneae	<i>Macaridion barretti</i>	*	NO	NO	NO
Araneae	<i>Macarophaeus varius</i>	NO	YES	NO	NO
Araneae	<i>Mangora acalypha</i>	*	*	NO	*
Araneae	<i>Metellina minima</i>	YES	NO	YES	---
Araneae	<i>Olios canariensis</i>	YES	YES	YES	---
Araneae	<i>Steatoda nobilis</i>	NO	NO	YES	YES
Araneae	<i>Tenuiphantes canariensis</i>	NO	NO	NO	---
Araneae	<i>Theridion musivivum</i>	NO	NO	*	NO
Araneae	<i>Xysticus canariensis</i>	---	YES	---	YES
Araneae	<i>Zoropsis rufipes</i>	YES	NO	YES	NO
Araneae	<i>Zygiella minima</i>	NO	NO	NO	NO
Coleoptera	<i>Acalles pilula</i>	---	---	YES	YES
Coleoptera	<i>Afrogethes canariensis</i>	*	NO	---	YES
Coleoptera	<i>Anaspis proteus</i>	YES	YES	NO	YES
Coleoptera	<i>Aplocnemus sculpturatus</i>	YES	---	YES	---
Coleoptera	<i>Atheta laeta</i>	NO	NO	---	NO
Coleoptera	<i>Atheta fungi</i>	NO	NO	NO	NO
Coleoptera	<i>Atlantocis canariensis</i>	YES	YES	---	---
Coleoptera	<i>Auletobius anceps</i>	NO	YES	NO	NO
Coleoptera	<i>Blabinotus spinicollis</i>	YES	---	YES	---

Chapter II

Order	Species	TF	LG	LP	EH
Coleoptera	<i>Dendroacalles ruteri</i>	YES	---	YES	---
Coleoptera	<i>Dromius angustus</i>	---	---	YES	YES
Coleoptera	<i>Echinodera hystrix</i>	---	---	YES	YES
Coleoptera	<i>Heterothops canariensis</i>	---	YES	---	YES
Coleoptera	<i>Holobus chrysopygus</i>	YES	---	YES	---
Coleoptera	<i>Holotrichapion rotundipenne</i>	NO	*	*	NO
Coleoptera	<i>Kalcapion semivittatum</i>	*	*	NO	*
Coleoptera	<i>Laparocerus ellipticus</i>	YES	---	YES	---
Coleoptera	<i>Laparocerus inaequalis</i>	YES	---	YES	---
Coleoptera	<i>Laparocerus lepidopterus</i>	NO	YES	NO	NO
Coleoptera	<i>Lauriacalles acutus</i>	YES	---	YES	---
Coleoptera	<i>Leiodes canariensis</i>	YES	YES	YES	---
Coleoptera	<i>Leiodes oceanica</i>	YES	YES	---	---
Coleoptera	<i>Leiosoma apionides</i>	---	YES	YES	---
Coleoptera	<i>Licinopsis obliterated</i>	---	YES	---	YES
Coleoptera	<i>Lordithon thoracicus</i>	YES	*	YES	---
Coleoptera	<i>Micrambe hesperia</i>	YES	YES	---	YES
Coleoptera	<i>Nesotes conformis</i>	NO	---	YES	YES
Coleoptera	<i>Nesotes congestus</i>	---	---	YES	YES
Coleoptera	<i>Nycteus wollastoni</i>	*	NO	---	NO
Coleoptera	<i>Octotemnus opacus</i>	YES	---	YES	---
Coleoptera	<i>Ocypus subaenescens</i>	---	---	YES	YES
Coleoptera	<i>Olibrus corticalis</i>	NO	NO	*	NO
Coleoptera	<i>Orthocis sagittiferus</i>	YES	YES	YES	---
Coleoptera	<i>Paradromius iucundus</i>	---	YES	YES	---
Coleoptera	<i>Placonotus granulatus</i>	*	*	YES	---
Coleoptera	<i>Pselactus affinis</i>	---	---	YES	YES
Coleoptera	<i>Quedius megalops</i>	---	YES	---	YES
Coleoptera	<i>Rhopalomesites persimilis</i>	YES	YES	---	---
Coleoptera	<i>Stagetus hirtulus</i>	YES	NO	NO	NO
Coleoptera	<i>Sunius brevipennis</i>	NO	NO	---	---
Coleoptera	<i>Taeniapion delicatulum</i>	NO	NO	NO	NO

Order	Species	TF	LG	LP	EH
Coleoptera	<i>Tarphius setosus</i>	---	YES	---	YES
Coleoptera	<i>Trechus flavocinctus</i>	*	NO	---	NO
Coleoptera	<i>Xenostrogylus canariensis</i>	NO	*	NO	NO

Table S5. Results of workflow Step 3a. Pairwise island-island N_{ST} comparison for the 36 species with island populations without significant N_{ST} values in Step 2a or non-monophyletic populations in Step 2b. In bold are highlighted pairwise comparisons with significant N_{ST} . Unsampled or unoccupied islands are indicated with "---". Island populations where N_{ST} calculation was not necessary since the rest of the islands were monophyletic are indicated with "*". Island populations that had a paraphyletic pattern are indicated with "***".

Order	Species	TF LG	TF LP	TF EH	LG TF	LG LP	LG EH	LP TF	LP LG	LP EH	EH TF	EH LG	EH LP
Araneae	<i>Araniella maderiana</i>	0.132	0.665	0.799	0.132	0.688	0.814	0.665	0.688	0.550	0.799	0.814	0.550
Araneae	<i>Cheiracanthium canariense</i>	---	---	---	---	---	---	***	***	***	---	---	---
Araneae	<i>Cladycnis insignis</i>	0.508	---	0.117	0.508	---	0.404	---	---	---	0.117	0.404	---
Araneae	<i>Cyclosa maderiana</i>	0.172	0.600	0.000	0.172	0.286	0.171	0.600	0.286	0.600	0.000	0.171	0.600
Araneae	<i>Echinotheridion gibberosum</i>	0.088	0.105	0.126	0.105	0.018	0.042	0.088	0.018	0.042	0.126	0.042	0.042
Araneae	<i>Enoplognatha sattleri</i>	---	---	---	---	0.921	0.803	---	0.921	0.074	---	0.803	0.074
Araneae	<i>Ero tuberculata</i>	0.041	0.093	---	0.041	0.243	---	0.093	0.243	---	---	---	---
Araneae	<i>Improphantes furcabilis</i>	---	---	---	---	0.077	---	---	0.077	---	---	---	---
Araneae	<i>Lathys dentichelis</i>	---	---	---	---	0.351	0.291	---	0.351	0.174	---	0.291	0.174
Araneae	<i>Macaridion barretti</i>	0.153	0.607	0.207	0.153	0.740	0.370	0.607	0.740	0.820	0.207	0.370	0.820
Araneae	<i>Macarophaeus varius</i>	---	0.318	0.361	---	---	---	0.318	---	0.265	0.361	---	0.265
Araneae	<i>Mangora acalypha</i>	0.028	0.858	0.205	0.028	0.639	0.082	0.028	0.639	0.283	0.205	0.082	0.283
Araneae	<i>Metellina minima</i>	---	---	---	***	***	***	---	---	---	---	---	---
Araneae	<i>Steatoda nobilis</i>	0.008	---	---	0.008	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
Araneae	<i>Tenuiphantes canariensis</i>	0.309	0.540	---	0.309	0.103	---	0.540	0.103	---	---	---	---
Araneae	<i>Theridion musivivum</i>	0.236	0.047	0.018	0.236	0.045	0.381	0.047	0.045	0.332	0.018	0.381	0.332
Araneae	<i>Zoropsis rufipes</i>	---	---	---	---	---	0.486	---	---	---	---	0.486	---
Araneae	<i>Zygiella minima</i>	0.120	0.385	0.167	0.120	0.455	0.301	0.385	0.455	0.282	0.167	0.301	0.282

Chapter II

Order	Species	TF LG	TF LP	TF EH	LG TF	LG LP	LG EH	LP TF	LP LG	LP EH	EH TF	EH LG	EH LP
Coleoptera	<i>Afrogethes canariensis</i>	0.280	---	---	0.280	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
Coleoptera	<i>Anaspis proteus</i>	---	---	---	---	---	---	***	***	***	---	---	---
Coleoptera	<i>Atheta laeta</i>	0.615	---	0.705	0.615	---	0.670	---	---	---	0.705	0.670	---
Coleoptera	<i>Atheta fungi</i>	0.025	0.509	0.151	0.025	0.592	0.154	0.509	0.592	0.202	0.151	0.154	0.202
Coleoptera	<i>Auletobius anceps</i>	---	0.131	0.182	---	---	---	0.131	---	0.147	0.182	---	0.147
Coleoptera	<i>Holotrichapion rotundipenne</i>	0.091	0.307	0.347	0.091	0.077	0.127	0.307	0.077	0.100	0.347	0.127	0.100
Coleoptera	<i>Kalcapion semivittatum</i>	0.007	0.218	0.016	0.007	0.314	0.011	0.218	0.314	0.179	0.016	0.011	0.179
Coleoptera	<i>Laparocerus lepidopterus</i>	---	0.357	0.423	---	---	---	0.357	---	0.152	0.423	---	0.152
Coleoptera	<i>Lordithon thoracicus</i>	---	---	---	*	*	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
Coleoptera	<i>Nesotes conformis</i>	***	---	***	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
Coleoptera	<i>Nycteus wollastoni</i>	0.127	---	0.054	0.127	---	0.288	---	---	---	0.054	0.288	---
Coleoptera	<i>Olibrus corticalis</i>	0.334	0.609	0.669	0.334	0.562	0.640	0.609	0.562	0.089	0.669	0.640	0.089
Coleoptera	<i>Placonotus granulatus</i>	0.333	---	---	0.333	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
Coleoptera	<i>Stagetus hirtulus</i>	---	---	---	---	0.922	0.546	---	0.922	0.484	---	0.546	0.484
Coleoptera	<i>Sunius brevipennis</i>	0.452	---	---	0.452	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
Coleoptera	<i>Taeniapion delicatulum</i>	0.467	0.722	0.878	0.467	0.140	0.518	0.722	0.140	0.441	0.878	0.518	0.441
Coleoptera	<i>Trechus flavocinctus</i>	0.031	---	0.457	0.031	---	0.563	---	---	---	0.457	0.563	---
Coleoptera	<i>Xenostromylylus canariensis</i>	0.007	0.516	0.042	0.007	0.460	0.069	0.516	0.460	0.501	0.042	0.069	0.501

Table S6. Results of workflow Step 3b. Island populations analysed in Step 3a are assessed for monophyly. Monophyletic populations are highlighted in bold. If all populations are not monophyletic, then the species are composed of a single type 1 ESU. Unsampled or unoccupied islands are indicated with "---". Type 2 ESUs delimited in previous steps are indicated with "**".

Order	Species	TF	LG	LP	EH
Araneae	<i>Araniella maderiana</i>	NO	NO	NO	NO
Araneae	<i>Cheiracanthium canariense</i>	*	*	Paraphyletic population	*
Araneae	<i>Cladycnis insignis</i>	YES TF+LG+EH		*	YES TF+LG+EH
Araneae	<i>Cyclosa maderiana</i>	NO	NO	NO	NO
Araneae	<i>Echinotheridion gibberosum</i>	NO	NO	NO	NO
Araneae	<i>Enoplognatha sattleri</i>	*	YES	YES	
Araneae	<i>Ero tuberculata</i>	YES			*
Araneae	<i>Improphantes furcabilis</i>	*	YES		---
Araneae	<i>Lathys dentichelis</i>	*	YES		
Araneae	<i>Macaridion barretti</i>	NO	NO	NO	NO
Araneae	<i>Macarophaeus varius</i>	YES TF+LP+EH	*	YES TF+LP+EH	
Araneae	<i>Mangora acalypha</i>	NO	NO	NO	NO
Araneae	<i>Metellina minima</i>	*	Paraphyletic population	*	---
Araneae	<i>Steatoda nobilis</i>	YES		*	*
Araneae	<i>Tenuiphantes canariensis</i>	NO	NO	NO	---
Araneae	<i>Theridion musivivum</i>	NO	NO	NO	NO
Araneae	<i>Zoropsis rufipes</i>	*	YES LG+EH	*	YES LG+EH
Araneae	<i>Zygiella minima</i>	NO	NO	NO	NO
Coleoptera	<i>Afrogethes canariensis</i>	YES		---	*
Coleoptera	<i>Anaspis proteus</i>	*	*	Paraphyletic population	*
Coleoptera	<i>Atheta laeta</i>	NO	NO	---	NO
Coleoptera	<i>Atheta fungi</i>	NO	NO	NO	NO
Coleoptera	<i>Auletobius anceps</i>	YES TF+LP+EH	*	YES TF+LP+EH	

Chapter II

Order	Species	TF	LG	LP	EH
Coleoptera	<i>Holotrichapion rotundipenne</i>	NO	NO	NO	NO
Coleoptera	<i>Kalcapion semivittatum</i>	NO	NO	NO	NO
Coleoptera	<i>Laparocerus lepidopterus</i>	YES TF+LP+EH	*	YES TF+LP+EH	
Coleoptera	<i>Lordithon thoracicus</i>	*	YES	*	---
Coleoptera	<i>Nesotes conformis</i>	Paraphyletic population	---	*	*
Coleoptera	<i>Nycteus wollastoni</i>	NO	NO	---	NO
Coleoptera	<i>Olibrus corticalis</i>	YES		YES	
Coleoptera	<i>Placonotus granulatus</i>	YES		*	---
Coleoptera	<i>Stagetus hirtulus</i>	*	YES		
Coleoptera	<i>Sunius brevipennis</i>	NO	NO	---	---
Coleoptera	<i>Taeniapion delicatulum</i>	NO	NO	NO	NO
Coleoptera	<i>Trechus flavocinctus</i>	NO	NO	---	NO
Coleoptera	<i>Xenostrogylus canariensis</i>	NO	NO	NO	NO

Table S7. Categorisation of type 2 ESUs as indicative of either (A) early stage inter-island differentiation, where divergences are consistent with expectations for intraspecific variation, (B) incipient or species-level differentiation, with divergences above the intraspecific threshold, but below the conservative interspecific threshold, or (C) species-level differentiation, with divergences higher than the conservative interspecific threshold. Uncorrected p-distance divergences to the most closely related sequence of another ESU are shown. Species containing paraphyletic populations used to obtain the closest genetic divergences are indicated with “*”.

Order	Species	Delimited ESUs (island/s and divergence)		
Araneae	<i>Cheiracanthium canariense</i> *	TF B: 1.73%	LG B: 2.07%	EH A: 0.17%
Araneae	<i>Cladycnis insignis</i>	TF+LG+EH A: 0.88%		LP A: 0.88%
Araneae	<i>Enoplognatha sattleri</i>	TF A: 1.14%	LG A: 1.14%	LP+EH B: 2.85%
Araneae	<i>Ero tuberculata</i>	TF+LG+LP A: 0.20%		EH A: 0.20%
Araneae	<i>Improphantes furcabilis</i>	TF B: 5.49%		LG+LP B: 5.49%
Araneae	<i>Lathys dentichelis</i>	TF B: 3.66%		LG+LP+EH B: 3.66%
Araneae	<i>Macarophaeus varius</i>	TF+LP+EH A: 1.12%		LG A: 1.12%
Araneae	<i>Metellina minima</i> *	TF A: 0.17%		LP A: 0.48%
Araneae	<i>Olios canariensis</i>	TF C: 8.23%	LG B: 4.12%	LP B: 4.12%
Araneae	<i>Steatoda nobilis</i>	TF+LG B: 1.80%	LP B: 1.80%	EH B: 1.80%
Araneae	<i>Xysticus canariensis</i>	LG B: 1.93%		EH B: 1.93%
Araneae	<i>Zoropsis rufipes</i>	TF B: 4.31%	LG+EH B: 3.00%	LP B: 3.00%
Coleoptera	<i>Acalles pilula</i>	LP B: 1.93%		EH B: 1.93%
Coleoptera	<i>Afrogethes canariensis</i>	TF+LG A: 0.91%		EH A: 0.91%
Coleoptera	<i>Anaspis proteus</i> *	TF B: 1.95%	LG A: 0.84%	EH B: 2.09%
Coleoptera	<i>Aplocnemus sculpturatus</i>	TF B: 3.24%		LP B: 3.24%
Coleoptera	<i>Atlantocis canariensis</i>	TF A: 0.76%		LG A: 0.76%
Coleoptera	<i>Auletobius anceps</i>	TF+LP+EH A: 0.80%		LG A: 0.80%
Coleoptera	<i>Blabinotus spinicollis</i>	TF A: 0.66%		LP A: 0.66%
Coleoptera	<i>Dendroacalles ruteri</i>	TF A: 0.67%		LP A: 0.67%
Coleoptera	<i>Dromius angustus</i>	LP A: 0.65%		EH A: 0.65%
Coleoptera	<i>Echinodera hystrix</i>	LP B: 2.07%		EH B: 2.07%
Coleoptera	<i>Heterothops canariensis</i>	LG B: 1.77%		EH B: 1.77%
Coleoptera	<i>Holobus chrysopygus</i>	TF B: 1.82%		LP B: 1.82%

Chapter II

Order	Species	Delimited ESUs (island/s and divergence)		
Coleoptera	<i>Laparocerus ellipticus</i>	TF A: 0.80%		LP A: 0.80%
Coleoptera	<i>Laparocerus inaequalis</i>	TF B: 1.70%		LP B: 1.70%
Coleoptera	<i>Laparocerus lepidopterus</i>	TF+LP+EH B: 1.73%		LG B: 1.73%
Coleoptera	<i>Lauriacalles acutus</i>	TF B: 2.25%		LP B: 2.25%
Coleoptera	<i>Leiodes canariensis</i>	TF B: 2.19%	LG B: 2.06%	LP B: 2.06%
Coleoptera	<i>Leiodes oceanica</i>	TF B: 7.63%		LG B: 7.63%
Coleoptera	<i>Leiosoma apionides</i>	LG B: 2.83%		LP B: 2.83%
Coleoptera	<i>Licinopsis oblitterata</i>	LG B: 2.77%		EH B: 2.77%
Coleoptera	<i>Lordithon thoracicus</i>	TF B: 1.69%	LG B: 1.69%	LP B: 1.82%
Coleoptera	<i>Micrambe hesperia</i>	TF C: 8.15%	LG B: 6.52%	EH B: 6.52%
Coleoptera	<i>Nesotes conformis*</i>	LP B: 2.27%		EH B: 2.41%
Coleoptera	<i>Nesotes congestus</i>	LP B: 3.05%		EH B: 3.05%
Coleoptera	<i>Octotemnus opacus</i>	TF A: 1.24%		LP A: 1.24%
Coleoptera	<i>Ocypus subaenescens</i>	LP A: 0.38%		EH A: 0.38%
Coleoptera	<i>Olibrus corticalis</i>	TF+LG A: 0.90%		LP+EH A: 0.90%
Coleoptera	<i>Orthocis sagittiferus</i>	TF B: 1.77%	LG A: 1.39%	LP A: 1.39%
Coleoptera	<i>Paradromius iucundus</i>	LG B: 2.13%		LP B: 2.13%
Coleoptera	<i>Placonotus granulatus</i>	TF+LG B: 1.71%		LP B: 1.71%
Coleoptera	<i>Pselactus affinis</i>	LP A: 1.41%		EH A: 1.41%
Coleoptera	<i>Quedius megalops</i>	LG A: 0.64%		EH A: 0.64%
Coleoptera	<i>Rhopalomesites persimilis</i>	TF B: 1.70%		LG B: 1.70%
Coleoptera	<i>Stagetus hirtulus</i>	TF B: 5.23%		LG+LP+EH B: 5.23%
Coleoptera	<i>Tarphius setosus</i>	LG B: 2.39%		EH B: 2.39%

Table S8. Summary of the delimited ESUs for each species tested throughout the workflow. Sorted by order and species. NNE means “native non-endemic” while E refers to “endemic species”. “Sampled distribution” column does not include low sample populations indicated in Table S3 or paraphyletic populations indicated in Table S6.

Order	Species	Sampled distribution	Status	Number identified ESUs	ESUs type
Araneae	<i>Araniella maderiana</i>	TF, LG, LP & EH	NNE	1	All populations conform a type 1 ESU
Araneae	<i>Cheiracanthium canariense</i>	TF, LG & EH	NNE	3	Three type 2 ESUs: one per island
Araneae	<i>Cladycnis insignis</i>	TF, LG, LP & EH	E	2	Two type 2 ESUs: LP and TF+LG+EH
Araneae	<i>Clubiona minor</i>	TF, LG, LP & EH	E	1	All populations conform a type 1 ESU
Araneae	<i>Cyclosa maderiana</i>	TF, LG, LP & EH	NNE	1	All populations conform a type 1 ESU
Araneae	<i>Dysdera silvatica</i>	LG & EH	E	1	All populations conform a type 1 ESU
Araneae	<i>Echinotheridion gibberosum</i>	TF, LG, LP & EH	NNE	1	All populations conform a type 1 ESU
Araneae	<i>Enoplognatha sattleri</i>	TF, LG, LP & EH	NNE	3	Three type 2 ESUs: TF, LG and LP+EH
Araneae	<i>Ero tuberculata</i>	TF, LG, LP & EH	NNE	2	Two type 2 ESUs: EH and TF+LG+LP
Araneae	<i>Hyptiotes flavidus</i>	TF, LG, LP & EH	NNE	1	All populations conform a type 1 ESU
Araneae	<i>Improphantes furcabilis</i>	TF, LG & LP	E	2	Two type 2 ESUs: TF and LG+LP
Araneae	<i>Improphantes multidentatus</i>	TF, LG & EH	E	1	All populations conform a type 1 ESU
Araneae	<i>Lathys dentichelis</i>	TF, LG, LP & EH	NNE	2	Two type 2 ESUs: TF and LG+LP+EH
Araneae	<i>Macaridion barretti</i>	TF, LG, LP & EH	NNE	1	All populations conform a type 1 ESU
Araneae	<i>Macaroeris nidicolens</i>	TF, LG, LP & EH	NNE	1	All populations conform a type 1 ESU
Araneae	<i>Macarophaeus varius</i>	TF, LG, LP & EH	E	2	Two type 2 ESUs: LG and TF+LP+EH
Araneae	<i>Mangora acalypha</i>	TF, LG, LP & EH	NNE	1	All populations conform a type 1 ESU
Araneae	<i>Metellina minima</i>	TF & LP	E	2	Two type 2 ESUs: one per island

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Order	Species	Sampled distribution	Status	Number identified ESUs	ESUs type
Araneae	<i>Microlinyphia johnsoni</i>	TF, LG, LP & EH	NNE	1	All populations conform a type 1 ESU
Araneae	<i>Misumena spinifera</i>	LG, LP & EH	NNE	1	All populations conform a type 1 ESU
Araneae	<i>Olios canariensis</i>	TF, LG & LP	E	3	Three type 2 ESUs: one per island
Araneae	<i>Pulchellodromus wunderlichi</i>	TF, LG, LP & EH	E	1	All populations conform a type 1 ESU
Araneae	<i>Steatoda nobilis</i>	TF, LG, LP & EH	NNE	3	Three type 2 ESUs: LP, EH and TF+LG
Araneae	<i>Tenuiphantes canariensis</i>	TF, LG & LP	E	1	All populations conform a type 1 ESU
Araneae	<i>Theridion musivivum</i>	TF, LG, LP & EH	NNE	1	All populations conform a type 1 ESU
Araneae	<i>Xysticus canariensis</i>	LG & EH	E	2	Two type 2 ESUs: one per island
Araneae	<i>Zoropsis rufipes</i>	TF, LG, LP & EH	NNE	3	Three type 2 ESUs: TF, LP and LG+EH
Araneae	<i>Zygiella minima</i>	TF, LG, LP & EH	NNE	1	All populations conform a type 1 ESU
Coleoptera	<i>Acalles pilula</i>	LP & EH	E	2	Two type 2 ESUs: one per island
Coleoptera	<i>Afrogethes canariensis</i>	TF, LG & EH	E	2	Two type 2 ESUs: EH and TF+LG
Coleoptera	<i>Anaspis proteus</i>	TF, LG & EH	NNE	3	Three type 2 ESUs: one per island
Coleoptera	<i>Aplocnemus sculpturatus</i>	TF & LP	E	2	Two type 2 ESUs: one per island
Coleoptera	<i>Atheta laeta</i>	TF, LG & EH	NNE	1	All populations conform a type 1 ESU
Coleoptera	<i>Atheta fungi</i>	TF, LG, LP & EH	NNE	1	All populations conform a type 1 ESU
Coleoptera	<i>Atlantocis canariensis</i>	TF & LG	E	2	Two type 2 ESUs: one per island
Coleoptera	<i>Auletobius anceps</i>	TF, LG, LP & EH	E	2	Two type 2 ESUs: LG and TF+LP+EH
Coleoptera	<i>Blabinotus spinicollis</i>	TF & LP	NNE	2	Two type 2 ESUs: one per island
Coleoptera	<i>Dendroacalles ruteri</i>	TF & LP	E	2	Two type 2 ESUs: one per island

Order	Species	Sampled distribution	Status	Number identified ESUs	ESUs type
Coleoptera	<i>Dromius angustus</i>	LP & EH	NNE	2	Two type 2 ESUs: one per island
Coleoptera	<i>Echinodera hystrix</i>	LP & EH	E	2	Two type 2 ESUs: one per island
Coleoptera	<i>Gabrius canariensis</i>	TF, LG & EH	E	1	All populations conform a type 1 ESU
Coleoptera	<i>Heterothops canariensis</i>	LG & EH	E	2	Two type 2 ESUs: one per island
Coleoptera	<i>Holobus chrysopygus</i>	TF & LP	NNE	2	Two type 2 ESUs: one per island
Coleoptera	<i>Holotrichapion rotundipenne</i>	TF, LG, LP & EH	NNE	1	All populations conform a type 1 ESU
Coleoptera	<i>Kalcapion semivittatum</i>	TF, LG, LP & EH	NNE	1	All populations conform a type 1 ESU
Coleoptera	<i>Laparocerus ellipticus</i>	TF & LP	E	2	Two type 2 ESUs: one per island
Coleoptera	<i>Laparocerus inaequalis</i>	TF & LP	E	2	Two type 2 ESUs: one per island
Coleoptera	<i>Laparocerus lepidopterus</i>	TF, LG, LP & EH	E	2	Two ESUs: LG and TF+LP+EH
Coleoptera	<i>Lauriacalles acutus</i>	TF & LP	E	2	Two type 2 ESUs: one per island
Coleoptera	<i>Leiodes canariensis</i>	TF, LG & LP	E	3	Three type 2 ESUs: one per island
Coleoptera	<i>Leiodes oceanica</i>	TF & LG	E	2	Two type 2 ESUs: one per island
Coleoptera	<i>Leiosoma apionides</i>	LG & LP	E	2	Two type 2 ESUs: one per island
Coleoptera	<i>Licinopsis oblitterata</i>	LG & EH	E	2	Two type 2 ESUs: one per island
Coleoptera	<i>Longitarsus kleiniiperda</i>	TF, LG & EH	E	1	All populations conform a type 1 ESU
Coleoptera	<i>Lordithon thoracicus</i>	TF, LG & LP	NNE	3	Three type 2 ESUs: one per island
Coleoptera	<i>Megarthus wollastoni</i>	TF, LG, LP & EH	NNE	1	All populations conform a type 1 ESU
Coleoptera	<i>Micrambe hesperia</i>	TF, LG & EH	E	3	Three type 2 ESUs: one per island
Coleoptera	<i>Nesotes conformis</i>	LP & EH	E	2	Two type 2 ESUs: one per island

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Order	Species	Sampled distribution	Status	Number identified ESUs	ESUs type
Coleoptera	<i>Nesotes congestus</i>	LP & EH	E	2	Two type 2 ESUs: one per island
Coleoptera	<i>Nycteus wollastoni</i>	TF, LG & EH	E	1	All populations conform a type 1 ESU
Coleoptera	<i>Octotemnus opacus</i>	TF & LP	NNE	2	Two type 2 ESUs: one per island
Coleoptera	<i>Ocypus subaenescens</i>	LP & EH	NNE	2	Two type 2 ESUs: one per island
Coleoptera	<i>Olibrus corticalis</i>	TF, LG, LP & EH	E	2	Two type 2 ESUs: TF+LG and LP+EH
Coleoptera	<i>Orthocis sagittiferus</i>	TF, LG & LP	E	3	Three type 2 ESUs: one per island
Coleoptera	<i>Paradromius iucundus</i>	LG & LP	E	2	Two type 2 ESUs: one per island
Coleoptera	<i>Philorinum floricola</i>	TF, LG, LP & EH	NNE	1	All populations conform a type 1 ESU
Coleoptera	<i>Placonotus granulatus</i>	TF, LG & LP	NNE	2	Two type 2 ESUs: LP and TF+LG
Coleoptera	<i>Pselactus affinis</i>	LP & EH	E	2	Two type 2 ESUs: one per island
Coleoptera	<i>Quedius megalops</i>	LG & EH	E	2	Two type 2 ESUs: one per island
Coleoptera	<i>Rhopalomesites persimilis</i>	TF & LG	E	2	Two type 2 ESUs: one per island
Coleoptera	<i>Scymnus canariensis</i>	TF & LG	E	1	All populations conform a type 1 ESU
Coleoptera	<i>Stagetus hirtulus</i>	TF, LG, LP & EH	E	2	Two type 2 ESUs: TF and LG+LP+EH
Coleoptera	<i>Sunius brevipennis</i>	TF & LG	E	1	All populations conform a type 1 ESU
Coleoptera	<i>Taeniapion delicatulum</i>	TF, LG, LP & EH	NNE	1	All populations conform a type 1 ESU
Coleoptera	<i>Tarphius setosus</i>	LG & EH	E	2	Two type 2 ESUs: one per island
Coleoptera	<i>Trechus flavocinctus</i>	TF, LG & EH	E	1	All populations conform a type 1 ESU
Coleoptera	<i>Xenostromylus canariensis</i>	TF, LG, LP & EH	E	1	All populations conform a type 1 ESU

Table S9. Binomial GLM results of the comparison between species of beetle comprised of only one ESU (N=14) and those comprised of two or more (N=35), according to their dispersal capacity (winged or wingless).

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	2.1401	0.7475	2.863	0.0042 **
Category	-1.7346	0.8353	-2.077	0.0378 *

Signif. codes: 0 '***', 0.001 '**', 0.01 '*', 0.05 '.', 0.1 ' ', 1

Table S10. Binomial GLM results of the comparison between species of spiders comprised of only one ESU (N=16) and those comprised of two or more (N=12), according to their dispersal capacity (ballooner or non-ballooner).

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	0.6931	0.7071	0.98	0.327
Category	-1.4663	0.8623	-1.70	0.089 .

Signif. codes: 0 '***', 0.001 '**', 0.01 '*', 0.05 '.', 0.1 ' ', 1

CHAPTER III

Integrative taxonomy unmasks cryptic species within the Canary Island endemic longhorn genus *Lepromoris* (Coleoptera; Cerambycidae)

Jiménez-García, E., Noguerales, V., Machado, A., Andújar, C., Emerson, B.C. & López, H. (*in prep.*). Integrative taxonomy unmasks cryptic species within the Canary Island endemic longhorn genus *Lepromoris* (Coleoptera; Cerambycidae).

Abstract

Oceanic islands, due to their uniqueness and isolation, present a large number of endemic species and genera. One of those genera that is striking due to its size is the canary cerambycid *Lepromoris* (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae). This monotypic genus distributed throughout the Canary archipelago, whose only described species is *Lepromoris gibba*, has the peculiarity of being apterous and associated with the endemic ecosystem of *Euphorbia* shrublands. Here, to study the evolutionary history of *Lepromoris*, we employ a comprehensive geographic sampling at population level with an integrative taxonomy framework, including mitochondrial and nuclear genomic markers together with morphological measurement. We infer a clear case of cryptic species, which differs from its sister species exclusively by the eye curvature. This new species occurs on the islands of Fuerteventura, Gran Canaria and the western region of El Hierro, while the known *Lepromoris gibba* is distributed on the islands of Tenerife, La Gomera, La Palma and the eastern and southern areas of El Hierro. Only El Hierro harbours both species, also including two independent lineages of *Lepromoris gibba*. One of these lineages, mitochondrially linked to an individual from La Palma, has a different evolutionary history from the rest of the sampled *Lepromoris gibba* populations, indicating an incipient process of divergence. However, the discrepancy between the mtDNA and ddRADseq analyses with respect to the individual from La Palma prevents us from inferring a clear conclusion about the genetic differences observed in this *Lepromoris gibba* lineage.

Introduction

Oceanic islands are known for their high proportion of endemic species, making them a priority target for conservation purposes (Kier *et al.*, 2009). Arthropods, the most diverse animal phylum in terms of number of species, have the highest number of endemisms compared to other animal phyla. This is documented in numerous species inventories developed in insular contexts, such as the Canary Islands (Arechavaleta *et al.*, 2009), Madeira and Selvagens (Borges *et al.*, 2008) and the Hawaiian Islands (Eldredge & Miller, 1997). Likewise, many of these endemic species belong to monotypic genera, i.e. genera composed by a single endemic species. For example, within the Canary Islands, such monotypic genera include the Hemipteran genera *Aetorhinella* Noualhier, 1893; *Eudolycoris* (Noualhier, 1893); and *Neocamptotelus* (Lindberg, 1953); the Lepidopteran genus *Pragmatodes* Walsingham, 1908; and the Coleopteran genera *Amaroschema* Jeannel, 1943; *Canarinus* (Desbordes, 1920), *Pelleas* (Wollaston, 1865), and *Transvestitus* (Evers, 1961), among many others (Arechavaleta *et al.*, 2009). However, with the incorporation of molecular data, many of these monotypic genera have been further splitted in a larger number of species to better explain the high molecular divergence highlighted in several of those lineages. For example, Falck and Karsholt (2023) utilised a combination of morphological and molecular data to analyse the extant material of the Lepidoptera monotypic genus *Chersogenes* Walsingham, 1908. Their findings resulted in the inference of 13 new species and the synonymisation of six species that had been erroneously identified within closely related genera. Consequently, the genus *Chersogenes* expanded from a single species to a total of 20.

With growing evidence for the widespread presence of cryptic species within arthropods (Bickford *et al.*, 2007; Li & Wiens, 2023; Pérez-Delgado *et al.*, 2022), DNA barcoding has become an important tool in the study of biodiversity within insular systems (Arjona *et al.*, 2023; Dopheide *et al.*, 2019; Emerson *et al.*, 2022), being useful for the description of new species (deWaard *et al.*, 2019; Packer & Ruz, 2017; Pérez-Delgado *et al.*, 2022), the detection of introduced species (deWaard *et al.*, 2009; Jiménez-García *et al.*, 2023) and the recategorisation of species previously considered native as introduced (Bidegaray-Batista *et al.*, 2015; Jiménez-García *et al.*, 2023). Combining morphological and genetic data has been successfully applied to infer new species within existing species complexes (Noguerales *et al.*, 2018) or cryptic clades of

new species in islands (Criscione & Köhler, 2015; Pérez-Delgado *et al.*, 2022). For example, the previously monotypic genus *Purpuraria* Enderlein, 1929, an Orthoptera flightless genus endemic to the eastern Canary Islands of Fuerteventura, Lanzarote and their respective islets (López *et al.*, 2013), provides a useful illustration. The genus has historically been considered monotypic, typified by the species *Purpuraria erna* Enderlein, 1929. Recent morphological and genetic analyses have revealed enough variation on the populations on the island of Lanzarote and the islet of Montaña Clara to justify the description of a new species, *Purpuraria magna* López & Oromí, 2013 (López *et al.*, 2013).

Among oceanic islands, the Canary Islands stand out for their high levels of endemism and species richness (Myers *et al.*, 2000). This oceanic volcanic archipelago is comprised of eight islands with ages ranging approximately from 1 to 20.2 million years (Troll & Carracedo, 2016). In the context of Canarian biodiversity, insects are the most notable group, with a total of 6,829 species recorded, including 2,588 endemic species (<https://www.biodiversidadcanarias.es/biota/> last visited 30 of January of 2024). Within the 2,264 species of Coleoptera, approximately 60% are endemic to the Canary Islands, totally 1,345 species. From these, 25 species represent monotypic endemic genera. One of these monotypic genera occurs within the Cerambycidae, a charismatic family of beetles well recognized for their long antennae. The family is represented by 31 species (16 endemic) within the Canary Islands. Amongst cerambycids, the genus *Lepromoris* Pascoe, 1864; is represented by a single described species, *Lepromoris gibba* (Brullé, 1839), a medium-size apterous species that is recorded across all islands of the archipelago in association with *Euphorbia* shrublands (locally called ‘tabaibal-cardonal’). The family Euphorbiaceae is predominantly dominant in this habitat, with a species composition that varies across the islands. The endemic species *Euphorbia canariensis* L., *Euphorbia lamarckii* Sweet, *Euphorbia handiensis* Burchard and *Kleinia neriifolia* Haw as well as the native non-endemic species *Euphorbia balsamifera* Aiton, *Euphorbia regis-jubae* J. Gay and *Periploca laevigata* Aiton are some examples of plants from this habitat (Aguilera Klink *et al.*, 1994; del Arco Aguilar *et al.*, 2010; del Arco Aguilar & Delgado Rodríguez, 2018).

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The taxonomy of *Lepromoris* had a complex history over time, involving several genus changes and corrections of specific epithets. The first record of the species was made by Bory de Saint-Vincent (1803) who misidentified the species with the well-known European species *Lamia pedestris* Poda, 1761. In 1833, Auguste Dejean recorded the name *Leprosoma asperatum* in his personal catalog (Dejean, 1833), without describing any details of the new species, only the name and its origin, Tenerife, being a *nomen nudum* by the criteria of the International Code of Zoological Nomenclature. Subsequently, Brullé (1838), using material collected by Webb and Berthelot in the Canary Islands, considered that the specimens collected were a new taxon of the aforementioned genus *Lamia* and described the species as *Lamia gibba*. The species was subsequently redescribed (Thomson, 1860) with the name *Leprosoma asperatum* (the same one given by Dejean), presumably using the same specimens as Brullé and designating one of them as the holotype (see Pascoe, 1864; Thomson, 1864). Finally, in successive works, Wollaston (1864, 1865) synonymized all names given to this species (e.g. *Lamia gibba*, *Leprosoma asperatum* and *Leprosoma gibbum*) under the current name, *Lepromoris gibba*, using the new genus, *Lepromoris*, following the indications given by Pascoe (1864), as the genus used previously, *Leprosoma*, was firstly used to designate species of Hemiptera.

It has been observed that the reduction or loss of flight capacity diminishes dispersal capacity, thus favoring population differentiation and subsequent speciation (Ikeda *et al.*, 2012; Suárez *et al.*, 2022; Waters *et al.*, 2020). This phenomenon has been recorded numerous times in other canarian Coleoptera genera such as *Calathus* Bonelli, 1810 (Emerson *et al.*, 1999) and *Tarphius* Erichson, 1845 (Emerson & Oromí, 2005). Given its wide distribution and poorly dispersal ability (flightless), *Lepromoris* is a perfect model to study a possible case of cryptic speciation. Therefore, the objective of this study is to understand the evolutionary history of *Lepromoris*. To achieve this goal, we sampled individuals throughout the distribution range of the genus. Then, we sequenced the barcode region (mtDNA marker) to obtain a comprehensive view of the genetic divergence among island populations. Utilising double digest restriction-site associated DNA sequencing (ddRADseq), we verified the genetic differences observed through mtDNA sequencing. Finally, we did a detailed examination of the morphology of individuals from each genetic group, finding evidences that support the genetic differences observed. This approach has allowed us to infer that the genus *Lepromoris* is composed of at least two species.

Materials and Methods

Depositories and collections consulted

CDS: personal collection of Daniel Suárez. **CEJG:** personal collection of Eduardo Jiménez-García. **CHL:** personal collection of Heriberto López. **CPO:** personal collection of Pedro Oromí. **CRV:** personal collection of Roberto del Valle. **DZUL:** collection of the Department of Animal Biology, University of La Laguna (Canary Islands, Spain). **IPNA:** Instituto de Productos Naturales y Agrobiología (Canary Islands, Spain). **MNHN:** Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle (Paris, France). **TFMC:** Museum of Natural Sciences of Tenerife (Canary Islands, Spain).

Field sampling, mtDNA sequencing and phylogenetic tree

Twenty-seven plots of *Euphorbia* shrublands, characterised by the presence of *Euphorbia canariensis* or *Euphorbia lamarckii*, the main host plants of *Lepromoris* larvae, were sampled in the Canary Islands between the years 2017 and 2024 (**Figure 1**; **Table S1** for more details about the sampling points).

Figure 1. Sampling sites within the *Euphorbia* shrublands of the Canary Islands with annotations of the geological age of each island according to Troll & Carracedo (2016).

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Individuals of the genus *Lepromoris* were collected through different methods, including active searching at night (searching the trunks and inflorescences of the plants), beating the plants, and looking for specimens in the dead or senescent parts of individuals of *Euphorbia* spp. For DNA extraction, a leg was used for adults, while a tissue sample or the entire animal was used in the case of larvae. These extractions were carried out using the Mag-Bind® Blood & Tissue DNA HDQ 96 kit (Omega Bio-tek) with a KingFisher Flex (ThermoFisher). DNA extracts were then amplified for the 658 bp barcode region of the Cytochrome c oxidase subunit 1 (COI) gene as follows: two μl of either pure or diluted (1/10) DNA extract was used as template for amplification and combined with 23 μl of PCR mix, for a total volume of 25 μl , consisting of 14.4 μl of water, 2.5 μl of 10x NH₄ buffer (Bioline), 1.5 μl of 50 mM MgCl₂ (Bioline), 2 μl of 2.5 mM dNTPs (Bioline), 0.5 μl of BSA (20 mg/ml), 1 μl of each primer (10 μM), and 0.1 μl of Taq polymerase (BIOTAQ). The primers used were FoldF and FoldR primers (Yu *et al.*, 2012), while the PCR amplification conditions were as follows: an initial 94°C for 2 minutes followed by 40 cycles, each comprising denaturation at 94°C for 30s, primer annealing at 42°C for 35s and primer extension at 72°C for 45s, and then a final extension at 72°C for 5 min. PCR products were sequenced using the Sanger DNA sequencing service of Macrogen (www.macrogen.com), with either the forward or reverse primer. Sequences were then processed and edited in Geneious (www.geneious.com) and aligned with MAFFT. Then, Bayesian inference phylogenetic analysis was performed for the mtDNA sequences using MrBayes 3.2.7a (Ronquist *et al.*, 2012). The analysis was run under a GTR+G+I model as recommended by Faria *et al.* (2016, and references therein) with two parallel runs of 10,000,000 generations, each using four Markov chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) chains. Sampling was done every 1000 trees with the first 25% of sampled trees discarded as burn-in. Parameter estimates were checked for stationarity and convergence in TRACER version 1.7 (Rambaut *et al.*, 2018), with only an estimated sample size greater than 200 being accepted for all parameters. The sequence of the cerambycid *Lamia textor* (Linnaeus, 1758) was used as an outgroup (Genbank accession number KM445206) due to its close phylogenetic relationship with *Lepromoris*, both genera belonging to the Lamiinae subfamily. MrBayes results were visualised in FigTree 1.4.4 (tree.bio.ed.ac.uk/software/figtree/).

ddRAD-seq library preparation

Five individuals (when possible) from each sampling site were selected for ddRAD sequencing (**Table S2**), selecting up to seven in some El Hierro sampling sites for the observed mitochondrial patterns in that island. The reason for this is that El Hierro is the only island that presents individuals from both of the main mitochondrial clades derived, as well as a small group (La Restinga) within one of the main clades that may be of interest. Samples were processed using the double-digestion restriction-site associated DNA sequencing protocol (ddRADseq, Peterson *et al.*, 2012) as described in Mastretta-Yanes *et al.* (2015) and García-Olivares *et al.* (2019). In brief, DNA was digested with the restriction enzymes MseI and EcoRI (New England Biolabs, Ipswich, MA, USA). Genomic libraries were pooled at equimolar ratios and size selected for fragments between 200-250 base pairs (bp) and then, paired-end sequenced (150 bp) on an Illumina NovaSeq6000 (Novogene, Cambridge, UK).

Bioinformatic analyses of ddRADseq data

Raw reads were quality checked in FASTQC version 0.11.7 (Andrews, 2010). Raw sequences were then demultiplexed, quality filtered and *de novo* assembled using IPYRAD version 0.9.93 (Eaton & Overcast, 2020). Only reads with unambiguous barcodes were retained (*max_barcode_mismatch*) and the strict filtering mode was applied to remove Illumina adapter contamination (*filter_adapters*). After trimming restriction overhangs for enzymes *EcoRI* and *MseI* (*restriction_overhang*), base calls with a Phred score <20 were converted into ambiguous sites (Ns) and reads with >5 Ns (*max_low_qual_bases*) were discarded. Retained reads within and across samples were then clustered considering a sequence similarity threshold of 85% (*clust_threshold*), discarding clusters with a minimum coverage depth of less than 5 (*mindepth_majrule*) and a maximum coverage depth of more than 10,000 (*maxdepth*). Statistical base calling was performed at a minimum depth of 6 (*mindepth_statistical*). Resulting loci shorter than 35 base pairs (bp) (*filter_min_trim_len*), containing one or more heterozygous sites across more than 50% individuals (*max_shared_Hs_locus*), and with more than 20% polymorphic sites (*max_SNPs_locus*) were discarded. In a final filtering step, only loci that were present in at least 80% of the samples (*min_samples_locus*) were retained. Finally, resulting unlinked Single Nucleotide Polymorphism (SNP) matrices were further filtered to discard non bi-allelic variants and those with a minor allele frequency (MAF) ≤ 0.03 using the '*gl.filter.maf*' function as implemented in the package *dartR* (Mijangos *et al.*, 2022) and the R version 4.2.2 (R Core Team, 2022).

Chapter III

Genomic clustering analyses of ddRADseq data

The nuclear genomic distinctiveness and cohesiveness of the different mitochondrial lineages observed was examined at different geographic and divergence contexts by partitioning the full dataset into three subsets including: (A) all individuals belonging to both mitochondrial clades inferred, (B) only individuals sampled in El Hierro as is the only island with both clades; and (C) only *Lepromoris gibba* mitochondrial clade, including La Restinga (El Hierro) and La Palma individuals. Population genetic structure was assessed using two complementary approaches for each of the three datasets. A Bayesian Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) clustering method was used as implemented in the program STRUCTURE version 2.3.3 (Pritchard *et al.*, 2000). STRUCTURE was run with 200,000 MCMC cycles after a burn-in step of 100,000 iterations, assuming correlated allele frequencies and admixture (Pritchard *et al.*, 2000) and performing 20 independent runs for each value of K ancestral populations (from $K=1$ to $K=6$). For each dataset, the most likely number of ancestral populations was estimated after retaining the 10 runs per each K -value with the highest likelihood estimates. Convergence across runs was assessed by checking the 10 retained replicates per K -value provided a similar solution in terms of individual probabilities of assignment to a given ancestral population (q -values; Gilbert *et al.*, 2012). As recommended by Gilbert *et al.* (2012) and Janes *et al.* (2017), two statistics were used to interpret the number range of ancestral populations (K) that best describes data: log probabilities of $\Pr(X|K)$ (Pritchard *et al.*, 2000) and ΔK (Evanno *et al.*, 2005), both calculated in STRUCTURE HARVESTER (Earl & vonHoldt, 2012). Finally, the Greedy algorithm in CLUMPP version 1.1.2 was used to align replicated runs of STRUCTURE for the same K -value (Jakobsson & Rosenberg, 2007). In addition, major axes of nuclear genomic variation were visualized for each dataset with a Principal Component Analysis (PCA) using the ‘*gl.pcoa*’ function as implemented in the package *dartR* (Mijangos *et al.*, 2022).

Phylogenomic inference

Phylogenetic relationships among the main nuclear genomic groups, as inferred with clustering analyses, were reconstructed using SNAPP version 1.5.2 (Bryant *et al.*, 2012), a coalescent-based method for species tree estimation, as implemented in BEAST version 2.6.7 (Bouckaert *et al.*, 2014). Due to the high computational burden of SNAPP, only three individuals per population were included, selecting those with the lower proportion of

missing data to retain the higher number of shared SNPs. SNAPP explicitly accounts for post-divergence gene flow, which can bias topological inferences especially at shallow levels of divergence. Therefore, only one sampling site per genetic group, as inferred by genetic clustering analyses, was included in this analysis. Since SNAPP derived topologies are sensitive to prior misspecification for the population size parameter (θ), analyses were replicated using different values of the shape (α) and inverse scale (β) parameters of the gamma prior distribution ($\alpha=2, \beta=200$; $\alpha=2, \beta=2,000$; $\alpha=2, \beta=20,000$) for θ (Noguerales *et al.*, 2018), representing alternative demographic scenarios ranging from small to large effective population sizes. The forward (u) and reverse (v) mutation rates were set to be calculated by SNAPP. The log-likelihood correction was used, sampled the coalescent rate and left default settings for all other parameters. Two independent runs were carried out for each gamma distribution using different starting seeds for 1 million MCMC generations, sampling every 1000 steps (~1000 genealogies). Log files were examined with TRACER version 1.7 (Rambaut *et al.*, 2018) to check stationarity and convergence of the chains and confirm that effective sample sizes (ESS) for all parameters were >200 . Ten percent of trees were removed as burn-in and then tree and log files from replicated runs were combined using LOGCOMBINER version 2.4.7 (Drummond & Rambaut, 2007). Maximum credibility trees were obtained using TREEANNOTATOR version 2.4.7 (Drummond & Rambaut, 2007). The full set of retained trees was displayed with DENSITREE version 2.2.6 (Bouckaert, 2010).

Morphological analysis

Five males were selected for each of the two well-differentiated mtDNA clades C1 and C2 to test whether genetic differences were also supported by morphological differences. Various measurements of the head, pronotum, abdomen, antennae and legs were taken using Motic Images Plus 3.0 software with a Moticam S20 camera mounted on a Motic SMZ- 171 stereoscope. Measurements were visually compared between groups to detect differences using packages ‘ggplot2’ and ‘ggpubr’ on the R version 4.2.2 (R Core Team, 2022), which allow you to see from the graphs whether there is any overlap between measurements. Male genitalia were extracted by soaking the specimens in a solution of acetic acid to soften the tissues for several days and were later cleaned with 5% KOH for several minutes. Specimens habitus were photographed using a Canon EOS-750D camera and the genitalia with a Moticam S20 camera. All photos were stacked with Zerene Stacker (Zerene Systems LLC., version 1.04).

Results

Sampling and mtDNA COI sequencing

One hundred thirty individuals (72 adults and 58 larvae) were sampled across the 27 sites (see **Table S1** for more details about the individuals sampled per site). Of the 72 adults, 30 were females while the 42 remaining were males. 114 *Leptomoris* were selected for barcode region-COI sequencing, avoiding selecting too many individuals in plots with high sampled population density in the same period of time like SAB or VAL (**Table S1**), due to the great probability that they are sister individuals with the same genetic sequence. Sequencing success was 98%, yielding a total of 112 COI *Leptomoris* sequences of 542bp (**Table S3**). The consensus tree obtained by Bayesian inference (**Figure 2**) showed two differentiated clades. For practical purposes, from hereon the clade containing the all individuals from Gran Canaria and Fuerteventura, together with the western area of El Hierro (**Figure 1**) will be called "C1" while the group formed by the individual sequences of the islands of Tenerife, La Gomera, La Palma and eastern and southern areas of El Hierro (**Figure 1**) will be called "C2". Within C2, mtDNA variation is apparently structured into two clades, with one comprising individuals from La Palma and RES from El Hierro, while the other comprising individuals from all other localities within C2. The minimum genetic divergence measured within clades C1 and C2 was 9.8%. This was calculated using p-distances with a neighbour-joining tree in Geneious. In addition, this was also measured between the two clades within C2, being the divergence of 3.1%.

Figure 2. MtdNA phylogenetic consensus tree obtained by Bayesian inference for 112 *Lepromoris* individuals plus on sequence of *Lamia texor* as outgroup, using sequences of 542bp from the barcode region (COI gene). Numbers in branches represent posterior probabilities. Each island has been assigned a unique colour in the labels, while the distribution of each inferred clade has been coloured black in the archipelago image. Details of the sampling plots and barcoded individuals can be found in **Table S1** and **Table S3** respectively.

Genomic data

Illumina sequencing provided a total of 65.1 million (M) sequence reads, with an average of 1.00 M reads per individual with a standard deviation (SD) of 0.43 M (**Table S2** and **Figure S1**). After the different filtering and assembly steps, each specimen retained on average 37,833 clusters (SD=8,468.61), with a mean depth per locus of 16.72 (SD=3.65) across individuals. On average, missing data across the SNP matrices was approximately 16.5%. Estimates of sequencing error rates was 0.0006 (SD=0.0001), while heterozygosity across individuals was on average 0.0079 (SD=0.0013). These values indicate an adequate specification of the clustering threshold (*clust_threshold*) parameter (Eaton & Overcast, 2020).

Genetic clustering analyses of ddRADseq data

Genetic clustering analyses using STRUCTURE, when including all individuals of both inferred mitochondrial clades, identified the most likely number of ancestral populations (K) to be K=2 according to the ΔK criterion (Evanno *et al.*, 2005). However, $\text{LnPr}(X|K)$ increased for higher K values until reaching an asymptote plateau for K=3 (**Figure S2**), suggesting hierarchical genetic structure among the main ancestral populations (Janes *et al.*, 2017). For K=2 (**Figure 3A**), the two ancestral populations corresponded to the mitochondrial clades C1 and C2 (**Figure 2**), with no evidence of genetic admixture between the two clades. When considering K=3 (**Figure 3A**), nuclear genomic variation within clade C2 was further structured into two genetic groups, consisting of (i) individuals sampled in RES, and (ii) all other C2 populations in Tenerife, La Gomera, La Palma and El Hierro. Some individuals showing admixed ancestry between these two last groups were found in La Gomera, La Palma, and Tenerife. Consistent with inferences from STRUCTURE, principal component analysis (PCA) also supported genetic variation to be largely organised into two independently genetic groups, with PC1 describing their differences in allele frequencies (**Figure 3B**). In concordance with STRUCTURE analyses when assuming K=3 (**Figure 3A**), variation in nuclear allele frequencies consistent with the mitochondrial structure within C2 partitioned across PC2, with individuals from RES forming a distinct group from the remaining El Hierro sites within C2 (**Figure 3**).

(A)

(B)

Figure 3. (A) STRUCTURE clustering analyses and (B) Principal Component Analysis (PCA) summarising the genetic variation detected using ddRADseq data within both inferred mitochondrial clades C1 and C2. Each individual is shown in the STRUCTURE analysis as a vertical bar, whose colour is defined by the probability of belonging to each of the inferred ancestral populations (K). In the PCA, each individual is represented as a dot whose colour is representative of the sampling area. STRUCTURE analyses were performed for K=2 (upper) and K=3 (lower). Further details concerning the *Lepromoris* individuals can be found in **Table S2**.

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When including exclusively individuals sampled in El Hierro, STRUCTURE analyses indicated the most probable number of ancestral populations to be $K=2$ under the ΔK criterion. However $\text{LnPr}(X|K)$ steadily increased up to an asymptote of $K=3$ (**Figure S3**). When considering $K=2$ (**Figure 4A**), one ancestral population coincides with individuals belonging to mitochondrial clade C1, with the other comprising individuals from mitochondrial clade C2. For $K = 3$ (**Figure 4A**), individuals from clade C2 are divided into two groups corresponding to the mtDNA divergence observed within C2. No signature of genetic admixture was observed for $K=2$ and $K=3$ clustering solutions. The PCA (**Figure 4B**) corroborated the inferences derived from STRUCTURE, with genetic variation organised into three concordant genetic groups, whose allele frequency differences were differentiated along the two first components.

(A)

(B)

(C)

Figure 4. (A) STRUCTURE clustering analyses and (B) Principal Component Analysis (PCA) summarising the genetic variation detected using ddRADseq data within only El Hierro *Leptomoris* individuals. Each individual is shown in the STRUCTURE analysis as a vertical bar, whose colour is defined by the probability of belonging to each of the inferred ancestral populations (K). In the PCA, each individual is represented as a dot whose colour is representative of the sampling area. STRUCTURE analyses were performed for K=2 (upper) and K=3 (lower). Panel (C) is a representation of El Hierro Island, coloured according to the results of the extrapolation for K=3 with blurred boundaries between ancestral populations. Further details concerning the sampling plots using on (C) and *Leptomoris* individuals can be found in **Table S1** and **Table S2**, respectively

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When only including the *Lepromoris gibba* individuals of the mitochondrial clade C2, STRUCTURE analyses inferred the most likely number of clusters to be $K=3$ according to the ΔK criterion, while the $\text{LnPr}(X|K)$ reached an asymptote at $K=4$ (**Figure S4**). When assuming $K=3$, one of the ancestral populations was sampled in RES (El Hierro), another was distributed in the remaining sampling sites of El Hierro, while the last one occurs in the populations of Tenerife and La Palma. Individuals from La Gomera exhibited admixed ancestry between the RES (El Hierro) and Tenerife and La Palma ancestral populations (**Figure 5A**). For $K=4$, a fourth ancestral population of single ancestry was identified, composed of individuals sampled in La Gomera, with only one individual from La Gomera showing admixed ancestry (**Figure 5A**). The results of the PCA (**Figure 5B**) are in concordance with the STRUCTURE analyses, revealing that genetic variation is organised in three concordant genetic groups, whose differences are explained by PC1 (**Figure 5B**).

(A)

(B)

Figure 5. (A) STRUCTURE clustering analyses and (B) Principal Component Analysis (PCA) summarising the genetic variation detected using ddRADseq data within the inferred mitochondrial clade C2 comprising only *Lepromoris gibba* individuals. Each individual is shown in the STRUCTURE analysis as a vertical bar, whose colour is defined by the probability of belonging to each of the inferred ancestral populations (K). In the PCA, each individual is represented as a dot whose colour is representative of the sampling area. STRUCTURE analyses were performed for K=3 (upper) and K=4 (lower). Further details concerning the *Lepromoris* individuals can be found in **Table S2**.

Phylogenomic inference

A total of six genetic groups identified through the PCA results (**Figure 3B**) were incorporated into SNAPP analyses. These groups correspond to the AGA, GUI, SSE, SAB, RES and VAL representative populations. (see **Figure 1** and **Table S1**). The resulting dataset comprised 16,549 biallelic unlinked SNPs shared across tips. The species tree reconstructed in SNAPP revealed two well-supported major clades corresponding to the mitochondrial clades C1 and C2 (**Figure 6**). The relative branch lengths within these two clades were found to be considerably shorter, indicating that diversification events have occurred relatively recently. Phylogenetic relationships within C2 were also well-supported, with the exception of the split involving the VAL population. Replicate runs considering different prior distributions for the θ parameter yielded similar topologies, with minor differences in relative branch lengths.

Figure 6. Species tree inferred with SNAPP showing the phylogenetic relationships among the main genetic groups as inferred with genetic clustering analysis. Values represent node support.

Comparative morphological analysis between clades

No observable morphological differences were identified across the 32 distinct measurements performed on the habitus of the 10 males selected from both inferred mitochondrial clades. Also, these measurements exhibited significant intraspecific variation, with a large overlap observed between the males of both clades C1 and C2 (**Table S4**, **Table S5** and **Figure S5**). Additionally, no significant variations were observed in the aedeagus of both groups, which exhibited a high degree of similarity, with considerable variability in the length of the tegmen, parameres, and the apical shape and curvature of the median lobe. As a consequence of the cryptic nature of the individuals of both mitochondrial clades and their shared habitus, a redescription of the genus *Lepromoris* will be employed as a general description of both inferred clades. The present study will expand the information provided in the original descriptions of the genus, as well as that indicated by Vives and Trócoli (2021). New information will be added regarding male genitalia and sizes. The diagnostic characters that allow them to be separated morphologically will be explained in a designated section. .

Taxonomy

Family **Cerambycidae** Latreille, 1802

Subfamily **Lamiinae** Latreille, 1825

Tribe **Parmenini** Mulsant, 1839

***Lepromoris* Pascoe, 1864**

Lepromoris Pascoe, 1864: p. 278; Wollaston, 1865: 349

Type species: *Lepromoris gibba* (Brullé, 1839)

Redescription

Body (♂). Small-medium apterous Lamiinae (length 11-22 mm; width 5-10 mm); body oblong-oval; integument from black to brown, sometimes greyish, covered by a dense whitish, greyish or brown pubescence mixed with golden tones; pubescence can be denser on the elytra, forming up to eight brown spots, often reduced or absent (**Figure 7**). *Head* hypognathous; mandibles elongated and acuminate, last maxillary palpomeres fusiform; eyes roughly faceted, strongly marginated and reniform (minimum distance between eyes narrower than the eye width); antennal tubercles prominent, distance between bases reduced, with a median longitudinal groove; forehead and antennal groove provided with pits in variable number (abundant or non-existent), irregularly distributed; antennae 11-segmented, reaching the elytral apices approximately at the apex of antennomere VIII, scape often with whitish pubescence in the apex, antennomeres II-XI with ringed coloration (whitish in the basal half and darker in the apical half), pedicel oblong and the smallest antennomere, antennomere III slightly longer than scape and V but shorter than IV (the largest), antennomeres VI-XI with length gradually decreasing. *Pronotum* transverse, armed in the middle area of the sides with an acuminate spine directed backwards; pronotal disc with three distinct tubercles (one in the central area and two further forward), pits variable in number and irregularly distributed, pubescence often dense and accompanied by scattered golden setae. *Scutellum* small, transverse, rounded. *Elytra* oval, globose, dense pubescence along with scattered setae, without humerus, approximately 3x as long as pronotum, wider than pronotal base with the maximum width approximately in half; presence of two or three elevated longitudinal ribs, sometimes accompanied by a row of short golden setae; elytra surface with several pits variable in

number and depth, irregularly distributed, along with numerous and distinct tubercles towards the base and sides of the elytra; apex briefly notched, with blunt or acuminate tips. Long thin *legs*, fusiform femurs; tibiae with two short and obtuse spines, golden pubescence in the apical area, anterior tibiae with internal groove, middle tibiae with external groove; short 4-segmented tarsi, IV tarsomere very reduced at the base of the nail; posterior I tarsomere as long as II+III; divaricated nails. *Genitalia*. Tergite VIII rounded at edge with short setae; aedeagus with rhomboid-shaped tegmen almost twice as long as it is wide; parameres slightly elongated, approximately $\frac{1}{2}$ length of tegmen, separated from each other, apex covered with setae; median lobe curvature highly variable, apex termination acuminate or blunt. No appreciable differences between species (**Figure 8**). *Females* very similar to males, a little more robust, with the antennae reaching the elytral apex at the apex of antennomere XI and barely exceeding it (males reach the elytral apex at the apex of antennomere VIII).

Distribution

The genus is endemic to the Canary Islands with presence on the islands of Lanzarote, Fuerteventura, Gran Canaria, Tenerife, La Gomera, La Palma and El Hierro.

Ecology and biology

The genus is distributed in *Euphorbia* shrublands, where it is predominantly associated with succulents such as *Euphorbia canariensis*, *Euphorbia lamarckii*, *Euphorbia balsamifera*, *Euphorbia regis-jubae* and *Euphorbia handiensis*. The female lays her eggs in the senescent or diseased part of these plants. The larvae feed there and subsequently create cocoons using the woody fibres of the plants. The adult is predominantly nocturnal in its habits, although during the diurnal hours it is possible to observe it in the most basal areas of plants or inside dead stems. There is no specific phenology, and adults can be observed throughout the year. It appears that both inferred species have the same ecology and host plants.

Figure 7. Photos of the habitus of *Lepromoris gibba* (A to D) and *Lepromoris* sp. nov. (E to H). Individuals selected are as follows: (A) male from LG-SSE (BC001546); (B) male from TF-MIF(BC001533); (C) male from TF-SN2 (BC001525); (D) female from TF-SN2 (BC001544); (E) male from FV-BET (BC001561); (F) male from EH-SAB (BC001559); (G) male from EH-SAB (BC001568); and (H) female from EH-SAB (BC001558). The scale is represented by a black line with a length of 1 mm. See **Tables S1** and **S3** for individuals details. Due to aesthetic considerations, some legs were cloned using Photoshop CS6.

Figure 8. Comparison of the male genitalia of *Lepromoris gibba* (A and B) and *Lepromoris* sp. nov. (C and D). Individuals selected are as follows: (A) TF-MIF(BC001533); (B) TF-SN2 (BC001525); (C) FV-BET (BC001561); (D) EH-SAB (BC001568). Each part of the genitalia was indicated with the following code: (ter) tergite VIII; (tgd) tegmen dorsal view; (tgv) tegmen ventral view; (mel) median lobe lateral view; and, (aml) detail of the apex of the median lobe. The scale is represented by a black line with a length of 1 mm. See **Tables S1** and **S3** for individuals details.

***Lepromoris gibba* (Brullé, 1839)**

Lamia pedestris Bory de Saint-Vincent, 1803: p.420. Misidentification.

Leprosoma asperatum Dejean, 1833: p.345. *Nomen nudum*.

Lamia gibba Brullé, in Webb et Berthelot 1839: p.62. **Original description.**

Leprosoma asperatum Thomson, 1860: p.23

Leprosoma gibbum, Wollaston, 1862: p.178; Heyden, 1875: p.143; Koeppen, 1910: p.97

Lepromoris gibba, Pascoe, 1864: p.278; Wollaston, 1865: p.349; Martínez de la Escalera, 1923: p.19; Peyerimhoff, 1923: p.47; Winkler, 1932; Uyttenboogaart, 1932: p.58, 1937: p.92; Demelt, 1971: p. 61, 1974: p.232; Oromí, 1984: p.238; Machado, 1985: p.454; Lorenzo & Prendes, 1987: p.99; Franz, 1996: p.112; Machado & Oromí, 2000: pp.200,201; García, 2005: pp.161,162; Vitali & Touroult, 2006: pp.193,194,195,196; Hernández-Teixidor *et al.*, 2009: p.95; Krátký & Aguiar, 2019 : p.5; Vives & Trócoli, 2021: pp. 29,30.

Material examined

Holotype. Tenerife, Canary Islands: ??/??/183X, 1♂ (MNHN EC21545), leg. Webb & Berthelot (depository MNHN). Used for the description of Brullé in 1839 and later by Thomson in 1860 (**Figure 9**).

Syntype. Canary Islands (most probably Tenerife): ??/??/183X, 1♀ (MNHN EC21544), leg. Webb & Berthelot (depository MNHN). Used for the description of Brullé in 1839 (**Figure 9**).

Tenerife. Arona, Costa del Silencio (28.0062, -16.6403): 08/12/1975, 1♀ (TFMC 14459), leg. De Laever (depository TFMC). El Fraile (28.0085, -16.6679): 02/05/2010, 1♀, leg. R. del Valle (depository CRV); 21/08/2010, 1♂, leg. R. del Valle (depository CRV). Las Galletas (28.0102, -16.6545): 01/10/1972, 1♂, leg. P. Oromí (depository CPO); 01/09/1976, 1♂, leg. P. Oromí (depository CPO). Malpaís de La Rasca (28.0199, -16.7035): 19/04/2007 1♂ (DZUL 8311), leg. GIET (Grupo de Investigaciones entomológicas de Tenerife; depository DZUL); 27/04/2007 1♂ (DZUL 8307), leg. GIET

(depository DZUL); 03/08/2007, 1♀, leg. P. Oromí (depository CPO); 20/03/2021, 1♂, leg. E. Jiménez-García (depository CEJG). El Médano (28.0433, -16.5465): 01/11/1995, 1♀, leg. P. Oromí (depository CPO). Adeje, Caleta del Rey (28.0779, -16.7213): 21/12/2022, 1♀, leg. R. del Valle (depository CRV). Montaña de Ifara (28.0931, -16.5292): 07/02/2021, 1♂, leg. H. López (depository IPNA). Punta del Tablero (28.0961, -16.4914): 09/01/2021, 1♂, leg. H. López (depository IPNA). Abades (28.1361, -16.4436): 01/10/2009, 1♀, leg. R. del Valle (depository CRV). Los Roques (28.2179, -16.4166): 16/12/2017, 1♂, leg. J. García & D. Suárez (depository CDS). Barranco Natero (28.2886, -16.8350): 01/10/2017, 2♂, leg. D. Suárez & D. Hernández (depository CDS). Malpaís de Güímar (28.2997, -16.3711): 10/04/2000, 1♂, leg. H. López (depository CHL); 03/08/2014, 1♀, leg. R. del Valle (depository CRV); 09/03/2023, 3♂, leg. H. López (depository IPNA); 11/03/2023, 2♂, leg. E. Jiménez-García (depository CEJG). Barranco de Carrizales (28.3198, -16.8677): 09/04/2019, 1♂1♀, leg. GEEI (Grupo de Ecología y Evolución en Islas; depository IPNA). Punta de Teno (28.3473, -16.9118): 04/02/1950, 3♂ (TFMC 14439, 14474, 14475), leg. C. González Padrón (depository TFMC); 28/07/1968, 1♂ (TFMC 14466), leg. M. Morales (depository TFMC); 29/06/1974, 1♀ (TFMC 14476), leg. J. M. Fernández (depository TFMC); 05/07/1978, 1♂ (TFMC 14473), leg. A. Aguiar (depository TFMC); 18/06/2004, 2♂ (DZUL 8304, 8309), leg. E. Cano (depository DZUL); 01/06/2013, 3♂, leg. R. del Valle (depository CRV); 09/04/2019, 1♂, leg. GEEI (depository IPNA); 24/04/2019, 2♂2♀, leg. E. Jiménez-García (depository CEJG). Candelaria (28.3482, -16.3700): 16/04/1968, 1♂ (TFMC 14454), leg. J. M. Fernández (depository TFMC). El Palmar (28.3576, -16.8431): 09/07/2019, 2♀, leg. H. López (depository IPNA). Santa María del Mar (28.4311, -16.3030): 01/07/1988, 1♀, leg. P. Oromí (depository CPO). Barranco Bufadero (28.5004, -16.2282): 13/11/1960, 1♀ (TFMC 14463), leg. J. M. Fernández (depository TFMC); 20/11/1960, 3♂1♀ (TFMC 14438, 14464, 14457, 14458), leg. J. M. Fernández (depository TFMC); 05/11/1961, 1♂3♀ (TFMC 14453, 14455, 14456, 14462), leg. J. M. Fernández (depository TFMC); 11/11/1962, 1♀ (TFMC 14460), leg. M. Morales (depository TFMC); 26/11/1970, 1♂ (TFMC 14451), leg. A. Santos (depository TFMC); 10/10/1971, 1♂ (TFMC 14449), leg. A. Santos (depository TFMC). San Andrés (28.5063, -16.1975): 10/03/1963, 1♂ (TFMC 14461), leg. J. M. Fernández (depository TFMC); 14/03/1978, 2♂ (TFMC 14477, 14478), leg. A. Aguiar (depository TFMC). Valle Brosque (28.5191, -16.2281): 07/03/2019, 1♂, leg. E. Jiménez-García (depository CEJG); 14/03/2019, 1♀, leg. GEEI (depository IPNA); 12/03/2019, 5♂1♀,

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leg. GEEI (depository IPNA). Barranco de San Andrés (28.5201, -16.1902): 22/03/2019, 1♂1♀, leg. GEEI (depository IPNA). Barranco de San Andrés (28.5299, -16.1945): 04/04/2008, 1♂, leg. P. Oromí (depository CPO); 21/03/2019, 4♂1♀, leg. GEEI (depository IPNA). Iguste de San Andrés (28.5332, -16.1595): 01/11/1970, 1♀ (TFMC 14450), leg. A. Santos (depository TFMC); 15/11/1970, 1♂ (TFMC 14452), leg. A. Santos (depository TFMC); 13/04/1973, 1♀ (TFMC 14468), leg. A. Aguiar (depository TFMC); 31/07/1973, 1♂ (TFMC 14471), leg. A. Aguiar (depository TFMC); 09/10/1973, 1♂ (TFMC 14467), leg. A. Aguiar (depository TFMC); 07/11/1973, 2♀ (TFMC 14469, 14470), leg. A. Aguiar (depository TFMC); 25/03/1978, 1♂ (TFMC 14465), leg. J. M. Fernández (depository TFMC); 20/09/1978, 1♂ (TFMC 14472), leg. A. Aguiar (depository TFMC); 20/03/2019, 1♂, leg. GEEI (depository IPNA). Chinamada (28.5634, -16.2928): 01/05/2017, 1♂, leg. GEEI (depository IPNA). Taganana (28.5651, -16.2113): 14/02/1974, 1♀ (DZUL 8310), leg. P. Oromí (depository DZUL).

La Gomera. San Sebastián de La Gomera (28.1037, -17.1181): 07/04/2021, 2♂2♀, leg. GEEI (depository IPNA). Tamargada (28.1955, -17.2478): 06/04/2021, 1♀, leg. GEEI (depository IPNA).

La Palma. El Remo (28.5524, -17.8852): 11/08/1992, 1♀, leg. P. Oromí (depository CPO); 25/06/2001, 5♂ (DZUL 8298, 8299, 8302, 8303, 8312), leg. H. López (depository DZUL); 25/06/2001, 2♂, leg. H. López (depository CPO); 26/06/2001, 1♀ (DZUL 8313), leg. H. Contreras & H. López (depository DZUL); 26/06/2001, 1♀ (DZUL 8301), leg. H. López & E. Morales (depository DZUL); 12/10/2001, 2♀ (DZUL 8300, 8308), leg. H. Contreras (depository DZUL); 20/10/2001, 1♂, leg. P. Oromí (depository CPO); 01/12/2001, 1♀ (DZUL 8297), leg. H. López (depository DZUL); 15/12/2001, 1♀ (DZUL 8306), leg. H. López & H. Contreras (depository DZUL). La Salemera (28.5751, -17.7676): 03/03/2021, 1♂, leg. GEEI (depository IPNA). La Grama (28.6646, -17.7742): 04/04/1983, 1♂, leg. R. García (depository CPO).

El Hierro. Frontera, Montaña Los Charcos (27.7548, -18.0068): 13/10/2000, 2♂, leg. H. López (depository CHL). Aeropuerto de El Hierro (27.8133, -17.8849): 31/03/2023, 1♀, leg. GEEI (depository IPNA). Montaña del Majano (27.8086, -17.8987): 20/12/2022, 2♂1♀, leg. R. del Valle (depository CRV). Parque Eólico de Valverde (27.7909, -17.9163): 07/04/2021, 1♀, leg. GEEI (depository IPNA). La Restinga (27.6602, -17.9755): 24/03/2021, 2♂, leg. GEEI (depository IPNA); 25/03/2021, 2♂2♀, leg. GEEI (depository IPNA).

Figure 9. Photos of the *Lepromoris gibba* types courtesy of Christophe Rivier, MNHN. Photos A to E corresponding to *Lepromoris gibba* holotype MNHN EC21545 being (A) dorsal view; (B) lateral view; (C) frontal head details; (D) face details; and (E) label details. Photos F to J corresponding to *Lepromoris gibba* Syntype MNHN EC21544 being (F) dorsal view; (G) lateral view; (H) frontal head details; (I) face details; and (J) label details. The scale is represented by a black line with a length of 1 mm.

Chapter III

Diagnostic remarks

Leptomoris gibba is distinguished from *Leptomoris* sp. nov. by its slightly convex eyes, with uniform curvature (zenith in the middle) (**Figure 10**). There are other morphological characters that could be used to identify the species, although these are not always observed in all individuals of this species. Therefore, these characters should be used with caution as generalisations. In the majority of cases, the forehead exhibits less than 15 pits, typically ranging from 8 to 12, situated within the groove between the antennal bases. These pits rarely extend beyond the level of the eyes, whether in the anterior or posterior direction. The elytral pilosity is less developed, although sometimes there are some long irregular setae at the base (resembling those on the pronotum) and short setae on the rest of the elytra. These setae are scarcer and much smaller than a tarsus nail. The aedeagus characteristically exhibits a minor curvature of the median lobe, with the apex terminating in a tooth that is more or less acuminate, although on occasion this may be rounded or absent..

Distribution

Tenerife, La Gomera, La Palma and El Hierro (Eastern and Southern)

Figure 10. Photos of the heads and eyes details of *Lepromoris gibba* (A to D) and *Lepromoris sp. nov.* (E to H), including a comparison of the eye curvature and zenith displacement (I) between an individual of *Lepromoris gibba* (left) and *Lepromoris sp. nov.* (right). Individuals selected are as follows: (A) male from LG-SSE (BC001546); (B) male from TF-MIF(BC001533); (C) male from TF-SN2 (BC001525); (D) female from TF-SN2 (BC001544); (E) male from FV-BET (BC001561); (F) male from EH-SAB (BC001559); (G) male from EH-SAB (BC001568); and (H) female from EH-SAB (BC001558). The scale is represented by a black line with a length of 1 mm. See **Tables S1** and **S3** for individual details.

Chapter III

Lepromoris sp. nov.

Material examined

Fuerteventura. Jandía, Valle de los Mosquitos (28.0798, -14.4216): 09/04/1955, 3♂3♀ (TFMC 14442, 14444, 14445, 14446, 14447, 14448), leg. C. González Padrón (depository TFMC). Jandía, Playa de Sotavento (28.1105, -14.2668): 19/07/1987, 1♀ (TFMC 14479), leg. J. J. Bacallado (depository TFMC). Betancuria (28.4409, -14.0565): 26/07/2021, 1♂, leg. M. Arechavaleta (depository IPNA). Vallebrón (28.5839, -13.9321): 11/07/2023, 3♂2♀, leg. H. López (depository IPNA).

Gran Canaria. Barranco de Arguineguín (27.7984, -15.6686): 10/04/2023, 1♂2♀ (**Figure 11**), leg. E. Jiménez-García, D. Suárez & I. Santos (depository IPNA). Mundo Aborigen (27.8129, -15.5811): 10/04/2023, 2♂1♀, leg. E. Jiménez-García, D. Suárez & I. Santos (depository IPNA). Barranco de Fataga (27.8336, -15.5788): 04/05/1990, 1♀, leg. P. Oromí (depository CPO). La Pasadilla (27.9451, -15.4665): 13/08/1999, 1♂, leg. H. López (depository CHL). Cuermeja (27.9826, -15.8074): 24/02/2024, 2♂ (**Figure 11**), leg. E. Jiménez-García (depository IPNA). Agaete (28.0936, -15.6818): 10/04/2023, 1♂, leg. V. Noguerales (depository IPNA).

El Hierro. Cruz de Bernardo (27.7339, -18.1405): 26/07/2023, 1♀, leg. GEEI (depository IPNA). Sabinar de La Dehesa (27.7511, -18.1425): 03/04/1958, 2♂1♀ (TFMC 14440, 14441, 14443), leg. C. González Padrón (depository TFMC); 24/03/2021, 1♂1♀, leg. GEEI (depository IPNA); 31/03/2023, 2♂4♀, leg. E. Jiménez-García, D. Suárez & I. Santos (depository IPNA); 24/07/2023, 3♀, leg. GEEI (depository IPNA); 26/07/2023, 3♂3♀, leg. E. Jiménez-García (depository CEJG). Mirador Lomo Negro II (27.7548, -18.1428): 25/07/2023, 3♂2♀, leg. GEEI (depository IPNA).

Figure 11. Photos of a male (A-E) and female (F-I) of *Lepromoris* sp. nov., both from the island of Gran Canaria (CUE and ARG, respectively). (A) male dorsal view; (B) male head-face details I; (C) male head-face details II; (D) male head-face details III; (E) male lateral view; (F) female dorsal view; (G) female head-face details I; (H) female head-face details II; and (I) female lateral view. The scale is represented by a black line with a length of 1 mm. See Table S1 for locality information.

Chapter III

Diagnostic remarks

Leptomoris sp. nov. is distinguished from *Leptomoris gibba* by its more convex eyes, with eccentric curvature (the zenith is displaced towards the outer margin of the eye) (**Figure 10**). There are other morphological characters that could be used to identify the species, although these are not always observed in all individuals of this species. Therefore, these characters should be used with caution as generalisations. The forehead typically exhibits between 25 and 60 pits, extending anteriorly to the eyes and frequently extending posteriorly to the vertex. The presence of more developed pilosity is evident at the base of the elytra, characterised by several long, erect, irregular and white setae, similar to those observed on the pronotum. The remainder of the integument is covered with smaller golden setae, which are arched and almost the size of a tarsus nail or somewhat longer, being associated with the major tubercles present on the ribs. The aedeagus is characterised by a greater curvature of the median lobe and a rounded apex, rarely acuminate.

Distribution

Fuerteventura, Gran Canaria and El Hierro (Western). It is hypothesised that the specimens recorded from Lanzarote are also this species, although no specimen could be accessed in the present study.

Discussion

The combination of morphological and genetic techniques provides robust support for the inference and description of a new *Lepromoris* species. While the barcode fragment already showed differentiation between clearly distinct mitochondrial clades (**Figure 2**), the nuclear genomic inferences provided by the ddRADseq data (**Figure 3**, **Figure 4** and **Figure 6**) show a clear pattern of genomic distinctiveness between the two inferred species, clearly supporting the observed mitochondrial differences. Once strong genetic differences between the two putative species have been demonstrated, efforts could be focused on the search for morphological characters that would allow visual differentiation of the species through morphometric analyses. Despite the large intraspecific variability found, both in body size and colour pattern, differences between both species could be observed in the eyes (**Figure 10**). Specifically, while *Lepromoris gibba* presented eyes with uniform curvature (zenith in the middle of the eye), *Lepromoris* sp. nov. presented eyes with greater convexity and eccentric curvature (zenith displaced towards the outer margin of the eye). The absence of notable differences in the male genitalia of both species is in agreement with what has been observed in other species of the subfamily Lamiinae, especially in the tribe Dorcadionini (Hernández, 2000; Hernández & Ortuño, 1992). Thus, in the case of *Lepromoris*, the genitalia is not an informative taxonomic character (**Figure 8**). This lack of difference in the genitalia has also been observed in other arthropod groups, such as spiders, in particular in the genus *Psilochorus* Simon, 1893 (Huber *et al.*, 2005).

Additionally, the geographical distribution of the new species, which occurs in the easternmost islands of Fuerteventura and Gran Canaria and the western region of El Hierro, does not overlap with that of the known species *Lepromoris gibba*, which occurs in Tenerife, La Gomera, La Palma and the eastern and southern areas of El Hierro. However, it is only on El Hierro that both species are found, although they do not occur in the same regions. The disjunct distribution of *Lepromoris* sp. nov., with observations in El Hierro and Gran Canaria, without any presence in the central islands of Tenerife, La Gomera and La Palma, is a distribution pattern also documented in other endemic species of the Canary Islands. For example, the Gekkonidae *Tarentola boettgeri* Steindachner, 1891, whose distribution in the Canary Islands is limited to Gran Canaria and El Hierro, with simultaneous presence on the Salvagens Islands (Salvador & Brown, 2009), or the Asteraceae *Carduus baeocephalus* Webb, with the same pattern

El Hierro-Gran Canaria (von Gaisberg, 2002). Although it is not the same species, the dipteran genus *Ruppellia* Wideman, 1830 has only two endemic species, one of which is found only on El Hierro and the other on Gran Canaria (Báez, 1982).

El Hierro: epicentre of three different Leptomoris lineages and colonizations

While the nuclear genomic separation between both species in El Hierro is completely clear (**Figure 3** and **Figure 4**), an additional *Leptomoris gibba* lineage, specifically RES individuals, was identified as being genetically distinct from the remaining *Leptomoris gibba* specimens, both in terms of nuclear DNA (**Figures 4** to **6**) and mitochondrial DNA (**Figure 2**). One of the two mtDNA *Leptomoris gibba* lineages sampled on El Hierro, the one formed by RES individuals, includes the only sequenced individual from La Palma (**Figure 2**). However, ddRADseq data places this individual from La Palma together with Tenerife and La Gomera, and not with individuals from RES (**Figure 5**). This incongruence prevents categorisation of the individuals from RES as a species other than *Leptomoris gibba*. An alternative hypothesis is that the individual from La Palma suffered mitochondrial introgression (e.g. Mischler *et al.*, 2018; Sloan *et al.*, 2017), which could explain the lack of congruence between mitochondrial and nuclear genomic data for this individual (e.g. Muñoz *et al.*, 2011). While no observable differences in morphology were detected between the two El Hierro lineages within C2, further genetic analysis of additional material from La Palma is required to ascertain the precise dynamics of *Leptomoris* populations on this island. Additionally, the employment of advanced morphological techniques, such as Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM), to meticulously examine the integument or stridulation plates, holds the potential to unveil distinguishing characteristics between the *Leptomoris* lineages, particularly within the El Hierro specimens. This approach has been successfully employed in analogous studies on other arthropods (e.g. Davranoglou *et al.*, 2023; Polilov *et al.*, 2019; Zych *et al.*, 2012).

A close examination of the STRUCTURE pattern for the island of El Hierro (**Figure 4**) and the genetic inferences displayed in the SNAPP tree (**Figure 6**) reveals compelling evidence of at least three distinct colonisations on the island by three separate *Leptomoris* lineages: one from *Leptomoris* sp. nov., most likely from Gran Canaria given the younger age of El Hierro; and two more from *Leptomoris gibba* populations. It is plausible that one of these *Leptomoris gibba* lineages may originate

from La Gomera, given the recent discoveries concerning the primary *Lepromoris* host plant, *Euphorbia canariensis*. This is supported by the findings of Coello *et al.* (2024), who identified La Gomera as the epicentre of *Euphorbia canariensis* colonization in the Canary Islands. The other El Hierro lineage, observing the findings of Coello *et al.* (2024) and the evident nuclear genomic separation observed between Tenerife and El Hierro in our results (**Figures 5** and **Figure 6**), may have originated from La Palma.

Lepromoris: opportunities for future research

A future approach that may prove fruitful would be to utilise ddRADseq to study the potential contact points between the three lineages present in El Hierro. This strategy would allow for the rejection of any potential hybridisation and would serve to provide stronger evidence that these lineages are indeed reproductively isolated. It would be interesting, given that the habitat of both species, the *Euphorbia* shrublands, constitutes a continuous habitat along the coastal areas of the island of El Hierro, to determine the point at which both species could converge, if such a point exists. Secondly, concerning the two lineages of El Hierro *Lepromoris gibba*, it would be worthwhile to ascertain the point at which both lineages overlap and to determine the genetic implications for the individuals involved, determining whether a genetic mixture occurs or not. It is also feasible to conduct an *ex situ* experiment with these individuals to test for sexual incompatibility. However, it is conceivable that there is no zone of sympatry between the different lineages of El Hierro. An alternative research line could involve the aforementioned phylogeography of one of its main host plants, *Euphorbia canariensis* (Coello *et al.*, 2024). The diversification patterns of the genus *Lepromoris* within the archipelago could be established by dating a mitochondrial or nuclear genomic tree with events such as the dispersal of *Euphorbia canariensis* or the age of the Canary Islands with BEAST (Bouckaert *et al.*, 2014). Ideally, it would be convenient to increase sampling on islands such as La Palma and La Gomera due to the low number of individuals available, as well as on the island of Lanzarote, where the genus *Lepromoris* is recorded, but no specimen has been obtained for this thesis and no specimens have been found in the collections consulted. Given its proximity to Fuerteventura and the geological history of the islands, where both formed a single island (Troll & Carracedo, 2016), it is hypothesised that the species inhabiting Lanzarote is *Lepromoris* sp. nov. A more extensive sampling on each island would provide a more comprehensive understanding of the origin and diversification of the genus *Lepromoris* in the Canary archipelago.

Conclusions

In this study, we demonstrate the efficacy of integrating morphological and genetic techniques as a methodological approach for the inference of new cryptic species. We also illustrate the significant effectiveness of combining barcoding with ddRAD sequencing in elucidating diversification patterns of recently diverged species complexes, as has been observed in other species complexes, such as *Geomitopsis franzi* (Pérez-Delgado *et al.*, 2022) and *Pardosa* species (Ivanov *et al.*, 2021). Consequently, the meticulous examination of endemic species inhabiting multiple islands, whose identity is presumed due to their broad distribution and abundance, is revealed to be essential for enhancing our comprehension of biodiversity, unveiling potential cryptic species, and consequently, refining conservation policies.

Supplementary material

- **Figure S1.** Number of reads per individual before and after different quality filtering steps by IPYRAD.
- **Figure S2.** Mean (\pm SD) log probability of the data ($\text{LnPr}(X|K)$) over 10 runs of STRUCTURE (left axes and open dots) for each value of K and the magnitude of ΔK (right axes, black dots and continuous line) for analyses based on all individuals analysed by ddRADseq (N= 65).
- **Figure S3.** Mean (\pm SD) log probability of the data ($\text{LnPr}(X|K)$) over 10 runs of STRUCTURE (left axes and open dots) for each value of K and the magnitude of ΔK (right axes, black dots and continuous line) for analyses based exclusively on El Hierro individuals (N= 25).
- **Figure S4.** Mean (\pm SD) log probability of the data ($\text{LnPr}(X|K)$) over 10 runs of STRUCTURE (left axes and open dots) for each value of K and the magnitude of ΔK (right axes, black dots and continuous line) for analyses based exclusively on *Leptomoris gibba* individuals, mitochondrial clade C2 (N= 42).
- **Figure S5.** Graphic comparison of the 32 measurements done on the selected males of the two inferred mitochondrial clades, with clear overlapping between *Leptomoris* sp. nov. (red) and *Leptomoris gibba* (blue).
- **Table S1.** Sampling plots location and *Leptomoris* individuals sampled per plot.
- **Table S2.** List of the 65 individuals selected for ddRAD sequencing and number of reads recover.
- **Table S3.** List of barcoded individual included on MrBayes analysis.
- **Table S4.** Results for the 32 measurements carried out on five males of *Leptomoris* sp. nov.
- **Table S5.** Results for the 32 measurements carried out on five males of *Leptomoris gibba*.

Figure S1. Number of reads per individual before and after different quality filtering steps by IPYRAD (see Table S2 for more information about individuals). The cumulative stacked bars represent the total number of raw reads obtained for each individual. Within each bar, the black color represents the reads that were discarded by IPYRAD after filtering out reads that did not comply with the quality criteria of number of Ns and minimum length. Light grey color represents the total number of retained reads used to identify homologous loci during the subsequent steps performed in IPYRAD. Black horizontal line indicates the average number of reads across all individuals ($n = 65$). Population codes as in Table S2.

Figure S2. Mean (\pm SD) log probability of the data ($\text{LnPr}(X|K)$) over 10 runs of STRUCTURE (left axes and open dots) for each value of K and the magnitude of ΔK (right axes, black dots and continuous line) for analyses based on all individuals sampled ($N= 65$) belonging to both inferred mitochondrial clades.

Figure S3. Mean (\pm SD) log probability of the data ($\text{LnPr}(X|K)$) over 10 runs of STRUCTURE (left axes and open dots) for each value of K and the magnitude of ΔK (right axes, black dots and continuous line) for analyses based exclusively on El Hierro individuals ($N=25$).

Figure S4. Mean (\pm SD) log probability of the data ($\text{LnPr}(X|K)$) over 10 runs of STRUCTURE (left axes and open dots) for each value of K and the magnitude of ΔK (right axes, black dots and continuous line) for analyses based exclusively on *Lepromoris gibba* individuals ($N=42$), inferred mitochondrial clade C2.

Chapter III

■ *Lepromoris* sp. nov. ■ *Lepromoris gibba*

Figure S5. Graphic comparison using 'ggplot2' and 'ggpubr' packages on R of the 32 measurements done for the selected males of *Lepromoris* sp. nov. (red) and *Lepromoris gibba* (blue). The lower numbers represent measurements in millimetres, whilst the vertical numbers denote the number of individuals that have achieved the measured value.

Table S1. Sampling plots location (order by longitude) and *Lepromoris* individuals sampled per plot. Clade denotes the mtDNA group inferred on the Bayesian inference phylogenetic consensus tree.

Plot Code	Plot name	Island	Latitude	Longitude	Individuals sampled	Adults	Clade
VBR	Vallebrón	Fuerteventura	28.5839	-13.9321	5	3♂, 2♀	C1
BET	Betancuria, Mirador Guise y Ayoze	Fuerteventura	28.4409	-14.0565	1	1♂	C1
MAB	Mundo Aborigen	Gran Canaria	27.8129	-15.5811	12	2♂, 1♀	C1
BAR	Barranco de Arguineguín	Gran Canaria	27.7984	-15.6686	9	1♂, 2♀	C1
AGA	Agate	Gran Canaria	28.0936	-15.6818	7	1♂	C1
CUE	Cuermeja	Gran Canaria	27.9826	-15.8074	2	2♂	C1
IG1	Bco. Igueste de San Andrés	Tenerife	28.5332	-16.1595	1	1♂	C2
SN3	Bco. de San Andrés III	Tenerife	28.5201	-16.1902	2	1♂, 1♀	C2
SN2	Bco. de San Andrés II	Tenerife	28.5299	-16.1945	5	4♂, 1♀	C2
BRO	Valle Brosque	Tenerife	28.5191	-16.2281	7	5♂, 2♀	C2
CHI	Chinamada	Tenerife	28.5634	-16.2928	1	1♂	C2
GUI	Malpaís de Güimar	Tenerife	28.2997	-16.3711	7	3♂	C2
PTB	Punta del Tablero	Tenerife	28.0961	-16.4914	1	1♂	C2
MIF	Montaña de Ifara	Tenerife	28.0931	-16.5292	1	1♂	C2
TN2	El Palmar	Tenerife	28.3576	-16.8431	2	2♀	C2
TN3	Bco. Carrizales	Tenerife	28.3198	-16.8677	2	1♂, 1♀	C2
TN1	Punta de Teno	Tenerife	28.3473	-16.9118	1	1♂	C2
SSE	San Sebastián	La Gomera	28.1037	-17.1181	5	2♂, 2♀	C2
TGA	Tamargada	La Gomera	28.1955	-17.2478	1	1♀	C2
SAL	La Salemera	La Palma	28.5751	-17.7676	1	1♂	C2
AEH	Aeropuerto de El Hierro	El Hierro	27.8133	-17.8849	1	1♀	C2
VAL	Road between Valverde and La Caleta	El Hierro	27.8086	-17.8987	12	0	C2
EOL	Parque Eólico Valverde	El Hierro	27.7909	-17.9163	1	1♀	C2
RES	La Restinga	El Hierro	27.6602	-17.9755	7	4♂, 2♀	C2
ABL	Arenas blancas	El Hierro	27.7663	-18.1271	10	0	C1
CBE	Cruz de Bernardo	El Hierro	27.7339	-18.1405	2	1♀	C1
SAB	Sabinar La Dehesa	El Hierro	27.7511	-18.1425	19	3♂, 8♀	C1
MLO	Mirador Lomo Negro II	El Hierro	27.7548	-18.1428	5	3♂, 2♀	C1

Table S2. List of the 65 individuals selected for ddRAD sequencing and number of reads recover.

Individual name	Plot name	Population code	Island	Clade	Reads obtained	Reads retained after filtering
EHAreBla1579	Arenas Blancas	ABL	El Hierro	C1	1147340	1141582
EHAreBla1580	Arenas Blancas	ABL	El Hierro	C1	620259	618160
EHAreBla1581	Arenas Blancas	ABL	El Hierro	C1	476084	475191
EHAreBla1583	Arenas Blancas	ABL	El Hierro	C1	1657312	1644750
EHAreBla1584	Arenas Blancas	ABL	El Hierro	C1	934564	931940
EHDehesa1558	Sabinar La Dehesa	SAB	El Hierro	C1	1106915	1103662
EHDehesa1559	Sabinar La Dehesa	SAB	El Hierro	C1	997683	990635
EHDehesa1563	Sabinar La Dehesa	SAB	El Hierro	C1	1214627	1201986
EHDehesa1564	Sabinar La Dehesa	SAB	El Hierro	C1	1152280	1147072
EHDehesa1571	Sabinar La Dehesa	SAB	El Hierro	C1	658514	655653
EHDehesa1572	Sabinar La Dehesa	SAB	El Hierro	C1	386373	385466
EHParEol1550	Parque Eólico Valverde	EOL	El Hierro	C2	1138129	1134978
EHRestin1551	La Restinga	RES	El Hierro	C2	307139	305927
EHRestin1552	La Restinga	RES	El Hierro	C2	903384	898833
EHRestin1553	La Restinga	RES	El Hierro	C2	1493829	1486307
EHRestin1554	La Restinga	RES	El Hierro	C2	891468	886210
EHRestin1555	La Restinga	RES	El Hierro	C2	927101	924244
EHRestin1556	La Restinga	RES	El Hierro	C2	839803	836325
EHRestin1557	La Restinga	RES	El Hierro	C2	929762	926287
LPSalame1535	La Salemera	SAL	La Palma	C2	877465	869192
EHAerHie1562	Aeropuerto de El Hierro	AEH	El Hierro	C2	1239721	1234270
EHValCal1587	Road between Valverde and La Caleta	VAL	El Hierro	C2	1398032	1391762
EHValCal1588	Road between Valverde and La Caleta	VAL	El Hierro	C2	701921	700764
EHValCal1589	Road between Valverde and La Caleta	VAL	El Hierro	C2	1393611	1387028
EHValCal1590	Road between Valverde and La Caleta	VAL	El Hierro	C2	852254	850747
EHValCal1591	Road between Valverde and La Caleta	VAL	El Hierro	C2	1559866	1552074
GCAgaete1601	Agaete	AGA	Gran Canaria	C1	920638	918041
GCAgaete1602	Agaete	AGA	Gran Canaria	C1	1825400	1820493
GCAgaete1603	Agaete	AGA	Gran Canaria	C1	1486114	1477036
GCAgaete1604	Agaete	AGA	Gran Canaria	C1	1915129	1907064
GCAgaete1607	Agaete	AGA	Gran Canaria	C1	417593	416736
GCBcoArg1608	Barranco de Arguineguín	BAR	Gran Canaria	C1	1357612	1351347
GCBcoArg1609	Barranco de Arguineguín	BAR	Gran Canaria	C1	587890	586555
GCBcoArg1610	Barranco de Arguineguín	BAR	Gran Canaria	C1	1383348	1379247
GCBcoArg1611	Barranco de Arguineguín	BAR	Gran Canaria	C1	1010731	1003696

Individual name	Plot name	Population code	Island	Clade	Reads obtained	Reads retained after filtering
GCBcoArg1613	Barranco de Arguineguín	BAR	Gran Canaria	C1	3065512	3049712
GCMunAbo1617	Mundo Aborigen	MAB	Gran Canaria	C1	956290	954699
GCMunAbo1618	Mundo Aborigen	MAB	Gran Canaria	C1	586721	586070
LGSanSeb1546	San Sebastián	SSE	La Gomera	C2	904204	897361
LGSanSeb1547	San Sebastián	SSE	La Gomera	C2	1076285	1070414
LGSanSeb1548	San Sebastián	SSE	La Gomera	C2	983438	978786
LGSanSeb1549	San Sebastián	SSE	La Gomera	C2	1051460	1047412
LGTamarg1545	Tamargada	TGA	La Gomera	C2	1395361	1385566
TFBcoAnd1521	Bco. de San Andrés II	SN2	Tenerife	C2	906065	903153
TFBcoAnd1523	Bco. de San Andrés II	SN2	Tenerife	C2	769639	766754
TFBcoAnd1524	Bco. de San Andrés II	SN2	Tenerife	C2	577808	575749
TFBcoAnd1526	Bco. de San Andrés III	SN3	Tenerife	C2	1083979	1077936
TFBcoAnd1527	Bco. de San Andrés III	SN3	Tenerife	C2	710671	707458
TFBcoIgu1528	Bco. Iguete de San Andrés	IG1	Tenerife	C2	815439	811741
TFCarriz1530	Bco. Carrizales	TN3	Tenerife	C2	791141	787289
TFCarriz1531	Bco. Carrizales	TN3	Tenerife	C2	917852	913427
TFChinam1534	Chinamada	CHI	Tenerife	C2	973548	964913
TFGuimar1536	Malpaís de Güimar	GUI	Tenerife	C2	676569	672312
TFGuimar1537	Malpaís de Güimar	GUI	Tenerife	C2	686579	683636
TFGuimar1539	Malpaís de Güimar	GUI	Tenerife	C2	1058491	1049961
TFGuimar1542	Malpaís de Güimar	GUI	Tenerife	C2	901844	896742
TFMonIfa1533	Montaña de Ifara	MIF	Tenerife	C2	855416	847535
TFPalmar11544	El Palmar	TN2	Tenerife	C2	1274666	1264954
TFPalmar1543	El Palmar	TN2	Tenerife	C2	1078012	1071739
TFPunTab1532	Punta del Tablero	PTB	Tenerife	C2	1090258	1083917
TFPunTen1529	Punta de Teno	TN1	Tenerife	C2	690799	688325
TFValBro1514	Valle Brosque	BRO	Tenerife	C2	412129	410516
TFValBro1516	Valle Brosque	BRO	Tenerife	C2	670672	668496
TFValBro1517	Valle Brosque	BRO	Tenerife	C2	600901	599560
TFValBro1518	Valle Brosque	BRO	Tenerife	C2	862481	859117

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Table S3. List of barcoded individual included on MrBayes analysis and ddRADseq. ‘---’ Denoted individuals with barcode but not used on ddRAD sequencing. Specimen from Chinamada (**Table S2**) was used for ddRAD sequencing with code “TFChinam1534” but it was not possible to obtain its barcode sequence.

Individual	Species	Island	Plot	Clade	ddRAD sequencing code	Status	GenBank Accession number
BC001514	<i>Lepromoris gibba</i>	Tenerife	BRO	C2	TFValBro1514	Adult	PQ275933
BC001515	<i>Lepromoris gibba</i>	Tenerife	BRO	C2	TFValBro1516	Adult	PQ275934
BC001516	<i>Lepromoris gibba</i>	Tenerife	BRO	C2	TFValBro1517	Adult	PQ275935
BC001517	<i>Lepromoris gibba</i>	Tenerife	BRO	C2	TFValBro1518	Adult	PQ275936
BC001518	<i>Lepromoris gibba</i>	Tenerife	BRO	C2	---	Adult	PQ275937
BC001519	<i>Lepromoris gibba</i>	Tenerife	BRO	C2	---	Adult	PQ275938
BC001520	<i>Lepromoris gibba</i>	Tenerife	BRO	C2	---	Adult	PQ275939
BC001521	<i>Lepromoris gibba</i>	Tenerife	SN2	C2	TFBcoAnd1521	Adult	PQ275940
BC001522	<i>Lepromoris gibba</i>	Tenerife	SN2	C2	---	Adult	PQ275941
BC001523	<i>Lepromoris gibba</i>	Tenerife	SN2	C2	TFBcoAnd1523	Adult	PQ275942
BC001524	<i>Lepromoris gibba</i>	Tenerife	SN2	C2	TFBcoAnd1524	Adult	PQ275943
BC001525	<i>Lepromoris gibba</i>	Tenerife	SN2	C2	---	Adult	PQ275944
BC001526	<i>Lepromoris gibba</i>	Tenerife	SN3	C2	TFBcoAnd1526	Adult	PQ275945
BC001527	<i>Lepromoris gibba</i>	Tenerife	SN3	C2	TFBcoAnd1527	Adult	PQ275946
BC001528	<i>Lepromoris gibba</i>	Tenerife	IG1	C2	TFBcoIgu1528	Adult	PQ275947
BC001529	<i>Lepromoris gibba</i>	Tenerife	TN1	C2	TFPunTen1529	Adult	PQ275948
BC001530	<i>Lepromoris gibba</i>	Tenerife	TN3	C2	TFCarriz1530	Adult	PQ275949
BC001531	<i>Lepromoris gibba</i>	Tenerife	TN3	C2	TFCarriz1531	Adult	PQ275950
BC001532	<i>Lepromoris gibba</i>	Tenerife	PTB	C2	TFPunTab1532	Adult	PQ275951
BC001533	<i>Lepromoris gibba</i>	Tenerife	MIF	C2	TFMonIfa1533	Adult	PQ275952
BC001535	<i>Lepromoris gibba</i>	La Palma	SAL	C2	LPSalame1535	Adult	PQ275953
BC001536	<i>Lepromoris gibba</i>	Tenerife	GUI	C2	TFGuimar1536	Larvae	PQ275954
BC001537	<i>Lepromoris gibba</i>	Tenerife	GUI	C2	TFGuimar1537	Larvae	PQ275955
BC001538	<i>Lepromoris gibba</i>	Tenerife	GUI	C2	---	Larvae	PQ275956
BC001539	<i>Lepromoris gibba</i>	Tenerife	GUI	C2	TFGuimar1539	Larvae	PQ275957
BC001540	<i>Lepromoris gibba</i>	Tenerife	GUI	C2	---	Adult	PQ275958
BC001541	<i>Lepromoris gibba</i>	Tenerife	GUI	C2	---	Adult	PQ275959
BC001542	<i>Lepromoris gibba</i>	Tenerife	GUI	C2	TFGuimar1542	Adult	PQ275960
BC001543	<i>Lepromoris gibba</i>	Tenerife	TN2	C2	TFPalmar1543	Adult	PQ275961
BC001544	<i>Lepromoris gibba</i>	Tenerife	TN2	C2	TFPalmar1544	Adult	PQ275962
BC001545	<i>Lepromoris gibba</i>	La Gomera	TGA	C2	LGTamarg1545	Adult	PQ275963
BC001546	<i>Lepromoris gibba</i>	La Gomera	SSE	C2	LGSanSeb1546	Adult	PQ275964
BC001547	<i>Lepromoris gibba</i>	La Gomera	SSE	C2	LGSanSeb1547	Adult	PQ275965
BC001548	<i>Lepromoris gibba</i>	La Gomera	SSE	C2	LGSanSeb1548	Adult	PQ275966
BC001549	<i>Lepromoris gibba</i>	La Gomera	SSE	C2	LGSanSeb1549	Adult	PQ275967
BC001550	<i>Lepromoris gibba</i>	El Hierro	EOL	C2	EHParEol1550	Adult	PQ275968
BC001551	<i>Lepromoris gibba</i>	El Hierro	RES	C2	EHRestin1551	Larvae	PQ275969
BC001552	<i>Lepromoris gibba</i>	El Hierro	RES	C2	EHRestin1552	Adult	PQ275970
BC001553	<i>Lepromoris gibba</i>	El Hierro	RES	C2	EHRestin1553	Adult	PQ275971

Individual	Species	Island	Plot	Clade	ddRAD sequencing code	Status	GenBank Accession number
BC001554	<i>Lepromoris gibba</i>	El Hierro	RES	C2	EHRestin1554	Adult	PQ275972
BC001555	<i>Lepromoris gibba</i>	El Hierro	RES	C2	EHRestin1555	Adult	PQ275973
BC001556	<i>Lepromoris gibba</i>	El Hierro	RES	C2	EHRestin1556	Adult	PQ275974
BC001557	<i>Lepromoris gibba</i>	El Hierro	RES	C2	EHRestin1557	Adult	PQ275975
BC001558	<i>Lepromoris</i> sp. nov.	El Hierro	SAB	C1	EHDehesa1558	Adult	PQ275976
BC001559	<i>Lepromoris</i> sp. nov.	El Hierro	SAB	C1	EHDehesa1559	Adult	PQ275977
BC001560	<i>Lepromoris</i> sp. nov.	El Hierro	SAB	C1	---	Larvae	PQ275978
BC001561	<i>Lepromoris</i> sp. nov.	Fuerteventura	BET	C1	---	Adult	PQ275979
BC001562	<i>Lepromoris gibba</i>	El Hierro	AEH	C2	EHAerHie1562	Adult	PQ275980
BC001563	<i>Lepromoris</i> sp. nov.	El Hierro	SAB	C1	EHDehesa1563	Adult	PQ275981
BC001564	<i>Lepromoris</i> sp. nov.	El Hierro	SAB	C1	EHDehesa1564	Adult	PQ275982
BC001565	<i>Lepromoris</i> sp. nov.	El Hierro	SAB	C1	---	Adult	PQ275983
BC001566	<i>Lepromoris</i> sp. nov.	El Hierro	SAB	C1	---	Adult	PQ275984
BC001567	<i>Lepromoris</i> sp. nov.	El Hierro	SAB	C1	---	Adult	PQ275985
BC001568	<i>Lepromoris</i> sp. nov.	El Hierro	SAB	C1	---	Adult	PQ275986
BC001569	<i>Lepromoris</i> sp. nov.	El Hierro	SAB	C1	---	Larvae	PQ275987
BC001570	<i>Lepromoris</i> sp. nov.	El Hierro	SAB	C1	---	Larvae	PQ275988
BC001571	<i>Lepromoris</i> sp. nov.	El Hierro	SAB	C1	EHDehesa1571	Larvae	PQ275989
BC001572	<i>Lepromoris</i> sp. nov.	El Hierro	SAB	C1	EHDehesa1572	Larvae	PQ275990
BC001573	<i>Lepromoris</i> sp. nov.	El Hierro	SAB	C1	---	Larvae	PQ275991
BC001574	<i>Lepromoris</i> sp. nov.	El Hierro	SAB	C1	---	Larvae	PQ275992
BC001575	<i>Lepromoris</i> sp. nov.	El Hierro	SAB	C1	---	Larvae	PQ275993
BC001576	<i>Lepromoris</i> sp. nov.	El Hierro	ABL	C1	---	Larvae	PQ275994
BC001577	<i>Lepromoris</i> sp. nov.	El Hierro	ABL	C1	---	Larvae	PQ275995
BC001578	<i>Lepromoris</i> sp. nov.	El Hierro	ABL	C1	---	Larvae	PQ275996
BC001579	<i>Lepromoris</i> sp. nov.	El Hierro	ABL	C1	EHAreBla1579	Larvae	PQ275997
BC001580	<i>Lepromoris</i> sp. nov.	El Hierro	ABL	C1	EHAreBla1580	Larvae	PQ275998
BC001581	<i>Lepromoris</i> sp. nov.	El Hierro	ABL	C1	EHAreBla1581	Larvae	PQ275999
BC001583	<i>Lepromoris</i> sp. nov.	El Hierro	ABL	C1	EHAreBla1583	Larvae	PQ276000

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Individual	Species	Island	Plot	Clade	ddRAD sequencing code	Status	GenBank Accession number
BC001584	<i>Lepromoris</i> sp. nov.	El Hierro	ABL	C1	EHAreBla1584	Larvae	PQ276001
BC001585	<i>Lepromoris</i> sp. nov.	El Hierro	ABL	C1	---	Larvae	PQ276002
BC001586	<i>Lepromoris</i> sp. nov.	El Hierro	ABL	C1	---	Larvae	PQ276003
BC001587	<i>Lepromoris gibba</i>	El Hierro	VAL	C2	EHValCal1587	Larvae	PQ276004
BC001588	<i>Lepromoris gibba</i>	El Hierro	VAL	C2	EHValCal1588	Larvae	PQ276005
BC001589	<i>Lepromoris gibba</i>	El Hierro	VAL	C2	EHValCal1589	Larvae	PQ276006
BC001590	<i>Lepromoris gibba</i>	El Hierro	VAL	C2	EHValCal1590	Larvae	PQ276007
BC001591	<i>Lepromoris gibba</i>	El Hierro	VAL	C2	EHValCal1591	Larvae	PQ276008
BC001592	<i>Lepromoris gibba</i>	El Hierro	VAL	C2	---	Larvae	PQ276009
BC001594	<i>Lepromoris gibba</i>	El Hierro	VAL	C2	---	Larvae	PQ276010
BC001595	<i>Lepromoris gibba</i>	El Hierro	VAL	C2	---	Larvae	PQ276011
BC001596	<i>Lepromoris gibba</i>	El Hierro	VAL	C2	---	Larvae	PQ276012
BC001597	<i>Lepromoris gibba</i>	El Hierro	VAL	C2	---	Larvae	PQ276013
BC001598	<i>Lepromoris gibba</i>	El Hierro	VAL	C2	---	Larvae	PQ276014
BC001601	<i>Lepromoris</i> sp. nov.	Gran Canaria	AGA	C1	GCAgaete1601	Adult	PQ276015
BC001602	<i>Lepromoris</i> sp. nov.	Gran Canaria	AGA	C1	GCAgaete1602	Larvae	PQ276016
BC001603	<i>Lepromoris</i> sp. nov.	Gran Canaria	AGA	C1	GCAgaete1603	Larvae	PQ276017
BC001604	<i>Lepromoris</i> sp. nov.	Gran Canaria	AGA	C1	GCAgaete1604	Larvae	PQ276018
BC001605	<i>Lepromoris</i> sp. nov.	Gran Canaria	AGA	C1	---	Larvae	PQ276019
BC001606	<i>Lepromoris</i> sp. nov.	Gran Canaria	AGA	C1	---	Larvae	PQ276020
BC001607	<i>Lepromoris</i> sp. nov.	Gran Canaria	AGA	C1	GCAgaete1607	Larvae	PQ276021
BC001608	<i>Lepromoris</i> sp. nov.	Gran Canaria	BAR	C1	GCBcoArg1608	Larvae	PQ276022
BC001609	<i>Lepromoris</i> sp. nov.	Gran Canaria	BAR	C1	GCBcoArg1609	Larvae	PQ276023
BC001610	<i>Lepromoris</i> sp. nov.	Gran Canaria	BAR	C1	GCBcoArg1610	Larvae	PQ276024
BC001611	<i>Lepromoris</i> sp. nov.	Gran Canaria	BAR	C1	GCBcoArg1611	Larvae	PQ276025
BC001612	<i>Lepromoris</i> sp. nov.	Gran Canaria	BAR	C1	---	Larvae	PQ276026
BC001613	<i>Lepromoris</i> sp. nov.	Gran Canaria	BAR	C1	GCBcoArg1613	Larvae	PQ276027
BC001614	<i>Lepromoris</i> sp. nov.	Gran Canaria	MAB	C1	---	Larvae	PQ276028
BC001615	<i>Lepromoris</i> sp. nov.	Gran Canaria	MAB	C1	---	Larvae	PQ276029
BC001616	<i>Lepromoris</i> sp. nov.	Gran Canaria	MAB	C1	GCMunAbo1617	Larvae	PQ276030
BC001617	<i>Lepromoris</i> sp. nov.	Gran Canaria	MAB	C1	GCMunAbo1618	Larvae	PQ276031
BC001618	<i>Lepromoris</i> sp. nov.	Gran Canaria	MAB	C1	---	Larvae	PQ276032

Individual	Species	Island	Plot	Clade	ddRAD sequencing code	Status	GenBank Accession number
BC001619	<i>Lepromoris</i> sp. nov.	Gran Canaria	MAB	C1	---	Larvae	PQ276033
BC001620	<i>Lepromoris</i> sp. nov.	Gran Canaria	MAB	C1	---	Larvae	PQ276034
BC001621	<i>Lepromoris</i> sp. nov.	Gran Canaria	MAB	C1	---	Larvae	PQ276035
BC001622	<i>Lepromoris</i> sp. nov.	Gran Canaria	MAB	C1	---	Larvae	PQ276036
BC001690	<i>Lepromoris gibba</i>	La Gomera	SSE	C2	---	Larvae	PQ276037
BC001700	<i>Lepromoris</i> sp. nov.	Gran Canaria	MAB	C1	---	Adult	PQ276038
BC001869	<i>Lepromoris</i> sp. nov.	El Hierro	CBE	C1	---	Larvae	PQ276039
BC001871	<i>Lepromoris</i> sp. nov.	Fuerteventura	VBR	C1	---	Adult	PQ276040
BC001872	<i>Lepromoris</i> sp. nov.	Fuerteventura	VBR	C1	---	Adult	PQ276041
BC001873	<i>Lepromoris</i> sp. nov.	Fuerteventura	VBR	C1	---	Adult	PQ276042
BC001874	<i>Lepromoris</i> sp. nov.	Fuerteventura	VBR	C1	---	Adult	PQ276043
BC001875	<i>Lepromoris</i> sp. nov.	Fuerteventura	VBR	C1	---	Adult	PQ276044

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Table S4. Results for the 32 measurements performed on five males of *Lepromoris* sp. nov. See **Table S3** for more information on the selected individuals. All measurements are in millimetres.

Measurement (in mm)	BC001568	BC001559	BC001700	BC001561	BC001567
Body size	16.95	20.1	16.92	17.62	14.06
Maximum head width	4.06	4.87	4.42	4.3	3.32
Maximum head width (eye level)	4.15	4.92	4.28	4.24	3.34
Head length	1.42	1.75	1.58	1.51	1.24
Eye width	0.23	0.28	0.27	0.23	0.19
Face height	2.6	3.38	2.99	2.78	2.32
Face width	2.72	3.37	2.8	2.85	2.31
Pronotum width (anterior edge)	4.59	5.47	5.08	4.88	3.82
Pronotum width (posterior edge)	4.38	5.27	4.68	4.75	3.54
Maximum pronotum width	6.25	7.38	5.92	6.59	5.01
Pronotum length	3.75	4.55	4.13	3.9	3.05
Pronotal spike length	0.81	1.15	0.6	0.95	0.72
Position of pronotal spikes with respect to the anterior edge	2.09	2.66	2.4	2.12	1.68
Elytra length	11.78	13.8	11.21	12.21	9.77
Maximum elytra width	7.24	8.45	7.28	7.53	6.02
Maximum length of antennomere 1	2.77	3.24	2.89	2.97	2.21
Maximum length of antennomere 2	1.14	1.17	1.04	0.95	0.85
Maximum width of antennomere 2	0.63	0.73	0.66	0.65	0.54
Minimum width of antennomere 2	0.39	0.48	0.42	0.4	0.37
Maximum length of antennomere 3	2.95	3.29	2.96	3.09	2.45
Maximum length of antennomere 4	3.24	3.66	3.29	3.23	2.66
Maximum length of antennomere 5	2.58	2.73	2.45	2.66	2.12
Maximum length of antennomere 6	2.31	2.37	2.23	2.26	1.81
Maximum length of antennomere 7	2.1	2.26	2.1	2.08	1.73
Maximum length of antennomere 8	1.88	2.11	1.93	1.79	1.5
Maximum length of antennomere 9	1.7	1.88	1.71	1.7	1.45
Maximum length of antennomere 10	1.66	1.75	1.56	1.5	1.32
Maximum length of antennomere 11	1.65	1.79	1.51	1.4	1.21
Length of tarsomere I	1.49	1.55	1.64	1.73	1.24
Length of tarsomere II	0.74	0.94	0.89	0.9	0.71
Length of tarsomere III	0.87	1.01	0.98	0.91	0.82
Length of tarsomere IV	1.26	1.45	1.24	1.4	1.07

Table S5. Results for the 32 measurements performed on five males of *Leptomoris gibba*. See **Table S3** for more information on the selected individuals. All measurements are in millimetres.

Measurement (in mm)	BC001521	BC001518	BC001540	BC001546	BC001529
Body size	17.75	19.09	12.38	18.21	16.05
Maximum head width	3.99	4.44	2.92	4.64	3.72
Maximum head width (eye level)	3.79	4.32	2.87	4.39	3.61
Head length	1.36	1.45	1.1	1.43	1.36
Eye width	0.18	0.22	0.15	0.24	0.2
Face height	2.67	2.85	1.98	3.01	2.56
Face width	2.61	2.92	1.98	2.93	2.42
Pronotum width (anterior edge)	4.6	5.21	3.43	5.06	4.15
Pronotum width (posterior edge)	4.57	5.08	3.3	4.97	4.09
Maximum pronotum width	6.33	7.1	4.32	7.03	5.83
Pronotum length	3.86	4.19	2.69	3.99	3.53
Pronotal spike length	0.97	1.14	0.41	0.91	0.93
Position of pronotal spikes with respect to the anterior edge	2.23	2.34	1.65	2.3	2.06
Elytra length	12.53	13.45	8.59	12.79	11.16
Maximum elytra width	7.71	8.44	5.55	8.1	7.45
Maximum length of antennomere 1	2.79	3.23	2.06	3.14	2.64
Maximum length of antennomere 2	0.9	1.02	0.76	1.18	0.99
Maximum width of antennomere 2	0.62	0.66	0.5	0.72	0.6
Minimum width of antennomere 2	0.42	0.41	0.37	0.53	0.39
Maximum length of antennomere 3	3.07	3.42	2.21	3.27	2.76
Maximum length of antennomere 4	3.37	3.73	2.46	3.55	3.11
Maximum length of antennomere 5	2.81	2.95	2.01	3.05	2.74
Maximum length of antennomere 6	2.46	2.55	1.69	2.51	2.28
Maximum length of antennomere 7	2.2	2.32	1.56	2.34	1.98
Maximum length of antennomere 8	1.88	2.14	1.43	2.17	1.91
Maximum length of antennomere 9	1.76	1.97	1.31	2.01	1.67
Maximum length of antennomere 10	1.6	1.74	1.19	1.79	1.58
Maximum length of antennomere 11	1.57	1.68	1.08	1.71	1.4
Length of tarsomere I	1.53	1.66	1.31	1.68	1.59
Length of tarsomere II	1.04	1.01	0.61	1.08	0.9
Length of tarsomere III	0.94	1.21	0.64	1.1	0.87
Length of tarsomere IV	1.35	1.44	0.99	1.51	1.09

GENERAL DISCUSSION

Mitochondrial DNA: a crucial ally in the effort to conserve biodiversity.

Current technical advances and reduced sequencing costs (Srivathsan *et al.*, 2021, 2024; Wang *et al.*, 2018) have facilitated the exploration, from a genetic and more objective perspective, of various ecological and evolutionary questions affecting species conservation. For exemplification, this approach has been successfully employed to detect introduced species (Cuthbert *et al.*, 2022; Diagne *et al.*, 2021) or to facilitate challenging conservation decisions in a context of resource scarcity (Hayward & Castley, 2018). In the present thesis, thanks to genetic advances, especially those concerning mitochondrial DNA such as barcoding, the central pillar of the thesis, it has been possible to achieve the proposed objectives. In this context, we have been able to test the mechanisms that promote the successful establishment of introduced species outside their natural environment (**Chapter I**). In addition, this thesis has successfully determined the impact of genetic connectivity between island populations on the risk of extinction of endemic and native non-endemic species (**Chapter II**). Finally, the application of genetic and morphological techniques has facilitated the study of the evolutionary history and populations of a particular multi-island endemic species, resulting in the inference of a novel cryptic species (**Chapter III**).

Regarding **Chapter I**, the barcoding approach permitted the testing of a series of classical ecological hypotheses concerning the establishment of species introduced into novel habitats (Jeschke & Heger, 2018). Here, we addressed a paradox involving two antagonist hypotheses: the preadaptation hypothesis (Duncan & Williams, 2002) and the competition-relatedness hypothesis (Darwin, 1859). The present study was conducted at the community level within an endemic ecosystem, the laurel forest of the Canary Islands. Additionally, this is the first approach using Coleoptera data to test the aforementioned hypotheses. To accomplish this, in addition to the 25 laurel forest plots described in Salces-Castellano *et al.* (2021), six additional plots were sampled in accordance with the protocol described by Emerson *et al.* (2017). Consequently, the laurel beetle communities were characterised both taxonomically and genetically, and their genetic distances were calculated. The results obtained demonstrated clear support for the preadaptation hypothesis, as opposed to the alternative hypothesis of competition-relatedness. This finding was consistent with the conclusions of other researchers, such as Li *et al.* (2015) and Marx *et al.* (2016), who also reported support for the preadaptation hypothesis using plant data. The conclusions suggest that, in these cases, introduced species are more likely

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to become established, particularly in laurel forests, if they are more closely related to the endemic and native non-endemic species already present in these ecosystems. Consequently, if an introduced species is detected in sympatry with closely related native species, its eradication should be a priority before it becomes established and displaces the other related species, as is beginning to be observed in the case of the introduced species *Ocypus aethiops* (Wojas, 2021), as explained in **Chapter I**.

Additionally, the implementation of barcode sequences to characterise laurel beetle communities in **Chapter I** also facilitated the identification of new species introduced into the laurel forests. Consequently, four new records for introduced species were identified (*Corticaria fagi*, *Corticarina cavicollis*, *Ischnopterapion modestum* and *Psylliodes instabilis*), along with two new genera (*Cephennium* and *Pterostichus*) that had not been previously recorded on the islands. Unfortunately, the species within these genera could not be identified through morphology or comparison with the available genetic databases. However, the most surprising discovery arose from the comparison of our sequences with those stored in databases such as BOLD Systems (Ratnasingham & Hebert, 2007) and GenBank (Sayers *et al.*, 2020). This analysis revealed that as many as 19 species previously classified as native non-endemic are, in fact, introduced species, displaying similarities of over 99% with sequences from outside the Canary Islands, including those from countries such as Germany, China, the United States and South Africa. We refer to this as the Humboldtian shortfall, that is, our limited knowledge about the true origin of species and the possibility of considering species that are actually of introduced origin as native. The criterion applied to modify the species' status from native to introduced, i.e. the similarity of the target species' barcode to individuals from outside the region at 99% or greater, aligns with the approach adopted by Cicconardi *et al.* (2017). Utilising the same criteria, Cicconardi *et al.* (2017) recategorised lineages of springtails that were previously designated as native as introduced. While this criterion may be open to debate, it is believed to be sufficiently robust due to the time required for mutations to occur and for populations to diversify. This is supported by the findings of Papadopoulou *et al.* (2010) for Tenebrionidae beetles, whose COI gene has an estimated divergence rate of 3.54% per million years (My^{-1}). In summary, if these species had been on the islands for a considerable time, they should exhibit a significant genetic differentiation from continental populations, rather than minor differences in a few mutations. However, it is

always challenging to distinguish between natural dispersal and human-induced dispersal, although in the context of globalisation, the latter is often the most plausible.

As was demonstrated in **Chapter I**, the issue of introduced species is a growing concern in the context of climate change and globalisation (e.g. Cuthbert *et al.*, 2022; Diagne *et al.*, 2021; Early *et al.*, 2016). Consequently, it is imperative to comprehend the risk of extinction of endemic and native non-endemic species in the Canary Islands laurel forests to ensure the effective conservation of communities and ecosystem services. In **Chapter II** of this thesis, the taxonomic approach was expanded by incorporating a dataset of spiders sampled in the laurel forest (Suárez *et al.* 2022), in addition to the coleopteran data set utilised in **Chapter I**. The primary objective of **Chapter II** was to analyse the extinction risk of multi-island endemic and native non-endemic species in the Canary Islands laurel forests based on their population connectivity. To avoid potential bias, two different orders were used to infer more general conclusions. For the purpose of this study, a subset of 77 species was selected which included 49 species of Coleoptera and 28 species of Araneae, with similar proportion between endemic and native non-endemic species. The selection was made on the criteria that the species were taxonomically identified with a high degree of certainty, and that the species were sampled on multiple islands. Also, the selected dataset presented a comparable proportion of species with poor and well dispersal strategies. Thus, using mtDNA sequences and the N_{ST} index, we applied to the selected species a protocol for delimiting ESUs (Evolutionary Significant Units: Ryder, 1986; Waples, 1995) This ESUs delimitation enabled the objective utilisation of genetic data to ascertain the degree of genetic connectivity among populations of different species and their associated extinction risks.

The results of the **Chapter II** demonstrated that a significant proportion of multi-island endemic (MIE) and native non-endemic (MINE) species comprise two or more ESUs. This finding suggested that many island populations within multi-island species may be genetically independent of each other. Consequently, these populations may be conceptually closer to single island endemic (SIE) or native non-endemic (SINE) species, with an associated increase in their extinction risk. It was also determined that the probability of a multi-island beetle species exhibiting multiple ESUs was increased when it had a reduced dispersal capacity (flightless). However, the relation between number of ESUs and dispersal capacity was only marginal in the case of Araneae. Consequently, given that poor dispersal capacity is recognised as a factor that increases the risk of

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extinction due to the reduction of gene flow between populations (Brown & Kodric-Brown, 1977), MIE/MINE flightless beetles were more susceptible to extinction, particularly when each ESUs was regarded as a SIE/SINE. Thus, according to our results, this easy-to-apply methodology, based on mtDNA and the N_{ST} index to infer independent lineages within species, holds considerable potential for implementation in the domain of conservation policy. The following recommendations are proposed: (i) prioritising species with multiple ESUs within their distribution as an indicator of limited gene flow between populations; (ii) selecting ESUs with higher genetic divergence compared to other ESUs of the same species and; (iii) of the most divergent ESUs, prioritizing poor dispersers (for example, flightless or non-ballooning) since they presented a higher risk of extinction (Suárez *et al.*, 2022). Additionally, and in accordance with extant literature, conservation measures could be amplified for species that are specialized in a rare habitat (Nolte *et al.*, 2019; Seibold *et al.*, 2015) or have a large body size (Nolte *et al.*, 2019; Terzopoulou *et al.*, 2015). In line with these insights, and in combination with complementary conservation criteria such as the IUCN Red List of Threatened Species (<https://www.iucnredlist.org/>), the efficacy of conservation measures could be enhanced. However, it is imperative that conservation efforts do not focus exclusively on the species in question. Indeed, there is a need to focus on the environment, with the objective of preventing problems such as habitat loss due to deforestation (Brook *et al.*, 2003), desertification (Huang *et al.*, 2020) or fires (Palm *et al.*, 2022).

Another results of the application of the mtDNA sequences in **Chapter II** refers to the delimitation of intraspecifics thresholds, which was supported by two well-explained conservative interspecific divergence thresholds of 8% for beetles (Jiménez-García *et al.*, 2023; Salces-Castellano *et al.*, 2021) and 6.8% for spiders (Suárez *et al.*, 2022). Thus, the delimitation of these intraspecific divergence thresholds could be achieved by employing and filtering large barcode databases of Coleoptera (Hendrich *et al.*, 2015) and Araneae (Astrin *et al.*, 2016), being 1.62% for beetles and 1.67% for spiders. The ESUs within species with multiple ESUs were then compared with the intraspecific and interspecific thresholds. This analysis revealed a notable number of cases of native non-endemic species (in the case of spiders) and endemic species (in both orders) that exhibited divergences that significantly exceed the intraspecific thresholds even the interspecific thresholds. This could be interpreted as an indication of incipient speciation or species-level differentiation. However, our position aligned with

the explained grey zone of speciation (Roux *et al.*, 2016) and the accumulation of reproductive isolation before speciation (Butlin & Stankowski, 2020; Stankowski & Ravinet, 2021). In consequence, we adopted a conservative stance, considering these intraspecific divergences not as possible species but as probabilities of speciation. This was due to the fact that they did not exceed the conservative interspecific threshold we had set and we preferred to avoid the mass description of species. However, our position is at odds with that of other researchers, like Sharkey *et al.* (2021), who described 403 species solely on the basis of differences in the barcode region when the 2.2% BOLD threshold was exceeded (Ratnasingham & Hebert, 2007, 2013). This massive species description has been the subject of substantial criticism from other researchers (e.g. Ahrens *et al.*, 2021; Engel *et al.*, 2021; Fernández-Triana, 2022; Meier *et al.*, 2022; Zamani *et al.*, 2022). A different case is that we also found in our delimitation of ESUs in two species, *Olios canariensis* (Araneae) and *Micrambe hesperia* (Coleoptera), since both exceeded the conservative genetic divergence interspecific threshold of 6.8% and 8%, respectively, clearly indicative of species-level divergence. It would be of interest to analyse in detail the populations of both cases, using a detailed morphological study and more informative genetic techniques such as ddRADseq (Peterson *et al.*, 2012), similar to the approach employed in **Chapter III**.

In accordance with the aforementioned proposal for the conservation of species set out in **Chapter II**, we designated a beetle species as the object of study in **Chapter III**, on the basis that it may be susceptible to high rates of extinction. Specifically, this study examined the case of the endemic monotypic beetle genus *Lepromoris*, a Coleoptera that exhibits a broad distribution along the Canary Islands. Its distinctive characteristics included being apterous (low dispersal capacity), having a medium body size and being specialised in an endemic habitat, i.e. *Euphorbia* shrublands (Vives & Trócoli, 2021). All of these characteristics were discussed in **Chapter II** in the context of higher extinction risk. Thus, the primary objective of **Chapter III** was to characterise how the genetic diversity of the genus was structured across its distribution and its significance with regard to its evolutionary history. This was achieved by a combination of genetic (barcoding and ddRADseq) and morphological techniques. Through the sequencing of the barcode region, we inferred at least two differentiated mitochondrial clades with a divergence greater than our interspecific threshold of 8% (**Chapter II**), a clear indication of cryptic species. One of these clades exclusively represented the

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sequenced individuals of Gran Canaria, Fuerteventura and the western region of El Hierro, while the other clade included all the sequenced specimens from Tenerife, La Gomera and La Palma, as well as the eastern and southern regions of El Hierro. It is noteworthy that El Hierro was the only island to have both clades, with a clear geographical separation between the two lineages. To corroborate the mtDNA results and perform a detailed analysis of the mitochondrial groups observed on the island of El Hierro, ddRAD sequencing (Peterson *et al.*, 2012) was employed to obtain nuclear DNA information. These analyses revealed a clear nuclear differentiation into two lineages that supported the major divisions observed in the mtDNA results, thereby inferring two distinct species. Thus, the proposed genetic methodology aligned with the success of other works (e.g. Ivanov *et al.*, 2021; Hernández-Teixidor *et al.*, 2024, Pérez-Delgado *et al.*, 2022) inferring species or cryptic lineages on oceanic islands.

In addition, the nuclear data (ddRADseq) supported the same three lineages observed with mtDNA: one of *Lepromoris* sp. nov. corresponding to the western area of the island, and two for *Lepromoris gibba*, one in the eastern area and another in the southern zone (La Restinga). However, there were differences when comparing the results for El Hierro *Lepromoris gibba* lineages obtained with nuclear and mitochondrial data, especially in the case of La Restinga. Utilising ddRADseq, the *Lepromoris gibba* lineage from the eastern zone was found to be closely related to other *Lepromoris gibba* individuals from La Palma, La Gomera and El Hierro. Notably, La Restinga individuals formed a distinct clade that was distinctly separated from the other populations. However, La Restinga individuals, separated from La Palma specimen using ddRAD sequencing, were joined with this individual mitochondrially, with a minimum genetic divergence from the other lineage of *Lepromoris gibba* of approximately 3.1%. The other individuals from the eastern region of El Hierro were linked mitochondrially with Tenerife and La Gomera specimens in the same way as the ddRADseq data show, although without La Palma individual. As discussed in **Chapter II**, focusing exclusively on the mitochondrial results, the individuals from the clade comprising La Restinga + La Palma exceeded the intraspecific mitochondrial threshold of 1.62% established for beetles. When we analyse this divergence in relation to our understanding of the grey zone of speciation (**Chapter II**), it suggests a probability of approximately 30% for speciation, which is insufficient to categorise this lineage as another distinct species. However, utilising an alternative criterion, such as that employed by Sharkey *et al.* (2021), this 3.1% discrepancy would

indicate that it is a distinct species from *Lepromoris gibba*, given that it exceeds the 2.2% BOLD threshold (Ratnasingham & Hebert, 2007, 2013). However, as previously mentioned, the discrepancy between the ddRADseq and mtDNA results for the island of La Palma does not permit a definitive conclusion and further samples from La Palma will be required to solve this uncertainty.

With the genetic divergences well characterised for the two main clades, the subsequent objective was to search for morphological differences that would support these genetic divergences. A meticulous study was conducted on individuals selected from both clades, which revealed a marked difference in the curvature of the eyes. The rest of the body characteristics and even the genitalia were found to be highly variable with significant overlap between the inferred species. Consequently, this approach facilitated the differentiation of the known species from the new one, with *Lepromoris gibba* being distinguished by its slightly convex eyes with uniform curvature (zenith in the middle). Also, the distribution of *Lepromoris gibba* has been restricted to the islands of Tenerife, La Gomera, La Palma and the southern and eastern areas of El Hierro. In contrast, the new species inferred in this study was distributed on Fuerteventura, Gran Canaria and the western region of El Hierro; and was characterised by its more convex eyes, with eccentric curvature (the zenith is displaced towards the outer margin of the eye). Finally, extrapolating these results to **Chapter II**, and given that *Lepromoris* transition from a single species on seven islands to two species on four islands each, it is evident that the extinction risk would have been underestimated without studying the genus. Thus, the results of **Chapter III** greatly support the use of our easy-to-apply mtDNA protocol to study populations and their genetic connectivity. This approach facilitates a more accurate assessment of extinction risk and even the identification of cryptic species, as evidenced by the aforementioned cases of the spider *Olios canariensis* and the beetle *Micrambe hesperia* (**Chapter II**).

Museomics: future opportunities to improve conservation policies

Among the current scientific advances, there is a field of research that may be crucial for conservation biology. This is the case of museomics (e.g. Fong *et al.*, 2023), i.e. the possibility of obtaining DNA from museum collections, a set of genetic techniques with increasingly satisfactory results, as can be seen in the research of D'Ercole *et al.* (2021), Korlević *et al.* (2021), Levesque-Beaudin *et al.* (2023), Mullin *et al.* (2023) and Santos *et al.* (2023), among others. These authors propose novel techniques to obtain the barcode region or even the entire mitogenome without destroying the museum specimen. Applied to our case, museomics would be of great help in obtaining genetic information on those endemic and native non-endemic species that are deposited in museums but are difficult to find in the wild (e.g. low population density or very restricted habitat). Thus, museomics would have a very positive impact on each of the chapters, as detailed below.

Concerning **Chapter I**, museomics could help to complete our mitogenome backbone tree used for the phylogenetic placement of the beetle COI sequences. Currently, we have a good representation of the mitogenomes of Canary Island beetle genera (approximately 39% of the 736 genera recorded for the Canary Islands) and families (66 of the 70 families recorded). However, with this technique it would be much easier to complete it with all the genera, obtaining genetic data from monotypic endemic genera that are difficult to sample. Thus, a complete mitogenome backbone tree of the Canary Island beetle genera could be a powerful tool for the detailed study of beetle communities, inferring phylogenetic relationships between species or calculating genetic distances with great precision. Similarly, these well-identified museum beetles could be used to complete a barcode reference base, which is essential for conservation studies (e.g. Astrin *et al.*, 2016; Dincă *et al.*, 2011; Hendrich *et al.*, 2015; Knebelberger *et al.*, 2014; Kuzmina *et al.*, 2012). In addition, this barcode reference database would also help to provide a secure status as endemic, native non-endemic or introduced to the Canarian fauna, thus helping to overcome what we call as Humboldtian shortfall. To illustrate, species that are very rare to detect or which have very old, non-detailed descriptions could in fact be occasional introduced species and not endemic or native non-endemic species as they were thought to be. For example, *Filistata tenerifensis* was a spider thought to be endemic to the Canary Islands, described in 1992 from harbour area specimens collected in the 1970s. However, subsequent research has revealed that this

species was erroneously described, and that it is in fact *Kukulcania hibernalis*, a species endemic to both North and South America (Zonstein & Marusik, 2019), which was introduced to the Canary Islands.

If we to apply museomics to **Chapter II**, we could, for example, increase the number of mtDNA sequences from populations that were rarely sampled and therefore could not be used in the calculation of the N_{ST} index due to their small population representation. Similarly, it would be potentially possible to use individuals from extinct populations to compare them with current populations. Thus, we could see how different they are from each other, which would strengthen the delimitation of ESUs for conservation policy, with the idea of not losing these unique evolutionary lineages. This would allow us to better characterise the island populations of the MIE and MINE species and thus ensure their better conservation and protection. A similar perspective could be applied to **Chapter III** to better analyse *Lepromoris* populations. For example, this technique could be used to extract DNA from the individual consulted from La Palma, all of them deposited in museums or private collections. In this way, we could extend the use of these individuals in genetic analyses and not just for morphological comparison, as has been done in **Chapter III** (except for the individual from the “La Salemera” plot). In the case of the rare individuals from Lanzarote, museomics would also be applicable to obtain DNA to confirm the species and use these individuals in the different genetic analyses or a potential phylogeography of the genus. Finally, this approach would allow us to obtain the barcode genetic sequence of the type material, which is of great value. In our case, as explained in **Chapter III**, the *Lepromoris* types simply present the Canary Islands or, in the best case, Tenerife, as the type locality on the type label. With these new techniques, we would be able to infer the origin of these specimens by comparing them with the existing populations.

Limitations of the thesis: alternative explanations and opportunities for the future

Although the results obtained in this thesis are robust and well contrasted, in some cases there are equally valid alternative explanations for the same problem using a different approach (e.g. **Chapter I**) or limitations due to the protocols or techniques used (e.g. **Chapter II** and **Chapter III**). For example, although our results in **Chapter I** were clear in terms of stronger support for the preadaptation hypothesis, there is one critical factor that can tip the balance towards the antagonist hypothesis: the size of the study area. For small or local areas, there is a favourable tendency towards the preadaptation hypothesis. This is the case of **Chapter I**, which is limited to the laurel forest of the Canary Islands; or in the study by Li *et al.* (2015), which was performed only in a single restricted plot. However, in other studies that also use genetic data but cover large areas, such as entire archipelagos without distinguishing between habitats (Schaefer *et al.*, 2011), or large spatial regions, such as southern Africa (Bezeng *et al.*, 2015), the competition-relatedness hypothesis is better supported. This discrepancy could be explained by the fact that larger spaces have more environmental heterogeneity. Because there are more ambient conditions or available niches, simply due to stochasticity, the introduced species that may arrive have the same chance of being related to the native community or being completely different. Thus, the effect of phylogenetic relationships within the community (preadaptation) would be reduced and other factors would be enhanced, such as better use of resources or possession of traits not previously observed in that community, as proposed by other hypotheses such as the novel weapon hypothesis (Callaway & Ridenour, 2004) or the enemy release hypothesis (Keane & Crawley, 2002).

With regard to **Chapter II**, some limitations arose during the implementation of the ESU delimitation workflow due to the nature of mitochondrial DNA. It is possible that the proposed methodology for ESU delimitation using mtDNA may lead to an underestimation of the number of delimited ESUs. For example, in cases of species where non-significant global N_{ST} are consistent with panmixia (Step 1 of our workflow), it would be necessary to verify whether these species are truly cases of panmixia, or whether a subtle regional population structure actually exists. For this, it would be necessary to use alternative nuclear markers such as ddRADseq (Deagle *et al.*, 2015; López *et al.*, 2022) or microsatellites (Palm *et al.*, 2009; Peel *et al.*, 2013). This approach could help to detect cases of mitochondrial introgression, which may mask population structure when nuclear

gene flow is restricted (Mischler *et al.*, 2018; Sloan *et al.*, 2017), thus underestimating the number of ESUs for that species. Another limitation of the ESU delimitation workflow relates to paraphyletic populations. Although it could be applied to see if there are differences between populations within each island, in our case we focused on an archipelago vision. Then, the genetic structure between different populations within the same island would not be detected or would be considered as an artefact that could not be resolved, and these populations would be excluded from the analyses. This occurs in four specific cases, summarised in **Figure 1**.

In detail, the four species with paraphyletic populations and the islands concerned are as follows (i) The Coleoptera *Nesotes conformis* (**Figure 1A**), with two clear geographical groups within the island of Tenerife: one belonging to the zone of Anaga and the other to Teno. This geographical dichotomy Teno-Anaga has been observed in other taxa, including *Solanum verpertillio* (Rodríguez *et al.*, 2023), *Canarina canariensis* (Mairal *et al.*, 2015) and *Kaloterms dispar* (Hernández-Teixidor *et al.*, 2024). (ii) The Coleoptera *Anaspis proteus* (**Figure 1B**), exhibits multiple lineages distributed across the island of La Palma, with instances of multiple lineages occurring in the same location. This phenomenon could be attributed to the high dispersal capacity of this species. (iii) The Araneae *Metellina minima* (**Figure 1C**), with two lineages in the laurel forest of La Gomera, the same island and forests where Moya *et al.* (2007) found different lineages for the Coleoptera *Paraeutrichopus pecoudi*. (iv) The Araneae *Cheiracanthium canariense* (**Figure 1D**), with numerous lineages on the island of La Palma. A comparable pattern is observed in *Anaspis proteus*, though in this scenario, the spider has a low dispersal capacity (non-ballooning). A comprehensive study of these specific paraphyletic populations, by analysing only the island with the workflow or with molecular markers such as ddRADSeq (e.g. Noguerales *et al.*, 2018; Pante *et al.*, 2015; Pérez-Delgado *et al.*, 2022) could help to resolve the evolutionary processes occurring within these populations. Additionally, the occurrence of these paraphyletic populations may be attributed to multiple colonisations by individuals from other islands within the archipelago. This hypothesis could be investigated through the application of STRUCTURE analyses, analogous to those performed in **Chapter III**.

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Figure 1. Neighbour-joining trees performed in Geneious (using p distances) for the four cases of paraphyletic populations detected with the ESU delimitation workflow. A) *Nesotes conformis*; B) *Anaspis proteus*; C) *Metellina minima*; and D) *Cheiracanthium canariense*

Finally, the limitations identified in **Chapter III**, which mainly relate to the individual from La Palma, can be easily resolved by extending the sampling on this island or by applying the aforementioned museomics. This would also allow us to infer the evolutionary history of the lineage of *Leptomoris gibba* present in the region of La Restinga (El Hierro). In addition, more advanced morphological techniques that have yielded good results in other studies (e.g. Polilov *et al.*, 2019; Zych *et al.*, 2012), such as scanning electron microscopy (SEM), could be used to meticulously examine the integument or stridulation plates. For example, changes in the structure of the stridulation plates could have influenced the sexual selection of the species (e.g. Davranoglou *et al.*, 2023), potentially explaining the differences between the two *Leptomoris gibba* lineages on El Hierro, although more research is needed on this topic.

CONCLUSIONS

1. At both the archipelago and island scales, the sampled introduced species of beetle in laurel forest are typically more closely related to native laurel forest species than would be expected by chance. This finding is consistent with the preadaptation hypothesis being dominant over the competition-relatedness hypothesis (**Chapter I**).

2. When analysing recently established introduced species (sampled in a single plot as a proxy), patterns of phylogenetic relatedness are consistent with a history of community assembly, prior to human-mediated species introductions, within which species establishment is essentially random with regard to the preadaptation and competition-relatedness hypotheses (**Chapter I**).

3. The utilisation of a combined barcoding and mitogenome phylogeny approach provides a generalisable framework to investigate the introduction and establishment dynamics of arthropod species (**Chapter I**).

4. The barcode sequencing of presumed native non-endemic species has determined origins mediated by human action, that is, introductions, of species until now considered native. The term Humboldtian shortfall has been introduced to describe the limited knowledge about the status of species as native or introduced species. (**Chapter I**).

5. The application of mtDNA sequences to characterise ESUs represents a scalable approach that can be applied within insular systems for a better understanding of local (island-level) extinction risks within species (**Chapter II**).

6. Island populations within multi-island species can be genetically independent of each other, revealing them to be conceptually closer to single island endemic species, with an associated increase in their extinction risk. In some cases, genetic divergences exceed even the most conservative species thresholds, indicative of cryptic species (**Chapter II**).

Conclusions

7. The dispersal ability of the species was found to be a significant predictor of multiple ESUs within species for Coleoptera, but not significant for Araneae (**Chapter II**).

8. The proposed ESUs approach has the potential to serve as a framework for a more refined understanding of species-level extinction risk. This could be achieved through the integration of relevant species-level trait data that has been associated with extinction risk in arthropods, such as body size, habitat specialisation, range size or population density (**Chapter II**).

9. The application of integrative taxonomy, which combines molecular and morphological techniques, has been demonstrated to be an effective approach for the study of arthropod species complexes, as evidenced by the inference of a new cryptic species of cerambycid (**Chapter III**).

REFERENCES

References

- Aguilera Klink, F., Brito Hernández, A., Castilla Gutiérrez, C., Díaz Hernández, A., Fernández-Palacios, J. M., Rodríguez Rodríguez, A., Sabaté Bel, F., & Sánchez García, J. (1994). *Canarias: economía, ecología y medio ambiente*. Francisco Lemus, La Laguna. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1344/b3w.8.2003.25473>
- Ahrens, D., Ahyong, S. T., Ballerio, A., Barclay, M. V. L., Eberle, J., Espeland, M., Huber, B. A., Mengual, X., Pacheco, T. L., & Peters, R. S. (2021). Is it time to describe new species without diagnoses?—A comment on Sharkey et al.(2021). *Zootaxa*, *5027*(2), 151–159. <https://doi.org/10.11646/zootaxa.5027.2.1>
- Alonso-Zarazaga, M. A., Barrios, H., Borovec, R., Bouchard, P., Caldara, R., Colonnelli, E., Gültekin, L., Hlaváč, P., Korotyaev, B., & Lyal, C. H. C. (2017). Cooperative catalogue of palaeartic Coleoptera Curculionoidea. *Monografías Electrónicas SEA*, *8*(1).
- Andersen, J. C., Oboyski, P., Davies, N., Charlat, S., Ewing, C., Meyer, C., Krehenwinkel, H., Lim, J. Y., Noriyuki, S., Ramage, T., Gillespie, R. G., & Roderick, G. K. (2019). Categorization of species as native or nonnative using DNA sequence signatures without a complete reference library. *Ecological Applications*, *29*(5), 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1002/eap.1914>
- Andrews, S. (2010). *FastQC: a quality control tool for high throughput sequence data*. Cambridge, United Kingdom.
- Andújar, C., Arribas, P., López, H., Arjona, Y., Pérez-Delgado, A., Oromí, P., Vogler, A. P., & Emerson, B. C. (2022). Community assembly and metaphylogeography of soil biodiversity: Insights from haplotype-level community DNA metabarcoding within an oceanic island. *Molecular Ecology*, *31*(15), 4078–4094. <https://doi.org/10.1111/mec.16560>
- Angelini, F., & De Marzo, L. (1983). Revisione degli *Agathidium* di Nord Africa e Isole Canarie (Coleoptera, Leiodidae). *Entomologica*, *18*, 17–76. <https://doi.org/10.15162/0425-1016/568>
- Arechavaleta, M., Rodríguez, S., Zurita, N., & García, A. (2009). *Lista de especies silvestres de Canarias. Hongos, plantas y animales terrestres*. Gobierno de Canarias.
- Arjona, Y., Arribas, P., Salces-Castellano, A., López, H., Emerson, B. C., & Andújar, C. (2023). Metabarcoding for biodiversity inventory blind spots: A test case using the beetle fauna of an insular cloud forest. *Molecular Ecology*, *32*(23), 6130–6146. <https://doi.org/10.1111/mec.16716>
- Arribas, P., Andújar, C., Moraza, M. L., Linard, B., Emerson, B. C., & Vogler, A. P. (2020). Mitochondrial Metagenomics Reveals the Ancient Origin and Phylogeny of Soil Mites and Provides a Phylogeny of the Acari. *Molecular Biology and Evolution*, *37*(3), 683–694. <https://doi.org/10.1093/molbev/msz255>
- Astrin, J. J., Höfer, H., Spelda, J., Holstein, J., Bayer, S., Hendrich, L., Huber, B. A., Kielhorn, K. H., Krammer, H. J., Lemke, M., Monje, J. C., Morinière, J., Rulik, B., Petersen, M., Janssen, H., & Muster, C. (2016). Towards a DNA barcode reference database for spiders and harvestmen of Germany. *PLoS ONE*, *11*(9), 1–24. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0162624>

- Atkins, Z. S., Amor, M. D., Clemann, N., Chapple, D. G., While, G. M., Gardner, M. G., Haines, M. L., Harrisson, K. A., Schroder, M., & Robert, K. A. (2020). Allopatric divergence drives the genetic structuring of an endangered alpine endemic lizard with a sky-island distribution. *Animal Conservation*, 23(1), 104–118. <https://doi.org/10.1111/acv.12519>
- Backs, J. R., & Ashley, M. V. (2016). Evolutionary history and gene flow of an endemic Island oak: *Quercus pacifica*. *American Journal of Botany*, 103(12), 2115–2125. <https://doi.org/10.3732/ajb.1600259>
- Báez, M. (1982). Dípteros de Canarias IX: Therevidae. *Boletín de La Asociación Española de Entomología*, 6(1), 79–99.
- Bankevich, A., Nurk, S., Antipov, D., Gurevich, A. A., Dvorkin, M., Kulikov, A. S., Lesin, V. M., Nikolenko, S. I., Pham, S., Prjibelski, A. D., Pyshkin, A. V., Sirotkin, A. V., Vyahhi, N., Tesler, G., Alekseyev, M. A., & Pevzner, P. A. (2012). SPAdes: A new genome assembly algorithm and its applications to single-cell sequencing. *Journal of Computational Biology*, 19(5), 455–477. <https://doi.org/10.1089/cmb.2012.0021>
- Bellard, C., Cassey, P., & Blackburn, T. M. (2016). Alien species as a driver of recent extinctions. *Biology Letters*, 12(4), 20150623. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsbl.2015.0623>
- Bellard, C., Rysman, J. F., Leroy, B., Claud, C., & Mace, G. M. (2017). A global picture of biological invasion threat on islands. *Nature Ecology and Evolution*, 1(12), 1862–1869. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41559-017-0365-6>
- Bernt, M., Donath, A., Jühling, F., Externbrink, F., Florentz, C., Fritzsich, G., Pütz, J., Middendorf, M., & Stadler, P. F. (2013). MITOS: Improved *de novo* metazoan mitochondrial genome annotation. *Molecular Phylogenetics and Evolution*, 69(2), 313–319. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ympev.2012.08.023>
- Bertrand, J. A. M., Bourgeois, Y. X. C., Delahaie, B., Duval, T., García-Jiménez, R., Cornuault, J., Heeb, P., Milá, B., Pujol, B., & Thébaud, C. (2014). Extremely reduced dispersal and gene flow in an island bird. *Heredity*, 112(2), 190–196. <https://doi.org/10.1038/hdy.2013.91>
- Besuchet, C. (1968). Psélaphides des Canaries et de Madère (Coleoptera). *Mitteilungen Der Schweizerischen Entomologischen Gesellschaft*, 41, 275–297. <https://doi.org/10.5169/seals-401564>
- Bezeng, S. B., Davies, J. T., Yessoufou, K., Maurin, O., & Van der Bank, M. (2015). Revisiting Darwin's naturalization conundrum: Explaining invasion success of non-native trees and shrubs in southern Africa. *Journal of Ecology*, 103(4), 871–879. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2745.12410>
- Bickford, D., Lohman, D. J., Sodhi, N. S., Ng, P. K. L., Meier, R., Winker, K., Ingram, K. K., & Das, I. (2007). Cryptic species as a window on diversity and conservation. *Trends in Ecology and Evolution*, 22(3), 148–155. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tree.2006.11.004>

References

- Bidegaray-Batista, L., Taiti, S., López, H., Ribera, C., & Arnedo, M. A. (2015). Endemism and evolution in the littoral woodlouse *Halophiloscia* Verhoeff, 1908 (Crustacea, Isopoda, Oniscidea) from the Canary Islands: implications for conservation policies. *Insect Conservation and Diversity*, 8(1), 17–30. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ICAD.12079>
- Biondi, M. (1995). *Gli Alticini delle Isole Canarie (Coleoptera, Chrysomelidae) (Vol. 26)*. Univ. Degli Studi Di Roma" La Sapienza", Dipartimento Di Biologia Animale Dell'Uomo.
- Boisvert, S., Laviolette, F., & Corbeil, J. (2010). Ray: Simultaneous assembly of reads from a mix of high-throughput sequencing technologies. *Journal of Computational Biology*, 17(11), 1401–1415. <https://doi.org/10.1089/cmb.2009.0238>
- Borges, P. A. V., Abreu, C., Aguiar, A. M. F., Carvalho, P., Jardim, R., Melo, I., Oliveira, P., Sérgio, C., Serrano, A. R. M., & Vieira, P. (2008). *Listagem dos fungos, flora e fauna terrestres dos arquipélagos da Madeira e Selvagens: A list of the terrestrial fungi, flora and fauna of Madeira and Selvagens archipelagos*. Direcção regional do ambiente, Governo regional da Madeira Amadora, Portugal:
- Borges, P. A. V., Rigal, F., Ros-Prieto, A., & Cardoso, P. (2020). Increase of insular exotic arthropod diversity is a fundamental dimension of the current biodiversity crisis. *Insect Conservation and Diversity*, 13(5), 508–518. <https://doi.org/10.1111/icad.12431>
- Bouckaert, R. (2010). DensiTree: making sense of sets of phylogenetic trees. *Bioinformatics*, 26(10), 1372–1373. <https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/btq110>
- Bouckaert, R., Heled, J., Kühnert, D., Vaughan, T., Wu, C.-H., Xie, D., Suchard, M. A., Rambaut, A., & Drummond, A. J. (2014). BEAST 2: a software platform for Bayesian evolutionary analysis. *PLoS Computational Biology*, 10(4), e1003537. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pcbi.1003537>
- Bowstead, S. (1999). A revision of the Corylophidae (Coleoptera) of the West Palearctic Region. *Instrumenta Biodiversitatis*, 3, 1–203.
- Braby, M. F., Eastwood, R., & Murray, N. (2012). The subspecies concept in butterflies: Has its application in taxonomy and conservation biology outlived its usefulness? *Biological Journal of the Linnean Society*, 106(4), 699–716. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1095-8312.2012.01909.x>
- Brook, B. W., Sodhi, N. S., & Ng, P. K. L. (2003). Catastrophic extinctions follow deforestation in Singapore. *Nature*, 424(6947), 420–423. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature01795>
- Brown, J. H., & Kodric-Brown, A. (1977). Turnover rates in insular biogeography: effect of immigration on extinction. *Ecology*, 58(2), 445–449. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.2307/1935620>

- Brown, J. H., & Lomolino, M. V. (1998). *Biogeography. 2nd Edition*. Sinauer.
- Brullé, M. (1838). Inséctes.–pp. 54-95 in: Webb, P.B. & Berthelot, S. *Histoire Naturelle des îles Canaries (1836-1844). II (2^a Partie)*. Paris: Bethune.
- Bruschini, C., Edwards, E. D., Talavera, G., Vaurasi, V. D., Latu, G. F., & Dapporto, L. (2023). A complete COI library of Samoan butterflies reveals layers of endemic diversity on oceanic islands. *Zoologica Scripta*, 52(4), 315–330. <https://doi.org/10.1111/zsc.12588>
- Bryant, D., Bouckaert, R., Felsenstein, J., Rosenberg, N. A., & RoyChoudhury, A. (2012). Inferring species trees directly from biallelic genetic markers: bypassing gene trees in a full coalescent analysis. *Molecular Biology and Evolution*, 29(8), 1917–1932. <https://doi.org/10.1093/molbev/mss086>
- Burns, J. H., & Strauss, S. Y. (2012). Erratum: More closely related species are more ecologically similar in an experimental test (Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America (2011) 108, 13 (5302-5307) DOI: 10.1073/pnas.1013003108). *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, 109(9), 3599. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1116085108>
- Bush, G. L. (1975). Modes of Animal Speciation. *Annual Review of Ecology and Systematics*, 6(1), 339–364. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.es.06.110175.002011>
- Butlin, R. K., & Stankowski, S. (2020). Is it time to abandon the biological species concept? No. *National Science Review*, 7(8), 1400–1401. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nsr/nwaa109>
- Callaway, R. M., & Ridenour, W. M. (2004). Novel weapons: Invasive success and the evolution of increased competitive ability. *Frontiers in Ecology and the Environment*, 2(8), 436–443. [https://doi.org/10.1890/1540-9295\(2004\)002\[0436:NWISAT\]2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1890/1540-9295(2004)002[0436:NWISAT]2.0.CO;2)
- Cardoso, P., Erwin, T. L., Borges, P. A. V., & New, T. R. (2011). The seven impediments in invertebrate conservation and how to overcome them. *Biological Conservation*, 144(11), 2647–2655. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2011.07.024>
- Carvalho, J. C., & Cardoso, P. (2014). Drivers of beta diversity in Macaronesian spiders in relation to dispersal ability. *Journal of Biogeography*, 41(10), 1859–1870. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jbi.12348>
- Cassey, P. (2002). Life history and ecology influences establishment success of introduced land birds. *Biological Journal of the Linnean Society*, 76(4), 465–480. <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1095-8312.2002.00086.x>
- Caujapé-Castells, J., García-Verdugo, C., Sanmartín, I., Fuertes-Aguilar, J., Romeiras, M. M., Zurita-Pérez, N., & Nebot, R. (2022). The late Pleistocene endemism increase hypothesis and the origins of diversity in the Canary Islands Flora. *Journal of Biogeography*, 49(8), 1469–1480. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jbi.14394>

References

- Caujapé-Castells, J., Tye, A., Crawford, D. J., Santos-Guerra, A., Sakai, A., Beaver, K., Lobin, W., Vincent Florens, F. B., Moura, M., Jardim, R., Gómes, I., & Kueffer, C. (2010). Conservation of oceanic island floras: Present and future global challenges. *Perspectives in Plant Ecology, Evolution and Systematics*, 12(2), 107–129. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ppees.2009.10.001>
- Cicconardi, F., Borges, P. A. V., Strasberg, D., Oromí, P., López, H., Pérez-Delgado, A. J., Casquet, J., Caujapé-Castells, J., Fernández-Palacios, J. M., Thébaud, C., & Emerson, B. C. (2017). MtDNA metagenomics reveals large-scale invasion of belowground arthropod communities by introduced species. *Molecular Ecology*, 26(12), 3104–3115. <https://doi.org/10.1111/mec.14037>
- Coates, D. J., Byrne, M., & Moritz, C. (2018). Genetic diversity and conservation units: Dealing with the species-population continuum in the age of genomics. *Frontiers in Ecology and Evolution*, 6(OCT), 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fevo.2018.00165>
- Coello, A. J., Vargas, P., Cano, E., Riina, R., & Fernández-Mazuecos, M. (2024). Phylogenetics and phylogeography of *Euphorbia canariensis* reveal an extreme Canarian-Asian disjunction but limited inter-island colonization. *Plant Biology*, 26(3), 398–414. <https://doi.org/10.1111/plb.13635>
- Coyne, J. A., & Orr, H. A. (2004). *Speciation*. Sinauer Associates.
- Craddock, E. M., & Kambysellis, M. P. (1997). Adaptive radiation in the Hawaiian *Drosophila* (Diptera: Drosophilidae): Ecological and reproductive character analyses. *Pacific Science*, 51(4), 475–489.
- Crampton-Platt, A., Timmermans, M. J. T. N., Gimmel, M. L., Kutty, S. N., Cockerill, T. D., Khen, C. V., & Vogler, A. P. (2015). Soup to tree: The phylogeny of beetles inferred by mitochondrial metagenomics of a bornean rainforest sample. *Molecular Biology and Evolution*, 32(9), 2302–2316. <https://doi.org/10.1093/molbev/msv111>
- Crandall, K. A., Bininda-Emonds, O. R. P., Mace, G. M., & Wayne, R. K. (2000). Considering evolutionary processes in conservation biology. *Trends in Ecology & Evolution*, 15(7), 290–295. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0169-5347\(00\)01876-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0169-5347(00)01876-0)
- Criscione, F., & Köhler, F. (2015). On the land snail *Damochlora* Iredale, 1938 and its cryptic sibling *Nannochlora* n. gen. (Stylommatophora: Camaenidae), each endemic to an island in the Western Australian Kimberley. *Molluscan Research*, 35(4), 275–286. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13235818.2015.1053172>
- Cuthbert, R. N., Diagne, C., Hudgins, E. J., Turbelin, A., Ahmed, D. A., Albert, C., Bodey, T. W., Briski, E., Essl, F., Haubrock, P. J., Gozlan, R. E., Kirichenko, N., Kourantidou, M., Kramer, A. M., & Courchamp, F. (2022). Biological invasion costs reveal insufficient proactive management worldwide. *Science of the Total Environment*, 819. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2022.153404>
- D’Ercole, J., Prosser, S. W. J., & Hebert, P. D. N. (2021). A SMRT approach for targeted amplicon sequencing of museum specimens (Lepidoptera) - Patterns of nucleotide misincorporation. *PeerJ*, 9, 1–18. <https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj.10420>

- Daehler, C. (2014). Darwin's Naturalization Hypothesis Revisited. *The American Naturalist*, 158(3), 324–330. <https://doi.org/10.1086/321316>
- Darwin, C. (1859). *On the origin of species*. Routledge.
- Davidson, A. M., Jennions, M., & Nicotra, A. B. (2011). Do invasive species show higher phenotypic plasticity than native species and, if so, is it adaptive? A meta-analysis. *Ecology Letters*, 14(4), 419–431. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1461-0248.2011.01596.x>
- Davranoglou, L. R., Taylor, G. K., & Mortimer, B. (2023). Sexual selection and predation drive the repeated evolution of stridulation in Heteroptera and other arthropods. *Biological Reviews*, 98(3), 942–981. <https://doi.org/10.1111/brv.12938>
- Deagle, B. E., Faux, C., Kawaguchi, S., Meyer, B., & Jarman, S. N. (2015). Antarctic krill population genomics: Apparent panmixia, but genome complexity and large population size muddy the water. *Molecular Ecology*, 24(19), 4943–4959. <https://doi.org/10.1111/mec.13370>
- Dejean, P. F. M. A. (1833). *Catalogue des coléoptères de la collection de M. le comte Dejean*. Mequignon-Marvis.
- del Arco Aguilar, M. J., & Delgado Rodríguez, O. (2018). *Vegetation of the Canary Islands* (Vol. 16). Springer.
- del Arco Aguilar, M. J., González-González, R., Garzón-Machado, V., & Pizarro-Hernández, B. (2010). Actual and potential natural vegetation on the Canary Islands and its conservation status. *Biodiversity and Conservation*, 19, 3089–3140. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10531-010-9881-2>
- Demelt, C. (1971). Beitrag zur Biologie palearct. Cerambycidae. *Nouvelle Revue d'Entomologie*, 1(1), 61–66.
- Demelt, C. (1974). Zusammenfassung und Revision der Cerambycidenfauna der Canarischen Inseln. *Nouvelle Revue d'Entomologie*, 4, 227–236.
- deWaard, J. R., Landry, J. F., Schmidt, B. C., Derhousoff, J., McLean, J. A., & Humble, L. M. (2009). In the dark in a large urban park: DNA barcodes illuminate cryptic and introduced moth species. *Biodiversity and Conservation*, 18(14), 3825–3839. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10531-009-9682-7>
- deWaard, J. R., Ratnasingham, S., Zakharov, E. V., Borisenko, A. V., Steinke, D., Telfer, A. C., Perez, K. H. J., Sones, J. E., Young, M. R., Levesque-Beaudin, V., Sobel, C. N., Abrahamyan, A., Bessonov, K., Blagoev, G., deWaard, S. L., Ho, C., Ivanova, N. V., Layton, K. K. S., Lu, L., ... Hebert, P. D. N. (2019). A reference library for Canadian invertebrates with 1.5 million barcodes, voucher specimens, and DNA samples. *Scientific Data*, 6(1), 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-019-0320-2>
- Diagne, C., Leroy, B., Vaissière, A. C., Gozlan, R. E., Roiz, D., Jarić, I., Salles, J. M., Bradshaw, C. J. A., & Courchamp, F. (2021). High and rising economic costs of biological invasions worldwide. *Nature*, 592(7855), 571–576. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-021-03405-6>

References

- Diez, J. M., Sullivan, J. J., Hulme, P. E., Edwards, G., & Duncan, R. P. (2008). Darwin's naturalization conundrum: Dissecting taxonomic patterns of species invasions. *Ecology Letters*, *11*(7), 674–681. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1461-0248.2008.01178.x>
- Dincă, V., Zakharov, E. V., Hebert, P. D. N., & Vila, R. (2011). Complete DNA barcode reference library for a country's butterfly fauna reveals high performance for temperate Europe. *Proceedings of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*, *278*(1704), 347–355. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rspb.2010.1089>
- Diniz-Filho, J. A. F., Loyola, R. D., Raia, P., Mooers, A. O., & Bini, L. M. (2013). Darwinian shortfalls in biodiversity conservation. *Trends in Ecology & Evolution*, *28*(12), 689–695. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tree.2013.09.003>
- Dopheide, A., Tooman, L. K., Grosser, S., Agabiti, B., Rhode, B., Xie, D., Stevens, M. I., Nelson, N., Buckley, T. R., Drummond, A. J., & Newcomb, R. D. (2019). Estimating the biodiversity of terrestrial invertebrates on a forested island using DNA barcodes and metabarcoding data. *Ecological Applications*, *29*(4), 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.1002/eap.1877>
- Drummond, A. J., & Rambaut, A. (2007). BEAST: Bayesian evolutionary analysis by sampling trees. *BMC Evolutionary Biology*, *7*, 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2148-7-214>
- Duncan, R. P., & Williams, P. A. (2002). Ecology: Darwin's naturalization hypothesis challenged. *Nature*, *417*(6889), 608–609. <https://doi.org/10.1038/417608a>
- Earl, D. A., & vonHoldt, B. M. (2012). STRUCTURE HARVESTER: A website and program for visualizing STRUCTURE output and implementing the Evanno method. *Conservation Genetics Resources*, *4*(2), 359–361. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12686-011-9548-7>
- Early, R., Bradley, B. A., Dukes, J. S., Lawler, J. J., Olden, J. D., Blumenthal, D. M., Gonzalez, P., Grosholz, E. D., Ibañez, I., Miller, L. P., Sorte, C. J. B., & Tatem, A. J. (2016). Global threats from invasive alien species in the twenty-first century and national response capacities. *Nature Communications*, *7*. <https://doi.org/10.1038/ncomms12485>
- Eaton, D. A. R., & Overcast, I. (2020). Ipyrad: Interactive assembly and analysis of RADseq datasets. *Bioinformatics*, *36*(8), 2592–2594. <https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/btz966>
- Eldredge, L. G., & Miller, S. E. (1997). Records of the Hawaii Biological Survey for 1996. *Museum Occasional Papers*, *1*, 3–22.
- Elton, C. S. (1958). *The ecology of invasions by animals and plants*. Springer Nature.
- Emerson, B. C. (2002). Evolution on oceanic islands: Molecular phylogenetic approaches to understanding pattern and process. *Molecular Ecology*, *11*(6), 951–966. <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1365-294X.2002.01507.x>

- Emerson, B. C., Borges, P. A. V., Cardoso, P., Convey, P., DeWaard, J. R., Economo, E. P., Gillespie, R. G., Kennedy, S., Krehenwinkel, H., Meier, R., Roderick, G. K., Strasberg, D., Thébaud, C., Traveset, A., Creedy, T. J., Meramveliotakis, E., Nogueras, V., Overcast, I., Morlon, H., ... Andújar, C. (2022). Collective and harmonized high throughput barcoding of insular arthropod biodiversity: Toward a Genomic Observatories Network for islands. *Molecular Ecology*, *32*(23), 6161–6176. <https://doi.org/10.1111/mec.16683>
- Emerson, B. C., Casquet, J., López, H., Cardoso, P., Borges, P. A. V., Mollaret, N., Oromí, P., Strasberg, D., & Thébaud, C. (2017). A combined field survey and molecular identification protocol for comparing forest arthropod biodiversity across spatial scales. *Molecular Ecology Resources*, *17*(4), 694–707. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1755-0998.12617>
- Emerson, B. C., & Gillespie, R. G. (2008). Phylogenetic analysis of community assembly and structure over space and time. *Trends in Ecology and Evolution*, *23*(11), 619–630. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tree.2008.07.005>
- Emerson, B. C., & Kolm, N. (2005). Species diversity can drive speciation. *Nature*, *434*(7036), 1015–1017. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature03450>
- Emerson, B. C., & Oromí, P. (2005). Diversification of the forest beetle genus *Tarphius* on the Canary Islands, and the evolutionary origins of island endemics. *Evolution*, *59*(3), 586–598. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.0014-3820.2005.tb01018.x>
- Emerson, B. C., Oromí, P., & Hewitt, G. M. (1999). MtDNA Phylogeography and Recent Intra-island Diversification among Canary Island *Calathus* Beetles. *Molecular Phylogenetics and Evolution*, *13*(1), 149–158. <https://doi.org/10.1006/mpev.1999.0644>
- Emerson, B. C., Oromí, P., & Hewitt, G. M. (2000a). Colonization and diversification of the species *Brachyderes rugatus* (Coleoptera) on the Canary Islands: Evidence from mitochondrial DNA COII gene sequences. *Evolution*, *54*(3), 911–923. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.0014-3820.2000.tb00091.x>
- Emerson, B. C., Oromí, P., & Hewitt, G. M. (2000b). Interpreting colonization of the *Calathus* (Coleoptera: Carabidae) on the Canary Islands and Madeira through the application of the parametric bootstrap. *Evolution*, *54*(6), 2081–2090. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.0014-3820.2000.tb01251.x>
- Engel, M. S., Ceriaco, L. M. P., Daniel, G. M., Dellapé, P. M., Löbl, I., Marinov, M., Reis, R. E., Young, M. T., Dubois, A., Agarwal, I., Lehmann A., P., Alvarado, M., Alvarez, N., Andreone, F., Araujo-Vieira, K., Ascher, J. S., Baêta, D., Baldo, D., Bandeira, S. A., ... Zacharie, C. K. (2021). The taxonomic impediment : a shortage of taxonomists, not the lack of technical approaches. *Zoological Journal of the Linnean Society*, *193*(2), 381–387. <https://doi.org/10.1093/zoolinnean/zlab072>
- Erber, D., & Scholler, M. (2006). Revision of the *Cryptocephalus*-species of the Canary Islands and Madeira (Insecta, Coleoptera, Chrysomelidae, Cryptocephalinae). *Senckenbergiana Biologica*, *86*(1), 85.

References

- Evanno, G., Regnaut, S., & Goudet, J. (2005). Detecting the number of clusters of individuals using the software STRUCTURE: A simulation study. *Molecular Ecology*, *14*(8), 2611–2620. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-294X.2005.02553.x>
- Falck, P., & Karsholt, O. (2023). The Symmocinae and Holcopogoninae in the Canary Islands and Madeira, with descriptions of 13 new species (Lepidoptera: Autostichidae). *SHILAP Revista de Lepidopterologia*, *51*(202), 269–314. <https://doi.org/10.57065/shilap.462>
- Faria, C. M., Machado, A., Amorim, I. R., Gage, M. J., Borges, P. A., & Emerson, B. C. (2016). Evidence for multiple founding lineages and genetic admixture in the evolution of species within an oceanic island weevil (Coleoptera, Curculionidae) super-radiation. *Journal of Biogeography*, *43*(1), 178–191. <http://doi.org/10.1111/jbi.12606>
- Fernández-Palacios, J. M., & Morici, C. (2004). *Ecología insular/Island ecology*. Asociación Española de Ecología Terrestres (aeet)-Cabildo Insular de la Palma: Santa Cruz de La Palma, Spain.
- Fernández-Triana, J. L. (2022). Turbo taxonomy approaches: lessons from the past and recommendations for the future based on the experience with Braconidae (Hymenoptera) parasitoid wasps. *ZooKeys*, *2022*(1087), 199–220. <https://doi.org/10.3897/zookeys.1087.76720>
- Firestone, K. B., Elphinstone, M. S., Sherwin, W. B., & Houlden, B. A. (1999). Phylogeographical population structure of tiger quolls *Dasyurus maculatus* (Dasyuridae: Marsupialia), an endangered carnivorous marsupial. *Molecular Ecology*, *8*(10), 1613–1625. <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1365-294X.1999.00745.x>
- Fong, J. J., Blom, M. P., Aowphol, A., McGuire, J. A., Sutcharit, C., & Soltis, P. S. (2023). Recent advances in museomics: revolutionizing biodiversity research. *Frontiers in Ecology and Evolution*, *11*, 1188172. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fevo.2023.1188172>
- Forester, B. R., Beever, E. A., Darst, C., Szymanski, J., & Funk, W. C. (2022). Linking evolutionary potential to extinction risk: applications and future directions. *Frontiers in Ecology and the Environment*, *20*(9), 507–515. <https://doi.org/10.1002/fee.2552>
- Frankham, R. (1997). Do island populations have less genetic variation than mainland populations? *Heredity*, *78*(3), 311–327. <https://doi.org/10.1038/hdy.1997.46>
- Franz, V. H. (1982). Revision der *Throscus*-Arten (Coleoptera) der Makaronesischen Inseln. *Zeitschrift Der Arbeitsgemeinschaft Osterr. Entomologen*, *34*(1/2).
- Franz, V. H. (1996). Die Ergebnisse meiner langjährigen Aufsammlungen der Coleopterenfauna auf der Insel Hierro (Kanarische Inseln). *Sitzb. Math.-Nat. Kais. Akad. Wiss.*, *202*(1995), 71–138.
- Fraser, D. J., & Bernatchez, L. (2001). Adaptive evolutionary conservation: Towards a unified concept for defining conservation units. *Molecular Ecology*, *10*(12), 2741–2752. <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1365-294X.2001.t01-1-01411.x>

- Fristoe, T. S., Chytrý, M., Dawson, W., Essl, F., Heleno, R., Kreft, H., Maurel, N., Pergl, J., Pyšek, P., Seebens, H., Weigelt, P., Vargas, P., Yang, Q., Attorre, F., Bergmeier, E., Bernhardt-Römermann, M., Biurrun, I., Boch, S., Bonari, G., ... Van Kleunen, M. (2021). Dimensions of invasiveness: Links between local abundance, geographic range size, and habitat breadth in Europe's alien and native floras. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, *118*(22), 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2021173118>
- Funk, W. C., McKay, J. K., Hohenlohe, P. A., & Allendorf, F. W. (2012). Harnessing genomics for delineating conservation units. *Trends in Ecology and Evolution*, *27*(9), 489–496. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tree.2012.05.012>
- Furlan, E., Stoklosa, J., Griffiths, J., Gust, N., Ellis, R., Huggins, R. M., & Weeks, A. R. (2012). Small population size and extremely low levels of genetic diversity in island populations of the platypus, *Ornithorhynchus anatinus*. *Ecology and Evolution*, *2*(4), 844–857. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ece3.195>
- García-Olivares, V., Patiño, J., Overcast, I., Salces-Castellano, A., López de Heredia, U., Mora-Márquez, F., Machado, A., Hickerson, M. J., & Emerson, B. C. (2019). A topoclimate model for Quaternary insular speciation. *Journal of Biogeography*, *46*(12), 2769–2786. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jbi.13689>
- García-Verdugo, C., Forrest, A. D., Fay, M. F., & Vargas, P. (2010). The relevance of gene flow in metapopulation dynamics of an oceanic island endemic, *Olea europaea* subsp. *guanchica*. *Evolution*, *64*(12), 3525–3536. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1558-5646.2010.01091.x>
- García, R. (2005). Distribución de la familia Cerambycidae (Coleoptera) en la isla de La Palma. *Revista de Estudios Generales de La Isla de La Palma*, *1*, 141–170.
- Gilbert, K. J., Andrew, R. L., Bock, D. G., Franklin, M. T., Kane, N. C., Moore, J. S., Moyers, B. T., Renaut, S., Rennison, D. J., Veen, T., & Vines, T. H. (2012). Recommendations for utilizing and reporting population genetic analyses: The reproducibility of genetic clustering using the program structure. *Molecular Ecology*, *21*(20), 4925–4930. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-294X.2012.05754.x>
- Gillespie, R. G. (2007). Oceanic Islands: Models of Diversity. In *Encyclopedia of Biodiversity*. Oxford. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-822562-2.00157-2>
- Gillespie, R. G., Rivera, M., & Garb, J. E. (1998). Sun, surf and spiders : taxonomy and phylogeography of Hawaiian Araneae. *Proceedings of the 17th European Colloquium of Arachnology, January 1998*, 41–51.
- Gillespie, R. G., & Roderick, G. K. (2002). Arthropods on islands: Colonization, speciation, and conservation. *Annual Review of Entomology*, *47*(February 2002), 595–632. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.ento.47.091201.145244>
- Grapputo, A., Boman, S., Lindström, L., Lyytinen, A., & Mappes, J. (2005). The voyage of an invasive species across continents: Genetic diversity of North American and European Colorado potato beetle populations. *Molecular Ecology*, *14*(14), 4207–4219. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-294X.2005.02740.x>

References

- Grewe, F., Kronforst, M. R., Pierce, N. E., & Moreau, C. S. (2021). Museum genomics reveals the *Xerces* blue butterfly (*Glaucopsyche xerces*) was a distinct species driven to extinction. *Biology Letters*, *17*(7). <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsbl.2021.0123>
- Hardy, O. J., & Vekemans, X. (2002). SPAGeDi: a versatile computer program to analyse spatial genetic structure at the individual or population levels. *Molecular Ecology Notes*, *2*(4), 618–620. <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1471-8286.2002.00305.x>
- Harter, D. E. V., Irl, S. D. H., Seo, B., Steinbauer, M. J., Gillespie, R. G., Triantis, K. A., Fernández-Palacios, J. M., & Beierkuhnlein, C. (2015). Impacts of global climate change on the floras of oceanic islands - Projections, implications and current knowledge. *Perspectives in Plant Ecology, Evolution and Systematics*, *17*(2), 160–183. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ppees.2015.01.003>
- Hausmann, A., Charles, H., Godfray, J., Huemer, P., Mutanen, M., Rougerie, R., Van Nieukerken, E. J., Ratnasingham, S., & Hebert, P. D. N. (2013). Genetic patterns in European geometrid moths revealed by the Barcode Index Number (BIN) system. *PLoS ONE*, *8*(12), 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0084518>
- Hayward, M. W., & Castley, J. G. (2018). Triage in conservation. *Frontiers in Ecology and Evolution*, *5*, 168. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fevo.2017.00168>
- Hebert, P. D. N., Cywinska, A., Ball, S. L., & DeWaard, J. R. (2003). Biological identifications through DNA barcodes. *Proceedings of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*, *270*(1512), 313–321. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rspb.2002.2218>
- Hebert, P. D. N., & Gregory, T. R. (2005). The promise of DNA barcoding for taxonomy. *Systematic Biology*, *54*(5), 852–859. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10635150500354886>
- Hebert, P. D. N., Penton, E. H., Burns, J. M., Janzen, D. H., & Hallwachs, W. (2004). Ten species in one: DNA barcoding reveals cryptic species in the neotropical skipper butterfly *Astraptes fulgerator*. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, *101*(41), 14812–14817. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.0406166101>
- Hebert, P. D. N., Ratnasingham, S., & DeWaard, J. R. (2003). Barcoding animal life: Cytochrome c oxidase subunit 1 divergences among closely related species. *Proceedings of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*, *270*, 96–99. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsbl.2003.0025>
- Heinen, J. H., van Loon, E. E., Hansen, D. M., & Kissling, W. D. (2018). Extinction-driven changes in frugivore communities on oceanic islands. *Ecography*, *41*(8), 1245–1255. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ecog.03462>
- Hendrich, L., Morinière, J., Haszprunar, G., Hebert, P. D. N., Hausmann, A., Köhler, F., & Balke, M. (2015). A comprehensive DNA barcode database for Central European beetles with a focus on Germany: Adding more than 3500 identified species to BOLD. *Molecular Ecology Resources*, *15*(4), 795–818. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1755-0998.12354>

- Hernández-Teixidor, D., Cussigh, A., Suárez, D., García, J., Scheffrahn, R. H., & Luchetti, A. (2024). Molecular analyses of the *Kaloterme*s dispar-complex (Blattodea: Kalotermitidae) from the Canary Islands reveal cryptic intraspecific divergence and a connection to a lone Nearctic congener. *Journal of Insect Science*, 24(4), 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jisesa/ieae072>
- Hernández-Teixidor, D., López, H., Pérez-Delgado, A. J., & Oromí, P. (2009). Fauna de artrópodos del malpais de La Rasca (islas Canarias). I: coleópteros. *Revista de La Academia Canaria de Ciencias.*, 101(2008), 83–101.
- Hernández-Teixidor, D., Suárez, D., García, J., & Mora, D. (2019). First report of the invasive *Reticulitermes flavipes* (Kollar, 1837) (Blattodea, Rhinotermitidae) in the Canary Islands. *Journal of Applied Entomology*, 143(4), 478–482. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jen.12592>
- Hernández, J. M. (2000). Estudio multivariante de la genitalia masculina y femenina en seis especies de *Iberodorcadion* (Lamiinae) de la Comunidad de Madrid (España) y propuesta de nuevas sinonimias para el grupo. *Boletín de La Asociación Española de Entomología*, 24, 97–129.
- Hernández, J. M., & Ortuño, V. M. (1992). Estudio de la genitalia femenina en *Iberodorcadion* (Breuning, 1943) y comentarios sobre su valor taxonómico (Coleoptera, Cerambycidae). *Graellsia*, 48, 91–97.
- Heyden, L. von. (1875). Bericht über die von Herrn Prof. Dr. Freiherrn von Fritsch und Dr. JJ Rein auf den Canarischen Inseln gesammelten Käfer. *Berichte Der Senckenbergische Naturforschende Gesellschaft*, 75, 135–145.
- Hobbs, R. J., & Huenneke, L. F. (1992). Disturbance, Diversity, and Invasion: Implications for Conservation. *Conservation Biology*, 6(3), 324–337. <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1523-1739.1992.06030324.x>
- Hobern, D. (2021). Bioscan: DNA barcoding to accelerate taxonomy and biogeography for conservation and sustainability. *Genome*, 64(3), 161–164. <https://doi.org/10.1139/gen-2020-0009>
- Hoelzel, A. R. (2023). Where to now with the evolutionarily significant unit? *Trends in Ecology and Evolution*, 38(12), 1134–1142. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tree.2023.07.005>
- Holland, B. S., & Cowie, R. H. (2007). A geographic mosaic of passive dispersal: Population structure in the endemic Hawaiian amber snail *Succinea caduca* (Mighels, 1845). *Molecular Ecology*, 16(12), 2422–2435. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-294X.2007.03246.x>
- Hortal, J., de Bello, F., Diniz-Filho, J. A. F., Lewinsohn, T. M., Lobo, J. M., & Ladle, R. J. (2015). Seven shortfalls that beset large-scale knowledge of biodiversity. *Annual Review of Ecology, Evolution, and Systematics*, 46(1), 523–549. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-ecolsys-112414-054400>

References

- Hoso, M. (2012). Non-adaptive speciation of snails by left-right reversal is facilitated on oceanic islands. *Contributions to Zoology*, 81(2), 79–85. <https://doi.org/10.1163/18759866-08102002>
- Huang, J., Zhang, G., Zhang, Y., Guan, X., Wei, Y., & Guo, R. (2020). Global desertification vulnerability to climate change and human activities. *Land Degradation and Development*, 31(11), 1380–1391. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ldr.3556>
- Hubbell, S. P. (2001). *The unified neutral theory of biodiversity and biogeography*. Princeton University Press.
- Huber, B. A., Rheims, C. A., & Brescovit, A. D. (2005). Speciation without changes in genital shape: A case study on Brazilian pholcid spiders (Araneae: Pholcidae). *Zoologischer Anzeiger*, 243(4), 273–279. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcz.2004.12.001>
- Ikeda, H., Nishikawa, M., & Sota, T. (2012). Loss of flight promotes beetle diversification. *Nature Communications*, 3, 647–648. <https://doi.org/10.1038/ncomms1659>
- Illera, J. C., Emerson, B. C., & Richardson, D. S. (2007). Population history of Berthelot's pipit: Colonization, gene flow and morphological divergence in Macaronesia. *Molecular Ecology*, 16(21), 4599–4612. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-294X.2007.03543.x>
- Israelson, G. (1971). A Revision of the genus *Astenus* Steph. in the Canary Islands with an Appendix on *A. indicus* (Kr.) and *A. chimaera* (Woll.) (Col. Staphylinidae). *Commentationes Biologicae*, 37, 26.
- Israelson, G. (1972). The *Stenichnus* species of the Canary Islands (Col. Scydmaenidae). *Entomologische Blätter*, 66(2), 103–114.
- Israelson, G. (1974). New or poorly known Anobiidae from the Canarian Islands, with keys (Col.). *Miscel. Lania Zoologica*, 71–89.
- Israelson, G. (1977). The Leiodini of the Canary Islands (Coleoptera, Leiodidae). *Vieraea: Folia Scientiarum Biologiarum Canariensium*, 7, 181–190.
- Ivanov, V., Marusik, Y., Pétilion, J., & Mutanen, M. (2021). Relevance of ddRADseq method for species and population delimitation of closely related and widely distributed wolf spiders (Araneae, Lycosidae). *Scientific Reports*, 11(1), 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-021-81788-2>
- Jackman, T. R., Larson, A., De Queiroz, K., & Losos, J. B. (1999). Phylogenetic relationships and tempo of early diversification in *Anolis* lizards. *Systematic Biology*, 48(2), 254–285. <https://doi.org/10.1080/106351599260283>
- Jakobs, G., Weber, E., & Edwards, P. J. (2004). Introduced plants of the invasive *Solidago gigantea* (Asteraceae) are larger and grow denser than conspecifics in the native range. *Diversity and Distributions*, 10(1), 11–19. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1472-4642.2004.00052.x>

- Jakobsson, M., & Rosenberg, N. A. (2007). CLUMPP: A cluster matching and permutation program for dealing with label switching and multimodality in analysis of population structure. *Bioinformatics*, *23*(14), 1801–1806. <https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/btm233>
- Janes, J. K., Miller, J. M., Dupuis, J. R., Malenfant, R. M., Gorrell, J. C., Cullingham, C. I., & Andrew, R. L. (2017). The K= 2 conundrum. *Molecular Ecology*, *26*(14), 3594–3602. <https://doi.org/10.1111/mec.14187>
- Jeschke, J. M., & Heger, T. (2018). *Invasion biology: hypotheses and evidence* (Vol. 9). CABI.
- Jeschke, J. M., & Strayer, D. L. (2006). Determinants of vertebrate invasion success in Europe and North America. *Global Change Biology*, *12*(9), 1608–1619. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2486.2006.01213.x>
- Jiménez-García, E., Andújar, C., López, H., & Emerson, B. C. (2023). Towards understanding insect species introduction and establishment: A community-level barcoding approach using island beetles. *Molecular Ecology*, *32*(13), 3778–3792. <https://doi.org/10.1111/mec.16962>
- Johnson, C. (1970). The *Atomaria* species (Col. Cryptophagidae) of Madeira and the Canary Islands including data on the Wollaston collections and Lectotype designations for his species. *Insect Systematics & Evolution*, *1*(2), 145–160.
- Juan, C., Emerson, B. C., Oromí, P., & Hewitt, G. M. (2000). Colonization and diversification: Towards a phylogeographic synthesis for the Canary Islands. *Trends in Ecology and Evolution*, *15*(3), 104–109. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0169-5347\(99\)01776-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0169-5347(99)01776-0)
- Kalmar, A., & Currie, D. J. (2006). A global model of island biogeography. *Global Ecology and Biogeography*, *15*(1), 72–81. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1466-822X.2006.00205.x>
- Kapp, A. (2019). Revision der westpaläarktischen Arten der Gattungen *Oligota* Mannerheim, 1830 und *Holobus* Solier, 1849 (Coleoptera, Staphylinidae, Aleocharinae, Hypocyphitini). *Linzer Biologische Beiträge*, *51*(1), 587–698.
- Keane, R. M., & Crawley, M. J. (2002). Exotic plant invasions and the enemy release hypothesis. *Trends in Ecology and Evolution*, *17*(4), 164–170. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0169-5347\(02\)02499-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0169-5347(02)02499-0)
- Kembel, S. W., Cowan, P. D., Helmus, M. R., Cornwell, W. K., Morlon, H., Ackerly, D. D., Blomberg, S. P., & Webb, C. O. (2010). Picante: R tools for integrating phylogenies and ecology. *Bioinformatics*, *26*(11), 1463–1464. <https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/btq166>
- Kennedy, S., Calaor, J., Zurápit, Y., Hans, J., Yoshimura, M., Choo, J., Andersen, J. C., Callaghan, J., Roderick, G. K., Krehenwinkel, H., Rogers, H., Gillespie, R. G., & Economo, E. P. (2022). Richness and resilience in the Pacific: DNA metabarcoding enables parallelized evaluation of biogeographic patterns. *Molecular Ecology*, *June*, 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.1111/mec.16575>

References

- Khan, A., & Ahmad, W. (2018). *Termites and Sustainable Management*. Springer. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-72110-1>
- Kier, G., Kreft, H., Tien, M. L., Jetz, W., Ibsch, P. L., Nowicki, C., Mutke, J., & Barthlott, W. (2009). A global assessment of endemism and species richness across island and mainland regions. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, 106(23), 9322–9327. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.0810306106>
- Kimura, M. (1983). *The neutral theory of molecular evolution*. Cambridge University Press.
- Kindler, C., & Fritz, U. (2018). Phylogeography and taxonomy of the barred grass snake (*Natrix helvetica*), with a discussion of the subspecies category in zoology. *Vertebrate Zoology*, 68(3), 269–281. <https://doi.org/10.3897/vz.68.e31615>
- Kneblsberger, T., Landi, M., Neumann, H., Kloppmann, M., Sell, A. F., Campbell, P. D., Laakmann, S., Raupach, M. J., Carvalho, G. R., & Costa, F. O. (2014). A reliable DNA barcode reference library for the identification of the North European shelf fish fauna. *Molecular Ecology Resources*, 14(5), 1060–1071. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1755-0998.12238>
- Koepfen, M. (1910). Reisetage auf den Glücklichen Inseln. *Entomologische Rundschau*, 27, 86–88.
- Korlević, P., McAlister, E., Mayho, M., Makunin, A., Flicek, P., & Lawniczak, M. K. N. (2021). A Minimally Morphologically Destructive Approach for DNA Retrieval and Whole-Genome Shotgun Sequencing of Pinned Historic Dipteran Vector Species. *Genome Biology and Evolution*, 13(10), 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.1093/gbe/evab226>
- Krátký, J., & Aguiar, A. M. (2019). A new Lamiine longhorn-beetle from Madeira and the key to the Macaronesian Parmenini (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae). *Bocagiana*, 246, 1–9.
- Kumschick, S., Gaertner, M., Vila, M., Essl, F., Jeschke, J. M., Pysek, P., Ricciardi, A., Bacher, S., Blackburn, T. M., Dick, J. T. A., Evans, T., Hulme, P. E., Kühn, I., Mrugala, A., Pergl, J., Rabitsch, W., Richardson, D. M., Sendek, A., & Winter, M. (2015). Ecological impacts of alien species: Quantification, scope, caveats, and recommendations. *BioScience*, 65(1), 55–63. <https://doi.org/10.1093/biosci/biu193>
- Kuzmina, M. L., Johnson, K. L., Barron, H. R., & Hebert, P. D. N. (2012). Identification of the vascular plants of Churchill, Manitoba, using a DNA barcode library. *BMC Ecology*, 12. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1472-6785-12-25>
- Landry, J. F., Nazari, V., Dewaard, J. R., Mutanen, M., Lopez-Vaamonde, C., Huemer, P., & Hebert, P. D. N. (2013). Shared but overlooked: 30 species of Holarctic Microlepidoptera revealed by DNA barcodes and morphology. *Zootaxa*, 3749(1), 1–93. <https://doi.org/10.11646/zootaxa.3749.1.1>
- Leclerc, C., Courchamp, F., & Bellard, C. (2018). Insular threat associations within taxa worldwide. *Scientific Reports*, 8(1), 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-018-24733-0>

- Lenzner, B., Latombe, G., Capinha, C., Bellard, C., Courchamp, F., Diagne, C., Dullinger, S., Golivets, M., Irl, S. D. H., Kühn, I., Leung, B., Liu, C., Moser, D., Roura-Pascual, N., Seebens, H., Turbelin, A., Weigelt, P., & Essl, F. (2020). What Will the Future Bring for Biological Invasions on Islands? An Expert-Based Assessment. *Frontiers in Ecology and Evolution*, 8(September), 1–16. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fevo.2020.00280>
- Levesque-Beaudin, V., Miller, M. E., Dikow, T., Miller, S. E., Prosser, S. W. J., Zakharov, E. V., McKeown, J. T. A., Sones, J. E., Redmond, N. E., & Coddington, J. A. (2023). A workflow for expanding DNA barcode reference libraries through ‘museum harvesting’ of natural history collections. *Biodiversity Data Journal*, 11, e100677. <https://doi.org/10.3897/BDJ.11.e100677>
- Levine, J. M., Vilà, M., D’Antonio, C. M., Dukes, J. S., Grigulis, K., & Lavelle, S. (2003). Mechanisms underlying the impacts of exotic plant invasions. *Proceedings of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*, 270(1517), 775–781. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rspb.2003.2327>
- Li, S. P., Cadotte, M. W., Meiners, S. J., Hua, Z. S., Shu, H. Y., Li, J. T., & Shu, W. S. (2015). The effects of phylogenetic relatedness on invasion success and impact: Deconstructing Darwin’s naturalisation conundrum. *Ecology Letters*, 18(12), 1285–1292. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ele.12522>
- Li, X., & Wiens, J. J. (2023). Estimating Global Biodiversity: The Role of Cryptic Insect Species. *Systematic Biology*, 72(2), 391–403. <https://doi.org/10.1093/sysbio/syac069>
- Liu, H., & Stiling, P. (2006). Testing the enemy release hypothesis: A review and meta-analysis. *Biological Invasions*, 8(7), 1535–1545. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10530-005-5845-y>
- Lökkös, A., Boukal, M., & Fikáček, M. (2014). The hydrophilid beetle *Pachysternum capense* (Mulsant, 1844) (Coleoptera: Hydrophilidae) became a world-wide adventive species: a summary of distribution with new records from Europe, Australia, and South America. *North-Western Journal of Zoology*, 10, 333–336.
- Lomolino, M. V. (2004). Conservation biogeography. In *Frontiers of Biogeography: new directions in the geography of nature* (Vol. 293). Sinauer Associates, Inc.
- Lopez-Vaamonde, C., Sire, L., Rasmussen, B., Rougerie, R., Wieser, C., Allaoui, A. A., Minet, J., DeWaard, J. R., Decaëns, T., & Lees, D. C. (2019). DNA barcodes reveal deeply neglected diversity and numerous invasions of micromoths in Madagascar. *Genome*, 62(3), 108–121. <https://doi.org/10.1139/gen-2018-0065>
- López, H., Hernández-Teixidor, D., Macías-Hernández, N., Juan, C., & Oromí, P. (2013). A taxonomic revision and species delimitation of the genus *Purpuraria* Enderlein, 1929 (Orthoptera: Pamphagidae) using an integrative approach. *Journal of Zoological Systematics and Evolutionary Research*, 51(3), 173–186. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jzs.12023>

References

- López, M. E., Bergenius Nord, M., Kaljuste, O., Wennerström, L., Hekim, Z., Tiainen, J., & Vasemägi, A. (2022). Lack of panmixia of Bothnian Bay vendace - Implications for fisheries management. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 9(November), 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2022.1028863>
- Lorence, D. H., & Wood, K. R. (1994). *Kanaloa*, a new genus of Fabaceae (Mimosoideae) from Hawaii. *Novon*, 4(2), 137–145. <https://doi.org/10.2307/3391582>
- Lorenzo, C. D., & Prendes, C. (1987). Contribución al conocimiento de las formas larvarias de coleópteros. II. *Vieraea*, 17(1–2), 99–104.
- Losos, J. B., & Ricklefs, R. E. (2009). Adaptation and diversification on islands. *Nature*, 457(7231), 830–836. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature07893>
- MacArthur, R., & Levins, R. (1967). The limiting similarity hypothesis. *American Naturalist*, 101(921), 377–385.
- Machado, A. (1985). New data on the Hierro giant lizard and the lizard of Salmor (Canary Islands). *Bonn. Zool. Beitr.*, 36, 429–470.
- Machado, A. (1992). *Monografía de los carabidos de las Islas Canarias* (Vol. 734). IBCER, La Laguna, Tenerife.
- Machado, A. (2022). *The Macaronesian Laparocerus (Coleoptera, Curculionidae, Entiminae). Taxonomy, phylogeny and natural history*. Publicaciones Turquesa.
- Machado, A., & Oromí, P. (2000). *Elenco de los coleópteros de las Islas Canarias*. Instituto de Estudios Canarios.
- Mack, R. N., Simberloff, D., Lonsdale, W. M., Evans, H., Clout, M., & Bazzaz, F. A. (2000). Biotic Invasions: Causes, Epidemiology, Global Consequences, and Control. *Ecological Applications*, 10(3), 689. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2641039>
- Mairal, M., Sanmartín, I., Aldasoro, J. J., Culshaw, V., Manolopoulou, I., & Alarcón, M. (2015). Palaeo-islands as refugia and sources of genetic diversity within volcanic archipelagos: The case of the widespread endemic *Canarina canariensis* (Campanulaceae). *Molecular Ecology*, 24(15), 3944–3963. <https://doi.org/10.1111/mec.13282>
- Martínez de la Escalera, M. (1923). *La Euphorbia canariensis y sus huespedes*. Madrid.
- Marx, H. E., Giblin, D. E., Dunwiddie, P. W., & Tank, D. C. (2016). Deconstructing Darwin's Naturalization Conundrum in the San Juan Islands using community phylogenetics and functional traits. *Diversity and Distributions*, 22(3), 318–331. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ddi.12401>
- Mastretta-Yanes, A., Arrigo, N., Alvarez, N., Jorgensen, T. H., Piñero, D., & Emerson, B. C. (2015). Restriction site-associated DNA sequencing, genotyping error estimation and *de novo* assembly optimization for population genetic inference. *Molecular Ecology Resources*, 15(1), 28–41. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1755-0998.12291>

- Mayr, E. (1942). *Systematics and the origins of species*. Columbia University Press.
- Mayr, E. (1963). *Animal species and evolution*. Harvard University Press.
- Mckenna, D. D., Wild, A. L., Kanda, K., Bellamy, C. L., Beutel, R. G., Caterino, M. S., Farnum, C. W., Hawks, D. C., Ivie, M. A., Jameson, M. L., Leschen, R. A. B., Marvaldi, A. E., Mchugh, J. V., Newton, A. F., Robertson, J. A., Thayer, M. K., Whiting, M. F., Lawrence, J. F., Ślipiński, A., ... Farrell, B. D. (2015). The beetle tree of life reveals that Coleoptera survived end-Permian mass extinction to diversify during the Cretaceous terrestrial revolution. *Systematic Entomology*, *40*(4), 835–880. <https://doi.org/10.1111/syen.12132>
- McKinney, M. L. (1999). High rates of extinction and threat in poorly studied taxa. *Conservation Biology*, *13*(6), 1273–1281. <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1523-1739.1999.97393.x>
- Mee, J. A., Bernatchez, L., Reist, J. D., Rogers, S. M., & Taylor, E. B. (2015). Identifying designatable units for intraspecific conservation prioritization: A hierarchical approach applied to the lake whitefish species complex (*Coregonus* spp.). *Evolutionary Applications*, *8*(5), 423–441. <https://doi.org/10.1111/eva.12247>
- Meier, R., Blaimer, B. B., Buenaventura, E., Hartop, E., von Rintelen, T., Srivathsan, A., & Yeo, D. (2022). A re-analysis of the data in Sharkey et al.'s (2021) minimalist revision reveals that BINs do not deserve names, but BOLD Systems needs a stronger commitment to open science. *Cladistics*, *38*(2), 264–275. <https://doi.org/10.1111/cla.12489>
- Meier, R., Wong, W., Srivathsan, A., & Foo, M. (2016). \$1 DNA barcodes for reconstructing complex phenomes and finding rare species in specimen-rich samples. *Cladistics*, *32*(2015), 100–110. <https://doi.org/10.1111/cla.12115>
- Mijangos, J. L., Gruber, B., Berry, O., Pacioni, C., & Georges, A. (2022). dartR v2: An accessible genetic analysis platform for conservation, ecology and agriculture. *Methods in Ecology and Evolution*, *13*(10), 2150–2158. <https://doi.org/10.1111/2041-210X.13918>
- Mirzaee, Z., Simões, M. V. P., Battiston, R., Sadeghi, S., Wiemers, M., & Schmitt, T. (2024). Biology, ecology, and biogeography of eremic praying mantis *Blepharopsis mendica* (Insecta: Mantodea). *PeerJ*, *12*, 1–30. <https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj.16814>
- Mischler, C., Veale, A., van Stijn, T., Brauning, R., McEwan, J. C., Maloney, R., & Robertson, B. C. (2018). Population connectivity and traces of mitochondrial introgression in New Zealand black-billed gulls (*Larus bulleri*). *Genes*, *9*(11), 1–19. <https://doi.org/10.3390/genes9110544>
- Mittermeier, R. A., Robles-Gil, P., Hoffmann, M., Pilgrim, J., Brooks, T., Mittermeier, C. G., Lamoreux, J., & Da Fonseca, G. A. B. (2004). *Hotspots Revisited: Earth's Biologically Richest and Most Endangered Ecoregion*. CEMEX. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oxfordhb/9780198832232.013.25>

References

- Molinari, J. (2023). A bare-bones scheme to choose between the species, subspecies, and ‘evolutionarily significant unit’ categories in taxonomy and conservation. *Journal for Nature Conservation*, 72(January), 126335. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jnc.2023.126335>
- Mori, N., Santoiemma, G., Glazer, I., Gilioli, G., Ciampitti, M., Cavagna, B., & Battisti, A. (2021). Management of *Popillia japonica* in container-grown nursery stock in Italy. *Phytoparasitica*, 50, 83–89. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12600-021-00948-2>
- Moritz, C. (1994). Defining ‘evolutionarily significant units’ for conservation. *Tree*, 9(10), 373–375. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0169-5347\(94\)90057-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/0169-5347(94)90057-4)
- Moritz, C. (2002). Strategies to protect biological diversity and the evolutionary processes that sustain it. *Systematic Biology*, 51(2), 238–254. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10635150252899752>
- Moya, O., Contreras-Díaz, H. G., Oromí, P., & Juan, C. (2007). Phylogeography of a ground beetle species in La Gomera (Canary Islands): The effects of landscape topology and population history. *Heredity*, 99(3), 322–330. <https://doi.org/10.1038/sj.hdy.6801004>
- Mullin, V. E., Stephen, W., Arce, A. N., Nash, W., Raine, C., Notton, D. G., Whiffin, A., Blagderov, V., Gharbi, K., Hogan, J., Hunter, T., Irish, N., Jackson, S., Judd, S., Watkins, C., Haerty, W., Ollerton, J., Brace, S., Gill, R. J., & Barnes, I. (2023). First large-scale quantification study of DNA preservation in insects from natural history collections using genome-wide sequencing. *Methods in Ecology and Evolution*, 14(2), 360–371. <https://doi.org/10.1111/2041-210X.13945>
- Muñoz, A. G., Baxter, S. W., Linares, M., & Jiggins, C. D. (2011). Deep mitochondrial divergence within a *Heliconius* butterfly species is not explained by cryptic speciation or endosymbiotic bacteria. *BMC Evolutionary Biology*, 11, 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2148-11-358>
- Murray, J., Murray, E., Johnson, M. S., & Clarke, B. (1988). The extinction of *Partula* on Moorea. *Pacific Science*, 42(3–4), 150–153.
- Myers, E. W., Sutton, G. G., Delcher, A. L., Dew, I. M., Fasulo, D. P., Flanigan, M. J., Kravitz, S. A., Mobarry, C. M., Reinert, K. H. J., Remington, K. A., Anson, E. L., Bolanos, R. A., Chou, H. H., Jordan, C. M., Halpern, A. L., Lonardi, S., Beasley, E. M., Brandon, R. C., Chen, L., ... Venter, J. C. (2000). A whole-genome assembly of *Drosophila*. *Science*, 287(5461), 2196–2204. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.287.5461.2196>
- Myers, N., Mittermeier, R. A., Mittermeier, C. G., Da Fonseca, G. A. B., & Kent, J. (2000). Biodiversity hotspots for conservation priorities. *Nature*, 403(6772), 853–858. <https://doi.org/10.1038/35002501>
- Noguerales, V., Cordero, P. J., & Ortego, J. (2018). Integrating genomic and phenotypic data to evaluate alternative phylogenetic and species delimitation hypotheses in a recent evolutionary radiation of grasshoppers. *Molecular Ecology*, 27(5), 1229–1244. <https://doi.org/10.1111/mec.14504>

- Nolte, D., Boutaud, E., Kotze, D. J., Schuldt, A., & Assmann, T. (2019). Habitat specialization, distribution range size and body size drive extinction risk in carabid beetles. *Biodiversity and Conservation*, 28(5), 1267–1283. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10531-019-01724-9>
- O’Dowd, D. J., Green, P. T., & Lake, P. S. (2003). Invasional ‘meltdown’ on an oceanic island. *Ecology Letters*, 6(9), 812–817. <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1461-0248.2003.00512.x>
- Ogden, N. H., Wilson, J. R. U., Richardson, D. M., Hui, C., Davies, S. J., Kumschick, S., Le Roux, J. J., Measey, J., Saul, W. C., & Pulliam, J. R. C. (2019). Emerging infectious diseases and biological invasions: A call for a One Health collaboration in science and management. *Royal Society Open Science*, 6(3). <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsos.181577>
- Oliveira, M. R. V., Henneberry, T. E., & Anderson, P. (2001). History, current status, and collaborative research projects for *Bemisia tabaci*. *Crop Protection*, 20, 709–723. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0261-2194\(01\)00108-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0261-2194(01)00108-9)
- Oromí, P. (1984). Nuevas aportaciones al conocimiento de la distribución de los coleópteros de Canarias. *Vieraea*, 13(1–2), 233–240.
- Otero, J. C. (2013). Cryptophaginae (Coleoptera) de la region paleártica occidental. *Coleopterological Monographs*, 4, 1–295.
- Packer, L., & Ruz, L. (2017). DNA barcoding the bees (Hymenoptera: Apoidea) of Chile: Species discovery in a reasonably well known bee fauna with the description of a new species of *Lonchopria* (Colletidae). *Genome*, 60(5), 414–430. <https://doi.org/10.1139/gen-2016-0071>
- Paini, D. R., Sheppard, A. W., Cook, D. C., De Barro, P. J., Worner, S. P., & Thomas, M. B. (2016). Global threat to agriculture from invasive species. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, 113(27), 7575–7579. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1602205113>
- Palm, E. C., Sutor, M. J., Joly, K., Herriges, J. D., Kelly, A. P., Hervieux, D., Russell, K. L. M., Bentzen, T. W., Larter, N. C., & Hebblewhite, M. (2022). Increasing fire frequency and severity will increase habitat loss for a boreal forest indicator species. *Ecological Applications*, 32(3), 1–18. <https://doi.org/10.1002/eap.2549>
- Palm, S., Dannewitz, J., Prestegard, T., & Wickström, H. (2009). Panmixia in European eel revisited: No genetic difference between maturing adults from southern and northern Europe. *Heredity*, 103(1), 82–89. <https://doi.org/10.1038/hdy.2009.51>
- Palm, T. (1975). Zur Kenntnis der Käferfauna der Kanarischen Inseln 8. Revision der Gattung *Malthinus* Latr. (Coleoptera: Cantharidae). *Insect Systematics & Evolution*, 6(2), 119–130. <https://doi.org/10.1163/187631275X00208>
- Palsbøll, P. J., Bérubé, M., & Allendorf, F. W. (2007). Identification of management units using population genetic data. *Trends in Ecology and Evolution*, 22(1), 11–16. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tree.2006.09.003>

References

- Pante, E., Abdelkrim, J., Viricel, A., Gey, D., France, S. C., Boisselier, M. C., & Samadi, S. (2015). Use of RAD sequencing for delimiting species. *Heredity*, *114*(5), 450–459. <https://doi.org/10.1038/hdy.2014.105>
- Papadopoulou, A., Anastasiou, I., & Vogler, A. P. (2010). Revisiting the insect mitochondrial molecular clock: The mid-aegean trench calibration. *Molecular Biology and Evolution*, *27*(7), 1659–1672. <https://doi.org/10.1093/molbev/msq051>
- Paradis, E., Claude, J., & Strimmer, K. (2004). APE: Analyses of phylogenetics and evolution in R language. *Bioinformatics*, *20*(2), 289–290. <https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/btg412>
- Park, D. S., Feng, X., Maitner, B. S., Ernst, K. C., & Enquist, B. J. (2020). Darwin's naturalization conundrum can be explained by spatial scale. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, *117*(20), 10904–10910. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1918100117>
- Pascoe, F. P. (1864). Additions to the Longicornia of South Africa: Including a Few Species from Old Calabar and Madagascar. *Journal of Entomology*, *2*, 270–291.
- Patiño, J., Carine, M., Mardulyn, P., Devos, N., Mateo, R. G., González-Mancebo, J. M., Shaw, A. J., & Vanderpoorten, A. (2015). Approximate Bayesian Computation Reveals the Crucial Role of Oceanic Islands for the Assembly of Continental Biodiversity. *Systematic Biology*, *64*(4), 579–589. <https://doi.org/10.1093/sysbio/syv013>
- Patiño, J., & Vanderpoorten, A. (2015). How to define nativeness in organisms with high dispersal capacities? A comment on Essl et al. *Journal of Biogeography*, *42*(7), 1360–1362.
- Patton, A. H., Harmon, L. J., del Rosario Castañeda, M., Frank, H. K., Donihue, C. M., Herrel, A., & Losos, J. B. (2021). When adaptive radiations collide: Different evolutionary trajectories between and within island and mainland lizard clades. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, *118*(42). <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2024451118>
- Peck, S. B., Heraty, J., Landry, B., & Sinclair, B. J. (1998). Introduced insect fauna of an oceanic archipelago: The Galápagos Islands, Ecuador. *American Entomologist*, *44*(4), 218–237. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ae/44.4.218>
- Peel, A. J., Sargan, D. R., Baker, K. S., Hayman, D. T. S., Barr, J. A., Cramer, G., Suu-Ire, R., Broder, C. C., Lembo, T., Wang, L. F., Fooks, A. R., Rossiter, S. J., Wood, J. L. N., & Cunningham, A. A. (2013). Continent-wide panmixia of an African fruit bat facilitates transmission of potentially zoonotic viruses. *Nature Communications*, *4*. <https://doi.org/10.1038/ncomms3770>
- Peng, Y., Leung, H. C. M., Yiu, S. M., & Chin, F. Y. L. (2012). IDBA-UD: A *de novo* assembler for single-cell and metagenomic sequencing data with highly uneven depth. *Bioinformatics*, *28*(11), 1420–1428. <https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/bts174>

- Pérez-Delgado, A. J., Arribas, P., Hernando, C., López, H., Arjona, Y., Suárez-Ramos, D., Emerson, B. C., & Andújar, C. (2022). Hidden island endemic species and their implications for cryptic speciation within soil arthropods. *Journal of Biogeography*, *49*(7), 1367–1380. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jbi.14388>
- Peterson, B. K., Weber, J. N., Kay, E. H., Fisher, H. S., & Hoekstra, H. E. (2012). Double digest RADseq: an inexpensive method for *de novo* SNP discovery and genotyping in model and non-model species. *PloS One*, *7*(5), e37135. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0037135>
- Peyerimhoff, P. (1923). Les Coléoptères des *Euphorbes* dans le Maroc méridional. *Bulletin de La Société Des Sciences Naturelles Du Maroc, Rabat*, *3*(3–4), 43–63.
- Pfingstl, T., Lienhard, A., Baumann, J., & Koblmüller, S. (2021). A taxonomist's nightmare – Cryptic diversity in Caribbean intertidal arthropods (Arachnida, Acari, Oribatida). *Molecular Phylogenetics and Evolution*, *163*(February), 107240. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ympev.2021.107240>
- Polilov, A., Ribera, I., Yavorskaya, M., Cardoso, A., Grebennikov, V., & Beutel, R. (2019). The phylogeny of Ptiliidae (Coleoptera: Staphylinoidea)-the smallest beetles and their evolutionary transformations. *Arthropod Systematics & Phylogeny*, *77*, 433–455. <https://doi.org/10.26049/ASP77-3-2019-4>
- Pons, O., & Petit, R. J. (1996). Measuring and Testing Genetic Differentiation With Ordered. *Genetics*, *144*(3), 1237–1254. <https://doi.org/10.1093/genetics/144.3.1237>
- Pritchard, J. K., Stephens, M., & Donnelly, P. (2000). Inference of population structure using multilocus genotype data. *Genetics*, *155*(2), 945–959. <https://doi.org/10.1093/genetics/155.2.945>
- Procheş, Ş., Wilson, J. R. U., Richardson, D. M., & Rejmánek, M. (2008). Searching for phylogenetic pattern in biological invasions. *Global Ecology and Biogeography*, *17*(1), 5–10. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1466-8238.2007.00333.x>
- Purvis, A., Gittleman, J. L., Cowlshaw, G., & Mace, G. M. (2000). Predicting extinction risk in declining species. *Proceedings of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*, *267*(1456), 1947–1952. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rspb.2000.1234>
- Pyšek, P., Hulme, P. E., Simberloff, D., Bacher, S., Blackburn, T. M., Carlton, J. T., Dawson, W., Essl, F., Foxcroft, L. C., Genovesi, P., Jeschke, J. M., Kühn, I., Liebhold, A. M., Mandrak, N. E., Meyerson, L. A., Pauchard, A., Pergl, J., Roy, H. E., Seebens, H., ... Richardson, D. M. (2020). Scientists' warning on invasive alien species. *Biological Reviews*, *95*(6), 1511–1534. <https://doi.org/10.1111/brv.12627>
- R Core Team. (2022). *R: a language and environment for statistical computing*. R Foundation for Statistical Computing. Versión 4.2. 2.
- Rambaut, A., Drummond, A. J., Xie, D., Baele, G., & Suchard, M. A. (2018). Posterior summarization in Bayesian phylogenetics using Tracer 1.7. *Systematic Biology*, *67*(5), 901–904. <https://doi.org/10.1093/sysbio/syy032>

References

- Ratnasingham, S., & Hebert, P. D. N. (2007). BOLD: The Barcode of Life Data System (<http://www.barcodinglife.org>). *Molecular Ecology Notes*, 7(3), 355–364. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1471-8286.2007.01678.x>
- Ratnasingham, S., & Hebert, P. D. N. (2013). A DNA-Based Registry for All Animal Species: The Barcode Index Number (BIN) System. *PLoS ONE*, 8(7). <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0066213>
- Reaser, J. K., Meyerson, L. A., Cronk, Q., De Poorter, M., Eldrege, L. G., Green, E., Kairo, M., Latasi, P., Mack, R. N., Mauremootoo, J., O'Dowd, D., Orapa, W., Sastroutomo, S., Saunders, A., Shine, C., Thrainsson, S., & Vaiutu, L. (2007). Ecological and socioeconomic impacts of invasive alien species in island ecosystems. *Environmental Conservation*, 34(2), 98–111. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0376892907003815>
- Rhymer, J. M., & Simberloff, D. (1996). Extinction by hybridization and introgression. *Annual Review of Ecology and Systematics*, 27, 83–109. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.ecolsys.27.1.83>
- Richardson, D. M., Pyšek, P., Rejmánek, M., Barbour, M. G., Dane Panetta, F., & West, C. J. (2000). Naturalization and invasion of alien plants: Concepts and definitions. *Diversity and Distributions*, 6(2), 93–107. <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1472-4642.2000.00083.x>
- Rodríguez, Á. M., Molina, R. J., & Coello, R. M. (2023). Diversidad taxonómica del género *Solanum* (subgénero *Leptostemonum*, sección *Melongenina*), en Canarias: precisiones sobre *Solanum vespertilio* subsp. *doramae* y descripción de la nueva subespecie *Solanum vespertilio* subsp. *silense*. *Botánica Macaronésica*, 33, 61–82.
- Ronquist, F., Teslenko, M., Van Der Mark, P., Ayres, D. L., Darling, A., Höhna, S., Larget, B., Liu, L., Suchard, M. A., & Huelsenbeck, J. P. (2012). MrBayes 3.2: efficient Bayesian phylogenetic inference and model choice across a large model space. *Systematic Biology*, 61(3), 539–542. <https://doi.org/10.1093/sysbio/sys029>
- Roques, A., Rabitsch, W., Rasplus, J.-Y., Lopez-Vaamonde, C., Nentwig, W., & Kenis, M. (2009). Alien terrestrial invertebrates of Europe. In *Handbook of alien species in Europe* (pp. 63–79). Springer.
- Roux, C., Fraïsse, C., Romiguier, J., Anciaux, Y., Galtier, N., & Bierne, N. (2016). Shedding Light on the Grey Zone of Speciation along a Continuum of Genomic Divergence. *PLoS Biology*, 14(12), 1–22. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pbio.2000234>
- Ryder, O. A. (1986). Species conservation and systematics: the dilemma of subspecies. *Trends in Ecology & Evolution*, 1(1), 9–10. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0169-5347\(86\)90059-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/0169-5347(86)90059-5)
- Saint-Vincent, J.-B. G. M. B. de. (1803). *Essais sur les Isles Fortunées et l'antique Atlantide: précis de l'histoire générale de l'archipel des Canaries*.

- Saitoh, T., Sugita, N., Someya, S., Iwami, Y., Kobayashi, S., Kamigaichi, H., Higuchi, A., Asai, S., Yamamoto, Y., & Nishiumi, I. (2015). DNA barcoding reveals 24 distinct lineages as cryptic bird species candidates in and around the Japanese Archipelago. *Molecular Ecology Resources*, 15(1), 177–186. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1755-0998.12282>
- Sakai, A. K., Wagner, W. L., Ferguson, D. M., & Herbst, D. R. (1995). Biogeographical and ecological correlates of dioecy in the Hawaiian flora. *Ecology*, 76(8), 2530–2543. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2265826>
- Salces-Castellano, A., Andújar, C., López, H., Pérez-Delgado, A. J., Arribas, P., & Emerson, B. C. (2021). Flightlessness in insects enhances diversification and determines assemblage structure across whole communities. *Proceedings of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*, 288(1945). <https://doi.org/10.1098/rspb.2020.2646>
- Salvador, A., & Brown, R. P. (2009). Perenquén de Boettger – *Tarentola boettgeri*. *Enciclopedia Virtual de Los Vertebrados Españoles*.
- Sanmartín, I., Van Der Mark, P., & Ronquist, F. (2008). Inferring dispersal: A Bayesian approach to phylogeny-based island biogeography, with special reference to the Canary Islands. *Journal of Biogeography*, 35(3), 428–449. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2699.2008.01885.x>
- Santos, B. F., Miller, M. E., Miklasevskaja, M., McKeon, J. T. A., Redmond, N. E., Coddington, J. A., Bird, J., Miller, S. E., Smith, A., Brady, S. G., Buffington, M. L., Chamorro, M. L., Dikow, T., Gates, M. W., Goldstein, P., Konstantinov, A., Kula, R., Silversen, N. D., Solis, M. A., ... DeWaard, J. R. (2023). Enhancing DNA barcode reference libraries by harvesting terrestrial arthropods at the Smithsonian's National Museum of Natural History. *Biodiversity Data Journal*, 11, e100904. <https://doi.org/10.3897/BDJ.11.E100904>
- Sayers, E. W., Cavanaugh, M., Clark, K., Ostell, J., Pruitt, K. D., & Karsch-Mizrachi, I. (2020). GenBank. *Nucleic Acids Research*, 48(D1), D84–D86. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkz956>
- Schaefer, H., Hardy, O. J., Silva, L., Barraclough, T. G., & Savolainen, V. (2011). Testing Darwin's naturalization hypothesis in the Azores. *Ecology Letters*, 14(4), 389–396. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1461-0248.2011.01600.x>
- Schluter, D. (2000). *The ecology of adaptive radiation*. OUP Oxford.
- Seibold, S., Brandl, R., Buse, J., Hothorn, T., Schmidl, J., Thorn, S., & Müller, J. (2015). Association of extinction risk of saproxylic beetles with ecological degradation of forests in Europe. *Conservation Biology*, 29(2), 382–390. <https://doi.org/10.1111/cobi.12427>

References

- Sharkey, M. J., Janzen, D. H., Hallwachs, W., Chapman, E. G., Alex Smith, M., Dapkey, T., Brown, A., Ratnasingham, S., Naik, S., Manjunath, R., Perez, K., Milton, M., Hebert, P., Shaw, S. R., Kittel, R. N., Alma Solis, M., Metz, M. A., Goldstein, P. Z., Brown, J. W., ... Burns, J. M. (2021). Minimalist revision and description of 403 new species in 11 subfamilies of Costa Rican braconid parasitoid wasps, including host records for 219 species. *ZooKeys*, 2021(1013), 1–665. <https://doi.org/10.3897/zookeys.1013.55600>
- Sharov, A. A., & Liebhold, A. M. (1998). Bioeconomics of managing the spread of exotic pest species with barrier zones. *Ecological Applications*, 8(3), 833–845. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2641270>
- Simberloff, D. (1974). Equilibrium Theory of Island Biogeography and Ecology. *Annual Review of Ecology and Systematics*, 5(1), 161–182. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.es.05.110174.001113>
- Simberloff, D. (2013). *Invasive species: what everyone needs to know*. Oxford University Press.
- Simberloff, D., & Wilson, E. O. (1970). Experimental zoogeography of islands. A two-year record of colonization. *Ecology*, 51(5), 934–937. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1933995>
- Simon, D. (2008). Biogeography-Based Optimization. *IEEE Transactions on Evolutionary Computation*, 12(6), 702–713. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TEVC.2008.919004>
- Sloan, D. B., Havird, J. C., & Sharbrough, J. (2017). The on-again, off-again relationship between mitochondrial genomes and species boundaries. *Molecular Ecology*, 26(8), 2212–2236. <https://doi.org/10.1111/mec.13959>
- Smetana, A. (1962). Inseln lebenden *Gabrius*-Arten aus der *nigritulus*-Gruppe (Col., Staphylinidae). *Entomologisk Tidskrift*, 83, 95.
- Smith, M. A., & Fisher, B. L. (2009). Invasions, DNA barcodes, and rapid biodiversity assessment using ants of Mauritius. *Frontiers in Zoology*, 6, 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1742-9994-6-31>
- Srivathsan, A., Feng, V., Suárez, D., Emerson, B., & Meier, R. (2024). ONTbarcode 2.0: rapid species discovery and identification with real-time barcoding facilitated by Oxford Nanopore R10.4. *Cladistics*, 40(2), 192–203. <https://doi.org/10.1111/cla.12566>
- Srivathsan, A., Lee, L., Katoh, K., Hartop, E., Kutty, S. N., Wong, J., Yeo, D., & Meier, R. (2021). ONTbarcode and MinION barcodes aid biodiversity discovery and identification by everyone, for everyone. *BMC Biology*, 19(1), 1–21. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12915-021-01141-x>
- Stankowski, S., & Ravinet, M. (2021). Defining the speciation continuum. *Evolution*, 75(6), 1256–1273. <https://doi.org/10.1111/evo.14215>

- Stüben, P. E. (2018). The Cryptorhynchinae of the Western Palearctic.—Die Cryptorhynchinae der Westpaläarktis.(Coleoptera: Curculionidae). *Curculio Institute, Mönchengladbach*.
- Stüben, P. E. (2021). Weevils of Macaronesia. *Curculio Institute, Mönchengladbach, Ca.*
- Suárez, D., Arribas, P., Jiménez-García, E., & Emerson, B. C. (2022). Dispersal ability and its consequences for population genetic differentiation and diversification. *Proceedings of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*, 289(1975). <https://doi.org/10.1098/rspb.2022.0489>
- Suárez, D., Arribas, P., Macías-Hernández, N., & Emerson, B. C. (2023). Dispersal ability and niche breadth influence interspecific variation in spider abundance and occupancy. *Royal Society Open Science*, 10(5). <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsos.230051>
- Terzopoulou, S., Rigal, F., Whittaker, R. J., Borges, P. A. V., & Triantis, K. A. (2015). Drivers of extinction: The case of Azorean Beetles. *Biology Letters*, 11(6), 1–4. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsbl.2015.0273>
- Thomson, J. L. (1860). *Essai d'une classification de la famille des cérambycides et matériaux pour servir a une monographie de cette famille*. Chez l'auteur et au Bureau du Trésorier de la Société entomologique de France.
- Thomson, J. L. (1864). *Systema cerambycidarum: ou, Exposé de tous les genres compris la famille des cérambycides et familles limitrophes* (Vol. 19). H. Dessain, imprimeur.
- Timmermans, M. J. T. N., Barton, C., Haran, J., Ahrens, D., Culverwell, C. L., Ollikainen, A., Dodsworth, S., Foster, P. G., Bocak, L., & Vogler, A. P. (2016). Family-level sampling of mitochondrial genomes in Coleoptera: Compositional heterogeneity and phylogenetics. *Genome Biology and Evolution*, 8(1), 161–175. <https://doi.org/10.1093/gbe/evv241>
- Torchin, M. E., Lafferty, K. D., & Kuris, A. M. (2001). Release from parasites as natural enemies: Increased performance of a globally introduced marine crab. *Biological Invasions*, 3(4), 333–345. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1015855019360>
- Trevino, H. S., Skibieli, A. L., Karels, T. J., & Dobson, F. S. (2007). Threats to avifauna on oceanic islands. *Conservation Biology*, 21(1), 125–132. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1523-1739.2006.00581.x>
- Triantis, K. A., Borges, P. A. V., Ladle, R. J., Hortal, J., Cardoso, P., Gaspar, C., Dinis, F., Mendonça, E., Silveira, L. M. A., Gabriel, R., Melo, C., Santos, A. M. C., Amorim, I. R., Ribeiro, S. P., Serrano, A. R. M., Quartau, J. A., & Whittaker, R. J. (2010). Extinction debt on oceanic Islands. *Ecography*, 33(2), 285–294. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1600-0587.2010.06203.x>
- Troll, V. R., & Carracedo, J. C. (2016). *The geology of the Canary Islands*. Elsevier.

References

- Tscharntke, T., Tylianakis, J. M., Rand, T. A., Didham, R. K., Fahrig, L., Batáry, P., Bengtsson, J., Clough, Y., Crist, T. O., Dormann, C. F., Ewers, R. M., Fründ, J., Holt, R. D., Holzschuh, A., Klein, A. M., Kleijn, D., Kremen, C., Landis, D. A., Laurance, W., ... Westphal, C. (2012). Landscape moderation of biodiversity patterns and processes - eight hypotheses. *Biological Reviews*, *87*(3), 661–685. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1469-185X.2011.00216.x>
- Turchetto, C., Segatto, A. L. A., Mäder, G., Rodrigues, D. M., Bonatto, S. L., & Freitas, L. B. (2016). High levels of genetic diversity and population structure in an endemic and rare species: Implications for conservation. *AoB PLANTS*, *8*, 1–17. <https://doi.org/10.1093/aobpla/plw002>
- Uyttenboogaart, D. L. (1932). Contributions to the knowledge of the fauna of the Canary Islands. XV. Curious habits of the larva of *Lepromoris gibba* Brullé.(Col. Cerambycidae). *Tijdeschr. Ent*, *75*, 58–59.
- Uyttenboogaart, D. L. (1937). Contributions to the knowledge of the fauna of the Canary Islands XIX. *Tijdschrift Voor Entomologie*, *80*, 75–118.
- Van Kleunen, M., Dawson, W., Schlaepfer, D., Jeschke, J. M., & Fischer, M. (2010). Are invaders different? A conceptual framework of comparative approaches for assessing determinants of invasiveness. *Ecology Letters*, *13*(8), 947–958. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1461-0248.2010.01503.x>
- Vilà, M., Espinar, J. L., Hejda, M., Hulme, P. E., Jarošík, V., Maron, J. L., Pergl, J., Schaffner, U., Sun, Y., & Pyšek, P. (2011). Ecological impacts of invasive alien plants: A meta-analysis of their effects on species, communities and ecosystems. *Ecology Letters*, *14*(7), 702–708. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1461-0248.2011.01628.x>
- Vilà, M., & Hulme, P. E. (2017). *Impact of biological invasions on ecosystem services* (Vol. 12). Springer.
- Villesen, P. (2007). FaBox: An online toolbox for FASTA sequences. *Molecular Ecology Notes*, *7*(6), 965–968. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1471-8286.2007.01821.x>
- Vitali, F., & Touroult, J. (2006). Contribution à la connaissance des états pré-imaginaux des longicornes des Canaries (Coleoptera, Cerambycidae, Lamiinae). *Lambillionea*, *106*(2), 193–201.
- Vives, E., & Trócoli, S. (2021). Cerambycidae de la Macaronesia (Coleoptera, Cerambycidae). *Faunitaxys*, *9*(44), 1–50.
- von Gaisberg, M. (2002). Contribución al conocimiento de la taxonomía, la biología reproductiva y la distribución de *Carduus baeocephalus* Webb. *Revista de La Academia Canaria de Ciencias:= Folia Canariensis Academiae Scientiarum*, *14*(3), 253–261.
- Wang, S. Q. (2020). Genetic diversity and population structure of the endangered species *Paeonia decomposita* endemic to China and implications for its conservation. *BMC Plant Biology*, *20*(1), 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12870-020-02682-z>

- Wang, W. Y., Srivathsan, A., Foo, M., Yamane, S. K., & Meier, R. (2018). Sorting specimen-rich invertebrate samples with cost-effective NGS barcodes: Validating a reverse workflow for specimen processing. *Molecular Ecology Resources*, *18*(3), 490–501. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1755-0998.12751>
- Waples, R. S. (1991). Pacific salmon, *Oncorhynchus* spp., and the definition of ‘species’ under the Endangered Species Act. *Marine Fisheries Review*, *53*(3), 11–22.
- Waples, R. S. (1995). Evolutionarily Significant Units and the Conservation of Biological Diversity under the Endangered Species Act. *American Fisheries Society Symposium*, *17*(1), 8–27.
- Waters, J. M., Emerson, B. C., Arribas, P., & McCulloch, G. A. (2020). Dispersal Reduction: Causes, Genomic Mechanisms, and Evolutionary Consequences. *Trends in Ecology and Evolution*, *35*(6), 512–522. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tree.2020.01.012>
- Weeks, A. R., Stoklosa, J., & Hoffmann, A. A. (2016). Conservation of genetic uniqueness of populations may increase extinction likelihood of endangered species: The case of Australian mammals. *Frontiers in Zoology*, *13*(1), 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12983-016-0163-z>
- Whittaker, R. J., & Fernández-Palacios, J. M. (2007). *Island biogeography: ecology, evolution, and conservation*. Oxford University Press.
- Whittaker, R. J., Fernández-Palacios, J. M., Matthews, T. J., Borregaard, M. K., & Triantis, K. A. (2017). Island biogeography: Taking the long view of nature’s laboratories. *Science*, *357*(6354). <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aam8326>
- Whittaker, R. J., Ladle, R. J., Araújo, M. B., María Fernández-Palacios, J., Domingo Delgado, J., & Ramón Arévalo, J. (2007). The island immaturity–speciation pulse model of island evolution: an alternative to the “diversity begets diversity” model. *Ecography*, *30*(3), 321–327. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.0906-7590.2007.04761.x>
- Wilson, E. O. (1961). The nature of the taxon cycle in the Melanesian ant fauna. *The American Naturalist*, *95*(882), 169–193. <https://doi.org/10.1086/282174>
- Wilson, E. O., & MacArthur, R. H. (1967). *The theory of island biogeography*. JSTOR.
- Winkler, A. (1932). *Catalogus Coleopterorum regionis palaearticae*. Wien.
- Wojas, T. (2021). *Ocypus* (*Pseudocypus*) *aethiops* (Waltl, 1835)-new but not unexpected rove beetle in Canary Islands (Coleoptera, Staphylinidae). *Baltic Journal of Coleopterology*, *21*(2), 141–145.
- Wolkis, D., Baskin, C. C., Baskin, J. M., & Rønsted, N. (2022). Seed dormancy and germination of the endangered exceptional Hawaiian lobelioid *Brighamia rockii*. *Applications in Plant Sciences*, *10*(5), 1–7. <https://doi.org/10.1002/aps3.11492>
- Wollaston, T. V. (1862). X. On the *Euphorbia*-infesting Coleoptera of the Canary Islands. *Transactions of the Royal Entomological Society of London*, *11*(2), 136–189.

References

- Wollaston, T. V. (1864). *Catalogue of the Coleopterous Insects of the Canaries in the Collection of the British Museum*. Taylor & Francis.
- Wollaston, T. V. (1865). *Coleoptera Atlantidum: Being an Enumeration of the Coleopterous Insects of the Madeiras, Salvages, and Canaries*. Taylor & Francis.
- Xu, M., Li, S. P., Dick, J. T. A., Gu, D., Fang, M., Yang, Y., Hu, Y., & Mu, X. (2022). Exotic fishes that are phylogenetically close but functionally distant to native fishes are more likely to establish. *Global Change Biology*, 28(19), 5683–5694. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.16360>
- Yeo, D., Srivathsan, A., & Meier, R. (2020). Longer is Not Always Better: Optimizing Barcode Length for Large-Scale Species Discovery and Identification. *Systematic Biology*, 69(5), 999–1015. <https://doi.org/10.1093/sysbio/syaa014>
- Yu, D. W., Ji, Y., Emerson, B. C., Wang, X., Ye, C., Yang, C., & Ding, Z. (2012). Biodiversity soup: Metabarcoding of arthropods for rapid biodiversity assessment and biomonitoring. *Methods in Ecology and Evolution*, 3(4), 613–623. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.2041-210X.2012.00198.x>
- Zaczek, K., Troll, V. R., Cachao, M., Ferreira, J., Deegan, F. M., Carracedo, J. C., Soler, V., Meade, F. C., & Burchardt, S. (2015). Nannofossils in 2011 El Hierro eruptive products reinstate plume model for Canary Islands. *Scientific Reports*, 5, 1–5. <https://doi.org/10.1038/srep07945>
- Zamani, A., Fric, Z. F., Gante, H. F., Hopkins, T., Orfinger, A. B., Scherz, M. D., Bartoňová, A. S., & Pos, D. D. (2022). DNA barcodes on their own are not enough to describe a species. *Systematic Entomology*, 47(3), 385–389. <https://doi.org/10.1111/syen.12538>
- Zerche, L. (1998). Phylogenetischsystematische Revision der westpaläarktischen Gattung *Metopsia* Wollaston, 1854 (Coleoptera: Staphylinidae, Proteininae). *Beiträge Zur Entomologie = Contributions to Entomology*, 48(1), 3–101. <https://doi.org/10.21248/contrib.entomol.48.1.3101>
- Zhang, S. Q., Che, L. H., Li, Y., Dan, L., Pang, H., Ślipiński, A., & Zhang, P. (2018). Evolutionary history of Coleoptera revealed by extensive sampling of genes and species. *Nature Communications*, 9(1), 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-017-02644-4>
- Zonstein, S., & Marusik, Y. M. (2019). A revision of the spider genus *Filistata* (Araneae: Filistatidae). *Arachnology*, 18(2), 53–93. <https://doi.org/10.13156/arac.2018.18.2.53>
- Zych, A. F., Mankin, R. W., Gillooly, J. F., & Foreman, E. (2012). Stridulation by *Jadera haematoloma* (Hemiptera: Rhopalidae): Production mechanism and associated behaviors. *Annals of the Entomological Society of America*, 105(1), 118–127. <https://doi.org/10.1603/AN11048>

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